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**A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS TO LEARN
RAJAYOGA MEDITATION AT BRAHMA KUMARIS
INTERNATIONAL HEAD QUARTERS MOUNT ABU
RAJASTHAN**

A

THESIS

**SUBMITTED TO THE
SHRI JAGDISHPRASAD JHABARMAL TIBREWALA
UNIVERSITY**

**FOR THE DEGREE
OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY**

**IN
MANAGEMENT**

By

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YEAR : 2016

THESIS DEDICATION

*This thesis is dedicated to Beloved, Sweetest, Dearest, Holiest & Highest World Almighty Authority -**GOD FATHER SHIVA** –Supreme father of all souls, who is my Supreme Father, Supreme Teacher & Supreme Guide whom I lovely remember as **SHIVABABA**.*

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I declare that this thesis entitled “**A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS TO LEARN RAJAYOGA MEDITATION AT BRAHMA KUMARIS INTERNATIONAL HEAD QUARTERS: MOUNT ABU, RAJASTHAN**” is my own work conducted under the supervision of **Dr.Surendra Kumar** and co- supervision of **Dr.A.Sachindra Babu**, Professor, Department of Dairy Economics and Business management, Dairy Science College, K.V.A.F.S University, Bangalore, Karnataka, approved by the Research Degree Committee of the University and that I have put in more than 200 days/ 600 hours of attendance with the supervisor.

I further declare that to the best of my knowledge this thesis does not contain any part of any work which has been submitted for award of any degree either in this University or by any other university/ deemed university without a proper citation.

Date: 03-11-2016
Place: Bangalore-30

Signature of the candidate

(Nagesh.N.V)

CERTIFICATE OF THE SUPERVISOR

It is certified that this work entitled “**A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS TO LEARN RAJAYOGA MEDITATION AT BRAHMA KUMARIS INTERNATIONAL HEAD QUARTERS: MOUNT ABU, RAJASTHAN**” is an original research work done by **Shri. Nagesh.N.V**, under my supervision for the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Management** to be awarded by **Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabaramal Tibrewala University**, Vidyanagari, Jhunjunu, Rajasthan, India and that the candidate has put the attendance of more than 200days / 600hours with me.

To the best of my knowledge and belief this thesis

- I. Embodies the work of candidate himself.
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- III. Fulfils the requirement of the ordinance related to Ph.D. degree of the University and
- IV. It is up to the standard in respect of both content and language for being referred to the examiner.

Signature of the Supervisor

(Dr.A.Sachindra Babu)

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ABBREVIATIONS

BK -Brahma Kumaris

BKRM -Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga Mediation

RY -Rajayoga

UN- United Nations

HQ –Head Quarters

Mt Abu- Mount Abu

WRST- world renewal spiritual trust

GHRC- Global hospital & research center

GS-Gyan Sarovar

BKWSU- Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university

UNO- United Nations Organization

NRM-New religious movement

NGO- Non-Governmental Organization

DPI – Department of Public Instruction

UK- United Kingdom

THESIS OUTLINE/ ABSTRACT

This is the matter of fact that the well defined presentation of a thesis has a great significance for stating efficient research subjective contents discussion and optimal knowledge transfer. The structured contents and research oriented discussion enables reader to understand subject matter efficiently. Hence, taking into consideration of the requirements of the optimal thesis presentation, in this thesis the overall contents have been divided into six individual sections. The overall thesis outlines defined are given as follows:

Chapter-1 Introduction

The introductory of any research initiatives and respective subjective introduction is of great significance. This chapter primarily discusses the introduction of the proposed research work, research motivations, objectives and contributions. In addition, the thesis outline has also been discussed in this section of the presented thesis.

In any research wok, the discussion of the key aspects of the research domain, and its significant theoretical discussion are of great significance. Thus, taking into consideration of these significances, in this section, the brief discussion of Brahma Kumaris, including its history, organizational structure, objective of the organization and its practices, meditation and its types, benefits of meditation, Raja Yoga meditation and its significances etc are discussed in this chapter. In addition, a brief of the concept of motivation is also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter-2 Literature Survey

The literature survey or the study and analysis of the existing researches and literatures have great significance towards defining certain foundation for innovation or optimization. Considering these significances, in this thesis, various literatures discussing psychological, physiological and spiritual significances of Raja Yoga meditation are discussed. In addition, some of the relevant literatures discussing Brahma Kumaris and its novel practices are also discussed. A brief of the motivational constructs as suggested by other researchers are also discussed in this section.

Chapter-3 Research Methodology

In this section of the presented thesis or dissertation, the research methodology considered is discussed. Various significant components, such as data collection, questionnaire preparation, population definition, sampling process, tools implementation, statistical analysis paradigms etc and other methodological approaches are discussed in this Chapter.

Chapter-4 Data Analysis and Interpretation

In this section, the statistical analysis of the collected responses from the respondents at Brahma Kumaris International headquarter are discussed. Data analysis using different statistical approaches, such as reliability test, mean, standard deviation, Chronbach Alpha values estimation, correlation estimation etc, have been done so as to examine the proposed hypothesis. The discussion of the responses and respective significances towards motivating people to join BKRM are also discussed in this section of the presented thesis.

Chapter-5 Summary, Conclusion, Future scope, Limitations and Recommendations

This chapter predominantly discusses the conclusion of the proposed research work and overall novel efforts made. In fact, the conclusion derived throughout the proposed research, research methodology, overall research outcome and its significances etc are discussed. Furthermore, the future scope, recommendation, limitation and delimitations are also discussed in this section.

Reference

In this section of the presented thesis, the references considered throughout the research work and thesis preparation are presented.

CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Preamble

The introduction of a research domain and associated key aspects is of great significance to enable optimal knowledge transfer and research understanding. Taking into consideration of these significant requirements, in this section a brief of the research domain, research motivations, objectives and thesis outlines etc have been discussed. The predominant objective of this section is to provide precise knowledge transfer about intended research and related significances. The research background intends to provide a brief of Brahma Kumaris and the Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. Later, the key motivations for the presented research are discussed, which has been followed by the discussion of research objectives. Research contribution section represents some of the key significances of the presented thesis work. The overall outline or organization of the thesis is given at the beginning of the chapter.

1.2 Problem on Hand

This is the matter of fact that the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University has emerged as a new religious movement that came into existence in 1936 in Hyderabad, Pakistan. It was founded by a retiring diamond merchant named Dada Lekhraj who initiated it on the basis of revelations that he received during the preceding two years. Initially, the religion consisted of little more than a close-knit gathering of Lekhraj's closest family, friends, and business associates, although it quickly grew by attracting mostly young women as members. The religious core of Brahma Kumaris life is characterized by the practice of a style of spirit-possession that has always been more deeply indebted to practices among the royal elite for communing with sovereign temple deities in their territory than with the more spontaneous rural practices that give voice to the underclass or object. Moreover, the Brahma Kumaris insist that the God whom they channel is the same God whom all other religions worship throughout the world. This kind of universalistic claim is not uncommon among Hindu sects, but the Brahma Kumaris are unusual insofar as they firmly reject polytheism, henotheism, pantheism, and all other understandings of God worldwide,

insisting instead on a strong form of monotheism wherein only one God has ever existed.

The Brahma Kumaris are registered with national governments and the global community of international non-governmental organizations as two separate corporate entities. One of these corporate entities is chartered as a religious organization, the other as an educational and cultural service organization. The religious organization is known as The World Renewal Spiritual Trust, and their secular educational and service organization is known as The Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University (also known as The Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa-Vidyalaya). The religious side is a “trust,” their secular side is a “spiritual university.” The connotations of these terms are partially inverted from their common applications, as “trusts” are often secular and “spiritual universities” are often religious. The partial inversion of these terms is the first indication that the Brahma Kumaris’ institution escapes easy categorization as either religious or secular. Moreover, the personnel of both institutions are nearly identical, and each chartered organization’s activities are inseparably integrated with the mission of the institution as a whole. Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation teaching spiritual knowledge and practicing the ancient technique of Raj Yoga Meditation, as taught by the Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya, Mount Abu, for the past 80 years. It conducts motivational paths and opposite on a wide spectrum of themes such as: Stress Free Lifestyle, Leadership Skills, Emotional Intelligence, Art of Right Thinking, Living Values, Exploring Inner Powers, Self Management, Harmony in Relationships and the Practical Technique of Raj Yoga Meditation.

Brahma Kumaris knowledge begins with God, who is said never to have become entangled with the world. Thus, God is not responsible for the world. God has never been embodied. God is the only soul whom the world has never tainted. Human souls take bodies and through their sensory experience, the world enters into them and become a part of who they are. Human souls have a dual nature: partly divine, partly worldly. Only God remains unstained by the world. Only God is wholly pure, wholly clean, and wholly divine. Brahma Kumaris knowledge teaches that God did not create the world. The world exists in itself as independent from God. God is not bound up in the world and God does not affect anything that happens in the world. The world is completely independent from God. The world creates itself a new approximately every 5,000 years after having deconstructed the previous world cycle. Each new

world cycle of 5,000 years repeats itself identically to every other world cycle. Every world cycle of 5,000 years is predestined to recur precisely as every other world cycle occurs.

The Brahma Kumaris believe in reincarnation and their doctrine consistently follows their teachings about God, souls, and the world: God never interacts with the world. Human beings are the only earthly creatures with souls. Unlike God, human souls have a dual nature. They are partly divine and partly worldly. It follows, then, that the lives of souls are also predestined every world cycle. Souls are tied to the history of the world.

Raj Yoga Meditation is awareness of the metaphysical self and absorption of one's mind in hopeful and purposeful consciousness of God and his divine attributes. The word 'Yoga' means 'to unite'; Yoga is, therefore, the practice or art of uniting or linking the mind with God by focusing attention on him as an incorporeal being-of-light and thinking of nothing but his divine qualities. This takes one into a state of absorption in bliss and peace through positive thinking. It recharges one's self or soul with light and might and fills one with creative energy. In the name 'Raj-Yoga' the word 'Raja' means the king, the sovereign or the supreme. This yoga is called Raj-Yoga because it is the supreme or the highest yoga, being true and most effective. Another reason for calling it 'Raj-Yoga' is that it is related mainly to mind and mind is considered as the 'King that rules the sense-organs and the body. Moreover, the term Raj-Yoga also implies that even such a person as a king, who is very busy and has so much to do, can practice it, there is no need to practice breath-control, physical postures, or use a mantra, or an image nor does it require one to stop all thoughts, but stop only, worldly or negative thoughts and concentrate our mind on God.

"...The word 'Meditation' means 'to think'. As we all know, man's mind is, ordinary, occupied with hundreds of thoughts of the world. In Raj-Yoga meditation, one withdraws one's mind from all the worldly thoughts, including the thoughts of one's own body, and one collects one's consciousness, at least for some time, and thinks of the shining and peaceful self as a point of divine and conscient light and then focuses one's attention on god as supreme soul, who also is a point of conscient light and is the ocean of peace."

The inhibition of worldly thoughts and the recollection or recapitulation of thoughts of the luminous self is attained by directing the flow of thoughts towards god i.e. the supreme soul in his supreme abode or Paramdham which is the world

of divine light. In this sense, this meditation is withdrawal or reversal of one's consciousness, from the body and its world to the soul and its silent world, or from the dark lanes of negative thoughts on the bright path of contemplation on god. Raj-Yoga meditation may therefore, be defined as a disciplined exercise of awareness, utilizing such processes as creatively thinking, intuitively perceiving and silently reflecting and concentrating on the metaphysical truths of self and god which lead to comprehension and realization of the subject. This practice involves the turning of one's mind and the flow of his love in the direction of god, giving him the hot-link to communicate with him.

Raj yoga Meditation is the way for realization of the real identity of the self and for experiencing it. It helps a person to know the truth about the real nature of mind or the self. Raj Yoga enables a person to withdraw from the thoughts of the body and the material world for a while. The philosophy of Raj yoga enables the participant to focus the mind on the metaphysical self and link itself love fully to the supreme soul who is light, bliss, peace, love and might personified in the form of a brilliant and radiant point. Raj Yoga meditation is refreshing, energizing, relaxing, reassuring and reawakening. Raj Yoga makes the soul increasingly aware of its divine origin, divine destiny and divine peaceful real nature. Raj Yoga possesses numerous social significances that helps in developing spiritual approach towards others and created an attitude of Universal Brotherhood in the aspirant of Yoga.

Raja yoga meditation can help in curing numerous psychological problems such as neurotic illness and many other diseases like hypertension, Insomnia, depression etc. Raj Yoga removes tension, nervousness, fear and other negativities, which disturb a person, hence relaxing the mind completely. This way the negative symptoms that the average middle class neurotics experience are cured with the help Raja yoga. Some of the neurotic diseases, which can be easily cured through Raj Yoga, are anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorders, phobias etc by combing Raj Yoga with conventional psychopharmacology and psychotherapy. Further more positive thoughts can be used during Raj Yoga to overcome stress, fear for holistic health. The dose of medicine can be reduced and the disease can be eradicated to the core, since meditation removes the root cause of psychosomatic diseases.

The above mentioned subjective discussion of Raj Yoga meditation illustrates the

there is the significant advantages of Raj Yoga meditation on psychological, physiological and other mental stability benefits, that might perhaps motivate people to adopt it. Furthermore, considering the novel approaches of Brahma Kumaris, it can be realized that this organization possesses numerous novelty that could attract people to consider its functional philosophy of life and hence people could be motivated through it. Thus, considering these all factors, some of the researches have tried to focus on understanding various advantages of Raj Yoga meditation and even some researches made effort to assess Brahma Kumaris organizational process and meditation practices at its world spirituality institutions. But still, there are no any existing researches which could examine the factual and precise motivational factors that encourage people to join Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris. This thesis intends to examine these motivational factors through an analytical and empirical research paradigm. In this thesis, the predominant focus has been made on assessing various motivational factors that encourages people to join Raj Yoga meditation practices at Brahma Kumaris International headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India.

1.2.1 Aims of Brahma Kumaris

- ☞ To offer learning in principles, values, and spiritual and moral understanding to those who are interested; to reaffirm the spiritual identity, inherent goodness, dignity, and worth of the human being; and to foster a spirit of universal brotherhood;
- ☞ To encourage transformation in individual awareness, attitude, and behaviour as the foundation of the overall advancement of the human condition throughout the world;
- ☞ To teach BK Raja Yoga meditation and related methods of personal development and positive thinking;
- ☞ To promote better understanding of and within the global human family through insight into the spiritual connections among the world's religions; environmental and human well-being and the promotion of equality.
- ☞ To clarify spiritual and moral perspectives on contemporary issues of personal, community and global concerns, and to facilitate a greater awareness of corresponding rights and responsibilities to foster long-term, human-centred

development. This would include moral and spiritual dimensions of education, the support of economic, social, environmental and human well-being and the promotion of equality.

☞ To enhance the skills, arts, and talents and higher levels of attainment and in personal, professional, and public life..

1.2.2 Some of the unique features of this spiritual organization are:

- It is the world's first and largest spiritual movement led by women.
- It is a truly one-of-its-kind global spiritual family that sustains itself by cultivating 'spiritual brotherhood' by methodically practicing soul consciousness.
- As a global educational facility it offers all its courses free of cost. It does not seek public funds and supports itself entirely by voluntary contributions made by its members.
- Exemplifying the fact that when we change the world changes, its regular members practice spiritual principles and a lifestyle that nurtures the purity of body, mind, soul, relationships and environment.
- A model of lifelong learning where daily spiritual study and early morning (4 am) meditation form the base for sustained Individual progress. 'Traffic control' meditation 2-3 minutes of inner silence - is practiced at regular intervals throughout the day to create peace in a hectic lifestyle.
- A formidable global network that connects a wide cross-section of socio-economic and cultural groups. It represents a large segment of civil society that works for development and sharing of human and social values.

1.2.3 Essential Teachings of Raja Yoga Shared by BKs

Raja Yoga is the sovereign yoga. This has two aspects: firstly, being the sovereign of oneself, secondly the connection with the most Sovereign Being, i.e. with the Divine or God. Raja Yoga meditation is therefore not so much a technique as a philosophy, which enables an individual to change self awareness. The teachings cover several topics:

Consciousness and Self-Realisation: the self, the soul, is envisaged as a being of light, a point of light, located in the centre of the forehead. The soul interacts with the world through the senses. Every soul has inherent original qualities – peace, love, truth, purity, and happiness.

Relationship with God: God is also understood to be an infinitesimal point of light, yet is an unlimited source of love, peace, truth, happiness. Our relationship with God provides everything needed to nourish the soul.

Karmic laws: these are explored not just as a way of accepting my situation or circumstance in life but as a proactive way of improving my life. The law of karma states that every action has an equal and opposing reaction. The motivation behind our action determines the quality of the action and its result. An awareness of spiritual values results in actions motivated by goodness that uplift the self and others.

Cyclic Time looks at the traditional four ages of Hinduism: Golden Age ('Sat Yuga'), Silver Age ('Treta Yuga'), Copper Age ('Dwapur Yuga') and Iron Age ('Kali Yuga'). Raja Yoga also explains a fifth age, the Confluence Age ('Sangam Yuga'), which is the age of transition. We are now at a unique point in history when, through a connection with God, a renaissance in consciousness is possible, enabling us to be at peace with ourselves and others. Such a change results in a worldwide transformation that can return us to the Golden Age of humanity again.

Tree of Life shows the connection of all our religious and spiritual traditions with God, the Seed, the Source of nourishment for the tree.

A Spiritual Lifestyle: For someone whose life is dedicated to spiritual study, there are certain principles of living that enhance spiritual development: daily meditation and study, vegetarian diet, celibacy and striving to lead a virtuous life. Individuals make the choice to follow these, when they feel ready.

Sensitivities: A Spiritual University with a specific body of teaching and lifestyle for those who are dedicated is viewed as wonderfully refreshing by some and with suspicion by others. Our response to concerns about what we do is always to give an invitation to experience our centres and our work at first hand. 'Religious or spiritual groups' such as the BKWSU (UK) offer a new and vital way of looking at the world that helps an increasing number of people make profound changes in their lives. More and more people are turning towards spirituality for the solutions to their problems.

Relevance to today's world: The Raja Yoga teachings are very timely, as they provide an explanation for the current state of the world. The spiritual tools that are offered through courses such as positive thinking, stress management, self esteem and anger management are extremely useful in dealing with life in today's world. People who work in the caring professions benefit from learning ways in which they can sustain and nurture themselves to avoid burn-out. In a world where people often feel

overwhelmed with the challenges of modern life, methods that can empower our positive, spiritual values give a great deal of inner strength and happiness.

1.3 Research Motivation

A number of researchers have recommended that Raj Yoga can be considered as the supreme or the highest yoga that empowers the self to rule the mind, sense-organs and the body. There are several psychological and physiological advantages of Raj-yoga meditation. In some recent researches, researchers have made effort to explore varied advantages of Raj Yoga meditation but still no significant research glance has been made or focused on the study of various motivation factors that encourages people to join Raj Yoga meditation, specifically at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. On the other hand, the high pace emergence of Brahma Kumaris organization has also attracted masses to join Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation (BKRM) practices at the worlds spiritual university, Mount Abu, which is a part of BK's International headquarters.

On the other hand, the world has recognized the significances of Yoga for healthy, wealthy and stress less life and during the year 2015 , June 21st was incorporated as World Yoga Divas across the globe. In such circumstances, the study and analysis various motivational factors influencing people to adopt Raj Yoga motivation at Brahma Kumaris becomes a significant research objective. In this world, where every individual makes efforts to achieve more and more worldly beings and prosperity, the adoption of Raj Yoga for long run and dedicating towards Brahma Kumaris is an interesting research domain to be explored about. The study of various motivational factors that put enthuse among people to adopt Raj Yoga, can help both the individual willing to join Raj Yoga at meditation at Brahma Kumaris as well as the organizational management to attract more and more followers of Raj Yoga meditation.

Interestingly, it has been observed that meditation and Yoga can be of great significance to enrich the quality of life and value based life style. In addition, it can be vital for psychological enrichment, physiological soundness and spiritual accomplishment etc. There are two predominant dimensions that significantly motivates researcher to do this research. The first motivational factor arises with an intention to explore the key factors and reason which enables BK to encourage people or devotees to join BKRM. In fact, here, it is intended to explore the various novelties and service provisioning by BK which motivates people to join it. On the other hand,

the second motivational factor arises from intend to explore the precise affinity variables, such as psychological, physiological and spiritual factors which motivates people to join BKRM. In addition, the exploration of the significance of meditation, specifically Raj Yoga meditation and its significance towards alleviating or reducing exponential rising stress, based life or conserved life, exponential rising crime in families & break up of relationships, anti social activities such as terrorism etc also motivates researchers to perform this research. The identification of the vital motivational factors can enable people to join Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, and Rajasthan, India.

1.4 Research Objectives

Taking into consideration of the research domain, existing research gaps and motivation, in this thesis, certain research objectives have been identified. The overall research objectives have been classified into two broad categories. These are general objectives and specific objectives. Here the general objectives represents the overall research intends or goal, which is intended to be accomplished at the end of the research. On the other hand, specific objectives represent the specific research approaches which are required to be performed so as to accomplish overall research objectives or general objective.

The defined research objectives are given as follows:

1.4.1 General Objectives

The predominant objective of this research work is to study and examine the various motivational factors among Raj Yoga practitioners at Brahma Kumaris organization, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. The predominant objective of this thesis is to explore various factors that motivate people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation and get associated with Brahma Kumaris organization and philosophies.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

Specific research objectives are given as follows:

- 1. To study & analyze significant demographic factors motivating Raj Yoga meditation.**
- 2. To study & examine predominant motivational factors to learn Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris organization & its spiritual enlightening practices.**
- 3. To examine various spiritual, psychological & physiological factors that motivates people to learn Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.**

4. To explore factors having positive effect/ influence on motivation to learn Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris Worlds Spiritual University, Mount Abu, Rajasthan.

1.5 Research Contributions

This is the matter of fact that there are a number of significances of the presented research work. Some of the predominant contributions of the presented research work are given as follows:

The presented research work has intended to explore the various motivational factors that significantly influence people to follow Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris. Thus the identification of various factors such as psychological factors, physiological factors and spiritual factors etc can be helpful for people to consider Raj Yoga meditation as per their specific intends and expectations.

Unlike conventional secondary data based analysis, this research has been made based on empirical and analytical research approach, where the relevant responses have been collected from the devotees/ rajayoga practioners at Brahma Kumaris, International Headquarters. It enables optimal and precise information and conclusion. The primary data retrieved from the devotees/ rajayoga practioners enables better and more effective interpretation and therefore the statistical analysis based recognized motivational factors can be stated to be the most relevant and optimal.

In the present day scenarios, where families are breaking due to lack of faith & understanding, anti social activities such as crime, terrorism etc are increasing exponentially, the motivation towards Raja yoga can motivate and help people to accomplish super natural and peaceful life. As discussed in this thesis, the presentation of various advantages of BKRM can induce/ enthuse people in masses to consider regular Raja Yoga meditation and live a peaceful, blissful and value enriched life.

The empirical research performed in this thesis also intends to explore the very precise motivational attributes of the physiological, psychological and spiritual factors which can be explored to prepare a conceptual model to motivate people to join BKRM. Here, the predominant contribution can be the selection or identification of the precise motivational factor which is having significance for an individual.

The empirical analysis also signifies that Raja Yoga meditation does have great significance to enable human life peaceful, blissful, spiritual and connected with self ,

GOD, society etc. These characteristics can significantly motivate people to follow universal godly knowledge, universal brotherhood and value based life rather biased and narrowed life culture.

The research has revealed that the factors like soul and god consciousness, love, peace, bliss, self-transformation, vice less and ego less stage, positive thinking and positive attitude, self control and personality building, self respect and zeal towards getting divine virtues and power etc can be obtained by Raj yoga meditation. Hence, people can consider it for enabling more value enriched human life.

Furthermore, the responses retrieved from the devotees practicing BKRM and respective data analysis in this thesis has revealed that BKRM can be significant to deal with various mental, physiological and psychological problems such as tension, nervousness, fear and other negativities such as heart related diseases, diabetes etc.

The research has revealed that various factors like soul and god consciousness, love, peace, bliss, self transformation, vice less and ego less stage positive attitude, self control and personality building, and zeal towards getting divine virtues and power etc motivate people to follow Raj Yoga meditation. The effective provisioning of Raja Yoga can motivate masses acrosss globe to join and practice Raj Yoga to build a better world to live in.

The presented thesis has intended to describe various aspects of Brahma Kumaris and Raja Yoga meditation in a well designed manner, which can significantly help readers to know about it and thus resulting into encouraging people to practice Raja Yoga meditation. Thus, taking into consideration of these key contributions, it can be stated that the proposed research work and resulting outcomes can be of great significance for both the organizations (like Brahma Kumaris providing Raja yoga) as well as people or devotees to know about varied significances of Raja Yoga meditation and various practices. In addition, it can be helpful to know about BKRM practices and useful benefits, thus motivating people to join spiritual institutions such as Brahma Kumaris and practice Raj Yoga meditation.

1.6 Research Hypothesis

Taking into consideration of research objectives of study & analysis of existing literatures on Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris, in this research

proposal certain research hypothesis have been defined. Some of predominant research hypotheses defined for overall research study are given as follows:

Hypothesis-1:

Demography factors play very significant role in motivating people to adopt Raja Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

Hypothesis-2:

Personage thrust towards search for true spiritual means of life motivates people to become Raja yogis with Brahma Kumaris organization.

Hypothesis-3:

Psychological, Physiological & Spiritual factors are vital motivational factors that put enthuse in Raj yogis or Raja Yoga practitioners.

Hypothesis-4:

Novel life culture, environment & holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World's spiritual center at Mount Abu, Rajasthan motivates people to get associated with it.

1.7 Brahma Kumaris: Background

The presented thesis intends to study and analyse the key motivational factors which encourages people to join Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. In order to understand these intended motivational constructs, it is important to understand and awareness of Brahma Kumaris and Raj Yoga meditation. With these objectives, in this section of the presented thesis, brief discussions of Raj Yoga meditation and Brahma Kumaris organization have been presented. Initially, the Brahma Kumaris spiritual organization has been discussed with its functional discussion, which has been followed by Raj Yoga meditation and its significances in human life.

The Brahma Kumaris is a millenarian new religious movement (NRM) established in Northwest India in the 1930s and in 2009 is located in more than 120 countries. It defines members (BKs) of the Brahma Kumaris as social ascetics. BKs live a life of rigorous purity, based around their central practice of meditation. The disciplines of these social ascetics are designed to free the mind, through mastery over the body, culminating in self-sovereignty. While some BKs live in ashrams in moderately cloistered communities, most live at home with their families and conduct normal lives according to their environment, culture and circumstances. For this reason, BKs endure and moderate unique tensions as they arbitrate

leading a life that is spiritually meaningful while maintaining authentic relationships and fulfilling their worldly responsibilities.

The great majority of Brahma Kumaris administrators throughout the organization are women. The Brahma Kumaris teach that patriarchy is one of the most obvious signs that our world has fallen from the purity of the Golden Age. They teach that souls have no gender and thus all human beings are equally divine. Patriarchal customs pervert this truth by encouraging men to assume greater worth for themselves than women, and for women to assume themselves to be less capable than men. The Brahma Kumaris look forward to the return of a rapidly approaching Golden Age wherein men and women are entirely equal. Meanwhile, in order to aid its members in their efforts to balance their souls and attain perfect purity before the coming world transformation, the organization elevates women to the highest offices so they may learn to exercise their leadership abilities and so men may learn humility.

Significantly, the word “Kumaris” in the organization’s name, “Brahma Kumaris,” means “Children” in Hindi, and the Brahma Kumaris understand themselves as children of God, making them all siblings to each other. One of the organization’s three primary modes of interaction is familial, and it is in precisely this sense of sisterhood (and brotherhood) that the Brahma Kumaris understand family, with God as the only true parent.

Brahma Kumaris earn their level in the hierarchical administration by deepening the purity of their spiritual attainments, specifically the virtue of their moral conduct, their capacity for dignity and respect

Advancement within the organization is familial, spiritual, and administrative. Each of these three modalities for the attainment of power work together to provide checks and balances against the others

The Brahma Kumaris is the world’s first and largest spiritual movement led by women. It is the leading institution in the world catering to the spiritual needs of women- Seventy-five years ago the founder of this spiritual university while honoring women stated, “Women power opens the door of heaven” and attributed them a dignified position. Hence the name given to this Vishwa Vidyalaya, “Brahma

Kumari” is the ultimate status and dignity to women. This was one of the revolutionary steps in the history of Brahma Kumaris and in the whole of the world. The Brahma Kumaris has as its prime purpose of spreading the message of peace, love, unity and harmony all over the world. To accomplish this task, it has established nearly 9000 spiritual centres in every corner of the world. While speaking in the Brahma Kumaris All-India conference on Universal Values in Higher Education held from Oct.14 to 16, 2001 at Mount Abu, the Honorable Justice Ranganath Misra, Former Chief Justice, Supreme Court of India said:

“This institution should take over the responsibility of igniting the light into the teachers, into the students and into the community. If there is any place in the world today where spirituality is the order, I think it is this institution. Therefore an institution of this type, this level, this disposition, is perhaps the most capable institution to enthuse into the community the right thinking and the right process of activity.”

Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university is entirely dedicated to the enhancement of applied spiritual knowledge and human values through practical methods in the world. It has created its own literature based on personal experience and scientific research covering a wide array of spiritual knowledge and values.

Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university believes in our first priority for improvement in self. Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university, Mount Abu known for its serenity, spirituality and silent meditation, is also lovingly called ‘Madhuban’ which means ‘Forest of Honey’. In Madhuban, in God’s lap and under shelter and blessings of seniors we enjoyed the fortune of being the first family of Brahma Kumaris in Mount Abu. There is a spiritual gold mine within us, from which we can extract everything we need to live life gloriously, joyously and abundantly.

Brahma Kumaris contributed in easily accessible and pulsating panorama of practical wisdom enriched in oriental heritage of values, spirituality and yoga in crystallization of the self from the darkness of ignorance, so one may be able to sense their subtle presence and savor the essence of their messages for peace, purification and illumination of the mind. Deeply understanding the need of the hour, the Brahma Kumaris literature and teachings is promoting practical wisdom of character building

and enriching values that lie at the core of our inner being. Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university has dedicated its literature towards the immediate call of the time and towards changing people's outlook in these changing times.

The time has now come when only through the realization of the importance of values and spirituality in life, can sorrows and problems be healed. The seeds of peace and respect can be sowed in place of violence, hatred and war. It has been seen in history that love has been victorious over hatred and peace over disharmony and it has been realized this truth that all the wars of the world are never ended with weapons of hatred but have ceased with feelings of love, mutual understanding and respect for each other.

1.8 Brahma Kumaris: Historical Background

Some of the recent case studies done on the Brahma Kumaris include those by Wallis (2002) and Nagel (1999). Since these studies date from the early 1980s, some idea of the historical, theological and cultural development of the Brahma Kumaris, since the 1980s can be gained from these academic studies. This brings us up to the present time, which is operating with a stronger post-modern focus in relation to religion as noted by Clarke (2006a).

The Brahma Kumaris began in the early 1930s (Ramsay and Smith 2008) as a small spiritual community in Hyderabad, Sindh, India (now part of Pakistan). Formalizing their congregation in August 1938 (Radhe 1943), the community called itself Avinashi Gyān Yagya but was referred to by others as Om Mandli (sacred circle). Om Mandli consisted primarily of young women from the Bhaiband community, a social caste of merchants and traders in Hyderabad Sindh. In the 1950s, the community was officially named Brahmā Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya, which translates as the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University.

Collectively, previous studies offer an important overview of the organization's change over forty years, particularly Nagel's (1999), which explores BK theology in depth. Walliss's study follows others (Babb 1984; Skultans 1993; Howell and Nelson 1997; Puttick 1997; Howell 2005; Howell 2000) that track the organization's changing identity over time. Walliss noticed that the imminent destruction of the world, predicted on at least three occasions, had not yet taken place (Beit-Hallahmi 2003)and, in consequence , the organization and its members became increasingly involved in world affairs. The movement had gone from one where members isolated themselves from the world, through being solely a teaching

organization in India with firm ideas on the date of world destruction, to a social movement. Placed in a post-modern world, the Brahma Kumaris had adapted itself and started offering a variety of programs to suit the needs of different groups of people (Clarke 2006a).

Another particular notation in a number of scholarly texts (Babb 1984; Howell 1998; Puttick 1997; Puttick 1999; Skultans 1993; Sudesh 1993) is the remarkable status of women in the Brahma Kumaris and the role the organization has played in changing cultural opinions of women in India (Lalrinawma 2004) particularly within and on the margins of extended BK communities. Babb refers to Brahma Kumaris as “indigenous feminism in a modern Hindu sect” (1984:399), and noted that the “sensibilities of women have contributed in very important ways to the ideology of the movement” (1982:50).

Despite local perceptions of women as ritually impure during menstruation (Olson 2007b) and generally more impure than men (Madan 2003; Sinclair –Brull 1997), the founder still considered that women held innate purity and made superior spiritual teachers. At the time of its foundation, and still in many countries where BKs operate, young girls and women of the community would normally have been betrothed at a young age, committing them to a family, and by definition unchaste, life. In joining the Yagya, and giving their dowries to the movement, young girls and women were dismissing tradition and choosing to live spiritually autonomous and celibate lives (Khandelwal 1997). Women left their family homes, not always with family support; female children, mothers and elderly women were repeatedly kidnapped by their families and suffered beatings; caste vegetarians were forced to eat pig meat by angry relatives; and women were shackled or placed in locked rooms for months at a time (Radhe 1939). This violence and suffering may be part of what led to members’ early seclusion and world rejection.

Today, the Brahma Kumaris organization is truly global (Smith 2008), with over 7000 centres in 128 countries, territories and islands. Many are located in places of unrest, including in the Middle East, Africa and communist Asia. In many of these places, the appointed BK representative must be extremely cautious, and present spiritual ideas in ways that are compatible with the ideas accepted within, and acceptable to, that culture. In at least one place, BKs teach people techniques to remain peaceful and to lead a happier life, but are unable to

use the words ‘meditation’, ‘yoga’, ‘soul’, ‘spirituality’ or ‘God’ because of the country’s political stance. While the BKs believe that the world will become an increasingly difficult place to inhabit, they consistently place themselves in some of its most challenging areas and work at creating authentic symbiotic relationships with people of repute to garner cooperation for their outreach work.

The Brahma Kumaris arose from a Hindu cultural base in Northwest India under strong Muslim influences. On one hand the Brahma Kumaris is classified as a Hindu sect (Babb 1984; Chowdhry 1996), or as Neo-Hinduistic (Clarke 2006b), yet many of the Brahma Kumaris tenets, such as monotheism, celibacy for women and no temple worship, sit clearly outside Hindu beliefs. Some BKs consider their path to be distinct from Hinduism, as do other Indian founded NRMs, including the International Society for Krishna Consciousness (ISKCON), Ad-Dharm (Juergensmeyer 1988) and Radhasoami (Jestice 2004). Brahma Kumaris’ daily theology draws on Hindu scripture as its reference point, but it also includes teachings from the Granth (Sikh scripture), the Bible (Christian scripture) and the Qura'n (Muslim scripture), as well as oral and text based knowledge of Buddha, Jainism and the Arya Samaj (the Hindi reform movement established in 1875). By touching on all faiths in its discourses, Brahma Kumaris theology can be seen as ecumenical rather than for or against any established religious path. However, many people who lived in the same community as Om Mandli members believed that their philosophy threatened fundamental Hindu values (Chaudhuri 2003).

The Brahma Kumaris founder, Dada Lekhraj, was born as Lekhraj KhubchandKriplani to a school teacher. Some authors maintain that he was born in 1876-7 (Piven 2004b) and others 1870 (Mitchiner 1992). Documents from founding members (Radhe 1939) and memories of local politicians (Hardy 1984) of the 1930s declare that he was 54 years of age in 1938 making his birth year 1884. In the beginning, members of the BK community may have surmised Dada’s age to be 60 because, according to dharma texts (Olson 2007b), this is the age at which a man initiates his spiritual life. Today, this age is colloquially referred to as sathiyana or ‘gone sixtyish’ in north Indian local vernacular (Cohen 1998) and serves as a useful cultural category and life marker that reflects age-specific attitudes, beliefs and behaviours.

With these ashramas in mind, and considering the restrictive society of the period when Om Mandli was founded, the fortuitous synchronicity of Dada 'being 60' may have been considerably more important than factual birth dates. In any case, names and dates of birth, the two forms of identity so important for many non-Indians, are historically fluid and changeable in India and subject to limited registration (Agrawal 1969). Nineteen and early twentieth century dates of birth in India were vague and unreliable at best (Weiner 1973), and birth names were sometimes changed to suit stages of life or astrological reckonings. Some elder BKs, who were children in the 1930s, relied on the physical stature and the reported age of their peers to help them determine their own age. This is an issue of contention for some inquirers, particularly from the United Kingdom, which is the home of a website that promotes heated and mostly negative debates about the Brahma Kumaris.

Dada Lekhraj was part of the Bhaiband merchant community and a Hindu follower of the Vallabacharya sect (a Vaishnav sect started by Sri Vallabhacharya(1479-1531) who promulgated Vedanta non-dualistic philosophy. The Hindus in Sindh were divided into two classes, the Amils and the Bhaibands. The Amils were highly educated, with many occupying professional and government positions in Hyderabad and Karachi. They were cultured and polished, often holding high offices. Conversely, the Bhaibands were businessmen who traded in silk, curios and textiles. Most were not well educated, the majority not having completed their secondary schooling. However, the Bhaibands earned wealth and notability through their diaspora to Singapore, Hong Kong and Bangkok, while still maintaining their home offices in Hyderabad. The men typically lived abroad, enjoying their mistresses and returning home for a month or so every couple of years. Their wives and children remained in Hyderabad and lived chaste and moral lives, as was expected of them. Due to the lengthy history of Muslim rule, Islamic values compounded local Indian and Hindu attitudes towards women in Northwest India, with restrictions on sexuality and inflexible ideas of morality (Ikram 1989; Chand 2006). The veiling and seclusion of women became the norm in this patrilineal and patrilocal society. Throughout his early life, Dada Lekhraj was a well-respected lay Hindu, had two gurus, and a facility for reciting sacred texts such as the central and revered Hindu scripture, Shrimad Bhagavad Gītā and the Sikh scripture, the Gurū Granth Sāhib indicating his affinity with the culture and religions of Northwest India. Dada enjoyed entertaining holy men, sages and ascetics, and going on regular pilgrimages through northern India. While he was young, he saved up his earnings as a small merchant of wheat, typical of a Bhaiband, and entered the diamond trade to work in Kolkata. Dada quickly developed a good reputation in the jewellery business and, as time passed, he formed friendships with many of the rulers and with people from the wealthy classes of Northwest India, who became his regular clients.

By 1984 the Brahma Kumaris was established in approximately 30 countries. In 1986 the Brahma Kumaris conducted its first international program, the Million Minutes of Peace, for which it received seven UN Peace Messenger awards. For Million Minutes of Peace, people from 88 countries donated minutes of peace through time spent in prayer, meditation and peaceful thought, creating a 'bank' of peace. In four weeks(mid September to mid – October 1986) 1,231,975,713 minutes (equivalent to 2,344 years) were collected. In 1988, the Global Cooperation for a Better world was created as a follow –up to million minutes of Peace. People were asked to share their visions of what a better world might look like through dialogue, art, performance and workshops. The Living Values Education Program (Tillman 2007), as well as other values –based initiatives (virola and corpus 2008), began from these pioneering initiatives.

As BK international membership has continued to expand, with 100,000 in 1988 and 850,000 in 2009, the organization has constructed two new campuses: Gyān Sarovar (1995) that accommodates 1700 people and is halfway down the mountain, and Shāntivan (1998), in the plains of Rajasthan at the foot of Mt Abu. Shantivan, the former farm where BKs would stop for fresh sugar cane on the way up the mountain, has been completely redeveloped. Shantivan now resembles a village (see Chapter Four), capable of feeding and accommodating more than 11,000 people a day. These campuses accommodate pilgrims who come in tens of thousands from within India and overseas for regular meetings and spiritual retreats during the summer season between September and April, the cooler season. There are particular times reserved for Indians and foreigners, arranged to expedite comfortable accommodation for large (15,000) and small (3,000) numbers respectively. The division between 'Indian season' and 'foreign season' is somewhat flexible, with both Indians and foreigners invariably present at each occasion. Visitors from India usually stay for only a few days given their large numbers, whereas the recommended length of stay for foreigners is two weeks, particularly considering the distances some non –Indian BKs cover to get there.

The practice of open- eyed raja yoga enables positive feelings and good wishes to be exchanged through the practice of drishti, a most fundamental form of spiritual dharnā (inculcation of divine virtues) and a sacred ritual for BKs. Drishti is both a natural spiritual gaze, and the act of exchanging positive energetic vibrations through the eyes. BKs understand that a meditative state of mind creates an

atmosphere the vibration of which can be transmitted to one another through the eyes. Drishti is considered to be one of the highest forms of expressing spiritual love, power and good feeling between souls. While the eyes are open, attention is focused inward, and so the eyes are passive, used only to transmit vibrations and not to 'see' (Whaling 1995).

Meditation for BKs is a relationship between the soul and the Supreme Soul. The starting point of meditation is always soul consciousness, and the techniques used by novices are the same as those used by BKs of seventy years in gyān. Through the ascetic practices of hypo-arousal techniques (Howell 1997:151) to discipline the mind, BKs first slow their thoughts and maintain mental quietude while concentrating on the self as a soul and remembering the Supreme Soul. The idea is to slow down the mind enough so that thoughts then produce experiences. This practice often produces altered states of consciousness (Howell 1997). During meditation and in daily life, BKs aim to experience the sustenance and happiness of all relationships, such as those of mother, father, friend, companion, child and guide, with Shiv Baba. BKs say they enjoy a meditative state free of all external supports (including mantras, breathing, positions and chanting), drawing all forms of power and sustenance from Shiv Baba.

As a leading institution imparting education in spiritual knowledge and human values the Brahma Kumaris offers people of all backgrounds an opportunity to explore the deep mysteries of the soul, God, karma, the cycle of time and the technique of Raja yogameditation. Various workshops and training modules help people practise positive thoughts, emotions, attitudes and behaviours that develop their innate values and powers.

The spirit of inclusiveness, co-operation and warmth in the Brahma Kumaris family helps individuals experience and express the best in them. Millions of individuals and families all over the world have brought about a qualitative change in their lives through these courses.

Apart from the basic course in meditation, the institution offers the following courses in places like hospitals, schools, prisons and business and industrial establishments:

- Foundation Course in Raja yoga Meditation
- Self- Empowerment Workshops
- Stress Management and Right Thinking

- Diploma, P.G. Diploma & M.Sc., in Values & Spirituality
- M.B.A. in Self Management & Crises Management
- Clean the Mind & Green the Earth Project
- Life Management Skills
- Positive Change in Life (for youth)
- Positive Approach to Total Health
- Values in Family Life (for women)
- The Art of Happy Living

Other Spiritual Courses

Throughout the world the Brahma Kumari's centres offer a variety of short courses, lectures and seminars which focus on the development of specific personal skills and qualities of character.

These include:

- ✓ **Positive Thinking**- How to use the mind in a positive and focused way.
- ✓ **Stress Free Living**-Understanding, managing and preventing stress.
- ✓ **Self Managing Leadership** – A course for professionals on how to manage one's thoughts, emotions and behavior when in a management role.
- ✓ **The Four Faces of Woman** – Reconnecting with the eternal self.
- ✓ **Self Management Quality of Life** – How to increase your self-value
- ✓ **The Secrets of Self-Esteem** – How to build and sustain self-esteem and self-worth.
- ✓ **Project Positive Change** – How to develop a Positive Personality
- ✓ **Positive Approach to Total Health (PATH)**
- ✓ **Stress Management And Right Thinking(SMART)**

1.9 Global Headquarters & Campuses:

The Brahma Kumaris global headquarters are based in Mount Abu, Rajasthan, in India. There are three campuses-two at Mount Abu and one at the foothills near Abu Road-that serve millions of people round the year as spiritual retreat centers, conference venues and academic facilities offering value education courses.

If the location of all the old civilization across the world like Egyptian, Easter Islands, Mayan etc, joined by a lay line on the earth, then Mount Abu which is in the Aravali Hills in India comes on the same lay line. The latitude and longitude of Mount Abu are 240N and 720E. With reference to the earth, there is an Rajasthan, India, hence it is the centre point of Earth. **At Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India is the centre point of Earth and GOD Shiva incarnates at this place and teaches the real spiritual**

knowledge and ancient Indian Raja yoga meditation which people wants to learn eagerly and through which the present Iron age will transformed into heaven.

On one side humanity is searching for GOD in temples, mosques, churches and Gurudwars at the same time scientists are doing deep research to reveal the secrets of this wonderful universe and on another side, Almighty GOD, has manifested Himself in the beautiful nature of arravali hills at the International HQ of Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan India. “THE ARTIST OF THE UNIVERSE, PAINTING THE GOLDEN REALITY WHICH WILL BE KNOWN TO THE WORLD IN THE NEAR FUTURE”.

Today, the fans of famous scientist Nikola Tesla are feeling that he will come back as he had mentioned on 17th July 1930 that, “SOMETIMES, BUT NOT NOW, I WILL ANNOUNCE SOMETHING WHICH YOU CANNOT FIND IN FAIRY TALES”.

Transformation of the universe from Iron age to Golden age is the top most event in the history o humanity which is going to happened and cannot found in fairy tales. For the forth coming Golden age, Nikola Tesla’s science of infinity and Eternal will be the reality and once again there will be the confluence of science and spirituality.

1.9.1 INTERNATIONAL HEAD QURTERS-MOUNT ABU, RAJASTHAN

In 1950, the institution moved to Mount Abu, a quiet place reputed for its ancient heritage and regarded as a sacred destination by many in search of spiritual rejuvenation and empowerment. Nestled high in the Aravali Mountains of Rajasthan, it provided an ideal location for reflection and contemplation. In the folklore of ancient texts, Abu is praised as a holy place and is associated with the names of sages and seers; thus there are many temples and hermitages to be found upon it

1.9.2 World Headquarters Campuses

However, a short walk takes you away from the maze of activity into the tranquil seclusion of this sacred destination whose atmosphere emanates a sense of enchantment; and to the worldwide headquarters of the Brahma Kumaris from whence the knowledge of the king of all yogas, Raja Yoga, is disseminated. The headquarters complex consists of mainly three campuses -Madhuban (Pandav Bhawan & Om Shanti Bhawan),Gyau Sarovar and Shantivan -- as well as a recreational park called Peace Park, and the Global Hospital & Research Centre (GHRC)

1.9.3 Madhuban-Forest of Honey

Over the decades the Madhuban campus has evolved into an expansive, yet still homely, complex of dormitories, residential units, meditation venues and buildings that house dining facilities, administrative offices, a literature shop, a telephone exchange and a dispensary.

Nestled amidst the Aravalli hills near Nakkl Lake, Madhuban- the Forest of Honey - exudes old world charm and a powerful spiritual ambience created by years of meditation by senior Rajyogis, Lakhs of BK students go to Madhuban each year for spiritual refreshment and advanced spiritual learning.

- It serves as the global headquarters of the Brahmakumaris.
- It is the campus where the founder of the institution, Prajapita Brahma, and its first administrative head, Mateshwari Jagadamba Saraswati, nurtured a small congregation into a nationwide spiritual movement in the 1950s and 60s.
- Besides residential quarters and offices, it has a grand Universal Peace Hall
 - Om Shanti Bhawan - a 3,000-seat auditorium that has been hosting international and national conventions since 1983.
- Saba's room, Saba's hut, Tower of Peace and History Hall • memorials dedicated to Prajapita Brahma are the main attractions for lakhs of spiritual pilgrims.

1.9.3.1 Madhuban Campus-Pandav Bhawan, Mt. Abu

Cradled by Mt. Abu 's rugged splendour and lush vegetation, and nestled near the still waters of Nakki Lake, lies 'Madhuban', the global headquarters of the Brahma Kumaris.

Madhuban is a place where thousands of BK students from nearly **142 countries** gather to deepen their meditation practice. Madhuban's clear and subtle atmosphere of spirituality inspires profound experiences. A practitioner of Raja Yoga meditation has no need to make radical changes in life-style or permanently leave home and family. However, a few weeks in Madhuban, away from worldly responsibilities, dramatically assists a student's spiritual growth. Lectures and workshops provide essential tools which enable students to explore and emerge the powers of spirituality innate within each human being.

1.9.3.2 Om Shanti Bhawan (Universal Peace Hall)

Om Shanti Bhawan was constructed in 1983 in which the main assembly hall, Universal Peace Hall, is situated. It is a very attractive assembly hall and 5,000 people can sit in it. Besides this, there is facility of translation in 16 languages simultaneously. It has been declared as a public tourist place. More than 8,000 people come here to see it daily. Every year spiritual conferences are organized here on a large scale. Special facilities of Raja yoga Education for Indian as well as for foreign brothers and sisters are available here. So, seminars relating to values and spirituality are held here.

1.9.3.3 Pandav Bhawan

The spiritual students experience extreme peace as they enter Pandav Bhawan at Abu. They remember God on the premises spontaneously. It is believed that Pandavas accepted God Shiva as their charioteer after they had renounced all the mundane luxuries. In the same way, the dedicated and surrendered souls who dwell here accept God Shiva as their Supreme Father, Teacher, Satguru ! The surrendered brothers and sisters live a very simple life style and experience deep meditation daily

1.9.3.4 Tower of Peace

Brahma Baba left his mortal coil on 18th January, 1969 and the memorial named 'Tower of Peace' was raised. This is a memorial that symbolizes sacrifice and tapasya of Pila Shri Brahma and eradicates the vices of the vicious people. The tower of peace, knowledge, might and purity inspire the people to lead pure and yogi life, It creates a feeling as if Brahma Baba is calling his children from the subtle world. The visitors regard it as a living temple. The B.Ks consider it as Maha Dham. God says, 'If you want to be powerful, come to this place.'

1.9.4 World Renewal Spiritual Museum

The Spiritual Museum is situated in the heart of Mount Abu , near the historical Nakki Lake. It attracts tourists coming from India and abroad. There are fascinating large statues and translights which very effectively show that the era of vices and sorrows is to be over soon and replaced by Satyuga having purity, peace, bliss.

This museum provides the knowledge of the whole world and the four yugas including the fifth short yuga of confluence - the Sangam yuga. The tableau of Golden Bharat fills our mind with ecstasy. It also provides the knowledge of karmic philosophy. In this museum, a laser show is shown free of cost which presents the perfect combination of science and spirituality. At the end of this show, the visitors experience the effect of Raja yogathrough the laser beams for a few minutes.

There is a Raja yogaroom in this museum wherein visitors are given Raja yogatraining. Godly knowledge and Raja yogacamps are organized here in the evening and morning.

1.9.5 Gyan Sarovar – Lake of Knowledge

Gyan Sarovar is officially known as 'The Academy for a Better World'. The name Gyan Sarovar is reminiscent of 'Mansarovar', about which a legend goes that anyone who dipped into the lake emerged in the form of a fairy or an angel. Gyan Sarovar is an environment which enables individuals to dip into the ' Lake of Knowledge ' and emerge highly transformed.

Founded by the Brahma Kumaris in 1996, the Gyan Sarovar Academy for a Better World was inaugurated as part o f the celebration of the University's 60th anniversary. The Academy is an international campus - a place where men, women and children can reach their unique human potential and cultivate the values of our common humanity.

1.9.5.1 Gyan Sarovar Campus

Gyan Sarovar is a community development project that involved the construction of a complete village complex on 35 acres of land. On this land, which is located on Mt. Abu four kilometres from Madhuban, the Brahma Kumaris have created a retreat atmosphere without disturbing the natural topography and the original environment. The design integrates both urban and rural elements into a harmonious and holistic environment which lends itself to being eco-friendly and free from air and noise pollution

1.9.5.2 Gyan Sarovar • Academy for Better World:

Gyan Sarovar is an ultra-modern campus in a rural setting that presents a soul elevating, eco-friendly atmosphere where learning and experiencing spiritual values become an unforgettable experience.

- Spread over 35-acres, it is located four kilometres from Pandav Bhawan.
- Inaugurated in 1995, it has a state-of-the art 1600-seat auditorium with translation facilities for 22 languages. There are 14 seminar and training rooms, accommodation for 800 guests, dining halls, a library, an art gallery, meditation rooms, a health clinic and orchards.
- Each year the academy hosts international events such as the Call of the Time Dialogue, Peace of Mind Retreat and National Dialogue, conferences and seminars that have attracted leading professionals from the fields of science, administration, healthcare, law, business and management, education and the media.

1.9.5.3 Spiritual Art Gallery

There is a Spiritual Art Gallery that is built with the co-operation of people of the world. This exhibits various spiritual facets and is equipped with art, sound and modern technology. This place is furnished by Bks. The knowledge of soul and Supreme Soul has been explained with the help of modern audio-visual aids. The technology of science and silence is also included. The main attractions are audio-visual shows, laser shows, hologram and multi-media presentations. No visit to Gyan Sarovar is complete without seeing The Spiritual Art Gallery. The entry to the Gallery is free of any charges.

Harmony Hall, Baba's Oval-shaped room, Meditation room, Russian fountain are worth seeing. Baba's Hut is a point of attraction for visitors. There is a Training Centre that has 13 halls which can accommodate 150 people each. There is another noteworthy place, Spiritual Application Research Centre (SPARC).

For the smooth administration of the Institution, it is divided into certain Wings for the welfare of the society such as Science and Engineering, Media, Sports, Education, Political, Religious, Administration, Cultural, Jurists, Security, Women. Social Service, Business and Industries, Youth, Medical, Transport and Rural. In these rooms, there is seating capacity for 75 to 150 people. There is a Shiva Bhola Nath Bhandara, Dining Hall in which 2000 people can dine simultaneously at 7

different counters. There is a big auditorium in the Academy, which is known as Harmony Hall. 1800 people can sit in it. There is a translation facility in 17 languages simultaneously. The sound system is excellent. The Hall is equipped with heating and cooling facilities.

There are 30,000 different kinds of trees and plants in this academy which make this place very charming. In 1996, the Academy was presented to Habitat II, the second UN Conference on Human Settlements held in Istanbul, Turkey. It was recognized as part of the Best Practice Initiative for Human Settlements.

1.9.5.4 Gyan Sarovar Programs

Because the Brahma Kumaris see spirituality as the key to an ethical and moral renaissance and lasting social harmony, the programmes offered at Gyan Sarovar include subjects such as self-empowerment, self-management, positive thinking, meditation, practical spirituality and organisational leadership. These programmes, courses and retreats focus on achieving long-term and lasting changes in attitude, behaviour and lifestyles. They draw on the experience and insights gained, and the methods, techniques and skills developed, during the Brahma Kumaris' sixty-year history

1.9.6 Global Hospital & Research Center (GHRC)

Western Rajasthan is one of the least privileged areas of India. Much of it is desert, water is in short supply and the illiteracy rate is high. The majority of the population has long been deprived of basic health measures. This situation began to change in 1990 with the establishment of the J. Watumull Memorial Global Hospital and Research Centre, a Brahma Kumaris initiative. Designed to provide high quality, modern, holistic healthcare services in a tranquil, rural environment, the hospital offers free or subsidised treatment and medicine to 100,000 people, of whom 54,000 are tribal residents inhabiting 855 primitive villages. The hospital is managed and run by a charitable trust established and supported by members of the Brahma Kumaris. To know more, please visit the Global Hospital & Research Centre.

The Global Hospital and Research Centre is a dream come true for the tribals and local people of Mount Abu. The GHRC was built with an aim to provide holistic health-care in this predominantly rural and poor area, by blending the

best of western science and oriental remedies with the techniques of Raja yoga meditation. The unique aspect of GHRC is its beautiful surroundings, clean interiors and the serene, smiling faces of the hospital staff.

Day to day operations in GHRC are supervised by qualified personnel, most of whom are also practitioners of Raja yogameditation. It has 15 clinics in the Out-Patient Department, 70 in-patient beds, fully equipped operating rooms, radiology and pathlab for diagnostic procedures and special clinics for homeopathy, magnetotherapy and nature cure. The hospital provides more than 80% of its services free of charge. Other salient features of GHRC are:

- Free consultation.
- Free treatment and free supply of medicines to those who are unable to pay, as well as to those who are dedicated to spiritual and religious orders.
- Providing free diagnosis, treatment and medicines in remote villages of Mount Abu under the Village Outreach Programme.
- Educating the local community about physical, mental and moral well-being.
- Providing ambulance services.
- Organizing diagnostic and screening camps for the ophthalmology department and general medicine patients.

Organizing Coronary Artery Disease Regression Programmes at regular intervals by changing life style

1.9.7 Peace Park

The Brahma Kumaris Peace Park is both lovely and serene, a natural environment where silence and recreation co-exist. The park offers a perfect recreational environment, with level playing fields, picnic areas, swings, and nature walks. Nestled between two famous peaks of the Aravali hills-the well known spiritual pilgrimage destinations of Gum Shikhar and Achal Garb-Peace Park is an oasis of natural beauty only 8 kms from the Madhuban campus.

1.9.7.1 Speciality of Peace Park: -

The Peace Park is a tribute to the Brahma Kumaris' commitment to sustaining natural environments. The park is an oasis of natural beauty where silence and recreation co-exist. It is located 8 km from the BK headquarters. The park offers:

- Guided tours to appreciate the natural beauty of the environs.

- Short video presentation on concepts of Rajyoga. Meditation experience in a choice of venues – open – air grass hut, stone cave or bamboo meditation hut.
- Perfect recreation retreat, with playing fields, picnic areas, swings, and nature walks.

Unique rock gardens with a wide variety of succulents. Orchard area, citrus corner, floral displays of ornamental shrubs, coleus, geraniums, hibiscus, climbers and creepers and a rose garden.

1.9.7.2 Main Attractions of Peace Park:

- Learning more about Raja yoga Knowledge and Self.
- Guide Lines for Inner Introspection, meditation and concentration with the Supreme Father.
- Experiencing external beauty and silence with internal beauty peace and bliss.
- Donating peaceful vibrations for world peace.
- Audio visual shows and meditations huts.
- Children's Park.
-

1.9.8 Shantivan

At the base of Mount Abu , just before Abu Road begins its climb up Mount Abu, to the left of the road, a magnificent complex, the third Brahma Kumaris campus, Shantivan. This sprawling collection of buildings was built in response to Institutions' ever-growing world-transforming activities in the area of spiritual education and training. It provides an excellent venue for holding large conferences, spiritual congregations and retreats, and features modern means of communication, transport, extensive kitchen and dining facilities, well-laid-out roads, electricity, and solar energy.

1.9.8.1 Shantivan-Forest of Peace (Talhati, Abu Road)

The fast pace of service across the world has seen the BK family growing and attracting spiritual seekers in large numbers. Consequently, by 1997 a huge campus, Shantivan, came up at the foot of Mount Abu, outside Abu Road town.

- It is the largest campus of Brahma Kumaris, hosting spiritual retreats, training programmes and conferences round the year.

- It includes accommodation for 15,000 people; a three-storey dining complex, a conference hall, six seminar halls, two meditation rooms and an art gallery.
- It has a printing press for publishing BK literature, magazines and publicity material.
- Its most striking feature is the mammoth Diamond Hall, which can seat 20,000 people.
- It has the largest parabolic solar facility in India for cooking and generating electricity.

1.9.8.2 Majestic Diamond Hall

The main attraction of Shantivan is its massive, awe-inspiringly Diamond Hall, built to commemorate the Diamond Jubilee of the University. Majestic in art, architecture and equipment, it has the distinction of being able to seat 20,000 people! The Shantivan complex includes a main conference hall and six smaller halls. The seating capacity of the conference hall is twelve hundred and there is facility for simultaneous translation in sixteen languages. The smaller halls each accommodate three hundred and fifty people and are suitable for lectures, seminars, workshops, etc. There are also two halls for meditation and a spiritual museum on this campus.

1.9.8.3 lotus-formed 'Tapasya Dham'

A lotus-shaped 'Tapasya Dham' is built in Shantivan. It is a round-shaped building of which the upper part is shaped like the leaves of a lotus. The gentle fountains around this Dham soothe the mind. There is a small garden where Rajyogis meditate at a solitary place and thus are benefitted spiritually.

In addition to this gigantic structure, Shantivan has the largest parabolic solar device in India, which provides steam heat for cooking; and, together with wind energy, provides electricity for computers, the telephone exchange and emergency lighting systems

1.9.8.4 Tower of Light (Prakash Sthambh)

Dadi Prakashmani ji, former Chief of Brahma Kumaris left her mortal body on 25th August, 2007. An eight pillar memorial, 'Tower of Light (Prakash Sthambh)' at Shantivan, Abu Road has been built in commemoration of Dadi's endearing spiritual administration and selfless services for over 38 years as Head of the Institution after

the demise of its Founder Prajapita Brahma on 18 January, 1969. The Tower of Light is octagonal in shape having eight angles symbolising eight divine powers which late Dadi Prakashmani embodied. The bottom portion of the tower is a raised marble-made pedestal capped with shape and picture of a globe symbolizing late Dadi's global spiritual services. And on the top of the tower is a big oval shaped greenish starlight representing "Jewel Of Light."

1.10 GODLY WOOD STUDIO

'Morality through Raja yoga Spirituality', is a concept which need to be revolutionized. It is like a show to be played and recorded in the mind of 'Media professors and advocates'. In its endurance to bring transparency in all walk and talk of media, Incorporeal God Shiva, through Brahma Kumaris, has gifted to every Robin hood of Multi media planet, a creation called Godly wood Studio.

Aims of Godly wood studio:-

- √ To awaken the masses with high –tech facilities and train them in Godly Knowledge and easy Raja Yoga
- √ To relay the live shows of Brahma Kumaris teachings and meditation courses
- √ To prepare and relay such courses for a tension free and spiritual living
- √ To bring about the manifestation of Godly plan of the new World through transformation and propagation of purity, peace and propriety.

Inspiration -This highly advanced electronic media studio creates television programs and films dedicated to spreading spiritual knowledge and Raja Yoga meditation. This ambitious studio project is intended to create various spiritually oriented TV programs and films was conceived and initiated by BK. Ramesh Shah, Managing Trustee of the Brahma Kumaris.

Location-Godlywood Studio, is situated at foothills of Aravalis Mountain Range, within boundaries of Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters-Manmohini Complex campus, located near Abu Road, Rajasthan, The inaugural ribbon cutting ceremony was celebrated on 16th October, 2012, through hands of Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris & .Her Excellence in Divinity, Respectable Rajyogini, Dadi Jankiji. Godly wood, from its time of

inception, from throughout the world, has been attracting talent, with value oriented temperament, meant for Conscience exhibition and Universal brotherhood.

Building & Architecture – Godly wood studio is a six floored building with cute construction & design and is a standing example of ‘Architectural beauty’ & Cultural wisdom.’ It is comprised with 3 state of art Video Studios, which are armored with Hi Tech Technology summarized in its Lightning Systems, Control rooms with audio visual switchers and facility of remote operation of the cameras. The whole shooting takes places through cameras which support High Definition (HD) program productions along with taste of Dolby.

Facilities – Godly wood studio has the Preview Theatre with 5.1 Mixing facility and prolific sound system. The preview Theatre has intake of 25 audiences for preview of films, drama & episodes. The Audio Recording Studio, present on its 6th floor, has instruments to bring life in the voice and rejuvenating effects in music. Animation Department of Godlywood, situated at 4th floor is gifted by creative team & supported by network of workstations which can roll eyes on animated, finer objects of creativeness.

Theme-Integrity with diversity Within walls of Godlywood-No one can miss the essence of " Integrity within Diversity" viz. the mosaic created due to different Regional language departments.

Programmes-Godlywood contains departments to support various programs that can run on regional languages, namely Gujarati, Bengali, Marathi, Malayalam & Telugu. The creations of Godlywood Studio are its shows, which get telecast on Peace of Mind or in Godlywood Web TV, a self run Internet based TV. Behind them, there is backbone of professionals, experienced in productions & entertainment.

Some of the important popular programmes from Godlywood are :

- a) Hindi Language :- Samadhaan, Ek Mulaqat, Divine Harmony, Ruhani Rahein, Aahwan, Shashwat Yogik Kheti, Sehat ki baat, etc.
- b) English language :- Fireside chat, all about brahma kumaris, The world we want, Light of Knowledge.
- c) Gujrati:- Aatma jagruti,
- d) Bengali:- Bhalo Tahkun Pratidin, Ghare ela maa,
- e) Marathi :- jeevan mulya, pankhaana bal daya,
- f) Telugu :- amrit dhara

g) The “Peace News” – It is the latest introduction – which is making waves among the viewers, can also be seen through the Web TV, Our Peace News covers many languages of Indian States like Marathi, Bengali, Malayalam and Gujarati as well as International BK news and represents in Hindi language.

Peace News Schedule :- One can watch Peace news on Peace of mind channel at 9am on Tuesday, Thursday and Saturday. Non stop news 50 on Sunday at 12.45pm & 10pm.

Other Initiative :- Web TV

It is one of most cherished dream of Godlywood studio and was inaugurated on December 3, 2013 by B.K. Rameshshahji, chairperson, who gave momentum to this hugely successful venture. Now the entire world can see what is happening in Godlywood studio through a new innovative web technology called "Web T.V.". Right now the Godlywood Studio produces many serials, talk shows and other value based programs which telecasts on peace of mind channel and other national or regional channels. Now these programs can also be viewed on Web TV with convenience and liberty of accessing to this TV anytime, anywhere, as they like. With the ultimate aim of serving the mankind through the spiritual powers, most of the contents will be based on spirituality, morality and educative themes. Some of the important popular programmes of Godlywood namely, Ek Mulaqat, Divine Harmony, Aahwan, the "Peace News" etc, can also be seen through the Web TV. Programmes covers many languages of Indian States like Marathi, Bengali, Malayalam ,Punjabi, Telugu and Gujarati apart from Hindi and English.

Technological upgradation :-

To achieve its vision, Godlywood studio has installed a HARMAN's Studer Vista 1 mixing console to serve at the heart of the studio, **marking the first installation of a Studer Vista 1 in India.**

In addition to the Studer Vista 1, Godlywood Studios deployed a full array of HARMAN technologies in the space, including three JBL 3730 Screen Array cinema loudspeakers, one JBL 4642A subwoofer and eight JBL 8320 compact cinema surround loudspeakers. The system is powered with five Crown DSi 1000 and two DSi 4000 amplifiers.

Godlywood Studios also features an audio dubbing studio equipped with AKG C414 microphones and dbx processors, as well as an HD multicam shooting floor that has JBL LSR4326 studio monitors.

One can visit the website <http://www.godlywoodstudio.org>, <http://www.youtube.com/c/Godlywoodstudio>, www.facebook.com/godlywoodstudio, <http://twitter.com/godlywoodstudio>, One can contact on email: godlywoodstudio@gmail.com.

1.11 PEACE OF MIND TV CHANNEL-GODS GREATEST GIFT TO SPIRITUAL ENLIGHTENMENT

With present day, media acting as strong eye opener for one and all, the necessity of offering "Positive Food for Thought" was felt strongly by Brahma kumaris. The BK institution have taken to this initiative in many ways, the latest one being launching of a TV Channel exclusively dedicated to the cause of inner awakening and strengthening the moral fibre of society. Brahma Kumaris brings Peace of mind Channel for living peaceful life.

ABOUT PMTV:-

Peace of Mind, as the name suggests, is a channel that helps viewers experience peace and joy in their life through programmes that not only entertain but also enrich, empower and enlighten them. Yet, this is not another religious channel. Peace of Mind shows viewers how they can lead a more focused, stable, healthy and successful life by using spiritual principles effectively. It shows a better way of life whereby one can achieve success without stress, enjoy harmonious relationships at work and at home, and have the inner strength to deal with all challenges.

The channel provides an eclectic mix of programmes, including guided meditation, songs, talks by experts on self-improvement and the practical application of spirituality in various walks of life, besides cultural programmes and panel discussions where viewers can get solutions to their various problems in life. There are also first-person accounts by well-known people who have used spirituality in their life and found that it works.

The programmes planned for the 24x7 Channel on Cable network will be offered in all major languages (English, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Marathi, Oriya, Tamil, Telugu) to reach Direct-To-Home (DTH) in India and many parts of the world.

Broadcasting 24 hours a day, Peace of Mind is brought to you by the Brahma kumaris, for helping hundreds of thousands of people to transform their lives for

the better. The institution nurtures respect for all faith traditions and delineates an enlightened lifestyle. Through numerous social service activities and partnerships, it promotes spiritual understanding, leadership with integrity and elevated actions towards a better world.

This TV channel provides the viewers to Watch all Brahma Kumaris Programmes and Live programmes from Madhuban, international HQ's of Brahma Kumaris and totally dedicated to the cause of re-establishing moral and spiritual values, and bestowing peace of mind to the maximum number of people, who are genuinely searching for inner peace and happiness.

PMTV CHANNEL TIMING

INDIA – Channel Timing

In Hindi Language

Aastha: 7.10 pm. - 7.40 pm(Daily) & 9.30pm -10.30pm (Sundays)

Zee Jagaran : 4.00 am. -6.00 am.

Sanskar: 10.10 pm. - 10.40 pm.

Soubhagya : 5.30 am. -6.00 am. & 3.30 pm. -4.00 pm.

Etv U.P. : 5.00 am. -5.30 am.

Etv M.P. : 5.00 am. -5.30 am.

Etv Bihar: 5.00 am. -5.30 am.

Etv Rajasthan: 5.00 am. -5.30 am.

Zee-24 Hours Chhattisgarh : 5.30 am. -6.00 am.

PMTV SCHEDULE :

It's a wonderful schedule designed by the Peace of Mind team. They have kept the aim of bringing benefit to all sections of society by exposing the vast richness of our ancient wisdom, cultural programmes, health guidelines, intellectual discussions, discourses and meditation techniques. This would catalyse the process of spiritual renaissance, re-empowerment and re-establishment of peace within and peace in the world.

TELECAST DETAILS

C-band width With MPEG 4 setup Box

Frequency – 4054

Symbol – 13230

Polarization – Horizontal

Satellite – INSAT-4A

1.12 RADIO MADHUBAN-90.4 FM: SUNTE RAHO MUSKURATE RAHO

Radio Madhuban is

- Registered under social asking for choice act XXI of 1860
- All India choice number S/401/2013
- PAN Number: AACTR1648D
- 12AA Registration Number: 2013-14/634-636
- 80G Registration Number: 2013-14/733-736

Radio Madhuban Community Society (RMCS)

Radio madhuban cluster Society (RMCS) has been kept with marvelous motivation driving serving all spaces of get-together. Radio madhuban pack Society (RMCS) is picked body under social deals Registration Act XXI of 1860 with all India selection no: S/401/2013. Picked office of society is sorted out at Karol Bagh, Delhi, Administrative office is at Mount Abu, Rajasthan & will work through its Governing body. Society will strengthen unmistakable connection hones which are useful to masses.

Centers & Objectives of Radio madhuban pack Society-RMCS

- Creating care in Healthy lifestyle/Hygiene/Cleanliness/Rural Sanitation
- Facilitate eager social security at towns.
- Literate populate/Value Education for all
- Women Empowerment/Child Care/Stopping of Female Feticide
- Stopping Drugs/Substance misuse battles
- Sustainability Initiatives/Environment affirmation works out
- Developing & Promoting considered gathering radio

RMCS has centered way to deal with oversee direct accomplish its objective of coming to masses through its association works out. Much go on has been done to perform advancement in keeping up relationship to society. Each & every person at little scale level ought to experience peace & have amazing time their lives, is astonishing clarification behind RMCS. RMCS looks ahead to perform subjective change in get-together through innovative connection channels.

RMCS Concern for Society

As social connection foundation, they have direct obligation & regulating society in different zones, for case, hugeness securing, water accreditation, waste association, (reusing works out), renewable centrality & so on.

Continuing thought in this heading has driven them to make certain tries, on test begin so they can be rehased & imitated in individuals when all is said in one eye - This has lead us to taking after suggestion.

1.12.1 Solar force battery worked transports inside incomprehensible structures

We have planned to get about 10 buses as per the Proposal - These will be used inside the brahma kumaris complex of Shantivan for movement of people from one place to another. Every year we have a gathering of more 1 million people congregating every year under various programmes. This gathering consists of a lot of top executives from various organizations who themselves use petrol/diesel driven vehicles inside their own factories, institutions, steel plants, universities, heavy electrical projects, etc. to name a few. When they practically enjoy the rides in side our complex, they will be motivated to replicate them for various reasons, like pollution free (both sound and carbon-dioxide), saving of huge quantity of Petrol/Diesel, high maintenance costs. Speed is not the criterion inside any complex, but safety and comfort. In a country like ours, One can imagine the amount of savings that will accrue to the organization specifically and to the country as a whole by way millions worth of fuel/oil, in the years to come. The vehicle is simple, costing around 5 lacs per bus, and the spares can be easily duplicated. Wear and tear is low as it is run by solar batteries

1.12.2 Service through our Global Hospital

We have a Global Hospital in Mt.Abu which renders medical services to the people visiting Mt.Abu. The team of doctors renders selfless service to the society. As part of our outreach programme, we are rendering services to a number of surrounding villages with the limited means now available. It is a constant thought of the hospital management as to how to improve the services, which in most cases are free or negligible cost to the patient, depending upon their capacity. The motto here is service to public with a human touch.

It is relevant here to mention that the hospital lacks in facilities, in diagnostic equipments, transportation of the patients to the hospital where necessary, number of beds available for in patients, regular periodic checkups to avoid epidemics, care of pregnant ladies, pre and post delivery, and ever so many related medical care. Right now, non availability of sufficient facilities drive the hospital authorities to undertake/suggest transport of the patients to Ahmadabad (taking 4 hours by road) for attention in bigger hospitals in critical conditions. Life becomes a chance!

Our proposal for up gradation of the Hospital is in keeping with the view to render timely remedy to the suffering masses on the spot or at the hospital. The proposal has been drawn with base minimum requirements and completion will augur well for the medical care of the poor, uneducated suffering masses. It directly becomes a divine service

1.12.3 One MW Solar Energy Power Plant

It is a well known fact to all that conventional Electricity Generation is a resource fast depleting. So with the help of Government of India and the German Government we are setting up a Solar Energy Power Plant capable of generating 1 MW Power for captive consumption as well as for taking care of the need of the surrounding areas. It is capital intensive initially, but over a period hardly involves any expenditure for power production. In other words, the power comes free of cost, apart from providing Hot water as a by product. Once the project goes into full production, it will stand out as an example for any number of large industries to acquire/copy the technology at much lesser cost reducing the dependence on hydro/thermal power production.

1.12.4 Bio-Gas Project: Bio Gas from Food Waste

Idea Inception : Our parent organization's campus is distributed into 5 residential and institutional parts. Together these campuses can host 30 thousand people at a time. Around 50,000 visitors from different parts of the world visit to these facilities every month. To provide milk and tea facility to the visitors the Brahma Kumaris is also nurturing 40 cows in its farm house. The cow dung collected in this campus is now used for preparing Cooking Gas.

The institution has installed 2 Biogas plants based on Cow Dung at its farm near village Kiwarli. Each of these plants can process 150 kg of cow dung every day. And both of them are producing 12 (6+6) cubic meter of biogas daily. The first plant is operational since Sep 2012 and second is in operation since Jan 2013.

As an institution of heavy floating population year round, we have realized the amount of wastages of different kinds, (food, vegetables,) and we have planned to convert these wastages for producing Cooking Gas thus saving a lot of money for acquiring Gas, apart from saving the environment from infections due to decaying wastages, and creating problems for disposal.

Actual project of BIOGAS generation from Food Waste: Energy conservation at Brahma Kumaris is also done by the proper management of food waste. A large number of visitors coming to the institution throughout the year are served with 3 meals per day, which produces a large amount of cooked and uncooked food waste. We are installing a biogas plant to process cooked and uncooked food waste. This plant will process up to 1500 kg of bio waste/ food waste daily. It will produce 150 m³ of cooking gas daily.

This project details are available in the website-www.chfourenergy.com

Details	1.5 Ton CH4 Biogas Plant
Technology	Anaerobic Digestion
Area	10x2- sq meter
Water	1000-1200 Ltr/day-Water discharged to STP
Electricity	14-16 units/day
Gas Production	130-150 m ³
LPG Equivalent	69 kg
Cost	35 Lacs

1.12.5 AWARDS:

- **National Community Radio Award – 2014**

Radio Madhuban was awarded with National Community Radio Award 2014 by the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting during 4th National Community Radio Sammelan at Vigyan Bhawan New Delhi. The Award was presented by Shri Bimal Julka Secretary, MIB, Govt. of India to Radio Madhuban Station Manager Mr. Yashwant Patil. Out of 165 Community Radio Stations in India Radio Madhuban was selected to receive the award in Thematic Category for its program "Gruhasan Se Singhsan.

- **Best Community Service Award – SDM, Mount Abu**

Radio Madhuban was invited to be the commentator for the football match. The chief guest Mr. Raghuveer Singh Meena, Collector, Sirohi Congratulated our team for our efforts to promote sports in the region. The

entire commentary was also broadcast on-air for our listeners Radio Madhuban was awarded a trophy and certificate for our contribution.

- **Participation in Manthan Award - DEF India**

Team Radio Madhuban was chosen as the Best Nominee and got an opportunity to represent Radio Madhuban's community development efforts in front of a national audience on 4th December 2014 at New Delhi.

- **Community Radio Award 2016 –**

Radio Madhuban was awarded with Community Radio Award 2016 by the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting at New Delhi in the area of Community Participation. The Award was presented by Shri Arun Jaitley, Hon'ble Union Minister of Information and Broadcasting, Govt. of India to Radio Madhuban Station Manager Mr. Yashwant Patil

1.13 ACHIEVEMENTS

The major achievements of the Institutions:

- ✓ The Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya is affiliated to the Department of Public Information (DPI) of the United Nations as a Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO).
- ✓ It holds General Consultative status in the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) & UNICEF of the United Nations.
- ✓ The United Nations “University for Peace” in Costa Rica receives its co-operation in the field of peace education by means of an official agreement.
- ✓ The Government of Mauritius has recognized it as a University by an Act of Parliament.
- ✓ The Government of Guyana has adopted the principle of starting the proceedings of their Parliament with three minutes Rajyoga meditation as suggested by this Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya.
- ✓ The Commonwealth of Russia has granted official recognition to this spiritual Vishwa Vidyalaya in their country.
- ✓ The project of “Living Values” and Education in Values and Spirituality” has been running in various educational organizations and Universities.
- ✓ More than 10 Lakhs of people have been imbued with the education in spirituality, peace, moral values and Raja yoga Meditation on a global level.

- ✓ In the year 1994, the Government of India published a postal stamp in memory of the founder of this institution and attributed pride and honors.
- ✓ **Mohanlal Sukhadia University of Udaipur (Rajasthan)** awarded the Honorary Degree of Doctorate of Literature (D.Litt) to Rajyogini Dadi Prakash Mani, the then Administrative Head of the Organisation.
- ✓ Gitam University , Vishakapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, honoured Doctorate Degree(D.Litt) to Rajayogini B.K.Dadi Janakiji, Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris
- ✓ Gulbarga University ,Gulbarga, Karnataka, honoured Doctorate Degree(D.Litt) to Rajayogini B.K.Dadi Ratan Mohiniji, Joint Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris
- ✓ **Rajyogini Dadi Janki appointed as the Brand Ambassador Of Swatch Bharat**

Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual Organization's Chief 100-year-old Rajyogini Dadi Janki has been appointed as the Brand Ambassador of Swatch Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission) by the Govt. of India. She has been invited to the President House for the Clean India Mission program on 10th September 2015. On Dadiji's behalf, Rajyogi BK Mruthyunjaya, Executive Secretary of Brahma Kumaris represented the High Tea meeting and Curtain Raiser held at President House organized by Hon'ble Shri Venkaiah Naidu, Minister for Urban Development, Govt of India.

CHAPTER-2

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 BACKGROUND

For any research the study and analysis of existing literatures play significant role to enable optimal understanding and assessment of existing researches and their respective significances. Taking into consideration of these factors, in this section of the presented thesis, some of the existing literatures discussing meditation, Raj Yoga meditation and its significances, Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris etc, have been discussed.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Meditation comes from the Latin “to heal”, to make whole. Addictions are manifestations of not only the fragmentation within the personality but also within society. Addiction is thought to be a spiritual sickness which meditation within a faith context heals. Research on meditation suggestive of its benefits has been compiled by Alexander, Robinson, Orme-Johnson, et al., (1994). They conducted a meta-analysis comparing relaxation and meditation techniques and found TM to be significantly more effective than relaxation practices or meditation for relaxation. It had the effect of reducing psycho-physiological arousal, decreasing anxiety, increasing positive mental health measures of selfactualisation and reducing nicotine, alcohol and illicit drug use. Other research focuses on the overarching concept of spirituality within which meditation is an aspect of lived faith practice.

Rajayoga meditation has tremendous medicinal, psychotherapeutic and healing potentialities in the sense that it cures many psychic disorders by creating quantum shift in deep psychic layers within the human soul and, also thereby with zero expense, brings psychosomatic order and harmony with its holistic healing efficacy and salubrious impact on the soul-mind-body matrix that every human being is essentially and originally moulded of (B.K.Yudhisthir)."

Prezioso (1987) claimed that the importance of spirituality is most clearly evidenced in the lives of substance abusers. The literature reports that positive spirituality helps alcoholics shift to an acknowledgment of the larger dimensions of their lives and while the specific elements of this transition are not well understood, spirituality

clearly plays a part in successful outcomes (Pardini, et al., 2000; Booth & Martin, 1998). Relapse prevention (RP) programmes, based on the principles of social learning theory by Bandura, combines behavioural skills-training procedures, cognitive therapy and lifestyle rebalancing. Within lifestyle rebalancing, meditation and physical exercise are used to enhance the maintenance of behaviour change in the direction of better personal habits to prevent relapse (Marlatt & George, 1998).

The meditation referred to in this study is taught in the context of the lived faith of BrahmaKumaris' Raja yogastudy and lifestyle. This is in keeping with the hypothesis that meditation is most efficacious when practised in its spiritual context. A more widely studied meditation technique known to be effective in drug addiction is Buddhist Vipassana (Fleischmann, 1986). Vipassana claims to be unique by working on the subconscious mind by emptying the conscious mind (Goenka, 2002). It is more technique focussed than Raja yoga but the effect is similar in that it fosters self dependence and inner strength. Like RajYoga, it is experiential rather than intellectual.

One of the key variables that arise in Raja yogapractitioners is that they experience peace of mind (BKRY, 1988; O'Donnell, 2000). They did not get this from just a meditation technique but from the experience of peace in meditation being applied to everyday life and its stressful situations. Raja yogais very much about retraining the mind in the direction of greater positivity and peace, to counter negative tendencies based on negative habits of thought and personality traits which make up the "addictive personality". Awareness is a key factor in this process of recovery.

In this section some of the predominant researches done for Raj Yoga meditation and its significances are discussed.

2.2.1 Review of Raja Yoga Meditation Physiological & Mental effects

Pardini et al., (2000) pointed out the paucity of empirical studies examining how spirituality assists in substance abuse treatment. Methodological problems and weak associations between variables have plagued previous studies on spirituality and meditation. These indeterminate results have been attributed to a studying meditation independent of its spiritual meaning, resulting in a weakening of its effect. Its benefits in stress reduction and hence health promotion, is arguably greatest when placed within a spiritual context and lived on a daily basis (Varma, 2003). Shapiro (1994), however, pointed out that removing the religious and philosophical context of

meditation was necessary to establish its credibility. The authors of this paper do not accept that this is helpful to individuals hoping for long-term benefits. This study was carried out to address both the lack of research on Raja yogameditation specifically and research on meditation in a context of lived faith in the treatment of substance abuse. Addictions are thought to be particularly responsive to meditation hence the choice of this problem for the purpose of the study (Canter, 2003). Current theory on the causation of substance abuse is consistent with the psychological role of transcendence and its incorporation into future.

Nishi et al (2013) examined the effect of duration of Raj Yoga Meditation practice on affective & cognitive functions in terms of attention/concentration, memory, visual processing, neuroticism, hope and happiness. Researcher collected responses from 64 healthy volunteers practicing Raj Yoga from 1 month to more than 10 years and segregated into two groups of beginners and practitioners and assessed their psychological and affective functions assessed using standard measures at a Raj Yoga Centre in Delhi, India. The results revealed that the group practicing Raj Yoga for longer duration had significantly less neurotic symptoms, scored higher on hope and happiness and higher on cognitive functions in comparison to the group practicing Raj Yoga for shorter duration. These results may be due to personality development, self-actualization and better attention and concentration achieved due to training in Raj Yoga.

Ghanshyam (2010) stated that meditation significantly improves critical cognitive skills. The researcher performed a cross sectional comparative study among Raja Yoga meditators and non-meditators, which was conducted at Yoga centre, Gurukul Kangdi Vishvavidyalaya, Haridwar, (UK), India. The self-reported Oxford happiness questionnaire (OHQ) was administered to all subjects and their happiness scores and status were assessed and compared. The results obtained illustrated that the mean happiness scores of BKRM were significantly higher in meditators as compared to those in non-meditators. The number of meditators experiencing happiness status was significantly higher in comparison with non-meditators. Additionally, meditators scored significantly higher on self-satisfaction items as compared to non-meditators. Research also found that Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga Meditation helps in significantly increasing self-satisfaction and happiness in life by enhancing positive thinking.

Neelam et al (2012) examined the impact of short-term and long-term Brahma kumaris Raja Yoga meditation on physiological variables such as heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP). In this research it was found that the physiological variables (HR, RR, SBP and DBP) reduces in long term meditators after meditation indicates a shift in the balancing components of autonomic nervous system towards the parasympathetic state. Sympathetic arousal was found to be reduced during Raja Yoga practice. Hence the load on heart due to sympathetic arousal is also minimized resulting in an improvement in cardiovascular parameters.

Sukhsohale et al (2012) explored whether Raja Yoga meditation bring out physiological and psychological general well being among practitioners. Primarily, the researchers assessed the effect of Raj Yoga meditation on physiological and psychological well being of its practitioners. Through their research they revealed that Raja Yoga meditation provides significant improvements in physiological cardio-respiratory functions by tilting of autonomic balance from sympathetic in favor of parasympathetic and also contributes significantly to the psychological well-being of subjects. The authors conducted a study among 100 practitioners of Brahmakumaris Raja Yoga meditation of either sex (33 men and 67 women) aged 30 years and above (mean age 52.06 ± 12.76 years). The subjects were divided into short term meditators (meditating for 6 months to 5 years with mean duration 3.37 ± 1.67 years) and long term meditators (meditating for more than 5 years with mean duration 11.19 ± 5.13 years). Physiological variables like heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR) per minute, systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were recorded before meditation practice and twice during the practice of meditation after every fifteen minutes. Also, detailed history regarding addictions, negative attributes and spiritual practices before and after practicing meditation was inquired as per the predesigned questionnaire. Fasting blood sugar was also estimated by glucometer. Both short term as well as long term meditators showed a significant declining trend in HR, RR, SBP and DBP 15 minutes as well as 30 minutes after meditation ($P > 0.005$). The study subjects particularly long term meditators got rid of addictions (tobacco chewing, smoking, alcohol, non-vegetarian diet) and negative attributes (anger, mental stress, negative/waste thoughts and irritability) after learning and

practicing meditation. Subjects also experienced various benefits in the form of mental peace and happiness.

Shirley et al (1993) studied changes in various autonomic and respiratory variables during the practice of Brahma Kumaris Raja yoga meditation and the analysis observed the increase in the heart rate during the meditation period in comparison to the preceding baseline period, as well as compared to the value during the non-meditation period of control sessions. In contrast to the change in the heart rate, there was no significant change during meditation, for the group as a whole, in palmer GSR, finger plethysmogram amplitude, and respiratory rate. This individual level analysis revealed that changes in autonomic variables suggestive of both activation and relaxation occurred simultaneously in different subdivisions of the autonomic nervous system in a subject. Apart from this, there were differences in patterns of change among the subjects who practiced the same meditation. Author stated that a single model of sympathetic activation or overall relaxation may be inadequate to describe the physiological effects of a Raj Yoga meditation technique.

Shivangi Maurya (2013) interestingly narrated the modern society and its mechanized life style which is making it unable to get peace and facing lots of physical and psychological problems. Researcher made an effort to provide some solutions regarding the problem relating physical and psychological problems. Researcher in her research work discussed a number of aspects of meditation and mechanisms of meditation and their respective significance towards psychological well being.

Abani Sonowal (2013) defined Raja Yoga as the “Royal Yoga” or “Royal Union” which is also known as Astanga Yoga and Classical Yoga. The Yogis of India discovered mystic secrets of mind through their inner experiences of Concentration, Meditation and Samadhi. The Raja Yoga sutra is an unparalleled work of ancient psychology, parapsychology and spirituality. Quoting Raj Yoga by Swami Vivekananda- Raja Yoga means the attainment of liberation by controlling the mind and the physical body. In Raja Yoga the mind and the body is controlled through the medium of some mental and physical disciplines. According to some Raja Yoga is the

ultimate path for attaining liberation or union with God. Therefore it is called Raja Yoga – The king of all Yoga. Raja Yoga is consisted of eight steps i.e. YAMA, NIYAMA, ASANA, PRANAYAMA, PRATYAHARA, DHARANA, DHYANA and SAMADHI. Raja Yoga teaches us to uncover those experiences by observing the internal states through the daily practice of meditation. In Raja Yoga we do not need to believe anything because everything is based on practical experiences. The most practical utility of Raja Yoga is the physical and mental therapy. By keeping the physical body clean, flexible and well lubricated we can significantly reduce the catabolic process of deterioration. Researcher suggested that to get maximum benefits of Raja Yoga one has to combine the practice of yogasana, pranayama and meditation.

Dilip V. (2013) discussed the Raja yogaMindfulness Programme [RMP], which is a scientific-spiritual programme that aims at restoring the Energy, Enthusiasm, Happiness and Mental peace among the cancer patients. Cancers come under a new group of diseases called NCDs – Noninfectious Chronic Diseases – that have become quite common today. Author stated that there is a strong pointer for having this type of study by the Medical Wing of Brahma Kumaris.

Neeta (2012) emphasized her research on the assessment of meditation in different forms from psychological effects of meditation to the physiological effects of meditation and elaborated various positive effect of meditation following the prescription of the use of meditation to the patients along with medicine. There have been many different studies in to the effects of meditation have been recently started to take notice by professionals in the field of the medical science. Although no ideal drugs or method has so far been discovered in science which neutralize the offending factors or root causes. This is non invasive, non drug type of method advocated by physicians which reduces the amount of meditation and helps in preventing the diseases.

Patel G (1984) suggested Raja Yoga therapy because of its cognitive characteristics and discussed varied aspects of Raj Yoga meditation, its history, practices, its physiological and psychological benefits etc

Telles & Desiraju (1993) presented the changes in various autonomic and respiratory variables during the practice of Brahmakumaris Raja yoga meditation. This practice

requires considerable commitment and involves concentrated thinking. 18 males in the age range of 20 to 52 years (mean 34.1 ± 8.1), with 5-25 years experience in meditation (mean 10.1 ± 6.2), participated in the study. Each subject was assessed in three test sessions which included a period of meditation, and also in three control (non-meditation) sessions, which included a period of random thinking. Group analysis showed that the heart rate during the meditation period was increased compared to the preceding baseline period, as well as compared to the value during the non-meditation period of control sessions. In contrast to the change in the heart rate, there was no significant change during meditation, for the group as a whole, in palmer GSR, finger plethysmogram amplitude, and respiratory rate. On an individual basis, changes which met the following criteria were noted:

- (1) Changes which were greater during meditation (compared to its preceding baseline) than changes during post meditation or no meditation periods (also compared to their preceding baseline);
- (2) Changes which occurred consistently during the three repeat sessions of a subject and
- (3) Changes which exceeded arbitrarily chosen cut- off points (described at length below).

This individual level analysis revealed that changes in autonomic variables suggestive of both activation and relaxation occurred simultaneously in different subdivisions of the autonomic nervous system in a subject. Apart from this, there were differences in patterns of change among the subjects who practiced the same meditation. Hence, a single model of sympathetic activation or overall relaxation may be inadequate to describe the physiological effects of a meditation technique.

Even the scientific investigations by recording E.E.G. of raja yogis have shown the totally relaxation and mental harmony they have achieved (Langley Porter Psychiatric Institute, (1978)). Most of the ten Raja yogis examined produced Alpha or Theta waves not only while meditating but even while performing complicated mental arithmetic. In one of the most eye opening study, EEG, EMG, Lung CO₂ levels, Abdominal & thoracic respiratory movements, In 1978, EEG measured in 10 members of Brahmakumaris at Langley Porter Psychiatric Institute. Dadi Jankiji, chief of Brahmakumaris registered Delta Waves (1-3 Hz.) in all channels under all

conditions. While engaged in conversation or performing mental arithmetic, while attempts were made to elicit various emotional responses.

Surya, Balakishore (2000) Surya, Balakishore (2000) research study was done by B.K Suryji (M.T ABU) & B.K Balakishoreji on depression management through Raja Yoga meditation (power of thought) in 2000. They used TAT test & symptom list. He also found good results in many cases.

With the current globalisation of the world's economy and demands for enhanced performance, stress is present universally (Kiran et al., 2014). Life's stressful events, anxiety and depression cause both deleterious and cumulative effects on the human body. The practice of meditation might offer a way to relieve that stress. Researchers studied to determine the effectiveness of a group stress reduction program based on Raja yogameditation for patients with anxiety and depression (Kiran et al., 2014). The study was conducted on 100 patients suffering from anxiety and depression who were on similar drug regime. They were randomised into two groups; Meditators (n=50; age 34.12±9.05 years) and controls (n=50 age 33.68±10.78 years). The meditators were taught Raja yogameditation and practised for 20 min/day, 7 d/week for 6 weeks. The control group did not practice any type of meditation. Results were assessed by using Hamilton anxiety and depression scales. The patient with anxiety and depression symptoms in intervention group and control group showed significant improvement following six weeks of intervention as suggested by significant reduction in scores of HAM-A ($p < 0.001$).

Bhupendra & Smita (2013) Spirituality and meditation have been used effectively in rehabilitation of the patients with mental illness, particularly in depression and anxiety. Though, rarely it has been used as the core therapy (or with routine medications) in the patients with psychotic symptoms. Spiritual healing and Raj yoga meditation were prescribed with the routine medications as the medicines alone were not showing any significant improvement. The major sessions lasted for 15 days and further follow ups continued for every 15 days till two months. A series of scales were administered before intervention and after intervention for different domains that are listed as Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale, Scale for Positive Symptoms, Scale for Negative Symptoms, Global Assessment of Functioning and Social and Occupational functioning. The individual showed significant improvement on depression, anxiety, stress (79.57%), positive symptoms (73.61%), negative symptoms (60.00%), Overall Functioning (33.33%) social and occupational functioning (33.33%). Discussion:

Spiritual healing and Raja yoga Meditation has been seen to be effective in treating the case with psychotic symptoms.

2.2.2 Review of Raja Yoga Meditation Health effects

Mental health refers to an individual's emotional and psychological well-being. **Merriam-Webster** defines mental health as "a state of emotional and psychological well-being in which an individual is able to use his or her cognitive and emotional capabilities, function in society and meet the ordinary demands of everyday life."

Practice of Rajayoga Meditation renders both physical and spiritual benefits for leading a sustainable, values-based and healthy life. The physical benefits are:

- (i) Rajayoga Meditation decreases cholesterol, workload on heart and high blood pressure;*
- (ii) improves airflow to lungs and helps asthma patients;*
- (iii) prolongs life expectancy younger biological age;*
- (iv) helps cure insomnia (sleeplessness);*
- (v) lowers cortisol and lactate - two stress causing chemicals.*

According to the model adopted in the unit, mental health is intimately related to spiritual health although both are distinct from each other. Conventional psychiatric practices are often based on symptom suppression with drugs that cause serious side-effects and so people are increasingly turning to alternative and holistic practices. This is what took the author to Global Hospital in Rajasthan, India where holistic and conventional therapies overlap. In the psychiatric unit which specializes in the treatment of addictions, Neuropsychiatry unit employs an integrative approach in using drugs, conventional psychotherapeutic interventions and the learning of Raja yogameditation. He found that this kind of meditation can work alone as a powerful therapeutic tool and undertook the present study to confirm his observation. The critical factor in eliminating unwanted behaviours is an understanding of how the mind produces suffering and spiritual discipline is the method for eliminating disturbing thoughts which lead to emotional distress and addictions.

Kiran et al (2014) studied the influence of Raj Yoga Meditation on cold pressure response to evaluate the sympathetic autonomic functions. Researchers stated that stress is often associated with unmanaged emotions and occurrence of increased sympathetic autonomic activity. Long term meditation cultivates mindfulness and has long been used to reduce overwhelming stress. The purpose of their study was to compare the rise in the mean value of Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) and Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) in acute stressful

condition in meditators of Raj Yoga meditation and non-meditators. The test was carried out in 50 meditators & 50 non-meditators and the results revealed that the meditators have a lower sympathetic activity in comparison to the non meditators during acute stress, suggesting that Raj Yoga meditation has a relaxing effect on sympathetic autonomic nervous system (ANS). The regular practice of Raj Yoga Meditation has been observed to maintain optimal level of autonomic equilibrium at rest and during exposure to stressful conditions.

Annapoorna (2013) studied on meditation through physiological approach. The research explored the significance of meditation and Yoga in psychological therapy. Author stated that Raj Yoga silences the surface activity of the mind, thereby allowing the person to look deeper within which illuminates the deeper and higher realities of existence.

Maini (2014) presented a case study on the effect of Rajayoga meditation on serum cholesterol and HDL and contemplated to highlight the hemodynamic and biochemical effects of Raj Yoga meditation by studying its impact on serum cholesterol and serum HDL levels of the individuals. Persons practicing Raj Yoga Meditation regularly are at a lower risk of developing cardiovascular diseases as compared to those who do not perform any meditation at all. So it can be safely conclude that meditation has a positive effect on cardiovascular system and with regular practice of meditation reduces the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases.

Samriddhi et al (2011) emphasized her research for assessing the impact of Sahaj Marg Raja Yoga meditation system on the physical health, psychological health and emotional intelligence of the practitioners of the Sahaj Marg. A group of practitioners of this meditation system for last one year who were able to cope up with challenging situation, untoward stressful life events, the shattering experiences, painful happenings, chronic diseases, stress and anxiety. Their research revealed that the practice of Sahaj Marg Raj Yoga meditation enhances the physical health, psychological health and emotional intelligence of the participants.

A preliminary study on 25 Raja Yogis was done in October 1984 by the medical wing of Raja Yoga education and research foundation (*Girish, 1984*) to observe the effect of meditation to the vital parameters. The results obtained exhibited

an overall decrease in the mean values of heart rate, systolic & diastolic blood pressure and respiratory rate within 6 months

Ankad Roopa (2011) evaluated the effects of pranayama and meditation on respiratory parameters. Researchers evaluated the respiratory parameters with both the pre-yoga and post yoga situations and found that there was significant increase in chest expansion, breath holding time and peak expiratory flow rate compared to pre yoga practice. The study showed beneficial effects of short term (15 days) regular pranayama and Raj Yoga meditation practice on respiratory functions irrespective of age, gender and BMI in normal healthy individuals.

Usha Kiran (2011) discussed the significance of physical and psychological preparation before coronary artery bypass surgery. In order to achieve better psychological stability, meditation is not only the best way to arouse relaxation response but has also been found a very successful tool for relief of fear and anxiety at many cardiovascular centres all over the world. Researcher has suggested the training of patients in Raja yogameditation of Brahma Kumaris at the Cardio-Neuro Centre, AIIMS that exhibited effective response in terms of reduced postoperative pain and depression following open heart surgery.

Behari et al (2005) correlated the chronic tension headache with blood cortisol level and its modulation by autogenic relaxation therapy. Researchers performed the randomized single blind parallel design prospective study among 380 patients of chronic tension headache and came with results that Raj Yoga meditation reduces headache approximately 96%, which was approved by headache index. The research came out with the lowered mean plasma cortisol levels in those suffering with chronic headache for over 5 years. Relaxation therapy with Raja yogameditation effectively modulated the plasma cortisol to normal range.

Patel Nikhil (1996) studied the Raj Yoga meditation and the variation in physiological variables such as EEG, muscle tension etc during meditation. Primary the research emphasized his research on the analysis of the effects of Raj Yoga meditation in treating neurotic illnesses.

Patel Girish (1984) A preliminary study on 25 Raja Yogis, including both males and females, practicing meditation regularly, in October 1984, by the medical wing of Raja Yoga education and research foundation to observe the effect of meditation to the vital parameters. This showed an overall decrease in the mean values of heart rate, systolic & diastolic blood pressure and respiratory rate within 6 months.

SpARC, Mount Abu (2010) The service through positive thoughts and positive vibrations were tested on group of patients in a state government run cancer hospital in Karnataka by spiritual applications research centre of Brahmakumaris. Many topics on self-respect and effect of positive vibrations were experimented. It was found that Raja Yoga brought about many positive changes among the patients and others who attended classes. Each participant had a new and unique experience: Each felt that there was a self progress, increase in will power and concentration, weightlessness and flying stage. Patients and their accompanied were automatically attracted to the meditation rooms where meditations were being conducted. They readily expressed their feelings to attend the free Raja Yoga course. So far up to 125 patients and 400 accompany who came with the patients have attended the course. The hospital staffs have expressed their feelings that the disturbances of evil souls have reduced. The hospital authorities desired to conduct training to their staff too. Raja Yoga has brought about many positive changes among the patients. The patients and the hospital staff who practiced Raja Yoga feel that the meditation and the philosophy is very much essential to overcome anxiety, tension and worries that engross the man.

Biju et al (2012) proposed the concept that yoga is helpful for the treatment of bronchial asthma has created great interest in the medical research field. In order to investigate whether physiological parameters and pulmonary functions were improved in asthmatic patients after yoga training, the present study was conducted on seventy patients with bronchial asthma. The present study was conducted on seventy patients with asthma who were on beta 2 agonist inhalers and yoga therapy for three months. Parameters like pulse rate, respiratory rate, body weight, FVC, FEV1, FEV2, FEV1% and PEFr were compared with controls on beta 2 agonist inhalers alone. Yogic practices resulted in significant improvement in pulmonary functions; decrease in respiratory rate; decrease in pulse rate and body weight (not statistically significant); decrease in frequency of asthma attacks and decrease in frequency of use of inhalers.

The disease status in controls deteriorated. Potential explanations for improvement in case group are effect on release of endorphins, balance of ANS and effect on airway smooth muscle dynamics.

Sharma A. (2009) has given different perspectives on Spirituality and Mental Health. The canvas that is painted has a wide range, depth, color and variety. Mental health has to be seen in its cultural context. Western psychology, psychotherapy and concepts of normality are linked to the history of Christianity and philosophically to reductionist Cartesian mind-body dualism. In contrast, Ayurveda and Yoga propound a holistic approach. In recognition of these roots the World Health Assembly, in 1999, added 'spiritual well being' to the WHO definition of health as secular medical science appeared mechanized and dehumanized.

Damsel tuberculosis who has several microbiologists into deep research is taking a heavy toll of mankind with its TDR AND XDR forms . NDM-1 gene carrying super bugs have defeated Pharmacologists in the race of antibiotics started by them. Cancer remains an enigma. Non-infectious Chronic Diseases [NCDs] are stress associated. Older medical jargon called them as Psycho-somatic diseases. The stress arises in Mind- an empirical, metaphysical virtual screen on which the thoughts, emotions and desires form as transient images. Infant medical science hardly knows anything about the most important mind. The patients are just unable to follow the suggested lifestyle modification in NCDs like Diabetes because the soul [Atman] is not having a controlling and ruling power over this nebulous mind. BK-Rajayoga- an evidence-based mental silence type meditation provides these two very essential powers - ruling and controlling power over mind; and open up a "Single window system" for infections, cancers and NCDs (Dilip et al., 2014). It is an easy remix of knowledge from Bhagavad Gita and Patanjali sutra used for health promotion. It is the most ancient Whole Person Medicine.

Vyas R et al (2002) observed that diastolic blood pressure was significantly lower in both short and long term meditators of Raja Yoga meditation as compared to non-meditators. Lipid profile showed a significant lowering of serum cholesterol in short and long-term meditators as compared to non-meditators. However contradictory results have been observed by Telles S et al (13), who conducted study in 18 males with 5-25 years of meditation (mean 10.1 ± 6.2) showing that heart rate during the meditation period was increased when compared to the baseline period, as well as

compared to the value during the non-meditation period of control sessions. No significant change was observed during meditation, for the group as a whole, in palmar GSR, finger plethysmogram amplitude and respiratory rate. Hence, a single model of sympathetic activation or overall relaxation may be inadequate to describe the physiological effects of a meditation technique

World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the need for greater psychological care post-disaster (Gist 1999; Roberts and Ashley 2008), and in Australia, spiritually sensitive social care is now being integrated in the curriculum of high level disaster training (Gray 2008; Spencer and Archer 2008) and forms part of the government's response to disaster (EMA 2002). However, little is mentioned about creating faith –based resilience in communities prior to disaster. BKs indicate three forms of understanding that contributed in their ability to moderate their experience of the Super Cyclone: a belief that they have a capacity to serve themselves and others through the mind; a tendency to find purpose and meaning in life's difficulties through their theology; and the practice of meditation that offers BKs a sense of transcendence that can lift them out of the tragedy of the moment. Just as one stockpiles utensils and food, and rehearses behaviour appropriate to safety and physical resilience in disaster, BKs stockpile the practice of meditation and positive thinking, coupled with thoughtful good action, as a method to develop inner endurance.

Ather Ali (2007) reviewed literatures to assess the efficacy of mind-body therapies (MBT) versus placebo or active control in the treatment of hypertension. The main outcome measures include change in systolic and diastolic blood pressure pre and post-intervention period. Relevant trials were identified in the register of trials maintained by the Cochrane Complementary Medicine Field Registry, The Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Medline, EMBASE, PsycInfo, and CINAHL. *Mind-body therapies:* A total of nine published trials of 480 hypertensive's satisfied inclusion criteria. Mind-body therapies significantly reduced systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure with high statistical heterogeneity. Subgroup analyses of imagery were inconclusive, while six meditation trials of 323 hypertensive's demonstrated significant reductions in systolic but not diastolic blood pressure. Yoga interventions significantly reduced both systolic and diastolic blood pressure. It remains unclear what quantitative benefits that mind-body therapies can bring for hypertensives.

Kamakhya et al (2005) aimed at finding out the effect of yoga nidra on hypertension and other psychological co-relates. The study conducted at Patliputra Seva Sansthan Patna City, Patna. Practice time was 30 minutes and the duration was fifteen days. Forty people suffering with mild hypertension (30 males and 10 females) were taken for the study. Where the males were businessman and females were house wives. The result shows a significant change as yoga nidra positively decrease the blood pressure (both systolic and diastolic) as well as pulse rate, respiration rate, stress, anger and fear. Whereas no significant change shown at the depression level.

Lata Gupta et al (2007) study is the first meta-analysis to examine the effects of yoga on blood pressure among individuals with prehypertension or hypertension. Overall, yoga was associated with a modest but significant reduction in blood pressure (≈ 4 mmHg, systolic and diastolic) in this population. Subgroup analyses demonstrated larger, more clinically significant reductions in blood pressure for (1) interventions incorporating 3 basic elements of yoga practice (postures, meditation, and breathing) (≈ 8 mmHg, systolic; ≈ 6 mmHg, diastolic) but not for more limited yoga interventions; (2) yoga compared to no treatment (≈ 8 mmHg, systolic; 6 mmHg, diastolic) but not compared to exercise. These reductions are of clear clinical significance and suggest that yoga may offer an effective intervention for reducing blood pressure among people with prehypertension or hypertension. As none of the included studies had methodologies with low risk of bias in primary domains additional rigorous controlled trials are warranted to further investigate the potential benefits of yoga for improving blood pressure in these populations and to determine optimal yoga program design and dosing.

Gupta Satish (2004) “Effect of 3D Heart Care on CAD patients” To combat the menace of epidemic of CAD J. Watumull Global Hospital & Research centre, Brahma kumaris, Mount Abu joined hands with defense institute of physiology and allied sciences (DRDO), New Delhi and various other prestigious heart institutes in collaboration with CCRYN, ministry of health and family welfare, Govt. of India in early 1998, During last six years more than 800 angiographically documented CAD patients referred from all over India have participated in an unique user friendly HEALTHY LIFE STYLE program for CAD Regression (Mount Abu Open Heart Trail) in groups of 20 to 30 patients with their spouses at Brahma Kumaris, Shantivan, Complex, Abu Road. Almost all the patients who have sincerely followed the program experienced highly impressive improvement in symptoms eg: angina,

breathlessness etc. Various tests Carried out have shown highly significant decrease in bad cholesterol (LDL), increase in good Cholesterol (HDL) levels, better control of diabetes, high blood pressure, impressive decrease in weight, freedom from smoking, alcohol etc. Repeat coronary angiography have shown opening of coronary blockages. Some patients who followed the program strictly have been able to open even calcified 100 % blockages. Highly significant decrease in number of anginal episodes and heart attacks was observed in patients, who adapted this program as compared to control group in this randomized controlled study.

Kaplan, Lonsdorf, Travis, ("1996), Effect of TM on blood flow to the brain” Increased Blood Flow to the Brain: Individuals who practiced the TM technique displayed significantly increased cerebral blood flow during the practice, in contrast to controls. Increased cerebral blood flow was found during the practice of the TM technique both in the occipital area of the brain, and also in the frontal area.

Kaplan, Lonsdorf, Travis, (1981), “effect of TM on EEG Coherence” Increased EEG Coherence: After two weeks of practice of the TM program, individuals showed significantly increased EEG coherence during the practice, in contrast to their own eyes-closed control condition before they learned the TM technique.

Ushakiran (1989) “effect of Raja yogaMeditation on patients of headache” In 1988, in one research study 121 patients who were suffering from headache have been taken & taught them Raja Yoga meditation for 3 months.After 3 months 53.9% patients got very good relief, 91.2% patients got very good relief and 9.4% patients got little relief.

2.2.3 Review of Raja Yoga Meditation Spiritual Effects

Spirituality is a concept or principle which is innate in, and born and grown from, the inner soul/self/spirit or core of an individual. Guillory (2000, p. 33 cited in Krishnakumar & Neck, 2002) defines spirituality as 'our inner consciousness' and 'that which is spiritual comes from within - beyond our programmed beliefs and values'. This perspective of spirituality argues that spirituality is something, which is beyond the rules and rituals of religion(s)

The spiritual benefits are:

- *Rajayoga Meditation increases empathy;*
- *improves personal and professional relationships;*
- *increases power to face situations;*

- *increases power to tolerate; (v) increases power to accommodate and accept; (vi) increases power to discriminate right from wrong;*
- *increases power to withdraw from untoward events;*
- *increases power of judgment and decision making;*
- *increases power of unity and cooperation;*
- *increases power to pack up and get ready.*

Spiritual health refers to recognizing man himself and others as the inner essential spiritual entity - soul or spirit/self, the spiritual child of the Supreme Soul, God Father- in contrast to the outer physical body composed of five elements of Nature, and to perceiving and behaving others as souls or spirits as he himself wishes to be perceived and behaved by others. It also refers to accepting 'the otherness of others' and assimilating the multi-diversities with realization of the 'uniformity of human consciousness' and of 'the similarities of essential and original nature of the spirit/soul', of the unity and integrity of one-world-family on the basis of universal Brotherhood of Man and Fatherhood of Incorporeal God. Human life is coordination between body, soul/spirit/self, mind, intellect, impressions/resolves and senses; and yoga is the key element for maintaining this coordination.

Raj Yoga meditation as an aspect of the “piritual dimension” to living endorses a whole range of positive valuations. According to personal construct psychology, spirituality is about people"s attempts to make meaning out of circumstances and situations, not simply through an appreciation of the immediate conditions, observable attitudes or palpable experiences, but through reflective, sensitive, ethereal and transcendent means (Mallick & Watts, 2001). It is a willingness to look continuously for meaning and purpose in life. Spiritual wellbeing is vital to overall healthy functioning. It is defined as the appreciation for the depth and richness of life, the vastness of the universe, and wonder at natural processes all of which operate within a personal belief system (Chandler, Holden, & Kolander, 1992). Spirituality, then, can be understood as an idiographic aspect of the person in contrast to religion which is a social phenomenon, an organized structure with many purposes beyond the individual. Spirituality lies, for most people, in the realm of

super-ordinate constructs, and is arguably the most abstract of the over-arching constructs which relate to personal meanings of life.

Raj Yoga psychotherapist, Pemell (2003), uses a model of the self to describe how addictions are created. Compulsions to use and then abuse result from habituation through repeated action. In normal functioning, thoughts from the mind go to the intellect, then the conscience, before acting on the will. However, the mind of an addict drives the will, bypassing the checks of intellect and conscience. Insight is deadened and decision-making severely impaired. Until people reach “rock bottom”, only spiritual healing can save the person.

Piedmont (2004) showed that spirituality represents a sixth dimension of personality and as such, brings to psychology the possibility of a deeper understanding of how we construct meaning and create a sense of unity among the many competing and conflicting forces that affect our lives. For recovering addicts, this broader meaning may provide ways of coping with stressful events (Corrington, 1989) or creating buffers against negative feelings (Warfield & Goldstein, 1996) as well as a higher level of personal maturity (Khantzian & Mack, 1989). “Mindfulness training” derived from Buddhism, is now being used as a psychotherapeutic intervention but its mode of use, like meditation, is without the proper context of lived faith and hence, may not be statistically significant enough as the case has been with previous studies on meditation (Varma, 2003).

Rajesh Meena (2013) studied the significances of meditation and spiritual exercises at work place. Author stated that the mankind needs knowledge which is strengthened and supported by science and religion, philosophy and common sense. Authors focused on the requirement of yoga’s to answer questions satisfactorily about the physical world and the spiritual reality. Further the researchers highlighted the values and spirituality, Ethical Values, Professional Values, Meditation and its various types, Benefits of Mediation, Spirituality, Spirituality at workplace, and process of meditation that helps in disconnecting from damaging habits of thought, feeling and reaction. The results illustrated that the conscious, positive release of energy emergence due to Raj Yoga improves the quality of your attitude, actions, and interactions. Author stated that engagement in spiritual service is finding an appropriate way to use ones growing spiritual power and understanding for the benefit of others in the wider community is also a method of sustaining its personal growth. Spiritual service can take place on many levels; including spreading peaceful

vibrations into the atmosphere and helping others develop awareness of their own spiritual qualities through good wishes and pure feelings.

Bhupendra et al (2015) studied the spiritual Healing and Raj Yoga Meditation in Schizo-Affective disorder and depression where they performed a series of scales before intervention and after intervention for different domains that are listed as depression anxiety and stress scale, scale for positive symptoms, scale for negative symptoms, global assessment of functioning and social and occupational functioning. The research results exhibited improvement on depression, anxiety and stress because of meditation.

Nikhil Patel (1995) carried out a retrospective study for overseas meditation practitioners at Brahma Kumaris spiritual institution during 1994-95, and assessed the efficacy of Rajayoga meditation to overcome psychoactive substance abuse/dependence. The researcher performed the analytical study for varied abuse/dependencies among 380 foreigners at Brahma Kumaris and his result concluded that the majority of the meditation practitioners (93%) abstained completely from all the substances within one month period of practice of Raj Yoga Meditation, without taking concurrent psychiatric treatment. Spiritual practitioners learn to be dexterous when managing chronic existential tensions and forms of unusual existential inquiry. It is often existential tension and inquiry that presents itself to people during disasters, so spiritual practitioners may potentially be well placed to offer spiritual care in disaster settings, and contribute their expertise to create resilient and better prepared communities better able to deal with hazardous, and sometimes catastrophic events.

A study was performed by Samriddhi et al (2011) where the effects of Raj Yoga meditation on brain waves (EEG) was assessed by recording E.E.G. of raja yogis that exhibited the totally relaxation and mental harmony they do achieve. In their research most of the Raja yogis examined produced Alpha or Theta waves not only while meditating but even while performing complicated mental arithmetic. In certain analysis no any sign of brain disease was observed among Rajyogis at Brahma Kumaris and most of them realized stable mind throughout study span.

Balakishore (2000) explored the impact of Raj Yoga on patients suffering from depression and conducted a case study at Brahma Kumaris World spiritual University, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. In order to examine the impact of Raj Yoga meditation,

researchers assessed the symptoms and respective variation over certain defined time span while observing Raj Yoga meditation among patients suffering from depression.

Kawalinder et al (2013) emphasized on the investigation on the impact of Raja yogameditation on autonomic reactivity in chronic tension type headache patients by studying its impact on blood pressure and heart rate. Researchers conducted their study on 50 chronic tension type headache (CTTH) patients, who were on similar analgesics and muscle relaxant drugs. During their researchers, the meditators were taught Raja yogameditation and practised for certain defined period. The control group did not practice any type of yogic exercises or relaxation techniques. Researchers assessed blood pressure (BP) and isometric handgrip (IHG) test were assessed at 0 week and after 8 weeks. Employing the mean, standard deviation, 't' test and one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied to find the significance. The research revealed that the basal cardiac parameters in terms of the heart rate and blood pressure were uniformly lower in meditators than non-meditators. On performing isometric handgrip test, non-meditators developed significant increase in blood pressure and heart rate during gripping than that seen in meditators. Researchers revealed that Raja yogameditation is effective in reducing BP in resting conditions in CTTH by decreasing the sympathetic reactivity.

Mandape et al (2015) emphasized the effect of Raja yoga meditation on serum lipid profile and fasting blood sugar (FBS) levels in healthy adults. The case-control study included total 100 participants of either sex, in the age 25-45 years. The participants were divided into two groups-meditators (50) doing Raja-yoga meditation for more than 5 years and non-meditators (50), who were age, height and weight, matched and served as controls. Serum total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoproteins (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), very LDL (VLDL) and FBS levels were estimated by kit method, where Raj yoga practitioner exhibited better lower levels of TC, TG, LDL, VLDL and FBS and higher level of HDL than non-meditators.

Kiran et al (2011) evaluated the sympathetic autonomic functions. Stress is often associated with unmanaged emotions and occurrence of increased sympathetic autonomic activity. Long term meditation cultivates mindfulness and has long been used to reduce overwhelming stress. Researchers compared the rise in the mean value of Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) and Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) in acute

stressful condition in meditators of Raja yogameditation and non-meditators, by performing CPT. Researcher made on Raj Yoga meditators showed a rise in mean value of SBP and DBP. Non-meditators showed rise in SBP and during CPT. The meditators showed lesser rise in the mean value of both SBP and DBP as compared to non-meditators; changes in both being highly significant thus implies that the meditators have a lower sympathetic activity compared to non meditators during acute stress, suggesting that Raja yogameditation has a relaxing effect on sympathetic autonomic nervous system (ANS).

Shah et al (2015) measured the emotional level using empirical analysis on the basis of general emotions before and after practicing Raj yoga meditation. Their research revealed that the result that the attitude of the students becomes positive and their inner strength increases through Raj yoga meditation. By developing the Spiritual perception and realization they are able to deepen understanding, compassion and empathy in the life. Developing the Spiritual perception and realization promotes positive emotions like self-confidence, patience, and satisfaction in them.

Seema et al (2011) highlighted haemodynamic Raja yoga effects of meditation by studying its impact on Coronary Heart Disease such as blood pressure, heart rate and ECG meditation is a technique of achieving harmony between the physical, mental, intellectual and spiritual personalities of man. Their research shown that Raja yoga reduces diastolic blood pressure, systolic blood pressure, heart rate and serum cholesterol levels thus it significantly reduces the risk of coronary artery disease.

Kiran Harsh et al (2014) determined the effectiveness of a group stress reduction program based on Raja yogameditation for patients with anxiety and depression. The empirical study was done with the mediators practicing Raja yogameditation. Researchers assessed the Raj Yoga practitioners using Hamilton anxiety and depression scales. Research revealed that the patient with anxiety and depression symptoms in intervention group and control group exhibited significant improvement following six weeks of intervention as suggested by significant reduction in scores of HAM-A and HAMD.

Jyotsana (2015) performed efficiency of Raj Yoga and explored the autonomic function tests where the results were compared using the Student- t test exhibited that Raj yoga is highly significant. Mean increase BP response to Hand Grip Test and Cold Pressor Test was significantly less in meditators than non-meditators. Raj Yoga

resulted shifting of the autonomic balance to parasympathetic side in Raja-yoga meditators, which suggests its utility to combat the ill effects of stress.

Kawalinder et al (2014) correlated the additive effect of meditation on CTTH patients receiving medical treatment. Authors observed the lessons and practical demonstration of Brahma Kumaris spiritual based meditation known as Raja yogameditation for relaxation therapy, in addition to routine medical treatment (analgesics and muscle relaxants). The parameters studied were severity, frequency and duration of CCTH, and their headache index calculated and the research revealed that relaxation therapy (Raja yogameditation) was highly effective in causing earlier relief in chronic tension headache as measured by headache parameter.

Kawalinder et al (2014) exhibited that psychological studies have shown that brief period of mindfulness meditation significantly improves critical cognitive skills. But, there are no studies which have assessed the effects of Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga Meditation (BKRM) practice on positive thinking and happiness in life. Their study was a cross sectional comparative study which was done between Rajayoga meditators and non-meditators. Researcher stated that Brahma Kumaris helps in significantly increasing self-satisfaction and happiness in life by enhancing positive thinking. Irrespective of age and years of short-term or long-term meditation practice, enhanced positive thinking increases self-satisfaction and happiness in life.

Tamasin & Smith (2008) presented the Indian-based BKWSU arose from a Hindu cultural base, but distinct from Hinduism. It began in the 1930s as a small spiritual community called Om Mandli (Sacred Circle), consisting primarily of young women from the Bhai Bund community of Hyderabad Sindh, now part of Pakistan. Since the 1960s the community has been known as the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University (BKWSU), translated from the Hindi, 'Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya'. It is significant that the movement included a 'world' focus in its name, even though active overseas expansion did not begin until 1971.

Kawalinder et al., (2014) designed to correlate the additive effect of meditation on CTTH patients receiving medical treatment. 50 patients (aged 18-58 years) presenting with a clinical diagnosis of CCTH, were divided in 2 groups. Group 1 (n=30) received 8 lessons and practical demonstration of Brahmakumaris spiritual based meditation known as Raja yogameditation for relaxation therapy, in addition to routine medical treatment (analgesics and muscle relaxants). Group 2 (n=20) patients received analgesics and muscle relaxants twice a day but no relaxation therapy in the form of

meditation. Both groups were followed up for 8 weeks period. The parameters studied were severity, frequency and duration of CCTH, and their headache index calculated. Patients in both groups showed a highly significant reduction in headache variables ($P < 0.001$) after 8 weeks. But the percentage of patients showing highly significant relief in severity of headache, duration & frequency in Group 1 was 94%, 91% and 97% respectively whereas in Group 2 it was 36%, 36% and 49% respectively. Headache relief as calculated by headache index was 99% in Group 1 as compared to 51% in Group 2. Even Short term spiritual based relaxation therapy (Raja yogameditation) was highly effective in causing earlier relief in chronic tension headache as measured by headache parameter.

Honourable Justice Ranganath Misra (2001) Former Chief Justice, Supreme Court of India While speaking in Brahma Kumaris All-India conference on Universal Values in Higher Education held from Oct.14 to 16, 2001 at Mount Abu, that, “This institution should take over responsibility of igniting light into teachers, into students & into community. If there is any place in world today where spirituality is order, I think it is this institution. Therefore, institution of this type, this level, this disposition, is perhaps most capable institution to enthuse into community right thinking & right process of activity.”

Jadgish Chander Hassija (2000) In book “Applied Spiritual Knowledge” he states that, Spiritual knowledge neither negotiates existence of world nor does it asks person to run away from problems or to have merely passive attitude but rather knowledge advises man to apply spiritual solutions to them. It explains that problem provides us with opportunities to develop our inner faculties & to refurbish our divine potential. Also, problems serve as tests & enable us to know how deeply we have understood spiritual knowledge & what progress we have made in practical or applied aspect of it.

Jagdish Chander Hassija (1981) In book “Adi Dev” has written that, our story begins in mid-1930’s in Sindh, region of north western India. At that time, religious practices among Hindus had degenerated from its once high level. Sustained impact of western attitudes had changed quality of life. Whole fabric of Sindh culture had become less refined.... In this bewildering atmosphere lived individual of Singh community, in city of Hyderabad, who was called by name Dada, whose full name

was Dada Lekhraj who was corporeal founding father & became instrumental to sustain Brahma kumaris organization.

Jagdish Chander Hassija (1981) In the book “Adi Dev”, in chapter ‘God & destruction of world’ one of his visions beautifully describes that it became turning point in life of dada Lekhraj, when Supreme Soul, Shiva, Himself entered his body & gave him introduction as

Nijanand Rupam Shivoaham Shivoaham

Gyan Swarupam Shivoaham Shivoaham

Prakash Swarupam Shivoaham Shivoaham

Later visions realized Lekhraj to become Divine medium of GOD in great task of transformation of this old world into new world. Dadi Brijendra, witnessed this & writes about miracles happened on that memorable night that, Yes, it was really so – GOD, Supreme Soul, SHIVA, Himself, had entered his body. Entire room filled with red coloured radiations & pure & lovely vibrations. & it was God himself who had given sign that Dada should be his medium & instrument for creating such divine world.

Jagdish Chander Hassija (1981) In the book “Adi Dev” has written that, later in October, 1937 Dada Lekhraj formed trust consisting of managing committee consisting of eight young women. Following that in February, 1938 he surrendered all his movable & immovable properties into trust to run institution. In this great act, he demonstrated highest regard & honour to women & since then, he became backbone of organization & young women took respected forefront role in Brahma Kumaris University. In course of time, Dada Lekhraj came to be known as Prajapita Brahma, this name was given to reflect & honour great spiritual perfection & transformation he made in his life. Those who were morally re-born or spiritually regenerated through oracles of God Shiva as passed through Brahma Baba came to be known as Brahma Kumaris & Brahma Kumars & this spiritually oriented educational institution came to be known Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya. It was registered as charitable trust in India. (Charity No. 269971)

H.E. Mr. S.R. Insanally (1994) Former President of United Nations, General Assembly during his visit to Brahma Kumaris Headquarters, Mt. Abu during 4th September, 1994 expressed his opinion that, “It is my view that closest thing perhaps that we have to earthly paradise is Brahma Kumaris University in Mount Abu. It is Shangri-La, community of people who are dedicated to universal peace & harmony.

There is so much good work being done in Mount Abu, including Global Hospital, where I was able to see first-hand that love is being practiced, not only preached. There are so many ways in Mount Abu of glorifying life, & glorifying Godhead, Supreme Being”.

H.E. Dr. Boutros Ghali (1995) Former Secretary General, United Nations, on occasion of inauguration of Academy for Better World, Brahma Kumaris. Mount Abu expressed that, “Here in Aravalli Hills, Brahma Kumaris have built remarkable new institution. This Academy is to be place of international endeavor place of where men & women can reach to realize their unique human potential & to cultivate values of our common humanity. These aims lie at heart of United Nations. Charter of United Nations makes it clear, while organization is made up of Sovereign States, its source of authority derives from people of world, & its sense of purpose is based upon dignity & worth of human person. Brahma Kumaris well understand need for human cantered approach to problems of peace & development. They well understand comprehensive nature of our task. This Academy, with its universal messages, its human-focused curriculum, its environmentally innovative facilities, is embodiment of their understanding. It is their latest contribution to worldwide collaborative effort for peace & enduring progress, I congratulate Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university on Inauguration of Academy for better world. To you all who will visit Academy, I wish every success in this important work.

Enrique Simo’s (2002) in practical guidebook “Gift of Peace” shares knowledge offered by Brahma Kumaris as method for enabling people to restore & accumulate within themselves positive self-image. Through developing different ways of thinking about ourselves

Jagdish Chander Hassija (1981) In the book “Adi Dev” explains that on 18th January, 1969, corporeal founding father Prajapita Brahma reached his own state of spiritual perfection & left his corporeal form. Consequently, new medium was adopted by Shiv Baba, this time in form of woman called Sister Gulzar (now Dadi Gulzar). Soul of Prajapita Brahma having achieved spiritual proximity with that of Shiv Baba, new part of Supreme Soul reincarnation with Prajapita Brahma in body of sister gulzar referred to as Bapdada. There on Avyakth part has started in Brahma kumaris.

Prajapita Brahma concluded entire teachings in THREE words before leaving corporeal medium. They are

“Nirakrai” – Incorporeal

“Nirahankar” – Egoless

“Nirvikari” -Viceless

Denise Lawrence, one of writers of Brahma kumrais Value Education Course materials, defines values as:

- Values are principles, standards or ideas.
- Values are those principles, standards or qualities regarded as worthwhile or desirable.
- Values are those principles or ideals which are essential to participate in life as social being.
- Values are self- imposed, or ethical policy we adopt in order to travel through life with clear conscience

Avyakth Murails (1990- 2016) essence of importance of murlis told by Almighty are, Murli, translated as ‘Flute of God’ is composed of elevated spiritual versions spoken by Supreme Soul God through human medium. These versions relate highest understanding of truth & righteousness. They explain application of spiritual wisdom of elevated codes of conduct in our daily lives. Murli has magical melody for soul. More soul gets lost in its sweet & profound wisdom in Murli, it works like magic & it begins to transform & divinize our viciousness into divinity. Most elevated of fortunes is sustenance of God’s love. Just as Father, GOD is highest of high, so too Godly sustenance is of order. God’s love & Godly attainments of listening to Murli, is experienced by only handful of souls out of millions in world. Murli explains different subjects of spiritual knowledge & Rajyoga. Supreme God uses words sweet children & dear children in Murli when he refers to students which gives elevated conscious to listener & also provides healing touch to stressful mind. Everyday important part of Brahma Kumaris education system is to read Murli, listen it attentively, study it deeply & then churns it to understand its meaning for benefit of self & world. Murlis in early days of founder were in Sindhi language. Hindi & English version of Murlis started later. Now days murlis are translated to almost all Indian languages & many foreign languages for benefit of entire world community.

National curriculum frame work for school Education (2000) is emphatic about importance of value—oriented education right from school level. Children, when young, are easy to mould & hence, integrated value-based education right from elementary level would bring forth students with strong integrity, with their roots firmly grounded in moral & ethical values.

Education commission (1964-66). observations of commission headed by D.S. Kothari are, “A serious defect in school curriculum is absence of provision in social moral & spiritual values. In life of majority of Indians, religion is great motivation force & is intimately bound up with information of character & inculcation of ethical values. National system of education that is related to life needs & aspirations of people cannot afford to ignore this purposeful force “. We recommend, therefore, that conscious & organized attempt be made for imparting education in social, moral & spiritual values with help, whenever possible, of ethical teachings of great religions.

Living Values: Guide Book (1995): Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university publication in honour of 50th Anniversary of United Nations, is serving as resource for value based educational purposes. Value statements in this book uphold principles & philosophy which address universal aspect of spiritual & moral human values as basis for living one’s life.

Anthony Strano: In book “Eastern Thought for Western mind” replicates insight of word Meditation. Meditation repairs inner wounds of spirit & restores health of soul, Latin word reflects: word ‘meditation’ comes from Latin word ‘meditari’ which is probable cognate of word ‘mederi’ meaning ‘to heal’. Journeying inside, discovering inner self & our true power is beginning of healing process, in which we are able to put back all broken pieces with lot of love.

Dadi Janki (1995) Dadi Janaki is present administrative head of Brahma kumaris & her thoughts on values as written in Living Values Book are as follows.

- Values are our “Parents” – human soul is nurtured by values it holds. sense of security & comfort comes through values in one’s life.
- Values are treasure of life, making humans wealthy & rich. Values are friends, bringing happiness in life. Life filled with values is life of self-respect & dignity. Soul is able to come closer to God, & life becomes real & meaningful.
- Values bring independence & freedom, expand capacity to be self-sufficient, & liberate one from external influences. Soul develops ability to discern truth & to follow path of truth.

- Values offer protection, & one who experiences this is able to share this protection with others. Values bring empowerment, & it becomes possible to remove weaknesses & defects. As innate goodness of individual is concentrated on values, link with God becomes strong & clear. Service is then rendered to others through thoughts, words, & actions. Soul with values is not trapped by any limited desires or attractions, but remains stable in unlimited.

LVEP-Living Value Educational Programme (1995): Educational programme grew out of international project begun in 1995 by Brahma Kumaris, called sharing our values for better world. This program offers variety of experimental activities & practical methodologies for teachers & facilitators to help children & young adults explore & develop 12 key personal & social values. Living values, educational programme - (LVEP) is partnership among educators around world; it is supported by UNESCO, Spanish Committee of UNICEF & Brahma Kumaris & developed in consultation with Education cluster of UNICEF, New York. LVEP is Part of Global movement for culture of peace in framework of United Nations International Decade for Culture of Peace & Non-Violence for children of world.

Mr. Javier Perez De Cuellar (1986): Former Secretary General of United Nations in September, 1986 made this important remark on self-peace: Peace must begin with each one of us through quiet & serious reflection on its meaning, creative ways can be found to foster understanding, friendship & co-operation among all peoples.

B.K. Jayanti (2002) Author of God's Healing Power writes: What is Meditation? Meditation is process of getting to know yourself completely, both who you are inside & how you react to what is outside. Above all, meditation is enjoying your self in literal sense of word.

True essence of Mahabharata & Gita (2000): Gita itself is massive teaching on synthesis of Yoga. Various types of Yoga's have been integrated harmoniously in different chapters of gita. All eighteen chapters in Gita are each designated to one type of Yoga. Main aim & function of Yoga is to train body & mind & in keeping with spirit of this message, Bhagavad-Gita, is great harmonizer of ideas & institutions.

Murli: Murali as basic literary text of Brahma Kumaris, has touched subject of meditation, spirituality & values for common masses. It has promoted subject of meditation & spirituality much further by not reserving it for particular sacred group, but making it available without discrimination for all, poor or rich, illiterate or

educated, men or women. Immense wealth of words has so generously, love fully, tenderly & unreservedly been bestowed upon all & raised them from position of toys of clays to replicas of divine. Writings started focusing on each professional so they could feel that their spiritual inspirations belong to them & transformation is possible.

Brahma Kumaris (1990): In Brahma Kumaris literature easy Rajayoga, it is explained that Sahaj “means” practical methods of yoga, which can be easily practiced by anyone in world. One of important features of this Sahaj Rajyoga is that it brings powers to doer to perform better & balanced actions. Worldwide Brahma Kumaris mediators are doing Yoga while performing their duties. Word Sahaj Rajyoga means I am peaceful soul & have deep feelings of love for God.

Brahma Kumaris (1977) In the book Way & Goal of Raj yoga, essence of Brahma Kumaris 'Yoga is "Be Holy: Be Yogi" which means be practical & natural Yogi, while performing day-to-day duties & responsibilities. "Yoga" does not mean renunciation of our worldly duties & actions as mentioned in Gita significantly, but rather, to renounce weaknesses of soul e.g., ego, lust, greed, attachment & anger, which are great enemies of human soul.

And Brahma Kumaris' meditation practice strongly emphasizes that there is “No other way but way of easy Rajyoga meditation” who can lead human soul from vices toward values of peace, love, bliss, light, joy & purity. There are other ways & methods but they can only be subsidiary & to progress. But “Rajyoga” meditation is most relevant royal way of Yoga.

True Essence of Gita (2006). In Gita words "Sri Bhagvan Uvaca" mean that Bhagvan, Supreme Authority himself is addressed. In these versions God, himself declares that whenever righteousness Dharma declines & unrighteousness or Adharma prevails, I manifest myself, when no other authority can establish righteousness. For protection, right & good of righteous & for destruction of wicked & vices, I come into being from age to age.

A national survey of adult Canadians (Bibby 1995) survey revealed that 52 percent of people acknowledged "spiritual needs". This survey is important in sense that it shows that not only in India but also in other parts of world, people have started awakening towards idea of spirit or soul, & understand it as their "spiritual requirement".

B.K. Frederic Labarthe (2001) “Satyam, Shivam, Sundaram” book of Brahma Kumaris publication is exclusively composed of words that do not belong to author. More than hundred titles (112) attributed to God have been extracted from BK Murlis for name of God & one such name is "Satyam, Shivam, Sundaram, which is also unique name of God which means ‘Trinity of Values’.

- Satyam is Truth
- Shivam is Goodness
- Sundram is Beautiful

Satyam, Shivam, Sundram is ancient Praise Song to Celebrate three main aspects of God’s personality:

One who is embodiment of truth,

One whose heart is -filled to depth with benevolence,

One whose beauty cannot be compared to anything in this world.

One week course (1996) In Bk publication book, Om Shanti is greetings of peace is positive expression in words. In Brahma Kumaris, "Om Shanti" is word attired with universal feelings of peace in thoughts, words, & actions. Aum. It says: “AUM is this imperishable word, AUM is Universe & this is exposition of AUM.” Mandukya Upanishad is attributing to Aum. It is then declared that Aum is part, present & future. & finally, it is declared that all else that may exist beyond bounds of Time, that too is Aum.

Greetings of Om Shanti are pronounced with divine drishti mean sharing peaceful vibrations through physical eyes. In spiritual terms, love & good wishes one soul has for another is conveyed through eye contact (drishti).

Keng, Smoski & Robins (2011). mechanisms of mindfulness meditation are regarded as effective in resolving psychological distress (rumination, anxiety, worry, fear, anger) & assisting in positively enhancing mental health Mindfulness meditation assists in regulating emotions & becoming resilient towards unpleasant emotions. One major factor that negatively affects happiness is tendency to engage in negative thought cycles. This negative feedback loop between thoughts & emotions offsets downward spiral creating feelings of anxiety, stress & depression. For many individuals living with mental illnesses such as depression & anxiety, negative & worrying thoughts are common occurrence offsetting feedback loop. During meditation, individuals learn to observe negative pattern of thoughts & disengage from them by redirecting attention away & bringing it to present moment through

focusing on breath. In one study conducted by Jain et al. (2007), individuals who attended month long course of mindfulness meditation experienced significant decrease in ruminative thoughts & increase in positive mood.

Holzel et al (2011). Practicing mindfulness meditation has been linked to reducing symptoms of psychological disorders such as anxiety, depression, eating disorders, substance abuse & bipolar. Meditational practice may be beneficial in assisting enhancement of cognitive functioning in individuals with bipolar or attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder Empirical evidence suggests that bipolar disorder is associated with impairments in sustained attention & executive function (Maletic & Raison, 2014). Throughout consistent practice of mindfulness meditation, those suffering with attention difficulties may strengthen attention regulation & ACC performance, resulting in better daily performance & concentration.

Zeidan et al (2010) Brief mindfulness training significantly improved working memory & executive functioning whilst reducing fatigue & anxiety. Research by Lykins & Baer (2009) found that meditators reported significantly higher levels of self-compassion & overall sense of well-being with lower levels of rumination, thought suppression & difficulties with emotion regulation when compared to non-meditators. Behavioral studies demonstrate evidence that practicing mindfulness meditation can change manner in which harmful stimuli such as physical pain are experienced. Although pain intensity is subjective experience, it is constructed by interactions between sensory, cognitive & affective processes Mindfulness meditation, uses mechanisms of enhanced cognitive control & emotional regulation to assist in relieving pain intensity through altering emotional responses & diverting attention

Lyubomirsky et al (2005). Research into happiness suggests that physical health is significant factor that contributes to individual overall well-being without general physical health, life satisfaction decreases as living with pain is not only physically damaging but cognitive & emotional strain is significantly debilitating in everyday life. Important characteristic that leads to state of positive affect & happiness is developing effective coping strategies in regards to life challenges & stress

Morone et al (2008) research study found that chronic pain patients who underwent eight weeks of Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) program significantly improved their pain symptoms & overall quality of life. Pain reduction is suggested to

increase as mindfulness meditation is practiced more frequently as sensory & affective pain ratings were reduced in experienced practitioners.

Apkarian et al (2005). Pain reduction is suggested to occur through employing cognitive control mechanisms (attention regulation) to control pain by activating this area. As previously mentioned, research supports activation of ACC during mindfulness meditation. Consequently, it can be suggested that mindfulness meditation reduces pain through resolving attentional conflict streams of information (pain) & bringing attention & awareness back to task focus of breath

Importance of developing positive & effective coping mechanisms is significant as poor coping strategies result in increase of stress & decline in mental & physical health. Mindfulness meditation develops adaptive coping strategy through skill of “reperceiving” (a meta-mechanism of action that leads to change & positive outcome) (Shapiro, Carlson, Astin & Freedman, 2006).

Shapiro et al (2006). Mindfulness based coping strategies give ability to take time & contemplate issue objectively without triggering negative affective states. Consequently, this results in less emotional reactivity to stress & enables response based on self-regulation & solution focus. Studies examining relationship between mindfulness & coping styles have found that undergoing mindfulness meditation & mindfulness based therapy influences coping styles in positive way. Individuals who mindfully meditate are more likely to implement approach coping strategies where future events are interpreted as challenge as opposed to avoidance coping where events are viewed as threatening

Bluth & Blanton (2014). Research has shown that one of proven benefits of mindfulness meditation is improvement in relationships. Relationships are essential to individual’s happiness as feeling of loneliness have detrimental effects to one’s happiness resulting in increase in negative mood, perceived stress & decline in life satisfaction. Studies have demonstrated that mindfulness meditation increased marital satisfaction.

Dekeyser et al (2008). Practicing mindfulness meditation increases awareness of internal states allowing one to become more attuned to their experiences. In turn, this results in greater capacity to understand & empathize with oneself. As ability to become more aware & empathize with oneself increases, so does ability to tune in & empathize towards one’s partner. Mindfulness meditation cultivates empathy which increases degree of openness to others thoughts & emotions. This is especially useful

during arguments as impulsiveness to react on “autopilot” often occurs creating destructive decline in relationship quality. By bringing awareness to one’s own thoughts & emotions, it increases heightened sense of empathy towards both parties. This makes disagreements more positive experience where rather than reacting objective is to understand & recognize emotional suffering.

Living Values: Guide Book (1995): Brahma Kumaris World phenomenal school dissemination in honour of 50th Anniversary of United Nations, is serving as asset for quality based instructive purposes. Worth clarifications in this book keep up gages & theory which address expansive part of capable & awesome human qualities as explanation behind proceeding with one's life.

Anthony Strano: In book "Eastern Thought for Western personality" duplicates appreciation of word Meditation. Thought repairs within injuries of soul & re-establishes thriving of spirit, Latin word mirrors: "reflection" begins from Latin word "meditari" which is possible related of "mederi" suggesting 'to recuperate'. Going inside, finding inside character & our authentic force is start of modifying framework, in which we can give back all broken pieces with tremendous measure of affection.

Dadi Janki (1995) Dadi janaki is present authoritative head of Brahma kumaris & her examinations on qualities as written in Living Values Book are as per going with.

- Values are our "Kin" – human soul is kept up by qualities it holds. Slant that all is well with world & solace comes through qualities for span of one's life.
- Values are fortune of life, making people well off & rich. Qualities are companions, getting satisfaction life. Nearness stacked with qualities is nearness of sentiment pride & respectability. Spirit can come nearer to God, & life winds up being veritable & significant.
- Values bring autonomy & versatility, build up ability to act really adequate, & one from outer impacts. Spirit builds up capacity to see truth & to take after strategy for truth.
- Values offer security, & one who encounters this can allow this affirmation to others. Values bring strengthening, & it finds opportunity to be conceivable to expel lacks & distortions. As intrinsic integrity of individual is revolved around qualities, relationship with God persuades chance to be solid & clear. Association is then rendered to others through considerations, words, & activities. Spirit with qualities is not got by any restricted wishes or attractions, yet rather stays stable in boundless.

B.K. Jayanti (2002) Author of God 's Healing Power makes: What is Meditation? Reflection is way toward getting chance to be acquainted with yourself totally, both your character inside & how you respond to what is outside. Most importantly, reflection is having awesome time in strict notion word.

True essence of Mahabharata & Gita (2000): Gita itself is gigantic preparing on blend of Yoga. Differing sorts of Yoga's have been created concordantly in specific territories of gita. All eighteen zones in Gita are each doled out to one kind of Yoga. Fundamental point & cut off of Yoga is to set up body & brain & regarding soul of this message, Bhagavad-Gita, is astounding harmonizer of thoughts & establishments. Murli: Murali as vital canny substance of Brahma Kumaris, has touched subject of thought, most critical sentiment being & values for key masses. It has impelled subject of examination & most noteworthy sentiment being much further by not saving it for specific heavenly amassing, yet rather making it accessible without disconnection for all, poor or rich, unskilled or educated, men or ladies. Immense abundance of words has so liberally, adore absolutely, carefully & wholeheartedly been accommodated all & raised them from position of toys of soils to pantomimes of great. Works began concentrating on every expert so they could feel that their huge motivations have spot with them & change is conceivable.

Brahma Kumaris (1990): In Brahma Kumaris making direct Rajayoga, it is cleared up that Sahaj "suggests" helpful procedures for yoga, which can be reasonably cleaned by anybody on planet. One of significant segments of this Sahaj Rajyoga is that it goes on qualities to master to perform better & adjusted activities. Worldwide Brahma Kumaris carruout Yoga while playing out their responsibilities. Word Sahaj Rajyoga derives I am serene soul & have critical sentiments of veneration for God.

Brahma Kumaris (1977) In book Way & Goal of Raj yoga, in book Way & Goal of Rajyoga, substance of Brahma Kumaris 'Yoga is "Be Holy: Be Yogi" which means be sensible & typical Yogi, while performing customary duties & commitments. "Yoga" does not mean renunciation of our essential duties & activities as decided in Gita fundamentally, yet rather, to keep lacks from guaranteeing spirit e.g., character, need, insatiability, affiliation & hatred, which are gigantic foes of human soul.

Also, Brahma Kumaris' appearance hone unequivocally concentrates on that there is "No other way however procedure for essential Rajyoga thought" who can lead human soul from obscenities toward estimations of peace, love, rapture, light,

satisfaction & morals. There are various ways & methods yet they ought to be partner & to advance. Regardless, "Rajyoga" thought is most essential preeminent strategy for Yoga.

True Essence of Gita (2006). In Gita words "Sri Bhagvan Uvaca" recommend that Bhagvan, Supreme Authority himself is tended to. In these alterations God, himself announces that at whatever point dependability Dharma decays & fiendishness or Adharma wins, I show myself, when no other power can set up goodness. For security, right & unimaginable of model & for pummelling of treacherous & obscenities, I appear from age to age.

A national survey of adult Canadians (Bibby 1995) study uncovered that 52 % of individuals saw "critical requirements". This study is basic as in it demonstrates that in India & also in different parts of world, individuals have begun mixing towards soul or soul, & distance it as their "powerful key".

2.3 SUMMARY

This is the matter of fact that a number of researches have been done for assessing the significance of Raj Yoga meditation on varied psychological and physiological variables, but as per our knowledge there is no any research discussing the motivations behind the Raj Yoga meditation. On contrary, it can also be found that very few researches have focused on Brahma Kumaris spiritual organization and allied meditation practices of Raj Yoga. More significantly and interestingly no any research has been done for exploring motivational factors influencing people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation. Thus, taking into consideration of these research limitations, in this research proposal the study of various motivational factors influencing practitioners at Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, has been done.

The presented thesis work is an empirical study based on mixed research paradigm. In the next chapter (Chapter-3), the research methodology considered in this research is discussed, which has been followed by data analysis in Chapter-4.

CHAPTER-3

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Background

In this section of the presented dissertation, the research methodology applied are discussed and various key constructs such as research design, sampling, data analysis approaches, conceptual model used for study etc are discussed.

3.2 Research Design

In recent years, a number of people have attracted towards Raj Yoga practices at Brahma Kumaris organization. In this world, where individual often makes efforts to achieve more worldly beings and prosperity, the adoption of Raj Yoga for long run and dedicating towards Brahma Kumaris is an interesting research domain to be explored about. The study of various motivational factors that put enthuse among people to adopt Raj Yoga, can help both the individual willing to join Raj Yoga at meditation at Brahma Kumaris as well as the organizational management to attract more and more followers of Raj Yoga meditation. Thus, taking into consideration of such significances, here in this thesis an empirical and descriptive analysis has been performed to analyze various motivational factors to join Raja yogameditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters. The below mentioned research questionnaires intends to explore precise information about the various motivational factors of Raja yogameditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan.

In order to perform study of various motivational factors that motivates people to join Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris organization at Mount Abu, Rajasthan, in this thesis, the mixed research paradigm that encompasses both the qualitative and quantitative research paradigm. Here, initially the qualitative research has been proposed which would assess varied significances and basic aspects of Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris International Spiritual University; Mount Abu, Rajasthan, which has been followed by an analytical or empirical analysis. The empirical study is based on the quantitative research paradigm using primary data/responses retrieved through questionnaire based semi-structured interviews at Brahma Kumaris Worlds spiritual university, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. Being a mixed research paradigm (qualitative and quantitative), this research and study has been proposed to be performed in certain defined research sequences to achieve optimal research objectives. The proposed sequential research process is given as follows:

The Overall research methodology encompasses following phases:

1. *Defining Research Objectives*
2. *Literature survey & analysis*
3. *Research Hypotheses definition*
4. *Questionnaires preparation*
5. *Primary Data collection*
6. *Sampling & data processing*
7. *Data analysis & Hypothesis test*
8. *Research conclusion & limitations analysis*
9. *Recommendation.*

overall proposed methodology applied in this dissertation is given as follows:

Fig. No. 1: Research Methodology

In this thesis, initially the qualitative study has been done where the predominant literatures discussing Raja yogameditation and various Raja yogapractices performed at Brahma Kumaris. In addition, various literatures discussing motivational factors

and other significances of Raja yogameditation etc have been discussed. The qualitative analysis has been followed by quantitative or empirical analysis. Here, to perform empirical and descriptive analysis, questionnaires with open ended as well as closed ended questions have been prepared as per defined research objectives and hypothesis.

Overall defined research hypothesis in this thesis are given as follows:

3.3 Conceptual Model

I this dissertation, a conceptual model has been defined to be applied to perform research and analysis for intended objectives and hypothesis. The developed conceptual model is given as follows:

:

Fig. No. 2: Conceptual model & Hypothesis formulation

As depicted in the above figure, the conceptual model reveals the research approach as the explorative effort to assess different motivational constructs and their impact on BKRM consideration and following up. Considering the hypothesis and their interrelation with the overall research objective, it can be found that initially in this thesis various demographic factors such as education; age, gender etc have been examined. In addition, the financial statuses of devotees and respective expectations or preferences have also been discussed in this study phase. Here, the impact of the demographic factors on motivation people to join BKRM has been investigated.

In the second hypothesis of the proposed conceptual model, the personal thrust, expectations and preferences including devotion, self-satisfaction and attainment, peace, mental peace and blissful life, devotion towards society and supernatural power etc have been examined to have their impact on motivating people to join BKRM.

In this third phase of research process, certain significant factors such as spiritual factors, physical factors, and psychological factors have been examined to have impact on motivating people towards BKRM, Mount Abu, Rajasthan (India). At the

last of the research phase, in forth hypothesis, the generic but very significant factors such as life style, way of living at BK, spiritual environment and various holy practices etc have been examined for its motivational significant towards Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga Meditation (BKRM).

In order to examine and investigate these factors, the primary data based empirical and analytical research has been performed using research questionnaires. The discussion of the data collection process and respective analysis is given in the following section of the presented thesis.

3.4 Data Collection

In qualitative study, the data has been collected from secondary sources like journals, magazines, various online and offline literatures and information catalogue available for Raj Yoga meditation, practices at Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga Meditation (BKRM) etc. The qualitative study, it has been intended to perform study and analysis of varied motivational factors that influence people decision making process to get allied with Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation and become a part of BRRM practices at its international headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. In qualitative study, the significant information has been retrieved through various internet resources and existing journals discussing Raj Yoga motivations.

In the initial phase of research work, the study of varied literatures and articles has been done, which has enabled extracting the critical information about Raj Yoga motivations and allied motivational factors at Brahma Kumaris. On the basis of the literatures studied, certain hypotheses have been formulated, which has been followed by the formation of research questionnaire to be used for response collection through semi-structured interviews at BK headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. To achieve empirical research analysis the questionnaires has been used to collect responses of the devotees associated with Brahma Kumaris organization for Raj Yoga meditation for certain period and their motivation towards being allied with Brahma Kumaris organization. In this thesis, the semi-structured interviews have been conducted with individual respondents to retrieve responses from the respondents at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, and Rajasthan. On the basis of data collected and responses retrieved the data analysis has been performed to justify the research hypothesis.

3.5 Data Source

In order to perform intended or defined research work, in this thesis, two predominant data sources have been considered. These are the secondary data source and primary data source. A brief discussion of these data sources are given as follows:

- **Secondary Data**

In this thesis, considering the significances of precise and accurate information, a number of practices towards Raj Yoga meditation and its significances are explored and the relevant information are studied. In the thesis, the secondary data sources such as books, ebooks, journals, research articles related to Raj Yoga meditation and its significances, subjective literatures, magazines, newspapers and varied other online (internet based) resources have been used. In addition, articles and documents available for various meditational practices at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters also known as Brahma Kumaris world spiritual centre have been studied to extract various significant information.

- **Primary Data**

The primary data sources represents the responses retrieved through questionnaire based semi-structured interviews. In this thesis, the questionnaires have been prepared in such a manner that it extracts significant information required to justify or assess the research hypothesis. The questionnaire encompasses the questions or queries related to various demographic as well as motivational factors that motivate people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation. The personal observations based data preparation has been considered as the primary data. The open ended as well as closed ended questionnaires intend to extract the significant information about the motivational factors that motivates people to adopt Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris. Here, the semi-structured interviews based primary data has been collected from the Raj Yoga practitioners, associated members of Brahma Kumaris international headquarters at Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India.

3.6 Sample Size

In this thesis, to perform empirical study and analysis, the responses have been collected from 500 respondents at Brahma Kumaris international headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. Here, 500 dedicated Raj Yogis performing Raj Yoga meditation at BK, specifically in the age group of 20-45 years, have been considered for interviews. The selected responses have been verified for replication or wrong

entry or repeated response. Thus processing for pruning, the final data samples have been prepared. Further, the random sampling scheme has been applied for data sampling process.

Once processing the data sampling, the sampled responses have been processed statistically to evaluate or verify the research hypothesis. A brief discussion of data processing approach applied in this thesis is given in the following section.

3.7 Data Processing

To perform hypothesis justification or verification, it becomes inevitable to assess retrieved responses statistically. In this thesis, to analyse the collected responses for various motivational factors towards Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, the statistical analysis approaches have been used. Here, three well known and significant statistical approaches have been considered to perform the study. These are:

- 1 *Reliability test*
- 2 *Mean, standard deviation*
- 3 *Correlation analysis*

3.8 Tools for Data Analysis

Taking into consideration of the significant requirements of highly accurate and efficient data analysis, in this research proposal the highly efficient tools such as SPSS and MS Excel have been proposed. These tools or software platforms can be significant for performing data analysis and results visualization. In the proposed work the two tools would be employed for data processing and analysis. These are:

- *Microsoft Excel*
- *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)*

3.9 Summary

In this Chapter the discussion of the various methodologies and associated constructs were discussed. Various mythological approaches such as research design, hypothesis formulation, data collection methods and the nature of data, tools implementation etc and their implementation to accomplish overall research objectives were briefed in this section of the presented thesis. In the next chapter (Chapter-4) the discussion of the data analysis and respective significances towards hypothesis justification is presented.

CHAPTER-4

4 DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

4.1 -: ACTIVITIES IN INDIA: -

Attractive unique Services

4.1.1 Rajayoga Meditation:

Every Brahma Kumaris centre offers a foundation course in Raja yoga meditation. It explains clearly the relationship between the mind and body and the interplay between the soul, God and matter. It leads one to self realisation, God consciousness and development of inner powers through meditation. Dally spiritual lessons and practical exercises help channel the spiritual energy into positive and productive actions in daily life. A process of continuous learning ensures renewal of our innate values at the deepest level.

4.1.2 Spiritual Service through Multimedia:

Electronic media: Talks on positive thinking, human values, spiritual empowerment and a holistic lifestyle are regularly broadcast on several TV channels such as Zee Jagaran, Sadhana TV and Sanskar, and Om Shanti audio channel (through DTH). The institution also offers a huge collection of audio CDs, VCDs, DVDs, MP3s and cassettes.

Helpline: Om Shanti Help Line provides 24-hour free assistance to people who are suffering from depression, sorrow and stress. The helpline is available in many languages and in several cities in India. Visit www.OmShanti HelpLine.com for details.

4.1.3 Print media:

Apart from literature in several regional and national languages, the Brahma Kumaris publishes several spiritual magazines in English, Hindi and regional languages. Prominent among these are Gyanamrit (Hindi monthly), World Renewal (English monthly) and Purity (English monthly). Spiritual articles by BKs are regularly published in many national and regional newspapers.

4.1.4 Cyber media:

There are lots of websites dedicated to providing information about the activities and courses of Brahma Kumaris. The official websites are: www.bkwsu.org and www.brahmakumaris.com. Important events in the institution are also webcast through the internet.

4.1.5 Interfaith Meets:

Brahma Kumaris have been constantly striving to build bridges between people of different faiths and cultures. They strive to promote the core spirituality in all faiths, which is the common thread that leads to mutual understanding and respect. Apart from lots of interfaith programmes at the local level, significant events such as the Inner Voice of Peace dialogue in 2005, Dharmacharya Sannam in 1993 and Universal Peace Conference in 1987 have been held at Mt. Abu.

4.1.6 Group Meditation for World Peace:

On the third Sunday of every month, group meditation for world peace is held at the same time in all BK centres in the world. Group meditation programmes are specially organised when calamities and disasters strike so that vibrations of peace can be created to support distressed people.

4.1.7 Community Service:

Every Brahma Kumaris centre, besides offering free meditation and self-development courses, works with the local community in various ways. The centres conduct awareness campaigns in the fields of health, education, de-addiction and environmental conservation. During major festivals and public occasions they join other local groups to bring people together by organising fairs, cultural events, tableaux, exhibitions, rallies and public talks in order to help enhance people's quality of life through the application of spiritual, human and ethical values.

There is a growing demand for the skills and services of Brahma Kumaris from public organizations. For instance, in Mumbai, the municipality has given several public parks that were lying in neglect to the BKs for maintenance and upgrading. Today the derelict parks have become beautiful oases of recreation and spiritual education.

4.1.8 Educational Service:

There are 19 service wings of Raja yoga Education and Research Foundation (RERF) that reach out to a wide cross-section of the society and offer the benefits of various courses developed by the Brahma Kumaris. The RERF is a sister body of the Brahma Kumaris which was established in 1982 for providing specialised services

to different sections of society. Throughout the year each wing holds seminars and conferences at BK campuses and organises activities to help people integrate values and spiritual wisdom into their lives and share them in their family and workplace.

4.1.9 Raja Yoga Education & Research Foundation (RE & RF) wings: -

In 1982, in addition to its International Spiritual Study Centres, the Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university for the implementation of universal human values through spirituality also established the "Raja Yoga Education and Research Foundation". This foundation functions as a sister organization to the Brahma Kumaris. It was established as a society and registered under the provisions of the Societies Registration Act XXI of 1860 with Delhi as its headquarters. The 18 wings of this Foundation were created to match the understanding and serve the spiritual needs of the people of various backgrounds. It aims to create a wave of positive elevated spiritual awareness that will empower people to counteract the increasing climate of negativity, corruption, hostility and degeneration of human values. The Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university's active working strength of these wings dedicated their spiritual services to the masses through their own practical examples of transformation. The members of these wings were also part of Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university at all its study centres.

The aims and objectives of these wings are:

- To open and establish centres of Rajyoga;
- To impart and propagate the principles of Raja yoga Education;
- To propagate and encourage the study and practice of the principles of truth nonviolence, spiritual love and divine virtue;
- To foster soul-consciousness and the spirit of universal brotherhood;
- To remove superstition, blind faith and ignorance;
- To work for the eradication of moral and social evils;
- To spread and promote literacy amongst the masses;
- To carry out activities for the upliftment and welfare of women;
- To undertake scientific research in Rajyoga;
- To work for and promote rural development.

The sectors served are: administration, art & culture, business & industry, education, jurists, media, medical, politicians, religious, rural development, science & engineering, security, social services, sports, transport, women, and youth. These wings through education and the practical examples of their lives are voluntarily contributing their services for the upliftment of values in society through

"spirituality".

1	Administrators Wing	2	Art and Culture Wing	3	Business and Industry Wing	4	Education Wing
5	Jurist Wing	6	Media Wing	7	Medical Wing	8	Politicians Service Wing
9	Religious Wing	10	Rural Development Wing	11	Scientists and engineers wing	12	Security Services Wing
13	Social Service Wing	14	Sports Wing	15	Women Service Wing	16	Youth Wing
17	SPARC Wing	18	Transport and travel Wing				
			a) Surface		b) Aviation Tourism		

Fig. No. 3: -Logos of the 19 service wings of Brahma Kumaris

- The Administrators Wing conducts courses in Excellence in Administration, Stress Management, the Art of Communication, Harmony in Relationships, Attitudinal Change, Self-Management, and Raja Yoga Meditation. Such courses have improved the lives of hundreds of administrators, managers and executives from

banks and corporations, etc. and benefited bureaucrats from various state governments and the Central Government.

- The Art & Culture Wing has benefited thousands of artists and performers through training programmes designed to help them conquer unhealthy habits as well as to divert their art from ‘art for art's sake’ to ‘art for the betterment of society’.
- The Business & Industry Wing fosters equitable business practices, value—based management and individual excellence. Its Self—Orientation Workshop spreads awareness of the importance of values in business and industry. The Self Managing Leader programme fuses the best modern management practices with the ancient management principles of Raja Yoga. Individuals from numerous organisations, including such industry giants as Nagarjuna Fertilizers and Chemicals, Iffco, Godrej, Atul Group, Oil and Natural Gas Commission, Bharat Heavy Electricals and Southern Petrochemicals Industrial Corporation, have benefited from these courses.
- The Education Wing promotes value—based education through a variety of programmes and activities, including Moral and Spiritual Raja yoga Education Training Courses conducted for in-service primary, higher primary and high school teachers, as well as for lecturers of pre-university colleges. These training courses are approved by the Department of Education Governments of Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Delhi, Gujarat etc. The Wing has also developed a diploma course: Education in Values and Spirituality. It also conducts children's' Personality Development camps and organizes national international seminars, conferences and educational dialogues.
- The Jurists Wing regularly organizes dialogues, seminars and conferences for professionals in different parts of India which have drawn participation from eminent personalities such as the former Chief Justice of India, Honourable Justice Ranganath Mishra; Judges of Supreme Court of India, Honourable Justice P.B. Sawant and Honourable Justice S.Mohan Wing also enjoys the support and patronage of internationally acclaimed jurist, the Honourable Mr. Justice V.R. Krishna Iyer.
- The Media Wing undertakes to bring the message of spiritual empowerment to media personnel and agencies at all levels, and ensures appropriate coverage of the Vishwa Vidyalaya's many activities and events. The wing produces Om Shanti

Media, a news letter which reports on the services conducted by Brahma Kumaris worldwide and which has been praised for its positive journalism by various media personalities. The wing also produces circulates "Good News" video cassettes and VCDs. The main T.V. channels cover programmes on "Spirituality and Values".

- The Medical Wing has a long and substantial history of achievements in raising public health awareness, researching the application of medication in illness prevention and health promotion and in serving medical and health professionals. The Wing's numerous all campaigns and Holistic Health Fairs have enabled thousands of individuals to free themselves from the use of alcohol, tobacco and drugs.
- The Politicians Service Wing, offers programmes, designed to enhance the will power and bring out the inner divinity of individual politicians across the political spectrum. Numerous Central Government and State Ministers, MP5, MLAs and Ambassadors of many countries have benefited from participation in the Wing's conferences and programmes, as well as from visits to Brahma Kumaris headquarters in Mount Abu.
- The Religious Wing works to bring religions together in a spirit of tolerance, respect and understand through gatherings of religious leaders such as the Adhyatmic Jeevan Darshan Maha Sammelan (1988), and the Dhamracharya Maha Sammelan (1993), both held in Mt. Abu and through innovative activities such as the Ishwariya Anubhuti Jyotirling Rathyatra (representing all 12 Jyotirlinga) which took place in 2000. It also conducts international Inter Faith and All religious conferences.
- The Rural Development Wing organizes exhibitions, video and film presentations, peace processions, educational programmes and meditation courses at the village and district levels to help the rural populace develop self-respect, co-operation and positive human values. It also arranges special seminars and conferences for administrative officials at village and district levels as well as for the Board members of rural cooperative societies and other development agencies. Recently research work has been started by the wing on yogic farming in which groups of Raja yogapractioners give positive vibrations to the crops. The effect of this practice has been enormous and it has also brought down the use of fertilizers and harmful pesticides significantly.

- The Scientists and Engineers Wing aids the integration of science and spirituality and promotes environmental awareness, value-oriented science, and eco-friendly technology as well as industrial peace, safety and productivity. It conducts lectures and technical seminars in many industrial settings and technical colleges and universities, and has developed a scientific exhibition which scientifically explain a number of phenomena, including spiritual concepts.
- The Security Wing offers Spiritual Orientation Programmes and seminars relevant to "Personnel in Uniform", including Army, Air Force, Navy, Coast Guard, Central Intelligence Agencies, Private Security Agencies, State Police, Fire Fighting, Civil Defense, Anti—Corruption and Jail Services, etc. It aims to strengthen the efficiency and equanimity of mind of individuals in these establishments, as well as their ability to cope with stress arising from their hazardous lifestyles.
- The Social Services Wing brings spiritual social services to physically, morally and disadvantaged people, and organizes programmes for social workers and representatives of social organisations. It has actively served the inmates of numerous prisons, both spiritual and physical relief to victims of natural calamities such as the earth which affected Bhuj and the Orissa Cyclone, and spiritually empowered thousands of workers from across India through its conferences and seminars.
- The Sports Wing promotes excellence in sports through national seminars and workshops, Raja yogaMeditation Camps and refresher courses for notational and international sports personalities. The sports Authority of India (SAI) has decided to conduct Meditation training for the national teams of the different sports disciplines during coaching camps,
- The Transport Wing Coordinates and organizes residential training programmes. In courses and slide presentations to aid the development of self—control, self—discipline, self—confidence and concentration, and a balanced state of mind for people in the transport industry, in Surface Transport, Railways, Civil Aviation and Marine Transport.
- The Women's Wing is committed to bringing the message and methods of empowerment to women throughout India and the world while at the same time endeavoring to raise men's awareness to support this. In addition to organizing conferences, symposia, exhibitions, Raja yogacamps, et cetera as other Wings do,

it publishes literature and conducts surveys on matters pertaining to women and celebrates International Women's Day.

- The Youth Wing conducts programmes such as the Positive Change Course to enhance youth's good judgment, concentration and self-confidence and facilitate freedom and protection from drugs, alcohol, smoking and violent tendencies. The Wing is achieving its aims with the help of more than 80,000 young who lead lives of celibacy and freedom from unhealthy habits and spend their energy in rendering voluntary service for the upliftment of society.

A lot of top-of-the-line organizations invite the BKs to conduct training programmes. To name a few: Godrej, NHPC, NTPC, HPCL, IFFCO, KRIBHCO, BHEL, Birla Cement, Asian Paints, Ranbaxy, Airtel, Indian Air Force, Defence Research and Development Organization, Jet Airways, Institute of Chartered Accountants of India, Rural Electrification Corporation, National Horticulture Board, Institute of Company Secretaries, Delhi Secretariat, Delhi Transco, MTNL (New Delhi), Deloitte Consulting, HCL Technologies, IBM, Hughes Software, Singapore Airlines, TCS, Birla Sunlife, Wipro Technologies, Indian Airlines, EXL Services, Indian Oil, Ministry of Railways, Lions Club and Rotary Club.

4.2 Most popular courses which have benefitted millions in India, are:

4.2.1 Stress Management: Very popular in all groups. Especially beneficial for administrators, office workers, hospital staff, police personnel, patients, caretakers, students and families. The course helps identify the type and level of stress that a person is experiencing, develop a constantly positive attitude, and protect the self from negative and stressful influences

4.2.2 Self-Development Leadership: It is a training course for executives and professionals at all levels who wish to develop their personal leadership capabilities to a higher level. The aim of the programme is to facilitate the participants to develop inner powers to cope with change and choose the right response to situations.

4.2.3 Spiritual Empowerment & Holistic Personality Development: A lot of academic, public and government organizations, including state legislatures, are seeking this course, which helps enhance one's inner powers and spiritual quotient for effective performance.

4.2.4 Education in Values & Spirituality: A programme developed by Brahma Kumaris Education Society. Extensively researched and meticulously developed courses by spiritualists offer integrated and holistic education in moral, human,

social, administrative, cultural and spiritual values. The courses have been introduced in South Gujarat University in Surat, Chaudhary Devilal University in Sirsa, University of Madras and many other centres of higher education.

4.2.5 Self-Empowerment Workshops : The Self empowerment workshops have been appreciated in women's organizations, youth forums, prisons, rehabilitation centres, senior citizens' groups, rural organizations etc. Regular spiritual empowerment courses are held in Tihar Jail in Delhi for prisoners and programmes are frequently organised in prisons in many states by local BK centres.

4.3 -: SOCIAL SERVICE: -

4.3.1 Rural Development Programs: Especially in the rural areas of Gujarat, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and the north-east, BKs have organised numerous rural outreach programmes to educate and empower people in subjects like hygiene, health, de-addiction, removing superstition, self-empowerment, self-esteem, values in family life etc.

4.3.2 Disaster Management: During calamities and natural disasters the Brahma Kumaris have reached out to provide material and spiritual aid. Extensive aid and rehabilitation work have been done after the earthquake in Gujarat, the Tsunami in Tamil Nadu and Kerala and during floods in various parts of the country.

4.3.3 Healthcare : Health and De-addiction Camps: Hundreds of health exhibitions, camps and fairs have been held all over India to explain the mind-body-medicine paradigm, to create awareness about psychosomatic diseases and the role of Raja yogain de-addiction of tobacco, alcohol and harmful drugs and to provide free health check-ups.

4.3.4 Coronary Artery Disease and Diabetes Management Camps: For the past five years a team of specialist doctors has been conducting camps of five to seven days for heart patients, diabetics and people suffering from similar symptoms. The patients are guided systematically to learn and practice healthy lifestyle habits and Raja yogameditation.

4.3.5 Global Hospital and Research Centre: In 1990 The J Watumull Memorial Global Hospital and Research Centre was established within walking distance of Madhuban. The hospital utilizes allopathic, homeopathic, ayurvedic and other indigenous methods of healing, and is staffed by local and foreign, professional and voluntary nursing and medical staff. There are inpatient and outpatient services, active surgical theatres and a critical care unit. The local

indigenous community is treated free of charge on site and through the Village Outreach Program. The hospital now has five additional branches specializing in eye care and trauma, facilitating the humanitarian work of the Brahma Kumaris, in the context of 'service' that, for BKs, means to bring spiritual nourishment and peace to people of the world.

The J. Watumull Memorial Global Hospital and Research Centre in Mt. Abu is designed to provide high-quality, modern, holistic healthcare services in a tranquil environment. It is managed and run by a charitable trust established and supported by members of the Brahma Kumaris.

- It offers free or subsidized treatment and medicines to 100,000 people, of whom 54,000 are tribal residents of 855 primitive villages.
- Its village outreach programme provides basic healthcare in 10 villages in Abu.
- Nutritional mid-day snacks are provided to a few primary schools.
- Teaches sewing skills to rural women.
- Provides vocational training and employment opportunities to local youth through a nursing training centre.

GHRC has opened many branches- the BSES MG hospital in Mumbai, G.V. Mody Rural Health Care Centre and Eye Hospital, Abu, Global Hospital Institute of Ophthalmology, Abu and a Clinic-cum-Diagnostic Centre in Vadodara.

4.4 MEGA EVENTS

4.4.1 Swarnim Bharat Yuva Padyatra: - The Youth Wing of RERF took up the task of meeting millions of people all over India to bring about awareness on spirituality and values by organising a Padyatra (journey on foot) from August to November 2006. The highlights of this rally are:

Number of Padyatras: 30 reaching 9 star network cities. Total distance: More than 25,000 km. No. of Padyatris: 25-35 permanent Padyatris in each yatra plus thousands of local yatris. Launched: Mumbai on 20-8-06. Finale: Ahmedabad on 26-Nov-06. Target groups: More than 15,000 programmes being arranged in schools, colleges, jails, government offices, clubs, private companies, police stations, youth organizations of villages and cities, BK centres etc. Service activities: Cleanliness campaigns, medical camps, lectures, personal interviews, cultural programmes, video shows, films on spirituality etc.

4.4.2 Orientation Programme for Education in Human VALUES :

More than 37,000 school teachers of State Council of Educational Research and Training, Delhi, attended an orientation programme for Education in Human Values in June 2006 at Om Shanti Retreat Centre near Delhi. Over the last four years several batches of principals from state government schools in Haryana, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa and Madhya Pradesh have benefited from the orientation programme.

4.4.3 President Abdul Kalam's Visit to Mount Abu :-Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, President of India visited Gyan Sarovar, BK Academy for a Better World, on April 28, 2006. Over two thousand youth, children and people from different professions gathered at the Harmony Hall to hear President Kalam share his views on moral education, science and spirituality and religious harmony. This was his fifth visit to the institution's headquarters and the first after he became President.

4.4.4 International Dialogue for Religious and Spiritual Leaders:-

Forty religious and spiritual leaders gathered at The Inner Voice of Peace Dialogue on 11th October at Om Shanti Retreat Centre. It was chaired by Rev. Marcus Braybrooke, President of the World Congress of Faiths, Rev. Charles Gibbs, Executive Director of the United Religions Initiative and Sister Jayanti, European Director of the Brahma Kumaris. The participants represented nine faiths and 19 countries. They also had a meeting with the President of India, Dr. Abdul Kalam, at Rashtrapati Bhawan before they moved to Mount Abu to continue their dialogue. Dr. L. M. Singhvi, eminent Jurist, parliamentarian and interfaith activist, Inaugurated the dialogue.

4.5 RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

4.5.1 CAD Regression Project: -

In 1997, a research project, the largest ever to see how lifestyle interventions - specifically a low-fat, high-fibre diet, an hour-long daily walk and stress control by Raja yoga meditation - can cause coronary artery regression, was initiated by Global Hospital and Research Centre in Mt.Abu.

Project High lights:

- Co-partnered by the Defence Institute of Physiology and Allied Sciences, New Delhi and commissioned by Dr.A.PJ Abdul Kalam, the then scientific adviser to DRDO.
- Nine-year study followed 516 patients in two groups.

- Conclusions: Lifestyle changes improved CAD regression and also reduced angina.
- Reduced stress hormones and bad cholesterol and increased good cholesterol and physical stamina.

Unveiling the study at a teleconference address during the World Congress on Clinical and Preventive Cardiology, September 2006 in Shantivan, Abu, Dr. Kalam said the study's healthy heart lifestyle module programme was user-friendly, safe and cost-effective..

4.5.2 Meditation & Medicine: -

Other research projects have been done by the department of neuropsychiatry at Global Hospital in Mount Abu on 'Effects of Raja yogameditation in overcoming drug addiction'. 'Effects of Raja yogameditation in treating neurotic illnesses', and 'Changes in Physiological Parameters – EEG, muscle tension, etc, - after Raja yogapractice'.

4.5.3 Renewable Energy Projects: -

The research and development programme of the Department of Renewable Energy (DRE), established in 1992 by the World Renewal Spiritual Trust, a sister body of BKS, extends to the following technologies: photovoltaic power packs; solar steam cooking systems; water recycling technologies; solar hot water plants; and passive solar architecture. DRE facilitates promotion of alternative energy technology in underprivileged remote villages in Rajasthan and elsewhere.

4.5.4 Research in Spiritual Applications: -

The Brahma Kumaris have a research wing called Spiritual Applications and Research Centre (SPARC) that undertakes research in application of Raja yogameditation in various fields such as health, education and science. The centre has supported studies involving application of Raja yoga on cancer patients in Bangalore, on improving memory and concentration in students and studies exploring spiritual truths from a scientific perspective.

4.5.5 Environment-friendly Initiatives: -

Brahma Kumaris strive for establishing a harmonious relationship between humanity and nature. The institution has been exploring reliable, cost-effective and fossil-fuel-free alternatives to diesel generators and electricity grid extension systems for more than a decade.

All the BK campuses have integrated eco-friendly technology in their buildings and energy consumption. The BKs have been global pioneers in the installation and use of solar energy within large communities. The BKs are the largest private producers of solar energy in the world. Some of the notable eco-friendly measures adopted by the BKs are:

- Installed largest parabolic solar device in Shantivan, Abu in 1998. It can provide steam for cooking a maximum of 38,500 meals a day.
- Solar hot water facilities that provide nearly 60,000 litres a day for bathing in the Madhuban and Gyan Sarovarcampuses.
- Hybrid wind-solar-diesel system with battery bank that ensures 24-hour power supply to the telephone and audiovisual systems in Gyan Sarovar and Shantivan.
- A Meditation Dome and a Solar House in Gyan Sarovar feature a newly-developed 'dome-and-vault design/construction technique' using stabilized mud bricks. These buildings are entirely reliant on wind and solar energy for their electricity supply while the street lighting between them is also solar-powered. They have an internal earth tunnel ventilation system which maintains a relatively stable year-round temperature.
- A unique waste treatment plant capable of treating 2,00,000 liters of waste water so that nearly 80% of it is available for re-use in gardens and orchards.
- Equipping the 1,000-year old village of Salgaon, which borders the Gyan Sarovar campus, with solar street lighting, solar lanterns and solar cooking boxes; similar assistance to other neighbouring villages is planned or is already being provided.
- With World Bank funding, equipping 60 BK centres in India with a 5KW solar PV system and providing 300 centres with a 1 KW system.

Promoting renewable energy technology in the public at affordable prices by providing information and selling solar lanterns, home lighting systems and solar cooking boxes.

4.6 BRAHMA KUMARIS WORLDWIDE

4.6.1 BRAHMA KUMARIS AT THE UNITED NATIONS: -

Fig. No. 4: Logo of United Nations

Brahma kumaris is an international non-governmental organization (NGO) of the United Nations accredited with general consultative status with Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) .The Brahma Kumaris have been in consultative status with ECOSOC since 1983, from 1983-1987 they held a Roster Status and in 1998, they were granted a General Consultative status. The Brahma Kumaris core expertise at the United Nations is: "The cultivation of pure awareness and reaffirming faith in the dignity and worth of the human person. The "spiritual technology": awareness, attitude, vision, action, and the world.

4.6.2 What is Brahma kumaris relationship with United Nations?

It also has

- Associate status with the department of Public Instruction(DPI)
- Consultative Status with United Nations Children's Emergency Fund(UNICEF)

It also is

- An Observer status to the United Nations Environmental Assembly of UNEP
- An observer organization to UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)
- A Flagship Member of education For Rural People (ERP), Food And Agricultural Organization(FAO)

In promoting the purpose and principles of the United Nations, the spiritual trajectory of awareness, attitude, vision and action is used by Brahma Kumaris in the areas of the Millennium Development Goals, Climate Change, Food Crisis, Gender Equality, Global Public Health, Humanitarian Emergencies, Human Rights, Women, Children, Youth, International Decades and Days.

4.6.3 How old is Brahma kumaris relationship with United Nations?

Brahma Kumaris became affiliated to

- DPI in 1980
- To ECOSOC in 1983
- To UNICEF in 1987
- To UNFCCC in 2009
- To UNEP in 2014

4.6.4 What are aims & purposes of Brahma kumaris & its course of action?

- To clarify spiritual and moral perspectives on issues of personal, community and global concerns.
- To facilitate a greater awareness of corresponding rights and responsibilities.
- To foster sustainable human centered development.
- The support of economic , social, environmental and human well being and the promotion of gender equality.

4.6.5 How does Brahma Kumaris contribute to work of United Nation?

- In promoting the purpose and principles of the United Nations Charter, the trajectory of awareness, attitude, vision, and action is used in the areas of the Millennium Development Goals, Climate Change, Food Crisis, Gender Equality, Global Public Health, Humanitarian Emergencies, Human Rights, Women, Children, Youth, International Decades, Days.
- Attending UN conferences, preparatory committee meetings, commissions: presenting oral and written statements; hosting parallel events; working with NGO committees and caucuses.

4.6.6 What UN conferences has Brahma Kumaris participated in over years?

1980s- The Brahma Kumaris initiated various outreach projects, including The Million Minutes Of Peace Appeal and Global Cooperation For A Better World.

1990s- The Brahma Kumaris participated in most UN World Conferences which included Conferences and summits on ageing, sustainable development, The Earth Summit, Information Society, Women, Civil Society, decent Work, Human Rights, Social Development, Conference against Racism, racial Discrimination, Xenophobia and related Intolerance, Human Settlements, Religious and Spiritual Leaders, Health and Youth.

2000-The Brahma Kumaris focused on the Millennium Development Goals. From 2009- The Brahma Kumaris focused on the Environment and participated in Conferences on :

✓ **Climate Change**

- United Nations Framework Conference on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Conference of Parties (COP)
- Where the Brahma Kumaris attended sessions, wrote statements, held side events, exhibitions, press conferences as well as participated in and held parallel events in the local communities, universities, and business arenas.
- COP 15 December 2009, Copenhagen, Denmark
- COP 16 November/ December 2010 Cancun, Mexico
- COP 17, November/December 2011 Durban, South Africa
- COP18, November/December 2012, Doha, Qatar.
- COP 19, November 2013, Warsaw, Poland.
- COP 20, December 2014, Lima, Peru
- COP 21, December 2015, Paris, France
- Bonn Climate Change Conference annually since 2010
- Climate Change Summit, September 2014, UN HQ, New York. And parallel to that- the Interfaith Climate Change Summit. The Brahma Kumaris were co-signatories of the Interfaith Statement.

✓ **COY Conference of Youth**

- COY is the gathering of young people occurring every year before COP. The organization of the COY is coordinate by several youth associations with strong environmental engagement including YOUNGO, which is the youth constituency of UNFCCC. Our BKUN Youth representative has played a significant role in the organization of the conference for past two years and has attended COY 7, 8, 9,10, & 11 (2010-2015).

✓ **Sustainable Development**

- UN Conference on Sustainable Development (RI0+20)

- Attended regional preparations for Latin America and the Caribbean, Asia Pacific Region, Africa Region and partners and Europe
- Rio+20 UN Conference on Sustainable Development, 20-22 June 2012, Rio, Brazil written statement, parallel events, exhibits.
 - Rio+20 People's Summit, 15-23 June 2012, Rio, Brazil - workshops, exhibitions.
- ✓ **Biodiversity**
Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity
 - COP 11, October 2012, Hyderabad, India
 - COP12, October 2014, Pyeongchang, South Korea

4.6.7 To what specific projects have Brahma Kumaris contributed to bring UN Programmes to masses worldwide?

The Brahma Kumaris have initiated and implemented global projects to help raise awareness on the significance of the UN programmes of action on people's lives and realities:

- The Million Minutes of Peace Appeal, held in observance of the International Year of Peace, in 1986. Brahma Kumaris in seven countries received Peace Messenger Awards for their significant contribution.
- Global Co-operation for a Better World, a peace messenger initiative, was a follow-up to the work done during 1986 and reached out to people in 129 countries, asking them for their vision of a better world. This was compiled into a book entitled, Visions of a Better World. (Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University, 1993).
- Sharing Our Values for a Better World a programme to honor the UN 50th Anniversary, in which people were asked to identify values that gave meaning to the lives of people in their country. A book entitled Living Values: A Guidebook was dedicated to the UN 50 (BKIS, 1995).
- The Living Values: A Guidebook and the Convention on the Rights of the Child were the context used as the core competencies of the Living Values Educational Initiative developed by the Brahma Kumaris and UNICEF.

International Decade for a Culture of Peace and Non-Violence. The University signed a partnership agreement with UNESCO and was designated as a 'Messenger for Manifesto 2000'. It actively promoted Manifesto 2000, collecting over 37 million signed pledges by individuals to implement it. The University also

organized 'flagship' and other events in 51 countries and held numerous seminars and workshops regarding and promoting the principles and values underlying a culture of peace..

4.6.8 What are some of on-going activities in support of UN Programmes?

Annual observance of UN-dedicated days such as:

- International Women's Day (8 March)
- International Day of Happiness (20 March)
- World Health Day (7 April)
- World Environment Day (5 June)
- International Day of Peace, (21 Sept)
- International Youth Day (12 Aug)
- International Day of Older Persons (1 Oct)
- International Day of Non-violence (2 Oct)
- United Nations Day (24 Oct)
- International Day of Tolerance. (16 November)
- International Day of Remembrance dedicated to Road Traffic Victims (3rd Sunday of November).
- Human Rights Day (10 December)

4.6.8.1 UN Weeks such as:

- World Interfaith Harmony week (1-7 February)
- UN Global Road Safety Week (23-29 April).

UN Decades such as:

- International Decade for Culture of Peace & Non-violence for Children of World (2001-2010).
- United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All (2014-2024)
- United Nations Decade of Action on Road Safety (2011-2020)
- United Nations Decade on Biodiversity (2011-2020)

4.6.8.2 Other Activities include:

- Promoting gender equality and the empowerment of young women through the Commission on the Status of Women.
- A world-wide initiative on the Spiritual Dimension of Decent Work, in support of the International Labour Organization's Decent Work Agenda.
- Research and development of renewable energy to ensure environmental sustainability.
- Brahma Kumaris Environment Initiative awakening greater environmental awareness within our own organisation, as well as collaborating and learning from others through dialogue, partnerships, UN conferences and local initiatives.

- Awareness Cum Training Center on Concentrating Solar Technologies by World Renewal Spiritual Trust (WRST) in Abu Road Rajasthan is an initiative under the UNDP-GEF assisted and Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India Project on Concentrated Solar Heat. <http://iwww.cshindia.in>, <http://www.india.one.net/CS TCenter.html>
- Reduction of child mortality and improvement of maternal health through the Global Hospital and Research Centre.
- Values in Healthcare: A Spiritual Approach, a personal and team development programme for healthcare practitioners, in partnership with the Janaki Foundation for Global Health Care.
- The Call-of-the-Time Dialogue Series: is convened annually in Oxford, UK, bringing together seasoned and young leaders representing diverse issues and different disciplines. The common thread being an understanding of the double helix of the spiritual and secular.
- The Future of Power - a series of exclusive conversations exploring the forthcoming 'shifts in power' and their impact on leadership in the 21st Century.

4.6.9 Brahma Kumaris support United Nations' activities in many ways:

- Supporting the UN Millennium Development Goals through a wide range of programmes promoting education, empowerment of women, holistic health and well being, and environmental sustainability.
- Sharing their expertise in human values to bring an ethical and spiritual approach to global issues.
- Highlighting the purpose and principles of the UN by initiating activities of social and humanitarian nature on a global scale.
- Providing platforms for dialogue through its international network of centres for people to voice their opinions on critical matters and present them at UN forums.

Presenting statements and position papers in UN world summits, such as on the Information Society in Geneva, on Sustainable Development in South Africa, at Habitat II in Istanbul, on Social Development in Geneva, on Human Rights and Values at UN's 50th anniversary, on Youth at Lisbon, on Women at Beijing, on Environment at Rio de Janeiro and others..

4.6.10 Focus for 2015-2030:

The new Development Agenda of the United Nations with its emphasis on universality and transformation-The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Adopted in September of 2015 by the UN General Assembly they signal a collective journey to end poverty, transform lives and protect the planet.

4.7 INTERNATIONAL PROJECTS OF BRAHMA KUMARIS

4.7.1 Just-a-Minute -2006

For a minute on September 17 around 4.25 BST, the Wembley Arena in London, full of 12,000 people, with many millions worldwide, went silent. J-a-m is a dynamic new campaign to create personal peace in an ever-increasing global climate of chaos and change by introducing the idea of regular breaks when Individuals can re-connect with their inner core self, their strengths and their values.

- It was the largest event dedicated to the United Nations International Day of Peace since its inception in 1981.
- The event aimed at creating the power of a peaceful and still mind, starting with just one minute at a time.
- Hundreds of events were organised simultaneously in Johannesburg, Rio, Moscow, Rome, Sydney, Athens, Mauritius, Madrid and Israel.

Millions of people in 118 countries participated in the event via satellite and webcast for a minute of silence.

4.7.2 Culture of Peace Manifesto-2000

In 2000, the UN International Year for the Culture of Peace, the Brahma Kumaris were designated 'Messenger for Manifesto 2000'. During the year 2000, through its network of 4,000 centres in over 20 countries, BKWSU held special activities, seminars and workshops to promote awareness of Manifesto 2000 and encouraged people to put its principles into practice. It also collected over 25,000,000 signatures in support of the Manifesto.

4.7.3 Sharing our Values for Better World -1994

This project was launched in 1994 with a view to promoting awareness about spiritual values and developing them at the individual and collective levels.

4.7.4 Global Co-operation for Better World 1988

This project was launched at the Houses of Parliament in London and dedicated to the UN as the first International Peace Messenger Initiative. It gathered hopes and visions for a better world from thousands of people in 129 countries, which were later developed into the Global Vision Statement and integrated into the publication, Visions of a Better World.

4.7.5 Million Minutes of Peace appeal -1986

During the United Nation's International Year of Peace the Brahma Kumaris launched this project to emphasise that peace begins with the self. Millions of people in 88 countries donated over one billion minutes of peace through prayer, meditation and positive thoughts. The Brahma Kumaris received seven Peace Messenger Awards from the UN for this project.

4.8 GLOBAL INITIATIVES BY BRAHMA KUMARIS

4.8.1 Living Values: Educational Programmed (LVEP)

Living Values: A Guidebook was published on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the UN. It helped 20 educators to develop a programme for value education. They produced the LVEP in consultation with UNICEF, UNESCO and the Brahma Kumaris.

LVEP offers a wide variety of experiential values activities and practical methodologies to educators, facilitators, parents and caregivers that enable children and young adults to explore and develop twelve universal values. It also offers special materials for street children, children affected by war and children affected by earthquakes. It has been used in 74 countries in over 7,000 places, bringing about positive change in teachers and students both inside and outside the classroom

4.8.2 Call of Time

The Call of the Time dialogues bring together leaders from all continents to explore the deepest inner values and universal truths and to integrate them in their spheres of activity. It allows participants to engage in extended periods of silence and meditation. Since 1998 approximately 1,000 people have taken part in these dialogues.

4.8.3 Self-Managing Leadership (SML)

A popular self-development programme, SML is designed for those facing the challenges of change. Self-management practices include integrating priorities, clarifying purpose and values, learning to focus mental energy, and developing authentic communication skills. A host of MNCs, govt. agencies and public enterprises have benefited from the SML programme. A few of them are Godrej Boyce, Indian Oil, Reliance, Parle, Nagarjuna Fertilizers, Cibatul in India and Motorola, Ford, Ericsson, Dell, Coca Cola, Glaxo, Microsoft, Sony, IBM, Volvo,

McDonalds, ILO, British Airways, government ministries, the police, armed forces, UN agencies and NGOs abroad.

4.8.4 Values in Healthcare

Values in Healthcare - A Spiritual Approach is a personal and team development programme for healthcare practitioners. It provides unique support to professionals and patients by enhancing interactive skills. Increased insight and compassion better equip a physician to convey hope to the patient, with powerful therapeutic results. It has been developed by The Janki Foundation, a UK-based charity that researches and promotes a values-based model of modern health care. It also supports the clinical and research activities of the Global Hospital and Research Centre in Mt Abu, India.

4.8.5 Four Faces of Women

Following participation in the UN's Fourth World Conference on Women held in Beijing in 1995, a series of international meetings, retreats and dialogues were held by BKs in 1996 across the world under the Four Faces of Woman banner. The aim of Four Faces retreats and programmes is to help women grow spiritually - by rediscovering their true worth, value and potential. Numerous programmes have been held around the world with the focus on uncovering the face of the Shakti, the source of divine power.

4.8.6 International Youth Forum - IYF: -

Through the IYF the BK youth are offered methods and opportunities for personal empowerment, development of social skills and creative talents, choosing leadership roles and serving humanity. Annual IYF retreats at Mount Abu provide a natural learning environment for BK youth (aged 16-25) from different parts of the world.

4.8.7 Interfaith Activities: -

For over thirty years, the Brahma Kumaris have been helping to bring people of different faiths together by fostering acceptance and respect to help create a culture of peace and non-violence. It has facilitated interfaith dialogues to help appreciate the essence and diversity of different faiths. In many countries, BK representatives serve on committees of local interfaith organizations, host local activities, and play an active part on religious education advisory committees such as in Australia, New Zealand, USA and Uruguay.

4.8.8 Images & Voices of Hope: -

Images and Voices of Hope is a global transformational dialogue intended to connect and expand the community of journalists, artists, and media professionals who understand their work in the media as a way to enhance awareness of the strengths and assets that give societies hope for the future. The IVOH dialogues help media persons to promote the role of the media as an agent of human welfare

4.8.9 Science & Consciousness: -

Following four international symposia on Science and Consciousness in Greece and Mexico in the 1990s, the Brahma Kumaris initiated a project entitled SPARC-Spiritual Applications and Research Centre-to explore the interplay of mind and matter.

4.8.10 Arts & Spirituality: -

A number of seminars and conferences have been organised with the focus on Spirituality In Arts. In the 1990s, international conferences in Sardinia, Italy brought together artists from over 50 countries to explore the role of meditation and spiritual values in creative expressions.

4.9 BRAHMA KUMARIS GLOBAL RETREAT CENTRES

Brahma Kumaris retreat centres organise courses, training, seminars and meditation retreats for different groups on weekends and holidays. Besides being equipped with modern facilities for comfortable stay they offer a peaceful and supportive atmosphere where people can experience spiritual values at the deepest level. Courses on Raja yoga meditation, Stress-Free Living, Positive Thinking, Self Empowerment etc. are held round the year at:

1. Global Retreat Centre- Nuneham Park, Oxford, England
2. Peace Village Retreat Centre- Haines Falls, New York, USA
3. Blue Mountain Retreat Centre- Leura, New South Wales, Australia
4. Baxter Retreat Centre- Melbourne, Victoria, Australia
5. Wilton Retreat Centre-Wilton, New South Wales, Australia
6. Casa sangam Retreat Centre, Gubbio, Italy
7. Villa Serra Serena, Serra Negra, Brazil
8. Centre for Spiritual Learning, Villa Elisa, Argentina
9. Centre for Spiritual Learning, Tagaytay, Philippines

Fig. No. 5–Worldwide Brahma Kumaris Branches

4.10 FOUNDER OF BRAHMA KUMARIS

4.10.1 INCORPOREAL FOUNDING FATHER OF BRAHMA KUMARIS

The Universal Light

Fig. No. 6: Universal light

4.10.2 CORPOREAL FOUNDING FATHER & MOTHER

Prajapita Brahma and Mateshwari Jagadamba

Dada Lekhraj Kripalani was a well-to-do diamond jeweller in Sindh. A series of divine visions and spiritual revelations by the Supreme Soul transformed his life and he became a spiritual leader and founding father of Brahma Kumaris in 1936 at the age of 60.

Mateshwari Jagadamba Saraswati was the first administrative leader who oversaw the physical and spiritual care of all the members of the spiritual family. She was only 17 years of age when she joined the organization but soon became the divine Mother because of her exemplary virtues and skills

Brahma Baba's rock-hard faith, steadfast vision and an innate ability to cope with challenges and change made him a natural leader who steered the fledgling institution through difficult times. He was a visionary who conceptualised and set the pace for worldwide service in his lifetime, which resulted in a groundswell of spiritual activities abroad in the 1980s and 1990s.

Mateshwari Jagadamba explored, practiced and exemplified each spiritual principle and nurtured the original group of spiritual students with her amazing stock of human and spiritual values. She epitomized the balance of feminine and masculine qualities tolerance, sacrifice, kindness, courage, determination and fearlessness-that gave direction to the young women and men who are now spearheading the global movement.

Brahma Baba foresaw women emerging as Shakti and leading spiritual and social development with their innate qualities. Seventy years on, Brahma Baba's vision and practical wisdom have stood the test of time. The Brahma Kumaris have emerged as global leaders in spiritual education. Mateshwari passed on in 1964 and Brahma Baba left this corporeal world in 1969. Their spiritual legacy is carried on by the Dadis-senior sisters and an ever growing global spiritual family

4.11 ADMINISTRATIVE HEADS:

Brahma Kumaris is the world's only organization where the women are leading from the front and making the dream come true of "One God One World Family."

Fig. No. 7: Corporeal Founding father with Administrative heads of BKs from 1936 till date

Mateshwari was the first administrative head who became an instrument for physical and spiritual cares of all the members of the BK spiritual family. She was only 17 years of age when she joined the organisation but soon became the divine mother because of her exemplary virtues and skills. Mateshwari passed on in 24th June 1964 and Brahma Baba left the corporeal founding father left the corporeal world in 18th January 1969. Their spiritual legacy is carried on by the Dadis, senior sisters of an ever growing global spiritual family.

In 2007, Dadi Prakashmani, the Chief Administrative Head of the Brahma Kumaris passed away at the age of 85. A gifted and natural leader, she was based in Mount Abu and looked after the entire organization, but with a focus on India. Dadi Janki, the designated Additional Administrative Head and based in London while Dadi Prakashmani was alive, succeeded Dadi Prakashmani as the Chief Administrative Head. Dadi Janki is now based in Mount Abu, India although she travels extensively and regularly. Dadi Gulzar is the Additional Administrative Head, and lives in Mount Abu. She divides her time between visiting Centres in India and conducting programs overseas. Since the recent change of leadership, Dadi Ratan Mohini based in Mount Abu has become the Joint Administrative Head again ensuring three original members continue to administer the Brahma

Kumaris worldwide. As the Dadis are growing older, the next generation of sisters is now taking a more active leadership role.

4.11.1 Late Rajyogini Dadi Prakashmani, Former Chief of Brahma Kumaris

The Jewel of Light - that is what her name signifies. So does her life. A beacon of spiritual enlightenment, Dadi Prakashmani was appointed Chief Administrative Head of the Brahma Kumaris in 1969. Her boundless enthusiasm, generosity and unlimited vision have helped guide the organization in its tremendous global growth. For her, leading this global institution is like being a guardian to a global family. She has served on a number of international committees, hosted a series of global conferences and received various honours and medals - the UN Peace Medal and an honorary doctorate to name a few. She attained an Angelic life on 25th August, 2007 and passed her responsibility to Rajyogini Dadi Jankiji, present Chief of Brahma Kumaris and to Rajyogini Dadi Hridaya Mohini ji, Addi. Chief of Brahma Kumaris.

4.11.2 PRESENT ADMINISTRATIVE HEADS:

4.11.2.1 Rajyogini Dadi Janki, Chief of Brahma Kumaris

Fig. No. 8: Dadi Janaki-Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris

A mine of wisdom and compassion, Dadi Janki seems to live beyond the time-space barrier as she tirelessly travels from one country to the other, offering insights and inspiration to millions of people. After establishing numerous centres throughout

India, in 1974 she established the first BK centre outside India, in London. Today, she co-ordinates the overseas BK centres in 140 countries. She has presided over numerous international conferences and engaged with leaders from various fields. She is one of the ten wisdom keepers of the world nominated by the World Parliament of Religions, and also the President of Janki Foundation for health care. A centenarian , living legend and Chief of Brahma Kumaris, **B.K.Rajayogini Dadi Janki** is like a light- house of wisdom to all, constantly caring, sharing and inspiring, to achieve noble objectives in life.

4.11.2.2 **Rajyogini Dadi Hirdaya Mohini, Addl. Chief of Brahma Ku maris**

Fig. No. 9: Dadi Hirdaya Mohini- Additional Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris

Also lovingly known as Dadi Gulzar, she joined Brahma Kumaris at the tender age of eight. Her spiritual charm derives from innocence, clarity of wisdom and her firm conviction in spiritual truths. She offers simple practical tips to guide spiritual seekers all over the world and spreads lightness and love with her presence and words. From an early age she had divine visions of a future world that is characterized by peace, prosperity and harmony. She has traveled worldwide several times and shared her spiritual wisdom for empowerment of human souls. She is the Director of BK centres in Delhi and chairs the service activities at the headquarters

4.11.2.3 **Rajyogi Dadi Ratan Mohini, Joint Chief of Brahma Kumaris**

Fig. No. 10: Dadi Ratan Mohini- Joint Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris

Dadi Ratan Mohini wears several administrative ‘hats’ in addition to being Joint Chief of the Brahma Kumaris. She is also the Director of the Personnel Department of the Madhuban campuses at the University’s headquarters in Mount Abu, Chairperson of the Youth Wing of the Raja Yoga Education and Research Foundation, Director of Teacher Training Programmes in India, and Zonal Head of Brahma Kumaris services in the state of Rajasthan. Yet this “most beautiful jewel”, as her name connotes, always appears light and tension-free. Known for her dedication to fostering spiritual and moral excellence in young people, Dadi, even in her eighties, is herself lively and young at heart.

4.11.2.4 **Other Office Bearers at Head Quarters:**

Rajyogi BK Nirwair Ji, Secretary General.

Rajyogi BK Brij Mohan Ji Addl Secretary General.

BK Ramesh Shah Ji Addl. Secretary General.

BK Karuna Chief of Multimedia

Rajyogi BK Mruthyunjaya Ji Executive Secretary of Brahma Kumaris

Rajyogini BK Mohini Bhen, In charge of Uttar Pradesh Zone, Chairperson, Rural Wing & Vice Chairperson of Politicians' Service Wing (RERF).

Rajyogini BK Munni Bhen, Excellent Organizer

Rajyogini BK Ishu Dadi –Handles correspondence & resources.

4.12 “75 YEARS OF BRAHMA KUMARIS AT GLANCE”

1936 - Originally known as Om Mandali, the Brahma Kumaris was founded in Sindh (now in Pakistan).

1936-50 - Around 300 people spend 14 years in Karachi as a self-sufficient community engaged in intense spiritual study, meditation and self development.

1950 - The original group shifted from Karachi to India and set up its base at Mount Abu in Rajasthan.

1950s

- First group of Brahma Kumaris set out to serve humanity. Several centres open in Delhi, Kanpur, Lucknow, Amritsar, Ambala, Patiala, Bangalore and Bombay.
- Basic courses and exhibitions on Raja yoga developed. Brahma Kumaris get invited to many conferences and gatherings. Service through exhibitions begins.

1960s

- Mateshwari Jagadamba passes away on June 24, 1964.
- Lot of expansion activities in the headquarters and other cities.
- Definitive policies, guidelines, codes and duties laid down by Brahma Baba to set up a smooth administrative system within the organization.
- Better methods of explaining knowledge, giving courses, lectures and organizing exhibitions evolved.
- After setting the organization on a strong spiritual base and putting its services on the path of expansion and growth, Prajapita Brahma passes away on January 18, 1969

1970s

- A lot of spiritual literature published in several Indian languages.
- In 1971, a BK delegation goes abroad to share Godly Knowledge. BK centres open London, Hong Kong and other cities in Asia, Europe, Africa, North and South America in the late 70s.
- Several international and national conferences organised in Delhi, Abu and other cities, bringing together top leaders.

1980s

- By the early 1980s BK centres established in over 40 countries outside India.
- Affiliated to UN's Department of Public Information in 1981.

- 1983-Universal Peace Hall inaugurated in Mt. Abu.
- Received seven Peace Messenger awards from the UN. Gets consultative status with UNICEF in 1987.
- Two international projects - Million Minutes of Peace and Global Co-operation for a Better World- launched in 1986 and 1988, respectively.
- India's President, Vice President, UN leaders and international leaders visit Mount Abu. All-India campaigns on health awareness and youth welfare organized.

1990s

- 1991- Global Hospital and Research Centre in Mt. Abu commissioned.
- 1993 - First international retreat house, Global Retreat Centre, opens in Oxford, England.
- 1994 - Commemorative postage stamp of Prajapita Brahma released by President Shankar Dayal Sharma at Rashtrapati Bhawan, New Delhi.
- 1995-Gyan Sarovar Academy for a Better World inaugurated.
- 1997 -Shantivan-the largest BK campus- constructed in Abu.
- 1998-Granted general consultative status with the ECOSOC.
- 1999- Largest retreat base, Peace Village, opens near New York.

2000-07

- 2000 - Designated 'Messenger for Manifesto 2000' by the UN to promote Culture of Peace. Collected maximum no. of signatures in the world.
- 2001-0m Shanti Retreat Centre- northern India BK campus-opens near Delhi.
- 2003-05 - Mega programmes addressing half lakh to two lakh people each held in 15 cities across India.
- 2004-Shanti Sarovar, south India BK campus, opens in Hyderabad.
- 2006 - President Abdul Kalam visits Mount Abu. Just-a-minute - a global event for peace held in London. All India Youth Rally launched. World Peace Festival-the largest event dedicated to the 70th anniversary of Brahma Kumaris being held in New Delhi from Oct 27 - Nov 5.

2007-

- (1) 'Swarmina Karnataka' - A Socio-spiritual Service Project launched to serve 28 thousands villages, 174 talukas, 28 districts covering over 5 crore population.
- (2) Akhil Bharatiya Sampurna Gram Vikas Abhiyan' (All-India Holistic Rural Development Campaign) was launched.
- (3) Dadi Prakashmani Spiritual Training Centre was inaugurated.
- (4) International Convention on "Environmental Crisis" from 21st to 24th September, 2007 was organised & Hosted at Gyan Sarovar, Mount Abu.

2008 - 'The Gokul Gaunv' (Village) scheme propagating and ensuring cleanliness, health, bio-fertilizer and agriculture through meditation in Indian villages and remote areas.

- The scheme 'My India, Healthy India' which aims at spreading health services and awakening amongst the rural people of Indian villages.

2009 - The scheme 'Value Education & Spirituality' aiming to bring revolution in the academic world. Under the scheme 'One-Year Post-Graduate Diploma in Value Education & Spirituality' and 'Two-Year Master of Science in Value Education & Spirituality' are already being run in collaboration with the Annamalai University. Some more new courses are also being devised and introduced.

2010-'Clean the Mind and Green the Earth' (2010) a multi-pronged project which aims at purifying the mind and attaining ecological balance by planting lakhs of trees throughout the country and specifically in the state of Rajasthan. The awareness of 'Clean the Mind & Green the Earth' is being created among the school & college students across the world.

2011-2012

2011

The year signifies the completion of 75 years of the organization and the spread of the Godly message to mankind. This great occasion has been launched as Platinum Jubilee at the Om Shanti Retreat Centre, Delhi, where the President of India H.E. Pratibha Patil, Vice President of India, Dr. Mohd. Hamid Ansari, Chief Minister of Delhi Mrs. Shiela Dixit, Former President of India Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Ka lam, Hon'ble Governor of Rajasthan & Punjab Shri Shivraj Patil, Senior Political Leaders like L.K. Adavani participated in the celebrations. The Platinum Jubilee Celebrations are taking place from 4th to 8th November, 2011 at the Brahma Kumaris World Headquarters, Mount Abu. (Rajasthan), along with at many other cities of India and abroad. The theme of the Platinum Jubilee Celebrations is 'One God, One World Family'.

- Similar programmes were held at the Head quarters , Mount abu , other places of India and abroad.
- This year the Education Wing launched two more courses on Value Education & Spirituality one of which is MBA in Self Management & Crisis Management.
- A 24- hour Radio FM channel called "Radio Madhuban" was launched.

4.13 BRAHMA KUMARIS – SCIENTIFIC & INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH ORGANIZATION

4.13.1 Solar Energy for sustainable Future: -

Today the world energy supply is dependent on the availability of low cost, conventional energy sources through gas, oil and coal. Global warming, environmental degradation and increased fuel prices negatively affect the whole of humanity. The general political consensus is that energy generation desperately needs to be transformed

In order to give a strong impulse towards the development of clean technology and a sustainable society, the World Renewal Spiritual Trust (WRST), a registered public charitable trust has established a Department of Renewable Energy in 1992. It became obvious to combine spirituality and values with research and development of renewable technology. **They believe that the fusion of both will drive them towards a better future.** For this purpose, the trust works in close liaison with its sister organization ie Brahma Kumaris

WRST has carried out various research and development projects with the Indian and German Governments, and received an official recognition as a **Scientific and Industrial research organization (SIRO) through the Ministry of Science and Technology, GOI in 2011.**

WRST has initiated 6 large solar steam cooking systems cross India which uses surplus steam for various process applications such as laundry, sterilization and water pasteurization. In addition WRST has installed and operates around 100 photo voltaic battery systems (Off grid) with a total capacity of 1.2Mw peak.

4.13.2 “INDIA ONE”- SOLAR THERMAL POWER PLANT PROJECT

4.13.2.1 Introduction/ Executive Summary

Energy is one of the most important requirements for this world to function properly. Its availability and regular supply are of paramount interest. As we are all aware, energy and fuel prices are rising day by day and the negative effects of global warming are more and more visible.

World Renewal Spiritual Trust (WRST), a registered Charitable Trust/ recognized Solar Research Centre and sister organization of the Brahma Kumaris, is setting up **“India One”** a 1.0 Mw el. Solar thermal power plant in order to demonstrate and multiply this innovative technology for India. “India One” will supply power and hot water for the headquarters of Brahma Kumaris (25 000 people) in Abu Road, Rajasthan, India.

“India One” is based on a Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) technology with a unique concept of 770 nos in-house developed 60 SQM flexible paraboloid dishes which offer a static focus with fully automatic dual axis tracking mechanism.

Due to the unique feature of a static focus, there is an advantage of integrating energy storage at the focus. High intensity solar radiation can be injected into a cavity receiver that acts as thermal energy storage; energy can be stored for 16 off-sunny hours, thus enabling 24 hour operation. Project delivers an indigenous technology suitable for India and provides standardized manufacturing process, enabling replication of the technology

For this project, WRST has teamed up with Fraunhofer Institute (ISE), enjoys the support of Wolfgang Scheffler and has secured part funding from the Indian and German Government. WRST is in close liaison with various solar R&D institutions and manufacturers and has started fabrication and erection by beginning of 2011.

“India One” is partly financed by the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India and Ministry of Environment (BMU) Government of Germany via the GIZ.

“The thermal solar power plant (solar only) will be the first of its kind in dish technology in direct steam generation mode, with full thermal storage for 16 hrs continuous operations for base load.”

4.13.2.2 PROJECT DETAILS

After examination of couple sun arranged movements, sun filled illustrative dish improvement has been discovered most reasonable for their motivations.

TECHNOLOGY ADOPTED

INDIA ONE solar thermal power plant is based on the three key technologies

1)Parabolic reflectors

The concentrated solar rays from 60m² dishes are focussed towards the in – house developed, highly efficient cavity receivers, whichj are positioned in front of each dish.The Innovative receiver is integrated into a heavy iron casting and thus provides excellent thermal storage. The heat exchanger coil is fully embedded into the thermal storage medium and allows an improved heat transfer. Excellent insulation and an automated shutter avoid substantial energy loses at night or in cloudy condition

2)Thermal storage

The thermal storage operates between 250 C to 450 C and can be discharged on demand. By means of the total thermal mass, the capacity will be sufficient to run the TURBINE round the clock.

3)Rankine Cycle

The plant is designed as a captive power plant (off grid) in cogeneration to provide electricity and heat for the WRST &Brahma Kumaris , Shantivan complex, This will substantially increase the overall efficiency.

4.13.2.3 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

- It is intended to set up the innovative solar thermal power plant based on the newly developed 60m² parabolic dish with 16 hrs steel core cavity receiver and storage for continuous operation with the following main technical specifications.
- Number of dishes : 770 nos. of 60m² paraboloid reflectors
- Electrical output : 1.0 Mw el. (net. 22000 kwh/24hrs)
- Thermal output : 140 Mwh th. (24hrs)
- Solar field : 25 Acres near to campus (1.3 km)
- Total mirror area : 45.000 m²
- Turbine : 1,0 Mw el. at 255C and 41 bar (Siemens)

4.13.2.4 Salient Features OF India One

- 770 nos of static cast iron cavity receivers with thermal storage for 24 hrs continuous operation
- Direct super heated (DSG) steam generation on demand, with no additional heat transfer fluids required
- Two stage twin turbine and generator from Siemens
- Anticipated power generation – 24 MWH / day
- Cogeneration - 1 million ltrs/day hot water at 60 deg.C
- Cultivation of vegetables and fruits under solar Reflectors

4.13.2.5 Budget

The budget for the project is 75 Crores Indian Rupees (~12 Mio. Euro) excluding cost of land. The World Renewal Spiritual Trust has received partly funding from the Indian Ministry of New and Renewable Energy Sources (MNRE) and the German Ministry for Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU).

4.13.2.6 Current Work Status

450 no's of reflectors were erected. Solar grade mirror were curved for 650 no's of reflectors. 10 receivers in series were tested with variable flow for thermal storage, DSG and thermal losses. Turbine and generator were installed and aligned by an engineer from Siemens. Information dissemination centre for the visitors was established and is operational on the site.

4.13.2.7 Partners, Good Wishers & Team

1) **Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) New Delhi**, Government of India provides the funds under its research and development scheme.

2) **German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)** within the bilateral initiative “Com Solar” provides part of the funds under its development scheme.

3) **GIZ Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit** – GIZ is an implementing agency of the German Government, coordinating support to “India One” project for Government.

4) **Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE**, Freiburg, Germany provides consultancy in the scope of plant simulation and then evaluation of the performance.

5) **“India Care” Trust Berlin, Germany**, standing partner of WRST in renewable projects

6) **Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University** parent organization of the WRST which teaches meditation, values and ethics, with headquarters in Mount Abu who are the user of the power and heat generated.

4.13.2.8 **Information Dissemination** “India One” project is daily visited by many guests who are willing to learn about the solar energy and the new technology. Among the visitors there engineering colleges, potential users, both institutional and individual, c working with renewable e various VIPs, from India as abroad

4.14 OTHER SCIENTIFIC & INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH PROJECTS

Sl. No.	Project	Collaborative organizations with SpARC
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1.	Effect of Raj Yoga Meditation on Physiological, Psychological & Affective Functions	<p>Three Labs of Defense Research & Development Organization (DRDO), Ministry of Defense, New Delhi:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIPAS (Defense Institute of Physiology & Allied Sciences) • DIPR (Defense Institute of Psychological Research) • INMAS (Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences)
2.	Neural Correlates of Well-Being in Long Term Raja Yoga Practitioners.	NIMHANS (National Institute of Mental Health & Neuro Sciences), Bangalore.
3.	Effect of Raj Yoga Meditation for Holistic Healing	ISIC (Indian Spinal Injuries Centre), New Delhi).
4.	Effect of Raj Yoga Meditation: Resting State simultaneous EEG-fMRI Study	Cognitive Neuroscience Center, Dept. of Neuroimaging & Interventional Radiology, NIMHANS , Bangalore.
5.	Creation of Universe in pursuit of Indian Philosophy & Science	Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), New Delhi.
6.	A study on Peace in Relation to Spirituality & creativity among Secondary School Teachers in Sikkim	Viswa Bharati University , Shantiniketan (for Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Education).
7.	Mapping of Default Mode Network in Long-Term Meditators using Simultaneous EEG-MRI	Cognitive Neuroscience Center, Dept. of Neuroimaging & Interventional Radiology, NIMHANS , Bangalore.

8.	Metaphysical & Psycho-physiological assessment of Raj Yoga Mediators	SpARC (Psycho-Physiological Research Lab) & INMAS , New Delhi.
9.	Psycho-Physiological evaluation in long term Raj Yoga Mediators & Study of their cognitive abilities	SpARC (Psycho-Physiological Research Lab) & INMAS , New Delhi
10.	Integrating Spiritual aspects as part of pre & post Disaster Management curriculum & training	NDMA (National Disaster Management Authority), New Delhi. NDMI (National Disaster Management Institute), New Delhi.
11.	HOLISTIC HEALING OF HUMAN SUFFERING THROUGH MANSA SEVA CANCER PATIENTS	Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology (KMIO), Bangalore.
12.	Attention profiling of Long term Rajayoga meditators	INMAS (Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences), DRDO, Delhi.
13.	Spiritual Empowerment of Young Girls at NIRMAL CHHAYA Rehabilitation Centre	Government of Delhi.
14.	Meditation effect on Cognitive and psychological factors in Breast Cancer Patient	All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS). New Delhi.
15.	Rajayoga Meditation Intervention in students with ADHD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * Central Institute of Education (CIE) • * Delhi University (DU) • * Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR)

Tab. No. 1: Summary of Scientific Research Studies by SpARC Wing of RERF in Collaboration with Research Organizations / Institutions as on 15.07.14

4.15 Spirituality

Spirituality is not the same as religion. There can be religion without spirituality, and spirituality can bring a sense of sacredness that is common to many religions and yet need not be expressed-through any of them. But to many people the word 'religion' has become merely a label, referring to a ritual or fundamentalism with little or no spirituality. Yet the root meaning of religion is 'to join together or to re-connect' suggesting a re-uniting of the self with its Source. And that is very spiritual; in fact it is the very purpose of spirituality. Three most important concepts that form the basis of spiritual understanding are:

- ✓ The understanding of myself and how I view myself in relation to the world.
- ✓ The understanding of the Source or Supreme and my relationship with Him.
- ✓ The understanding of the law of cause and effect or 'Karma'.

Avyakt Murli of 30-1-85 expresses the beauty of Satyug is about how the five elements will serve us there:

Fig. No. 11: view of Golden age(heaven) & its lifestyle

- In Satyug, the five elements become the instrument to provide happiness for the duties.
- The air will move like a natural fan for you and will also become a method for your entertainment.

- The branches and the twinges will create a variety of sounds and it will be life automatic music playing for your entertainment.
- The sky will become the Royal path way for you.
- The water will work like a perfume spray, because of the fragrant herbs and the plants with it. Even the water there will be full of energy, full of power.
- Everyone will be experiencing the happiness of that time. The earth will give such elevated fruit that whatever kind of taste you are looking for a fruit of the particular taste will be in front of you.
- There will be great natural beauty. There will be some in the form of birds and flowers.

‘Spiritual people develop inner power, which can be used not in a miraculous way but just to give good wishes. One of the magnificent examples of "living spirituality and peace" is the ‘generous hearted soul is senior Rajyogi Brahma Kumar Nirwair, Secretary General of Brahma Kumaris and author of books, entitled Spiritual Treasures, Insights of a Rajyogi, Living Spirituality and Peace. He has presented the power of spirituality with the deeper insight of his practical life experience:

To remain turned to the source and fill the self with love, power and divinity. These virtues are then transmitted automatically from us in the form of vibrations. Many times our vibrations attract unknown people who say, " You don't have to say anything, I simply enjoy being with you". When we are linked with Baba (God) on a subtle level, there is an automatic flow of Baba's qualities to us, which are reflected onto others.

The basis of forming this spirit is to

- ✓ *First understand that everyone belongs to God.*
- ✓ *Secondly, everyone has a unique role to play.*
- ✓ *Thirdly, each soul has specialties.*
- ✓ *Fourthly, everyone is a great server, playing a hero role in transforming the world. With these specialties in mind, and automatic feeling of respect in our heart develops for one other.*

Mahatma Gandhi also believed that paradise is here on this earth not above in the sky. This is similar to the Brahma Kumaris' spiritual philosophy that suggests when people free themselves from vices and ego, they will be living a life of virtues and this earth will be a paradise of deities. Mahatma Gandhi remarked:

"If there is a Paradise on earth, It is here, It is here, It is here". There will be neither paupers nor beggars, nor high nor low, neither millionaire employer nor half starved employee, nor intoxicating drinks or drugs. There will be the same respect for women as vouchsafed to men, and the chastity and purity of men and women will be guarded. Where there will be no untouchability and where there will be equal respect for all faiths."

The idea of a "peaceful and perfect world" is respected in many different civilization of the world. But this idea was not dream, it was reality. It existed and there will be paradise on this earth again. It will be possible only when human souls are free from vices and practice values in their life. There is no need to labour to establish a harmonious and peaceful society, nation and world. It will be here not above in the sky. When souls are peaceful, the world will be peaceful. This is the harmonious connection between spirituality, values and peaceful world.

All spiritual life is in its principle a growth into divine living. It is difficult to fix the frontier where the mental ceases and the divine life begins, for the two projects into each other and there is a long space of their intermingled existence. A great part of this inters pace, When the spiritual urge does not truth away from earth or world altogether, can be seen as the process of a higher life in the making.

As the mind and life become illuminated with the light of the Spirit, they put on or reflect something of the divinity, the secret greater reality and this must increase until the inter space has been crossed and the whole existence is unified in the full light and power of the spiritual principle.

Spirituality is an art which beautifully harmonizes values with the practice of meditation. Spirituality is science with wonderful results, yet it is not fully understood by science. It is the secret of living from the inside out and about knows ourselves again internally, and recovering an ability to draw on the energy of our inner truth "What one has to do is to be able to turn inwards. When one turns within, one is able to accumulate the spiritual energy with which to live in this world free of fear.

Human are the crown of the entire earthly creation and spirituality is the essence. The Brahma Kumaris' literature is also recognized as "the renaissance of spirituality and

universal human values in various different ways and the researcher is modestly presenting that literature with a focus on central theme of "spirituality and values". It is not only a record of written information but also the methodology has been translated into practical actions by adopting different new dimensions of implementation of spirituality and values. As introduced in the previous chapter, the researcher has defined the power that comes with the practice of meditation for a better world and that spirituality or spiritual knowledge is the basis of meditation practice. In presenting the synthesis of Yoga in the previous chapter, the researcher has mentioned the subject of knowing the Soul as the basis of spiritual understanding, the understanding of God or the Supreme, which is common in both spirituality and meditation.

Spirituality and values is the centre of the moral philosophy of human culture. Education in values and spirituality enriches awareness in our personality. The new dimensions of implementation of universal human values through spirituality will sow the seeds for a new beginning of peace, harmony and love. In an ideal society, values are respected and practiced by people. The inner light of spirituality destroys evil. The practices described in the literature of the Brahma Kumaris well-built spirituality to be the only tool for transforming weaknesses into strengths, failures into successes, and vices into values. In ancient times, the primary goal of literature was to promote spirituality and human values in life. Spirituality and values present the aspirations of religious and philosophies that aim to guide people from the darkness of vices to the lightness of virtues. Our ancient Vedic system of education was based on higher ideas of spirituality and the divine atmosphere that chanted vibration of aspiration:

"Lead me from falsehood to Truth.

Lead me from darkness to Light

Lead me from death to immortality"

We are observing a gulf of difference between the past and the present system of education. The Brahma Kumaris has been playing a strong leading role in the restoration of spirituality and human values. Through new dimensions of implementation of universal human values through spirituality, the Brahma Kumaris are filling the missing link of education. According to Swami Vivekananda the education of literature is the manifestation of the perfection of the spirituality already existing in the human being. The challenge lies in the fact that the level and quality of

spirituality and values in our society is not improving as required by the need of the hour. It is therefore important to explore and gain access to more effective methods for the development of values and spirituality in our life. The Brahma Kumaris believe that when values are cultivated together with spirituality and practice of meditation is integrated into the process, then implementation becomes successful.

The Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university is implementing unique methods for the progress of values through spirituality in the world. How can spirituality and values be developed together? What new dimensions are available? There is no need to separate the efforts used to develop-spirituality and values. Spirituality and values are co-related in such a way that when spirituality is developed values automatically emerge; and when values are developed, they increase spirituality.

This is the matter of fact that today we are facing the challenging crisis in implementation of values and spirituality into almost every field of society. At present, youth are greatly influenced by western culture and media and usually ignore ancient ethics and values. Thus the implementation of spirituality and values is not an easy task in the present scenario. These challenges can be cultural, religious, historical, intellectual, personal, professional and educational disorders.

The dark clouds of international terrorism, religious obscurantism and cultural irredentism are turning ominous and have threatened to rupture our social and culture life. It will indeed need a Herculean effort of global statespersons to save Mother Earth from these scourges of civilization. However, in the midst of these challenges people tend to find fault with religious beliefs and cultural systems which are foolhardy and also fraught with inherent danger. The role of religion in human life can never be undetermined as religious beliefs help human beings in overcoming the trials and tribulations of life- There are so many breaking points in life that one is forced to look for solace, spiritual synoptic relief and more often than not, this is provided by religion. The history of religion is not overburdened with crusades and crucifixion; rather it has its fair share of reform, revolt and renaissance. Jesus preaching of universal love, Buddha's emphasis on compassion, Mohammad's conceptualization of a land of peace and the How of devotion and self—realization in Vedas and Upanishads are universal treasures.

There are separatist tendencies at work today all over the world. The family is splitting up, the institutions are breaking up and even nation—states have a tendency

to break up into various smaller states based on ethnic, linguistic or other differences. 'I here are divisionistic trends almost everywhere and there are organized groups which indulge in violent and secessionist acts for having a separate homeland. Every religion also has become divided into many sects. The tree of religions has grown to its full mature state, with many branches, sub-branches, twigs and leaves. Not a single religion exists today which has not been split up into sects and sub-sects. These fragmentary tendencies are based on dissension hatred, enmity, intolerance, lack of understanding, lack of adjustment a lack of co-operation.

The Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya is not only building toward helping to develop the 'integrated personality' of people but it is also promoting emotional integration between various religious communities and ethnic, racial, linguistic and regional groups. Thus the Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya is not a religious institution, preaching any one cult or sect, it is an institution that imparts education on universal spiritual values and brings understanding and unity to all and peace to the planet Earth.

The Researcher wants to clarify that since this university gives education in values and spirituality; it also celebrates some religious festivals and respects the ideas of other religions. Some people get the impression that it is a religious institution. They miss the silent features of this educational institution, which distinguishes it from religious institutions. The Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university is called a spiritual university because it is not religious sect but it is secular. Since it is not a religion, people of all different religious backgrounds, language, caste, colour and nationality come here for spiritual study. Thus, the Brahma Kumaris is not any religious cult or sect. On the other hand it is an institution that imparts education in universal values and brings understanding and unity to all and peace to the planet earth. **It is practical example of unity in diversity:**

Where as most other universities enable a person to attain a Master's Degree in one of the arts or science...this Vishwa- Vidyalaya enables him to be the master of his own thoughts, desires, emotions and sense-organs.....This Vishwa-Vidyalaya does not impart education in all those subjects which are being taught in other Universities, for that would just be the duplication or the overlapping of efforts. **The thrust of knowledge imparted.....is first to make man, in 'reality, a man and to enable him to have practical wisdom and to learn lessons for constant peace and happiness**

and for excellence in life.

"The New Dimensions of Implementation" is an enlightened new capacity of implementation. The Oxford Dictionary Thesaurus meaning of "Dimensions" is capacity, extent, scope, an aspect or feature. In this chapter the researcher's main aim, by using the new dimensions of implementation, is that she wants to present new features or aspects of the practical results explored in the practice of values and spirituality — "Seeing is believing" and implementation is practical experience. The greater authority is that of experience in life. The human soul wants experience. 'The clarion call of the time is experience. Since time immemorial history shows knowledge and practice enforce an enrichment of the experience of life. Today science has various tools to measure physical and external experiments. But science still is unable to measure spiritual experiences. The subject of spirituality and soul is so subtle and vast that it is even difficult to explain in words. As soul is non-physical and the physical body senses are limited in their skill to express spiritual taste. The beauty of these experiences is that physical eyes cannot see "Divine Light". It can be seen only through the "Divine Eye" the Soul. Since childhood the researcher herself has experienced 'Divine Light', during meditation, which filled her with a deep experience of inner joy and peace. She observed changes in the lives of many people as well as her own deep spiritual experiences which inspired her to present those new dimensions of implementation of spirituality and values.

The Brahma Kumaris' practices of spirituality through these new methods has transformed the lives of many. In this transformation does not mean 100% change. It means in comparison with the state of the human being before the practice of meditation and spirituality and after the practice, people have shown different levels of transformation in their life. And one thing was very clear in the results of these experiences, there is a change in thoughts, words, and actions as per their efficiency of practice in their personal life. The strength behind these practical results is following efforts:

The practical New Dimensions of Implementation of Brahma Kumaris:

- ✓ 9200 spiritual study and value education centres in India and 142 countries of the World.
- ✓ All over the World dedicated working strength of the people serving enthusiastically for the promotion of human values and spirituality. This dedicated strength not only

spreading the message but also practising spirituality and values in their lives.

- ✓ Under Raja Yoga Education and Research foundation of Brahma Kumaris value based programmes are being conducted for the 19 various professional groups or wings.
- ✓ Brahma Kumaris education wing and Research foundation in collaboration with many Universities, running Diploma/ Post Graduate Diploma/ Degree/Master Degree courses in value education and spirituality in India & abroad
- ✓ Correspondence one week advanced course including four main subjects of Brahma Kumaris (1) Spiritual knowledge (2) Raja yoga(3) Dhama (practice) (4) Spiritual service.
- ✓ National and International conferences and projects on spirituality and values. Training courses in Self management leadership, Quality management, Stress Management, Positive thinking, Personality development and values in healthcare.
- ✓ For youth "Touch the Light" based on value and spiritual education programmes for school children.
- ✓ "Awakening with Brahma Kumaris" popular "Spiritual awakening" program at Aastha channel and also on various main T.V. channels regular programmes on values and spiritual themes.
- ✓ Entertaining methods of implementations are spiritual fairs, exhibitions, films, light and sound shows and variety of multimedia devices, CDs cassettes, devotional songs, radio, internet and Web sites of the Brahma Kumaris.

Education is not only for earning a living but also for learning to live. It is not only to raise the standard of living but also to raise self realizations. In other words education is meant to generate new life through self and God realization. It implies the drawing out of the best potential so as to lead humans towards right knowledge. In the light of above mentioned. "Practical New Dimensions of Implementation of Brahma Kumaris", the researcher wants to present the leading practical methods of universal human values through spirituality, Since the information and definitions of these subjects are already covered in previous chapters, the main emphasis here is presenting the practical spiritual study and the positive strength of spirituality in daily life.

The Brahma Kumaris as called at "spiritual university" because there is daily spiritual study which is the most significant part of the spiritual education. The basic four subjects of this spiritual study are:

Fig. No. 12: Brahma Kumaris: basic four subjects of this spiritual study

The balance of these four subjects in everyday life includes a beautiful synthesis of knowledge and practice. These subjects are integrated with each other.

Gyan or study of spiritual knowledge — is the first founding subject of the spiritual study. This everyday study is based on listening and reading the Divine Godly versions of the Murli. The Murli is the direct direction (Shrimat) of the Ocean of Knowledge Supreme God (Baba) to his beloved children. The 'Murli' covers all the four subjects of spiritual study. The Murli not only gives the knowledge and study of these subjects but also gives direction about how to implement these subjects in daily life. The spiritual knowledge means complete knowledge of Soul which leads to self realization..

4.16 Seven Day Course

In this section, the seven day fundamental course of Raj yoga meditation is discussed. The "Seven Day Course" is the basic course that is imparted at all studies centres of the Brahma Kumaris before regular study of the above four subjects. The foundational one week study course for new beginners covers the topics of the soul, God, Rajyoga, the human world tree, the glory of the rise and fall of the human soul, the world drama, philosophy of karma, and spiritual life style.

Introduction to 7days course of Brahma Kumaris:-

Fig. No. 13: Shri Lakshmi & Shri Narayan-Aim & focus of Brahma Kumaris

Central to the Brahma Kumaris practice is the teaching of all their core beliefs in 7 one, or one and a half hour, long lessons traditionally called "The 7 Day Course". Once these 7 lessons are understood, students were then introduced to unpublished scriptures considered to be the direct teachings of God called "Murlis" named after the flute that the Hindu God Krishna is generally illustrated holding. These comprise of the core philosophy of their religion and are known as "Gyan" or "The Knowledge".

The use of the word "Knowledge" is specific to these beliefs and absolute faith in this knowledge is seen as central to the liberation of the soul.

Seven basic lessons learnt during the course are:

1. The Soul
2. The Supreme Soul
3. The Law of Karma
4. The Cycle
5. The Tree of Religions
6. The Founder Brahma Baba
7. Brahma Kumaris' Lifestyle and Principles

DAY-1

4.16.1 Realizing Self

Sometime in the journey of life, some of the following questions might have crossed your mind. Even if they haven't they eventually will certainly occur

- Who am I? What am I? What is my real identity?
- How do my thoughts and feelings interact with the body?
- How to make my mind powerful? Breaking the mysteries of mind;
- Understanding thoughts, how they come and go, how to regulate them
- Why do we come under emotions, feelings, tension and stress
- How does an individual develops behavioral patterns, traits etc; how to transform them
- How to enjoy this precious life? How to lead a life of peace and bliss?

The first lesson is all about complete understanding of these if, which has remained a mystery that has eluded scientists, philosophers, great thinkers and many other intellectuals

4.16.1.1 Soul & body

The human body is a complex pattern of physical energies. Atomic particles build together to form the organic structures and inorganic minerals, which perform the body's chemical interactions, thus forming the basis of the hormonal and nervous control of the body. What we see as the old or young, ugly or beautiful, male or female, are also the differing levels of physical energies. However marvelous a machine the body may be, it is the presence of the non-physical conscious energy, the soul, which makes it function.

4.16.1.2 What Am I?

I am a living entity different from the body! Just as a person who speaks with the help of a telephone or listens to a call with the help of that instrument, has his entity different from that of the telephone -he himself being a living person who has the faculties or characteristics of feeling, thinking, willing and making effort. Similarly, the conscious entity in the body which uses the word "I" is different from the body which has eyes, ears, nose etc as its components. I am not the eyes, the ears or the mouth but I see with my eyes, speak through the mouth, hear with the ears and am their master. I am a soul (Atma), eternal and immortal. The body is mortal; I have got it to do actions and to experience the result of my actions. I am the doer and the one who experiences.

The soul is like a driver in-charge of the body, which serves as a carriage to the soul. The soul is a diamond, the body being the casket for it. When the soul leaves the body, the body is declared 'dead'. Then people set about cremating it because, its valuable owner, the soul, has already left and the body is of no use. When the soul has relinquished the body, people say, "the light (which is soul) has gone, that which lived in it has departed and the drama is over"

4.16.1.3 Faculties of Soul

Fig. No. 14- Soul & its faculties

The soul is a living or a sentient being. It is said to be conscient or living because it can think and reflect; it can experience pleasure and pain, so also bliss and peace; it can be stir itself and make efforts and actions -good or bad. A soul has three faculties-mind, intellect and predispositions.

Mind is the thinking faculty of the soul. It is the mind that imagines, thinks and forms ideas. The thought process is the basis of all emotions, desires and sensations. It is through this faculty that, in an instant, thought can be projected to a distant place, past experiences and emotions can be relived or even the future can be anticipated. It is the mind that experiences the variations of moods. The mind is a faculty of the metaphysical soul, not be confused with the heart or the brain.

Intellect is used to assess thoughts. This is the faculty of understanding and decision-making which stands out as the most crucial faculty of the three. With the deepening and broadening of the intellect, clear understanding and the realization of the knowledge becomes natural, and the power to decide and reason becomes clear. It is the intellect which remembers, discriminates, judges and exercises its power in the form of will.

Predispositions (called Sanskaras in Hindi) are the "impressions" or "sub-consciousness" which is the record of all the soul's past experiences and actions. Sanskaras can take the forms of habits, talents, emotional temperaments, personality traits, beliefs, values or instincts. Every action as an experience either creates a Sanskaras (this is how a habit begins) or reinforces an old one. What ever impression is etched in the soul remains within it, forming a complete archive of all the experiences that the soul has had. When we speak of defects, specialties or virtues, we are referring to the Sanskaras. The Sanskaras are the basis of the soul's individuality.

4.16.1.4 Seat of Soul

The soul is located in the middle of the fore head in between the two eye brows. This is the seat of the soul. The brain is the "control-room". Just as a driver controls the car using different parts of the mechanism seated at one place, the soul employs the brain to control the body. Brain is the machine by means of which the soul thinks, remembers, receives messages from or gives directions to the sense-organs. The brain is the meeting place of all nerves, which carry sensations from all parts of the body to brain which functions like a control-room and makes the body to work. It is in the brain that the soul, through the nerves, puts the body to work and experiences physical sensations, pleasure and pain or happiness and sorrow. But, the brain is separate from the soul, brain is a complex thing made of matter where as the soul has the life principal or consciousness

4.16.1.5 Nature of Soul

A soul is a tiny, metaphysical, conscient point of spiritual light. There are a finite number of souls. Each soul is eternal. They were never created, and will never be destroyed. Each soul is unique. We are all souls, unique and different and remain so eternally. As such, souls are invisible to the naked eyes, but one can experience its

presence. A soul has no gender. The intrinsic nature of the soul is that of love, peace, happiness, truth, bliss, purity. Therefore, souls always desire for experiences of these qualities. These are the qualities that naturally emerge when the soul is aware of itself, or in other words, is soul-conscious.

Body-Consciousness-the root cause of all evils in the world

A person is in body conscious when he/she identifies himself or herself with the physical body, i.e., when the thinking, feeling, actions and behaviors are with the awareness that he or she is a body. Being in body conscious is the root cause of all the evils in the world because the vices like lust, anger, greed, attachment and ego are all having their roots in body-consciousness.

Soul-Consciousness-the key for a blissful life : When a person is in the state of awareness that "I am a Soul and not this physical body", then he/she would be in soul consciousness. In other words, the person thinks, feels, acts, behaves, compare set with the awareness that he or she is a soul, the master of the body. When in soul consciousness, the original qualities of a soul naturally emerge. Then it is possible to experience lasting peace and bliss.

4.16.1.6 Karma Philosophy

There are times when thoughts of distress and tension raise their ugly head. There are situations when a person searches for right answers. Here are some typical examples- Why are we here? Why was I born here and he there? Why is she beautiful and I ugly? Why is so and so crippled for no apparent fault of theirs? Why does the egotistical bully who browbeats his business companions, fiddles his income tax returns and beats his wife, attain outstanding worldly success? Why does the timid, quiet little widow who has never said a harsh word to anyone, live in appalling conditions and die unwanted and uncared for? Why did he have to die? Why did he do that to me? Why is there so much suffering? Why this, why that?

The answers lie in one eternal truth-based on the Law of Karma or the Karma Philosophy -that no one can escape the result of his or her karma. Depending on the bad or good karma or action, one will suffer or enjoy, either in this or the next life. No one can escape the result of his or her karma. The law of Karma is inviolable. So everyone must act with a sense of responsibility. Ignorance of the law is no excuse.

So we must acquire right knowledge of what is good and what is bad action. The morale of the story-I have to do right karma for my benefit; it is not for showing it to anyone outside. Every human action has a moral aspect. If a person's certain act is morally good, the person gets ultimately benefited. If, on the other hand, his acts are morally bad, he suffers. It would require a lot of space to express what is morally good and bad. But in one sentence, it may be said that, if a person acts under the influence of hatred, anger, lies, prejudice, greed, ego, partiality, lust and such other acts under the influence of body-consciousness, then his actions are bad or negative. These create disharmony and conflict and sufferings in the society.

4.16.1.7 Power of Thought

The most powerful instrument that mankind possesses is thought power. Thoughts build our consciousness and shape our attitude. One needs to know how important thoughts are. Every human creation we see in this world is due to powerful thoughts in human minds. Thoughts shape our world. Thoughts are fertilized by knowledge. A person with a certain kind of knowledge usually creates thoughts in harmony with that knowledge. Knowledge gives wisdom; a person without knowledge is a person whose thoughts will be formed in ignorance.

Every action is preceded by thoughts. The quality of thoughts determines the quality of our karma. The karma in turn has good or bad effect on us. This again influences our thinking. Raja Yoga meditation helps us in doing the right thinking that leads to righteous actions. This also helps in remaining mentally strong amidst turbulent situations.

DAY-2

4.16.2 Where have I come from?

When I begin to view myself as to be to be soul, requesting of ten makes, "Where do souls come from?" In reflection, I can examine estimations of consideration past physical resources. Experiencing these estimations accumulates my idea regarding authentic substances of thought & feeling certainly recognize me to position of total peace, wisdom & quiet in which I feel as if I've swung to my novel 'home'. Together, physical, clear & soul "universes" wire three standard levels of human intelligence.

Fig. No. 15- Three worlds

4.16.2.1 Physical World

The world in which we are now living is known as the physical or corporeal world, because all living beings here have a gross, corporeal or manifest form. The physical earth can be thought of as a vast stage where we 'play our parts' in the drama of life, in different bodily 'costumes'. It can also be thought of as a field, where seeds of action are sown and fruits are reaped as experiences of happiness and sorrow. Here 'time', 'space', 'history' and 'geography' are important parameters of existence; here the laws of science apply. It is a world of expression and experience.

4.16.2.2 Subtle World

Beyond the limits of the vast expanse of our solar system and distant galaxies there are regions of non-material light, unreachable by physical means and inaccessible to the physical senses. These realms can only be experienced through deep meditation and divine insight. The subtle world is an intermediate dimension of pure, positive luminous energy in which there is the experience of one's subtle body of light and communication with other souls through pure spiritual thoughts and vibrations.

4.16.2.3 Soul World

Beyond the physical realm of action and the subtle realm of pure thought lies an infinite, timeless dimension of complete stillness, silence and peace. Suffused with golden-red luminosity, this is the realm of God, the Supreme Being, Parent of all souls. It is the original home of all souls, where we once dwelt in a dormant, seminal state of total belongingness and bliss. Experiencing this 'supreme region' (Paramdham) of highest consciousness in meditation renews and recharges the soul, empowering it with the strength to play its part in the physical world with peace, equanimity and enlightened clarity.

4.16.2.4 Going

In Raja Yoga meditation, not only do I journey inward to experience my essential self; I also journey upward into higher consciousness, going beyond the awareness of the physical body and the physical world. With practice I am able to perceive and experience the dimension of pure soul consciousness, beyond sound, activity and thought. In this place or state of awareness I experience complete freedom, peace, rest and comfort, as if I've come home to a place where I truly belong and where I can simply be.

4.16.2.5 Knowing God

In this world, many beliefs exist about God. As a result, people understand God in their own way and often in their own imagination. But what is required is the understanding God as He is, what He is and how He is. The correct understanding about God has to be given by God Himself.

There are some who don't believe in the existence of God, often the reason being His existence cannot be proved like that of human beings. But because we cannot see God with the gross eyes, it doesn't mean that God doesn't exist. Just like wind, which cannot be seen but can be very much felt it is possible to experience God's presence through Godly knowledge and meditation

Fig. No. 16: Incorporeal God & HIS attributes

DAY-3

4.16.3 Who is God & what is His form & name?

We shall now try to understand who God or the Supreme Soul is. The term 'Supreme Soul' means He is supreme among all souls. It implies that, He is also 'a soul', though He is the Highest of all. He is above birth and death. God is the Supreme Father-Mother, Supreme teacher and Supreme Preceptor to all the human beings and He himself has no father-mother, teacher and preceptor.

God is a subtle, infinitesimal point of Light. He is not visible to the naked eye but it is very much possible to experience His presence and proximity in meditation. He is incorporeal in the sense that he does not have a body of his own. He is not a human being nor does He have a human form. He is immune to pleasure and pain unlike human beings.

Names are a means of identification of human beings after they are born. They do not speak of qualities and actions of the person; they are simply proper nouns and are not

attributive names. But the name of the supreme soul or God is based on His qualities and actions. His self revealed name is 'Shiva'. 'Shiva' means doer of good or benefactor. God does well to all and therefore He is called Shiva. All souls ask for salvation and be attitude i.e., peace and happiness from Him. People remember Him by many other expressive names.

4.16.3.1 His Virtues

Fig. No. 17 Three Acts of God

God is the Supreme Father of all. He is called the creator. He is oceanic in his virtues- the ocean of peace, the ocean of love, the ocean of bliss, the ocean of knowledge, the ocean of happiness, the ocean of mercy, etc. He is the truth. He is the Almighty and Authority. He is reputed to be the preserver or sustainer of virtues and the destroyer of all evils. He is also the liberator, the guide, and the bestower of salvation, therefore the sadguru. He dispels sorrow, bestows joy. God is perfect in always and absolutely detached and loving. He is very benevolent and helpful and so souls ask all things of him. When in sorrow and losing all hope, souls turn to him intuitively and inevitably.

Many are the religions and paths that souls take in their quest for reaching God. Many wars have been waged in his name. However, he does not exclusively belong to anyone. He belongs to everyone equally.

4.16.3.2 Supreme Father of all Souls

God is the father of all souls in this world. It is observed that all religions have images, idols or memorials bearing one name or another to represent the form of Light that God is. All over India, the images of the form that Shiva has is found installed; these images are without any human form, in the form of linga, which is the symbol of an incorporeal Being. At Mecca, in the holy place of Kaaba, a stone image with oval form is called "Sang-e-As wad". The devotees who go for Haj kiss this holy stone. Jesus Christ said, "God is Light". Guru Nanak, the founder of Sikhism also sang the praise of Him who is 'All-Light' (ek Omkar) and is incorporeal. In olden days, the Jews held a stone of this shape in their hands while taking a solemn oath and it is believed that Moses had vision of this form of God when he saw a flame behind the bush. The Zoroastrians worship God as fire. The ancient Egyptians worshipped the sun as god. A Buddhist sect in Japan focuses the mind on a small oval shape. They call it Kami, the peace giver.

It seems therefore that human beings, without realizing, have all been worshipping and trying to discover the same God. There is only one God and His form is a point of light. He is called by different names in different religions.

4.16.3.3 Divine Abode of God.

Fig. No. 18: God is Omnipotent

Where does God live? Is there some where one can go to see Him, to be with Him? God is a subtle point of light, and He does not pervade the physical universe. Nor does he live in the heart of any human being or in any matter. Neither is He omnipresent; nor is He having a human form. His home is the incorporeal world, an infinite expanse of golden-red light, which is beyond this physical world we live. It is the original abode of all souls as well. The incorporeal world is known as Paramdham or Brahmlok. Knowing where the Supreme Father is, we can establish connection with Him through thoughts during meditation.

4.16.3.4 Divine Descent of God

Fig. No. 19: Shivarathri

God descends into this world when it is under the spell of extreme darkness of ignorance, unrighteousness, moral turpitude, spiritual lassitude and religious decrepitude. This is described in scriptures as "Dharma Glani". Looking at the state of affairs today, it should not be difficult for us to conclude that the time the world is undergoing at present is indeed the Dharma Glani. This is the period of darkness when sins and crimes of all kinds usually take place; when man gropes around for want of clear vision. It is at this time that God intervenes in the affairs of mankind. The divine intervention takes place at the darkest hour of human history when the human soul is groping in the darkness of ignorance about the self, the creator and

the creation; when the souls are blinded by the vices of lust, arrogance, anger, greed and attachment

It is in this time that God descends in the body of an ordinary man to reveal the Godly Knowledge, which paves way to victory over vices and cultivate divine qualities in life. This enables human beings to transform into divine beings again.

DAY-4

4.16.4 Genealogical Tree of mankind

Fig. No. 20: Kalpa Tree of Religions

It is an indisputable fact that religion has an important influence on human mind. Along with the religion, the race, the language, the nationality, the culture, the ancestry with which a person identifies himself or herself has got a great bearing on his/her personality, beliefs, outlooks, attitude, consciousness and thinking. These are often the reason for so many conflicts in this world. So it is necessary to understand the original religion and culture of the mankind.

In order to elucidate the growth of this world and to illustrate the world developments, this world is compared with a tree which may be called 'the Genealogical Tree of mankind'. It is also known as kalpa tree because it depicts the history of the whole kalpa (one full cycle of all eras), the beginning the mid-period and the end of all the religio-political dynasties of the world.

In the beginning, depicted by the trunk, there was only one religion, which is the religion of the deities, and there was only one dynasty, called the sun dynasty. There was the deity-sovereignty, which set in vogue all righteous traditions and customs. The masses were, like their rulers, vice less and possessed divine qualities. Because they did good nature was perfectly under their control. There was no fury of nature, neither ill-health nor want of money or food. All the elements were clean and excellent and therefore were instruments of happiness. Since there was complete purity, peace and prosperity in that Age, kings and queens and their righteous subjects are shown with a halo of light around them. They were called deities because they were naturally holy, habitually righteous and instinctively spiritual and vice-less. There was such great mutual regard and love in those days that it is said of the age in which a lion and a goat together drank from the same stream. There was unlimited wealth. Since people in that Age led viceless lives, they lived long and there was no case of premature death. They willingly gave up the body when they had reached old age. In other words, death never laid its hand on them.

In Golden age the souls were complete in all respects. In silver age, there was a slight decline in divine qualities. But even then there was sovereignty of complete peace and happiness. Copper age follows the Silver Age. By this time, the souls, who had transmigrated through several lives, become body-conscious. The vices like lust, anger, greed, attachment and ego cast their shadows on them. And they had thus fallen from the state of purity and worthiness and become vicious and unworthy, As they forget their true selves and broke with purity, natural laws came to be violated. Even nature deviated from her usual course, having thus beg unto harm them, even though slightly. It is in this age that various religions were established .A good many faiths began appearing like branches coming forth from

the World-Tree. Abraham founded Judaism; Buddhism was founded by Buddha; Jesus Christ founded Christianity; Shankaracharya established the class of recluses and hermits; Mohammed Prophet established the Muslim religion. The previous deity religion came to be known as Hindu religion because they lost their deity-hood or divinity in them. The population also increased considerably. Whereas in the beginning, everything was one, now there are many religions, many kingdoms, languages, cultures and dynasties. Thus grew mutual strife, divisions and disunity and this state of affairs continued.

In the Iron Age that follows the Copper-Age, problems, difference of views and disputes begin to increase. The souls in this age are over-powered by vices and darkness of ignorance. They become vicious and impious. There is quite a crop of dissensions due to religious, communal and sectarian difference. Women are treated with utter contempt. Nature becomes instrumental in causing distress to man. Disease, grief, old age, premature death, death by accident, etc., afflicted mankind.

When all the religions reach their lowest level, and all people, men and women become diabolic, there is misery and uproar. This is the time of wickedness and irreligion. People are given to sensual pleasures; they acquire bad qualities, ready to cause bloodshed on the score of differences in languages, views, politics, faiths, castes and states. Fighting among the nations brings about a great destruction of the world. Instead of behaving like brothers, people look upon one another as so many different beings and, therefore, they deal with each other as enemies. Being guided wholly by the feelings of nepotism, unrighteousness, lawlessness, selfishness, attachment, adulteration and bribery they desire to lay their hands on others' possessions by any means. People discard all the feelings of mutual love and fight like demons.

What will happen next?

The world will not go on like this forever. Somebody has to put an end to all these evils. Otherwise the state of the world will be incomprehensible. This task is beyond the reach of any human being and only one Almighty God can establish lasting peace on earth. Incorporeal God Shiva descends in the body of

an ordinary person, names him Prajapita Brahma, and through him, gives the Godly Knowledge and teaches the easy Raja Yoga. He shows the path by which anyone can become completely vice less and most righteous. In this way, God purifies the human beings of the old, impious world and transmutes them into pious ones, creating the Golden Age again.

4.16.4.1 Cycle of Time.

Fig. No. 21: World Drama Wheel

In this lesson, we learn about the beginning, the middle and the end of one complete 'time cycle' of this world. More than anything else, we will understand the great significance of the period we are undergoing at present.

The world has been in existence since eternity and it will continue to be eternal. The world was neither created anytime before nor will it get destroyed later, because matter can neither be created nor destroyed, it only undergoes

transformation from one form to another. Similarly this world also undergoes changes in its characteristics, but as such the world was not created out of nothing or there a total annihilation.

The cycle of time is best understood with the help of the picture of the world drama wheel. It illustrates the "flow" of time. In the middle of it is the Fylfot (Swastika) which divides the Time into four equal parts. The Swastika is considered to be very auspicious.

In the first part of this Wheel of Time, marked by Swastika is shown Golden Age. Here the arm of the Swastika is pointing towards right because the right arm symbolizes what is good or what brings about goodness. In these early times, when the cycle started, people of the deity religion (Sanatan Dharma) were possessed of divine qualities and nature and they enjoyed complete purity, 100% peace and complete prosperity.

Then came the Silver Age. In this era too, people were possessed of purity, peace and prosperity to a very high degree. But the degree of their divine qualities had decreased a little. They were two degrees less divine than the people of the Golden Age who were divine to the extent of 16 degrees. Therefore the arm of Swastika that indicates this epoch is bent downwards because souls in this era had come down from the state of super-righteousness to what is just righteous.

Next came Copper Age. After having experienced beatitude and fruition for many a life, turned it the path of vices or unrighteousness. This is why the arm is reversed because the left hand symbolizes what is impure and auspicious. People then were second-grade by their nature, qualities and actions. Mankind is now divided on various religions; strifes and disputes started to appear and the five vices brought disquiet and sorrow in homes.

Steadily, unrighteous doings, i.e. the actions done under the sway of one or the other of these five vices, led the world to more and more impurity and sufferings and the world came under the yoke of Iron Age (Kaliyuga). Strives, wars, bellicosity and the resulting peacelessness increased rapidly in frequency and intensity in this era. Therefore the fourth of Swastika is shown raising itself up

to indicate the rise in conflicts, clashes and calamities. Then, a stage comes when ignorance, lassitude, stupor, moral turpitude and sin become dominant. People become devilish by nature and religion becomes utterly degenerate.

4.16.4.2 Significance of present period

Fig. No. 22: Confluence age

At present, we are undergoing through a critical phase in the history of mankind. This is the period of the confluence of the ending phase of the Iron Age and the starting phase of the Golden Age. This is the most important of all epochs, called the Confluence Age, when God, the Highest Being, descends in this world to meet the human beings, His beloved children and gives the most precious boons of Redemption and Beatitude.

Through the Godly Knowledge and the easy Raja Yoga, God creates the Golden Age or new vice less order. The act of 'creation' does not mean constructing something out of nothing but it means the moral reconstruction of mankind or the re-establishment of the ancient most Deity Religion. The reader would be pleased to know or, perhaps, surprised to know that God Shiva, the Supreme Father of all, is indeed doing this great task of resurrection of mankind at present.

The world will soon be free of all miseries and the paradise, which is full of peace and happiness, will be established again.

4.16.4.3 Nature of World Drama Cycle

The cycle of five epochs, comprising Golden-Age Silver Age, Copper-Age and Iron Age and the confluence Age repeats exactly every time after it has turned full wheel. During every cycle, the souls who are the actors on this world-drama stage will be the same. Each soul will act the same part in every cycle since, in the soul itself is indelibly ingrained the part it has played life after life in the previous cycle or that it has to repeat cycle after cycle. Just as in a tape record or a gramophone record, a whole song or drama is recorded and it repeats every time the record is played, even so, a soul's role in this world drama is recorded in the soul itself which is only self-luminous, conscient point. The soul replays the part once every 5000 years because each one of the four eras of the world-drama being equal to 1250 years, the duration of one World Cycle is 5000 years.

4.16.4.4 Rise & Fall of Humans

Fig. No. 23: Ladder of 84 human births & ages

We will understand this lesson with the help of the adjoining picture. It is a wonderful story of how the souls, who once were deities, became the devotees and very ordinary human beings. It also explains how they lost the divine virtues, spiritual and moral values and developed devilish tendencies. The illustration shows that originally, human souls had complete purity, peace and

prosperity and that they became defiled and peace less lately. Now it is time to again inculcate those lost virtues.

First of all is shown the Golden Age or the Satyuga, which is completely righteous. Shri Lakshmi and Shri Narayana and their dynasty ruled the world free from disease, sorrow, worry or vice. The people then had truly virtuous nature and outlook. During this period of 1250 years, the average age was 150 years. In this epoch, the people are most elevated, completely viceless and are invested with all good qualities and live under Divine Law. These people are considered to be class of deities.

Next comes Silver Age. In this epoch of 1250 years, average age of a person varies from 100 to 125 years. All are happy in this period as well. They have the rank of what are called Kshatriyas because they are not as pure as their predecessors -the deities. Then in the Copper Age, they become body-conscious and are led to vices. So they have a fall, from a deity's position which is worship-worthy exalted position to be just supplicant men or poor worshippers. Their rank is of middle class or Rajopradhana type. Their position is that of 'Vaishyas' – mediocre. After this comes the Iron Age (Kaliyuga). The picture represents how in this epoch, Maya which symbolizes the vices, has grown in power over the world. In Iron Age, tamoguna, the basest form in man -is pre-dominant. All the persons are ranked as Shudras. In this epoch of 1250 years, there are 42 births. In this era, we see disputes and strives, based on want of respect for authority and differences in ideology, religion, states and languages. People do not look upon one another as spiritual brothers and are thus turned away from God, who is the Supreme Father.

At present, we are in the Confluence Age - the confluence of the fag end of the Kaliyuga and the dawn of Satyuga or the Golden Age. This is the time to receive Divine Knowledge from God and practice spiritual discipline and easy Raja Yoga and re-acquire deity status. When the Iron Age is very near it's end, unrighteousness is eliminated to make room for Righteousness (Dharma) and the deity-world. With this comes the Golden Age.

DAY – 5

4.16.5 Understanding Raja yoga

Fig. No. 24: Lotus like life – spiritual life style

The word Yoga means 'connection'. The mental connection between the soul and Supreme Soul or the remembrance of the Supreme Soul by the soul is called meditation or Raja Yoga. Stability in the Soul-consciousness and God-consciousness will bring peace and bliss to the soul. By this means, all the latencies of the vicious actions of the past lives will be destroyed because intellectual communion with God acts like fire. It burns the sins of the past. Yoga washes off all dirt from the soul; bathing in a river may clean the body but a soul is cleansed only in the remembrance of the Supreme Soul.

Yoga is the only means through which soul gets link or association with God, who is the truth. By dint of Yoga, man controls his otherwise fickle sense organs and overcomes diverse vile thoughts. Yoga has such great force that, under its influence, even the elements of nature are brought to elevated state and the righteousness and peace is established in the world.

Through the meditation or Raja yoga, the soul gets immense joy of an extraordinary kind from its link with the Supreme Soul.

4.16.5.1 Knowledge of our relationship with God

What is our relationship with God? Knowledge of the relationship between the soul and the supreme soul is very essential to remembrance. In his dealings in life, man remembers every now and then only those who are bound to him by ties of one kind or another. The closer the relationship, the more easily one is reminded of it without any effort, as it were. It is very important to realize and feel that God indeed is our Supreme Father-Mother, Teacher, true Friend and Guide, and the real Protector. Relationship is the lever that can lift us to the state of Yoga. So if we have clearly before us, our relationship with God, we shall every now and then be reminded of Him and only this true link redeems all the human beings.

4.16.5.2 God is most beautiful being

Beauty is a thing that bewitches man and draws his mind and understanding again towards itself. But beauty of the physical body and other physical things is only temporary and subject to gradual decline and decay. On the contrary, it is the Supreme Soul, the Supreme Father, who is absolutely and truly beautiful. His beauty is spotless; it never suffers change or decline. Remembering Him will make a soul clean and beautiful.

4.16.5.3 How to practice Raja Yoga?

Fig. No. 25: Basis for Raja yoga

The benefits of meditation are enormous. It calms our mind and body. In these fast and frenetic times, it has the most important ability to replenish mental and emotional energy.

Meditation enables you to create new attitudes and responses to life, giving you a clear spiritual understanding of yourself.

Meditation is the process of re-discovering, enjoying and using the positive qualities latent within you. Like any skill, meditation requires practice to achieve positive and satisfying results. By doing a little every day, it soon becomes a natural and easy habit, which generously rewards you for the little effort it involves.

4.16.6.1 What Does Meditation Do?

Fig. No. 27: Attainments of eight powers through Raja yoga

Meditation energizes your awareness bringing both peace and wisdom to a busy mind. It expands your capacity to love and heals broken hearts. Also it dissolves many fears replacing them with lightness and freedom from anxiety.

Meditation is both the journey and the destination, revealing the secrets of consciousness and the treasures of the soul. It develops the power to be more alert and to be effective in our interaction with each other and with our precious

world. But perhaps the greatest gift that comes with meditation is the glow of inner peace that is both gentle and strong.

The practice of Raja Yoga meditation or intellectual communion with God brings into the soul many powers. Of these, eight are very important. Please refer to the adjoining diagram.

The Power To Pack-Up

With the ability to go within, one can learn how to pack up all wasteful thinking in a second, so that there is lightness and freedom from burdens and worries, though there may be many responsibilities. One's mind is scattered over the wide world and so much drawn out to men and matters that he is unable to sleep or to detach himself at his will. With the practice of meditation, one can wind up one's thoughts at one's own will.

Power To Tolerate

Just as trees offer the same fruits to people whether they gently pluck the fruits or pelt stones at them, a yogi tolerates all attacks on him and does good even to those who offer brickbats at him. In the light frame of mind, one will be able to tolerate all types of situations and people to the extent that there is no sense at all of having to tolerate something or someone. With the understanding that each one is simply playing their role in this immense world-drama, impatience, irritation and annoyance disappear like mists before a bright sunlight.

The Power To Accommodate

Just as the ocean accepts different rivers that flow into it, whether polluted or clean, one will be able to adjust to all that is happening around him, so will a yogi be able to accommodate others with him. It power makes one broadminded. One will be able to adjust into all the happenings around him. Even when the atmosphere is charged with negativity or impurity, one remains unaffected.

The Power Of Judgment

One will learn to take correct and quick decisions. One will get the ability to accurately assess any situation with clarity and confidence. In a detached,

impartial state of mind, one can judge one's own thoughts, words and actions to see if they are beneficial. One will become a judge of the self and not of others.

The Power Of Discrimination

Just as an expert jeweler can easily distinguish between the false and the pure diamonds (or gems), one will acquire the power to distinguish between right and wrong or good and bad. One can accurately discriminate between real truth and the apparent truth, between things of temporary value and those of eternal value and between superficial and the subtle. The power helps in recognizing illusions even when they are sweetly decorated and enticing.

The Power To Face

Meditation develops the power to endure hardships. Adversities like death of those on whom one depends may come and high storms may rage strongly, yet his flame of equanimity does not get extinguished. Having confidence in one's spiritual state brings the courage to face any type of situation.

The Power To Co-Operate

The natural result of all the powers is that I am able to share with others the tasks and qualities that my Father has given to me. There is no feeling of competition, so I can give as well as accept suggestion as to how to proceed with the task of world upliftment. By learning meditation, one will develop the spirit of co-operation. This is a great achievement because if everyone gives his little finger, the society could lift great mountains.

The Power to Withdraw

With full awareness that I (soul) am is an entity different from the body, one can withdraw from the senses and become a point. In the same way that a tortoise retreats into its shell in a moment of danger, or just to rest, a person would be able to retract himself from any situation and remain protected.

4.16.6.2 Spiritual Lifestyle

Fig. No. 28: Pillars of Raja yoga

What supports the practice of meditation but does not require leaving home, career and family?

A Spiritual Lifestyle

The journey awakens within,
when the songs of remembrance begin,
the child of the Father is lost in the Ocean of Love.

Holding the hand of the Guide,
through the path of confusion inside,
tears become pearls in the silence and passing of time.
The song of remembrance is sung in unlimited rhyme,
the song of remembrance is sung in unlimited rhyme,
Dance away, to the beautiful music you wanted to play,
dance away, in your heart, in your heart.

4.16.6.3 What is Spiritual Lifestyle?

A spiritually fulfilling life is based on a foundation of four pillars:

- Daily practice of meditation / Yoga
- Regular spiritual study

- Spiritual relationships and fulfilling responsibilities
- The service of humanity

Daily Meditation Practice

Daily meditation/yoga provides the means to explore, discover and reconnect with one's self and with God

Regular Spiritual Study

Regular, daily spiritual study provides the right quality food for mind and intellect, the two key faculties of the soul.

Spiritual Relationships & Responsibilities

Through the experience of soul-consciousness others are recognized as spiritual beings and a feeling of brotherhood grows. By transcending the divisions of color, sex and religion, relationships become more smooth and rewarding. The exchange of respect and spiritual love becomes the basis of interaction. The decision to deal with others' good qualities means there is no longer the give and take of sorrow, rather an emphasis on acceptance and tolerance.

Spirituality is not an escape from life's responsibilities. You have a responsibility to your immediate relationships-family, colleagues and friends-and it is in those relationships that your ability to apply what you are learning spiritually will also be tested and strengthened.

Spiritual Service

Finding an appropriate way to use your growing spiritual power and understanding for the benefit of others in the wider community is also a method of sustaining your personal growth. Spiritual service occurs on many levels, including spreading peaceful vibrations into the atmosphere and helping others develop awareness of their own spiritual qualities through good wishes and pure feelings.

Vegetarian Diet

In respecting and caring for our bodies, diet needs deep consideration. A vegetarian diet is especially beneficial in developing the clarity, concentration and subtle focus which spiritual development requires.

With an understanding of the power and quality of thoughts and vibrations, we also give attention to the quality of our consciousness as we prepare and eat our food..

4.16.6.4 Physical & Mental Relaxation

Fig. No. 29: Relaxation through Raja yoga

Providing rest and relaxation for the body is as important as it is for the mind. The body will not relax if the mind is not relaxed; however even when the body is injured or ill, it is still possible for the mind to relax. Meditation is an important self-healing component when one is recovering from physical illness.

The timing and extent of physical relaxation activities depends on your personal metabolism as well as your professional and family responsibilities. However it has long been recognized that the most effective time in the daily cycle for meditation and spiritual development is in the early morning, before the routine activities of the day begin. Taking time each morning to meditate, study and understand spiritual principles and values provides both mental and spiritual nourishment for the day to come.

4.16.6.5 History of Brahma Kumaris

Fig. No. 30: Prajapita Brahma- Corporeal founding father of Brahma Kumaris

Fig. No. 31: Prajapita Brahma- Corporeal founding father & administrative heads of Brahma Kumaris

Perhaps few organizations have stimulated as much change and discussion at the time of their inception, or have undergone such expansion in succeeding decades, as the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University. Yet, throughout its growth and development, the BKWSU has managed to maintain its original principles and adhere to its original purpose.

When the University came into being under the name "Om Mandali" it consisted of only a handful of men, women and children living in Hyderabad, Sindh (now part of Pakistan, but at that time part of colonial India). After a respected and wealthy member of their community, Dada Lekhraj, experienced a series of visions in 1936, these spiritual pioneers were inspired to transform their lives. Founder's Visions Dada Lekhraj's visions revealed a body of knowledge about the nature of the soul, of God and of time - concepts so simple in their

expression but so profound in meaning that they awakened a powerful sense of recognition in those with whom the visions were shared.

A year after Om Mandali's establishment, the organization moved from Hyderabad to Karachi. For fourteen years, until two years after the partition of India and Pakistan, the founding group of nearly 400 individuals lived as a self-sufficient community devoting their time to intense spiritual study, meditation and self transformation.

4.16.6.6 World Spiritual Headquarters

Fig. No. 32: Pandaw Bhawan Campus - World headquarters of Brahma Kumaris

In 1950, the community moved to Mount Abu, a quiet place reputed for its ancient heritage and regarded as a sacred destination by many in search of spiritual rejuvenation and empowerment. Nestled high in the Aravali Mountains of Rajasthan, it provided an ideal location for reflection and contemplation. After a few years in a rented building, the community moved to the site which remains the University's world spiritual headquarters: Madhuban (meaning 'Forest of Honey'). Om Shanti !!!!!

4.17 Brahma Kumaris scale new heights in higher Value Education

Education Wing of Raja Yoga Education and Research Foundation of Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya proposed to conduct a formal education programme "Post Graduate Diploma in Value Education and Spirituality" for the

graduate degree holders of Indian nationality. World renowned Chiddambaram Annamalai University agreed to launch the programme in Technical Collaboration with Brahma Kumaris Education Wing as a Distance Education Programme. A memorandum of understanding was signed on 7th February, 2009. The details of the courses offered through different universities in INDIA in collaboration are given below

Tab. No. 2: Value Education courses offered through various colleges in INDIA.

Sl. No	Name of University & Jurisdiction	Type & Year of Commencement	Name of Courses offered	Languages
1	Annamalai University- Tamilnadu. All India & Nepal	Distance Education 2009-10 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diploma in value Education & Spirituality • Post Graduate Diploma in value Education & Spirituality • Post Graduate Diploma in value in Health care • B.Sc. In value Education & Spirituality • M.Sc. in value Education & Spirituality • MBA (Self-Management & Crisis Management) 	English, Hindi, Tamil, Gujrat, Marathi, Oriya, Malayalam, Telugu & Kannada
2	Yeshwantrao Chavan Maharashtra Open University, Nasik, Maharashtra – Maharashtra	Distance Education 2012-13 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diploma in values & Spiritual Education • Advanced Diploma in values & Spiritual education • BA (values & Spiritual Education) 	English, Hindi, Marathi
3	Bardhaman Mahaveer Open University-Kota,	Distance Education 2013-14 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certificate course in value Education & Spirituality 	English, Hindi

	Rajasthan- Rajasthan		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post Graduate Diploma in value Education & Spirituality 	
4	Ram Krishna Dharmarth Foundation University-Bhopal, Madhya Prades- RKDF University	Distance Education 2013-14 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One course / paper on Values, Rajayoga meditation & Consciousness in all UG Courses • One course / paper on Values, Raja yoga& Consciousness in all PG Courses 	English, Hindi
5	Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh, -Assam	Distance Education 2013-14 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBA (Self-Management & Crisis Management) 	English
6	Ganapt University- Mahsana, Gujrat- Ganpat University	Distance Education 2014-15 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One course / paper on Values & Ethics in all UG Courses • One course / paper on Values, Raja yoga meditation & Consciousness in all PG Courses 	English, Hindi
7	Tamilnadu Teachers Education University, Chennai Tamilnadu – Chennai	Part Time 2015-16 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post Graduate Diploma in value Education & Spirituality 	Tamil
8	Assam Down Town University, Guwahati, Assam- Assam, Bangladesh, Butan & Nepal	Distance Education 2015-16 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diploma in value Education & Spirituality. • Post Graduate Diploma in value Education & Spirituality • Post Graduate Diploma in value in Health 	English

			care	
9	Karnataka State Open University, Mysore, Karnataka – All India	Distance Education 2015-16 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diploma in value Education & Spirituality. • B.A (value Education & Spirituality) • M.A (value Education & Spirituality) 	English, Kannada
10	Thiagarajar College-Madurai, Tamilnadu – Thiagaraja College	Regular stream 2013-14 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two course in each year on Value Education & Spirituality to UG students 	Tamil
11	Sri Ramaswamy Naidu Memorial College – Sattur – Tamilnadu-SRNM College	Distance Education 2014-15 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certificate course in value Education & Spirituality • Diploma in value Education & Spirituality 	English, Tamil

Tab. No. 3: Details of courses offered through collaboration in ABROAD are given below

Sl. No	Name of the University	Type & Year of Commencement	Name of Courses offered	Languages
1	University of West Indies Trinidad & Tobago	Distance Education 2014-15 onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value based Education & research for both Teachers & students 	English

Convocations held at Head Quarters Mount abu:

Education Wing of RE & RF of Brahma Kumaris in collaboration with different universities has successfully conducted SEVEN convocation programmes till June 2016 and thousands of students have been awarded diploma, degree and master degree in Value Education and spirituality

The details of Convocations held at Abu Road Shantivan complex. are given below.

First convocation - 10.10.2010

Second convocation- 02.12.2011

Third convocation- 02.09.2012

Fourth convocation- 10.10.2013

Fifth convocation- 21.11.2014

Sixth convocation- 24.05.2015

Seventh convocation- 18.03.2016

Marching on to the Path of Growth

The Education Wing, like the process of continuous education, intends to move on from one milestone to the other from one goal to the other till the whole human race gets the benefit of the Godly Knowledge. Hence two more courses have been added during this academic year 2011-12 – Master of Business Administration (MBA) in “Self Management & Crisis Management”, and the other is Diploma Course in “Value Education * Spirituality”. Launching ceremony was held during June 2011.

Further, one course – “Post Graduate Diploma In Value Education in Health Care” was added during 2014 and Post Graduate Course in Counseling and Hypnotherapy was added during 2015. During the year 2016. Bachelor of Science In value Education & Spirituality as added.

As on date there are 135 PCP centres throughout India and Nepal, Courses will be given in 9 languages for the current academic year.

Tab. No. 4: REVEREND DADIS HONOURED WITH DOCTRATE DEGREE (D.Litt.)

Sl. No.	Name of Person	Designation	Name of University where Doctorate Degree was honored	Year
1	Rajayogini BK Dadi Prakshmaniji	Former Administrative Head, Brahma Kumaris	Mohanlal Sukhadiya University, Udaipur, Rajasthan	30.12.1992
2	Rajayogini BK Dadi Janakiji	Administrative Head, Brahma Kumaris	Gitam University, Vishakapatnam, Andhra Pradesh	20.08.2011
3	Rajayogini BK Dadi Ratan Mohiniji	Joint Administrative Head, Brahma Kumaris	Gulbarga University, Gulbarga, Karnataka	20.02.2014

4.18 Brahma Kumaris Organization: Defining in Leader's Words

4.18.1 Brahma Kumaris Institution attempting Value Education is commendable.

*Value Education increases importance of individual & helps to improve society. Efforts in way for obtaining ancient values & tradition through excellent education along with spiritual growth is right step. In India growth of education is main reason to maintain country's flexible governance. We have profound faith in our Indian philosophy & culture. We believe that synergy between values will lead to progress. **Brahma Kumaris Institution attempting Value Education is commendable.***

**His Excellency Shri Pranab Mukharjee
President of India**

4.18.2 Brahma Kumari Institution doing service of Human character building

Fig. No. 33 : Hon'ble Shri Narendra Modi,

**Former Chief Minister of Gujraath in conversation with Dadi Prakashmani,
Former BKs Administrative head**

The Service itself is Paramo dharm & you people associated with this are salutable. Service fructifies only when it is Selfless service. We develop sense of belonging from advaita. By doing service with Benevolence & Sympathy, emotions within is revealed. For service, post, prestige & respect is not needed. It cannot be divided into boundaries of high or low level, religion or unrelation.

***Brahma Kumari Institution doing service of Human character building is not only commendable but also exemplary.** Service sectors maybe different but of all services service you do is great. By wearing tunicle of human rights &*

who support terrorists must ask them that there is no lack of such people in this country who consider service as paramount & dedicated their lives to serve society. Based on positive human thinking character building, excellent nature grows & develops society. It feels pleasure doing service to poor with mercy, compassion, sympathy & warm expressions. India is world leader in Forgivingness & Tolerance. In our country spirit of service to society is of ancient standing. This spirit cross bordered country as 'vasudeiva kutumbam' & 'sarva jana hitaya, sarva jana sukhaya' reflecting great character from which it is possible to build new society.

-Honorable Shri Narendra Modi
Prime Minister of India

4.18.3 Promoters of Peace, Love & Harmony

*Brahma kumaris concept of "One God One World Family" has inspired me to participate in Global Peace Festival. Their spiritual wisdom & social work has been recognized worldwide. **This itself is testimony of their global presence as promoters of peace, love & harmony.***

- His Excellency Shri Hamid Ansari, Vice President of India

4.18.4 Promoting Values, spirituality & raja Yoga Meditation

I feel greatly honored to inaugurate Diamond Jubilee celebration of Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya. I congratulate them for completing their successful 60 years in service of humanity, promoting values, spirituality & raja yoga meditation. Their spiritual & scientific approach has lifted & empowered lakhs of brothers & sisters to lead pure & peaceful life. They are doing commendable work by promoting peace & harmony in world. I am proud to know that, their work has been appreciated by United Nations & thus, honoring institution with "Peace Messenger award."

- His Excellency Shri Shankar Dayal Sharma, Former President of India

4.18.5 Our culture is being praised in other countries

Fig. No. 34:

- Shri Atal Bihari Vajpayee, Former Prime Minister of India with Former Brahma Kumaris Administrative head- Dadi Prakashmani

You (Brahma Kumaris) have created this Harmony hall, & you are running centers to inspire positivism in people. You have been providing training of various types: even foreigners are taking share from that. Here they understood that it is first step of ladder of human welfare. It is a matter of great pleasure that our culture is being praised in other countries also. Organizations engaged in this noble task should be honored, they should be provided co-operation.

His Excellency Shri Atal Bihari Vajpayee, Former Prime Minister of India

4.18.6 To Promote International Understanding

I have been in touch with brahma Kumaris for a pretty long time. I feel that this organization is doing lot of solid work in promoting values & spirituality, which is dire need of hour. Their greatest contribution is to unify country despite its regional, linguistic & cultural disparities. Rather, it will be in fitness of things to say that they are trying their level best to promote international understanding. I wish them all success in this noble cause.

-His Excellency Shri H.D. Deve Gowda, Former Prime Minister of India

4.18.7 “One God One World Family”

Fig. No. 35:

Her Excellency Smt. Pratibha Devisingh Patil, Former President of India with Former Brahma Kumaris Administrative head Dadi Prakashmani
Brahma Kumaris organization has touched people from all cultures, castes & sections of society & united them into spiritual brotherhood. So, theme of Platinum Jubilee- “One God One World Family” – is apt. I congratulate Brahma Kumaris for being women-run organization, for service & sacrifice are natural to women just like trees bear fruits for others, rivers flow to give life to civilization & cows give milk to human beings. Human life is meant for rising above self-interests for service unto others.

- **Her Excellency Smt. Pratibha Devisingh Patil,
Former President of India**
While Inaugurating Global launching of Platinum Jubilee Celebrations

4.18.8 Spirituality provides power to eliminate ego

Mr. Lal Krishna Advani with Dadi Prakashmani

Fig. No. 36

Shri. Lal Krishna Advani, Former Deputy Prime Minister of India with Former Brahma Kumaris Administrative head Dadi Prakashmani

People from entire world come here (Mount abu). Judges, parliamentarians, bureaucrats, teachers, educationists, media persons & executives-all come here & participate in seminars & find that they could, perhaps, not make excellent arrangement they see. Management in real sense of term what is seen here in its practical form. Spirituality provides power to eliminate ego. It is written here, 'Ego's root cause of all sufferings. More we eliminate ego in self, to that extent our sufferings will decrease & society will also proper. Once telephone company of New York conducted survey to see which word is used maximum number of times by telephone users. They had thought that perhaps most used word would be "HELLO" but result of this survey showed that word was "I".

**-Shri. Lal Krishna Advani,
Former Deputy Prime Minister of India**

4.18.9 This place is like our home & people living here are god's blessed people

Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, the then President of India with Dadi Prakashmani

Fig. No. 37

Dr.A.P.J. Abdual Kalam, Former President of India with Dadi Prakashmani –Former Administrative head, Brahma kumaris

Today vision of Vedas ‘Vasudhaiv Kutumbakam’ has become reality not because of various philosophical paths of teachings, but because of teachings of Brahma Kumaris, which revolve around mutual brotherly love. Unless we have love for each other, how can you establish one united world? Keep always smiling. There is no ceiling limit for love. Draw & manifest powers within & bring about change in human system for better world. Whenever I leave Brahma Kumaris Headquarters after short stay here, I usually have feeling that I am leaving place where I should be as was stated by Dadi, this place is like our home & people living here are god’s blessed people”.

Bharat Ratna Dr.A.P.J. Abdual Kalam, Former President of India

4.18.10 Earthly Paradise

It is my view that closest thing perhaps that we have to earthly paradise is Brahma kumaris university in Mount Abu. It is Shangri-La, community of people who are dedicated to universal peace & harmony. There is so much good work being done in Mount Abu, including Global Hospital, where I was able to see firsthand that love is being practiced, not only preached. There are so many ways in Mount Abu of glorifying life & glorifying Godhead, Supreme being.

-His Excellency Mr.S.R. Insanally,

Former President of United Nations General Assembly (on 4th September 1994) during his visit to Brahma Kumaris Headquarters, Mt. Abu

4.18.11 Knowledge & science based on spiritual power will rule the world.

Mr. Rajiv Gandhi, the then Prime Minister of India with Dadi Prakashmani

Fig. No. 38

His Excellency Shri Rajiv Gandhi, Former Prime Minister of India with Dadi Prakashmani –Former Administrative head, Brahma kumaris

There is urgent need to give up narrow mentality & develop mutual goodwill & co-operation. This will provide new direction top world peace & development. If we cannot take human civilization to its zenith, we have to eradicate all sorts of discrimination. Efforts of Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya are highly commendable. Here two things have impressed me: Self transformation is pre- requisite for world transformation & there should be peace in mind. It is only peace in minds of lacs of people which will bring world peace. Knowledge & science based on spiritual power will rule world.

-His Excellency Shri Rajiv Gandhi, Former Prime Minister of India

4.18.12 Education

Education is foundation for successful life. Government of India has given more importance by enacting law that education is fundamental right.

*University & college teachers have major role in nation building.
Brahma Kumaris institution is focusing on empowering human life with values
& spiritual wisdom. Their academic programmes adopted in different
universities will make difference in learning & help in character building*

-His Excellency Smt. Margaret Alva, Former Governor of Rajasthan

4.18.13 Dedication & devotion

Mr. B.D. Jatti, the then President of India with Dadi Prakashmani

Fig. No. 39

**- His Excellency Shri B.D. Jatti, Former Vice-President of India with
Dadi Prakashmani –Former Administrative head, Brahma kumaris**

*I am indeed greatly honored to inaugurate Conference on 'Future of
Mankind' being held here in Vigyan Bhawan. I have been associated with
activities of Brahma Kumaris as Chief Minister of Karnataka, Lt. Governor of
Pondicherry & Governor of Orissa. I am deeply impressed by their socio-
spiritual activities & peace- making mission. Their dedication & devotion to
cause of spiritual & moral empowerment is worth emulating.*

-His Excellency Shri B.D. Jatti, Former Vice-President of India

4.18.14 To promote unity without breaking individual religious structures

Fig. No. 40

Shri Gyani Zail Singh, Former President of India with Dadi Prakashmani –Former Administrative head, Brahma kumaris

walls of religion divide men from each other, but I am happy to find that Brahma Kumaris are endeavoring to promote unity without breaking individual religious structures. Their method is spiritual teaching & pious thoughts created through yoga power. I consider it to be excellent method – simple formula to establish peace.

-His Excellency ShriGyani Zail Singh, Former President of India

4.18.15 Most capable institution

Man, has landed into lot of problems today through lack of balance. Just as when motorcar battery loses power, it needs re-charging, so we need charging of Soul. beauty of this place (Brahma Kumari complex) is to keep balances very much alive. This institution should take over responsibility of igniting light into teacher, igniting light into students & into community. If there is any place in world today & where spirituality is order, I think, it is this institution. Therefore, institution, of this type, this level, this position, is perhaps most capable institution to enthuse into community right thinking & right process of activity.

**-Honorable Justice Shri Ranganath Mishra,
Former Chief Justice of India**

4.18.16 Maha Vidyalaya, Super University Or divive university

It is unique Institution, institution of its own kind in world, & engaged in activities of its own kind, trying to educate people without awarding any degrees. It is institution which is not created by any act of parliament or legislature, yet, at is called University or Vishwa Vidyalaya. It should be called Maha Vishwa Vidyalaya, Super University or Divine University. I hope that this institution grows to be unique institution, one of its kind in world, to prove its value, position & stature. This is one institution, which has done something which others could not do.

Dr. Hari Gautam

Former Chairman, University Grants Commission, New Delhi

All—India Conference on Universal Values in Higher Education held at Mount Abu from October 14 to 16, 2001

4.18.17 Stress on Value education

I have been in touch with Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Vishwa Vidyalaya for past 11 years. In other Universities stress is on different subjects but here it is on value education. In other Universities, education is examination –oriented but here it is personality – oriented. There should be proper balance between material & spiritual development for sustainable growth.

Prof.V.N. Rajashekar Pillai

Former Vice Chairman, University Grants Commission, New Delhi

4.18.18 Wisdom to world

Generally, universities impart only material knowledge for purpose of employment & material progress. Here, Brahma Kumaris, who are already revealing effectiveness of this knowledge in their practical lives, are providing this wisdom to world. I am pleased & proud that you are empowering people with this knowledge & I am assuring that in this way, whole world will become paradise on earth

Prof. Dr.M. Ramanathan

Vice –Chancellor, Annamalai University, Tamil Nadu

4.18.19 This world better place to live in

I hope that human beings not only in India but also across globe will very soon adopt teachings of Shiv Baba through Brahma Kumaris to make this world better place to live in. I am, indeed, indebted to this organization for giving me

opportunity to express my views in various media seminars.

Shri. N.K. Singh
General secretary, Broad cast Editors Association of India, Delhi

4.18.20 Promoting lofty ideals of Country

I have been in close contact with Brahma Kumaris since long. This organization lays great stress on celibacy & spirituality, which is quite in tune with Indian culture. It is matter of great pleasure that Brahma Kumaris services are spread throughout world, promoting lofty ideals of country. I pray that this moral movement may gain momentum day by day.

Dr. Ved Pratap Dainik
Renowned thinker & journalist & Former Editors-PTI Bhasha

4.18.21 Ultimate Key is LOVE

UN diplomats should receive course in peace making & spiritual understanding before being allowed to enter diplomatic arena World leaders should formulate conscious forward looking strategy for peace as it cannot be our ultimate goal to destroy ourselves with nuclear weapons. We must have reverence & respect for life which is great miracle of this universe. Ultimate key is love – love for life, greatest gift. People have been bound together on national level by love for their countries. Now great new historical challenge is to develop love I strongly support efforts of Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University.

-Dr. Robert Muller,
Assistant Secretary General, United Nations

4.18.22 Firm Commitment for Universal Peace

I found many or all of objectives of Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University to be identical to objectives of United Nations. Thus, UN have given them consultative status on roster of its ECOSOC. Moreover, University is also member of Department of Public Information of UN as Non-Governmental Organization. I find it very comfortable working together with people from Brahma Kumaris Spiritual University, which has firm commitment for universal peace. Here are people who are convinced that peace will become reality. I have found profound feeling of contentment, peace, courtesy & friendliness here. If we could bring spirituality into our lives, we would be able to maintain

balance between scientific achievement & inner peace Dr. James O.C. Johan, Assistant Secretary General at United Nations, New York Continuing spate of crime, corruption, commercialism & lust for power had tarnished image of politics in India. It could be effectively countered by politicians with practice of India's ancient spiritual wisdom, eternal values & Raja yoga meditation as imparted by Brahma Kumaris institution through its centers all over India & abroad.

- Her Excellency Pratibha Devisingh Patil, Former Governor of Rajasthan.

4.18.23 Spiritual awareness & value based life style.

Holistic development was necessary for developing mutual understanding, respect, cooperation, peace & amity among people & it called for great deal of spiritual endeavour along with material development. Simple values like sweetness & compassion go long way to make lives of others better. I Commend efforts of Brahma Kumaris in spreading spiritual awareness & value based lifestyle in India & abroad, efforts of Brahma Kumaris would be great inspiration for promoting peace & spirituality.

-Smt. Shiela Dixit,
Former Chief Minister of Delhi & Former Governor of Kerala

4.18.24 Divine family.

I am very happy & honored to be part of this Brahma Kumaris divine family. As Muslim, I find there is nothing here against any religion. members of Brahma Kumaris Organization consider humanity as one family, which is what I have really experienced here. I am deeply touched by their warmth & by their extremely high stage of purity.

-Dr. Jehan El Sadat,
Wife of Late President Anwar Sadat of Egypt

4.18.25 Right organization

Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University is right organization to implement IYCP project as in past University has successfully coordinated Million Minutes of Peace Appeal & Global Co-operation for Better World.

-Mr. Cassam Uteem, President, Republic of Mauritius

4.18.26 Universal Peace Charter

There should be new way of looking at borders between nations. Instead of seeing border as line of division & confrontation between two states, it must be viewed as meeting point for welfare of two nations. Hence I propose Universal Peace Charter. In this context, I highly commend efforts of Brahma Kumaris.

H.E.Mr. Steve Naraine
Former Vice President of Guyana

4.18.27 Jewel on Globe

On behalf of people of Mauritius & in my own personal name, may I express my loving greetings to all of you & especially to Dadi Prakashmani, administrative head of Braha Kumaris World Spiritual University & to Dadi Janaki, addl. administrative head. We all agree today that Education should not be confined to four walls of class room of school. Hence, your open institution known as Braha Kumaris World Spiritual University is really jewel on globe.

Rt. Hon'ble Shri Anerood Jugnauth
Former Prime Minister of Mauritius

4.18.28 Peace Messenger

Prajapita Brahma kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya has important role in it on account of which it has been honored with Peace Messenger award. There is urgent need to constantly strive for bringing transformation in world. This day change is visible in every field — political, social or economic.

Mr. Vasily S. Safronchuk
Former Under Secretary General United Nations.

4.18.29 Spirituality- unifying principle of all religions

efforts of Prajapita Brahma kumari is Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya in field of world peace, universal brotherhood & unity of mankind are highly appreciable. Spirituality — Unifying Principle of All Religions.

Mr. Jeyraj Fernandopulle,
Minister for Plan Implementation & Parliamentary Affairs, Govt. of Sri Lanka

4.18.30 Spirituality- Worldwide movement

Bitter experiences in life led me to many situations. Thus, I reached this Vidyalaya, which transmits light to whole world from its Headquarters at Mount Abu. I used to visit every week Brahma Kumaris Centre at Delhi when I was in Supreme Court. Since this institution is instrumental for spiritual elevation I am attracted to it again & again. So, I used to visit Mount Abu at least once in two years or three years & spend their two or three days. As result of this I could enjoy spiritual peace. Now I am convinced, this is helpful for attainment of internal peace, which is distinct from mere utterance of 'OM SHANTI'. When I came closer to this movement many of its characteristics struck my heart. Mount Abu now represents worldwide movement. I have toured many countries. Wherever I went, I found Brahma Kumaris centers. Once I had been to Newziland & Australia, as directed by Maharshi Mahesh Yogi. In all these countries, I could witness presence of Brahma Kumaris centers. Two years back when I visited New Jersey in United States, I found out center of Brahma Kumaris with help of telephone directory.

-Justice V. R. Krishna lyre, Former Judge of Supreme Court of India

4.18.31 Endeavoring to re-build India & Rajasthan.

Today we see weaknesses all around society. At such crucial time, role of media persons in strengthening country is very important. Now is time to amend us. We can learn noble conduct from Brahmakumaris organisation. In pious environment of Shantivan here, one can create positive thoughts through Rajayoga. Brahmakumaris organization has been endeavoring to re-build India & Rajasthan. By establishing Global Hospital & Research Centre, they have contributed lot in field of social service.

—Sh. Chhoga Ram Bakolia,
Transport Minister, Rajasthan.
Conference of Rural Media persons held at Shantivan, Abu Road

4.18.32 Values & spirituality- way of life

Brahma kumaris have made values & spirituality their way of life. I feel need of such qualities not only in Indian Political System but in other spheres of life as well.

—Shri.Ramdas Agarwal,
Member of Parliament, Jaipur, Rajasthan.

4.18.33 **Spiritual light house for whole world**

It was very good to visit Brahma Kumaris institution & experience peace & happiness across campus. I hope that this institution will lead in building of National Character & Spiritualism. This institution is just like Spiritual Light House for whole world.

—**Shri.Arjun Ram Meghwal, IAS(Retd.)**
Member of Parliament, Bikaner, Rajasthan.

4.18.34 **Spiritual bridge between man & God**

After seeing exceptionally soothing atmosphere of spirituality on Brahma kumariscampus, I regret that I could not come here earlier. People have time for doing anything under sun but no time for turning to God. Brahma kumaris need to be thanked for their role in building spiritual bridge between man & God. Their aim is to inculcate deity- like qualities among human beings, so that they can become angels of peace, purity, love & happiness.

-Dr. Jaya Prada
Former Member of Lok sabha, Uttar Pradesh
Bollywood actress, Director & Producer.

4.18.35 **‘Om shanti’ mantra can defuse even most powerful nuclear bomb.**

To be very frank, I initially evaded Brahma Kumaris, for I did not know anything about them & that was very long ago. But as soon as I learnt what they were working for, I felt enamored of them. Today, I find lot of stress, violence & fear in world. But, I feel that their spiritual smiles can dispel gloom & their ‘Om shanti’ mantra can defuse even most powerful nuclear bomb.

-Swamy Chakrapani
President, Hindu Mahasabha, Delhi

4.18.36 **Worthy of appreciation.**

efforts of organization of Brahma Kumaris in encouraging deliberations on role for values in bringing about peace & development in world is worthy of appreciation. I have no hesitation in calling upon men & especially women to bear mantle of value based communication & cause world to develop global village where purity of thought brings “constant & true peace & happiness.”

-Justice G.N. Ray
Former Chairman, Press Council of India

4.18.37 Remember one Incorporeal God, Shiva.

There is no other organization like Brahma kumaris & they have enlightened people all over world with their simple spiritual approach. They remember one Incorporeal God, shiva. I participate in programmer of Brahma Kumaris whenever I am in India. They have beautiful greeting 'Om Shanthi' which helps us to have awareness of our original peaceful nature.

-Shri Bappi Lahiri
Famous Singer, Mumbai

4.18.38 Teaching world art & science of purposeful living

I have very much liked Brahma Kumaris Platinum Jubilee theme, viz., One God, One World Family. It transcends all divisions of caste, color, creed, religion & even nationalities; it corresponds to law of universe, which is perfect unity & harmony. Wherever you go, Brahma Kumaris organization is respected & admired for its total dedication to spiritual uplift of humankind. It is teaching world art & science of purposeful living

Padmashri D.R. Karthikeyan
Advisor, Law- Human Rights Corporate affairs &
Former Director, CBI

4.19 AWARDS

International Peace Messenger Award presented Dadi Prakashmani by UN Secretary General

Fig. No. 41: International Peace Messenger Award presented to Dadi Prakashmani, Former Administrative Head of Bks by former Un Secretary General Javier Perez De Cuellar during 1987

- ✓ Received 7 UN Peace Messenger Awards for its work in promoting peace during international Year of Peace, 1987.

late Dr. M.Channa Reddy, the then Governor of Rajasthan honouring by
Doctorate Degree to Dadi Prakashmani

Fig. No. 42:

-Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur, Rajasthan, honoured Doctorate Degree (D.Litt.) to Raja yogini B.K. Dadi Prakashmani, Former Administrative Head of Brahma Kumaris from Late Dr.M. Chenna Reddy, Former Governor of Rajasthan.

- ✓ Brahmakumaris chief “**Dr.Dadi Janaki**” being conferred “**Bharat Gaurav Award**” at House of Commons, London on Wednesday 23rd July2014 in presence of Dignitaries from all over the world.
- ✓ His majesty King Abdullah bestows the **Independent Medal of the First order** on Indian Spiritual leader and activist **Dadi Janaki** on Monday 31st may 2014. Dadi Janaki was honored in recognition of her efforts to promote understanding and dialogue among cultures and religions as well as her Endeavour in social development and health affairs- Jordan Times (Amman)Tuesday ,1 June 2014 .
- ✓ RajYogi B.K.Karunaji, Vice Chairperson, Media Wing ,PRO and Multimedia Chief of Brahma Kumaris was awarded with the prestigious “ **PRCI Hall Of Fame 2010**” by Public Relations Council Of India (PRCI) on 3rd Apr 2010 at the 4th Global meet, New Delhi, India.

- ✓ RajYogi B.K.Mruthyunjaya, Executive Secretary & Vice Chairperson, Education Wing of Brahma Kumaris was conferred with the coveted “ **Hall Of Fame Award**” an ultimate award for PR professionals, instituted by Public Relations Council Of India at the 7th Global Communication Conclave at Hyderabad, India
- ✓ On the occasion of UN day, “Media for spirituality”- an international media award has been awarded to B.K.Om Prakash, Chairperson, Media wing, by the institutions affiliated to UN namely International association of educators for world peace (USA) and Common wealth association and training for adults(UK) at Ghandhinagar on 24th Oct2004

4.20 Three Worlds

As well as the mind and character of God, during meditation BKs also commonly focus on the place where the Supreme Soul resides. The ‘home’ of all souls, including the Supreme Soul, is the Soul World or Paramdhām. It is also known as Nirvāna, Moolvātan, and Brahmānd and refers to the place of essence, meaning and life, beyond that which is inert and beyond the physical world. BKs understand there are three realms, worlds or regions. Ascending from the grossest to the most refined, they are the Physical World (Stoolvātan or the land of inertia), Subtle Regions (Sookshmavātan or the land of refined forms of energy, such as thought and vibration) and Soul World (Moolvātan or the land of absolute essence).

At the bottom of Figure 2.1 is the obvious and tangible Physical World made up of matter, the earth and its galaxies. Everything is experienced through the five senses of taste, touch, sound, smell, and sight. In murlis it is described as the world of ‘talkie’.

The Subtle Regions represented above as a layer of white light, is created and sustained on the basis of pure thought and is the home of visionary experience, trance and creative meditation. BKs who have experienced the Subtle Regions explain that its defining characteristic is a warm, nurturing and gentle white light, with a profound feeling of comfort and belonging. The Subtle Regions is a silent but visual world, where communication is primarily through thought and secondarily through movement. It is the world of ‘movie’.

The Soul World is the original home of all souls and the eternal home of the Supreme Soul. It is soundless, beyond thought; it is the land of absolute essence. It is described

as a land of warm golden red light. When souls reside in the Soul World, they are in ‘seed’ form, in a state of deep peace, beyond experience. The most accurate description is that souls are in a dreamless sleep. BKs say the deepest sense of peace is achieved through focusing on the Supreme Soul, in the Soul World. BKs believe the mind can travel through thought. The object of the mind’s focus shapes directs the experience of meditation, as does the kind of thought and intent behind the thought. During meditation, BKs practice ‘going’ to the Soul World and the Subtle Regions as the focus of their attention. BKs think of the Soul World as their metaphysical home.

4.20.1 Spiritual deprivation, environmental demise

The early members of the Yagya lived simply, using little and recycling everything – even making shoes out of old car tires when resources were scarce – but it was imminent destruction that was in the forefront of their minds, not managing climate change or having a small carbon footprint. The founder’s mystical experiences, retold, are part of the foundation theology of the organization and BKs’ tension is mirrored in this origin theology. How does one practically reconcile the understanding of cataclysmic world destruction- no matter how many steps towards environmental responsibility are taken – with the desire for peace in the world, environmental care and a genuine wish to prevent suffering? It is discussed as follows:

BKs understand that what or how one thinks forms the foundation of character, behaviour and so life itself. The soul performs actions through the medium of the physical body, on the basis of the cyclical interplay of the mind, intellect and Sanskāras, as every action performed through the body gives rise to a correspondingly positive or negative reaction. Thus the condition of the world around us is a reflection not just of the quality of our actions but the quality of our internal spiritual state. Every human action has an effect upon matter, and no one is immune to the effects or consequences of her or his actions.

For BKs, meditation slows down the mind and refines the intellect, so that one is not so compelled to act on the basis of one’s habits or attitudes that might be rooted in selfish personality traits. BK philosophy maintains that forgetting the essential truth of souls’ immortality, and ensuing greed and selfishness, has ultimately led to environmental degradation

Fig. No. 43: Relationship amongst self & environment

For BKs, the material world is intimately linked to the inner world of awareness, attitude, thoughts and feelings, with the self being the starting point, as shown in Figure 43 above. BKs reiterate that the foundation of any visible and lasting change calls for deliberate introspection because consciousness, action and the environment are inherently connected, and the relationships between them are responsible for the ways that attitudes are exhibited. The first relationship with the environment is the way in which the mind directs the soul's activities through the body. BKs say that although in a human being it is the soul that holds the greatest value, it is the body that is the chariot or the temple for the soul, it and so must be treated with regard. Therefore, how the soul performs mundane activities through the body, such as eating, drinking and bathing, is the first point of interaction with the world's natural resources. What the soul then does through the body during the day directly shapes and impacts upon social relationships.

Relationships are the construct of society and, broadly and collectively, BKs believe that each one's actions influence those around them, bringing gradual and broad social changes in the most commonplace ways, reflected in historical change. UNBKs are concerned that, without addressing the subtle inner awareness that informs the outer states, the world's decision makers will attempt to reduce and simplify the problem, apportioning blame unnecessarily, only serving to create more division, without any hope of lasting environmental change. The most powerful entry point to changing one's relationship with the world, BKs attest, is changing one's attitude. Thought is its foundation and, to empower the mind, meditation is a potent tool.

As a spiritual service organization, it brings out the truth that an individual has a body with a spirit. The spirit wears the body. The spirit is the real person. Spirituality is to have a lot of spirit in the spirit. The spirit should manifest in terms of enthusiasm, zeal, creativity, enterprising nature and peace. Spirituality is goodness within and without. The goodness should manifest in terms of compassion, sympathy, kindness, fairness, love, cooperation, humility, tolerance, empathy, sacrifice and service. The true consciousness is awakened to understand and experience that one is a spirit – the soul. Humanness is the maturity of soul consciousness. The universal

value of brotherhood is properly understood and practiced in daily life. The spiritual education focuses on meditation to empower oneself to perform practically what one preaches in life. God, the supreme is the fountain head of all goodness. Loveful mental and emotional feelings for the Supreme bring about spiritual growth in individuals.

4.21 Spiritual purity

BKs feel that they must help themselves and others to deal with approaching disaster and suffering foremost through maintaining a state of spiritual purity, which will convey a state of peace and strength to others around them and the world in general. Depending on the level of one's transformation, one can also be a resource to others during disasters .”if within yourself you havemade yourself ever- ready , then through your own readiness... all souls can be benefited” (Lawrence 1996:18)

The Brahma Kumaris therefore brings complexity back into discussions of world issues. Issues of climate change, the BKs argue, must be resolved holistically. While doing good and taking care of the environment physically, the Brahma Kumaris philosophy values the inner world, and does not give particular significance to making decisions solely based on physical proof or scientific evidence.

The Brahma Kumaris does not see its millenarian beliefs and its concerns about global warming as incompatible or illogical. BKs recognize this period of time to be one of great possibility. Consciousness and attitude are the seeds of the actions that created the world of paucity, inequity and degradation in which we now live. The actions taken yesterday have created the world we live in today. Similarly, the actions taken today write the script for the circumstances of tomorrow. . When this is understood, one becomes aware that we, as a global population, and I as an individual within that population, contribute to and are responsible for the state of today's world. Considering the above principle, BKs maintain that each individual, as well as collectives such as governments and multilateral agencies like the UN can act with care and regard in consideration of the environmental paucity that is the cause of increasing natural disaster and suffering.

Those in positions of leadership rely on teams of advisors for their decision making. With financial , scientific , social, and political advisors , one has to to ask how often the spiritual advisor is consulted. When – if ever – is the spiritual perspective taken into account as one of the areas of understanding necessary for a holistic

perspective? Instead of regretting the past, this is a call to action for the present; BKs offer the idea that a spiritual perspective provides a balance between accepting responsibility for the past and acting with care and regard for the environment from now on. The declaration from the UN NGO/DPI Conference was one in which NGOs committed themselves to developing a framework to be implemented over the ensuing 12 months. It included both individual and collective action plans to tackle issues of climate change. NGOs also reiterated their pledge to be active partners of the UN, local governments and civil society, to implement adaptation and mitigation strategies. The Conference Declaration was subsequently presented to the Secretary- general .

Since this conference, the Brahma Kumaris has undertaken physical and spiritual actions towards taking care of the environment. Possibly the largest solar energy construction in the world was recently completed in Rajasthan, India. This natural energy will support an entire village in Talheti, home to more than 20,000 people. An increasing number of Brahma Kumaris centres are installing solar energy and tanks, according to their capacity and resources. Retreat centres worldwide have adopted green policies, including recycling and reusing materials where possible and establishing organic gardens. The Brahma Kumaris Environment Initiative 2009 was recently established, will be presented at the Climate Change Conference in Copenhagen, December 2009, and aims to be implemented across the global Brahma Kumaris community. Meditation also continues at Brahma Kumaris centres around the world, with special sessions for recent events precipitated by climate change, like the 2009 bush fires in Australia, floods in India (2008) and earthquake in Italy (2009).

The World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the need for greater psychological care post – disaster (Gist 1999: Roberts and Ashley 2008), and in Australia, spiritually sensitive social care is now being integrated in the curriculum of high level disaster training (Gray 2008; Spencer and Archer 2008) and forms part of the government’s response to disaster (EMA 2002). However, little is mentioned about creating faith – based resilience in communities prior to disaster. BKs indicate three forms of understanding that contributed in their ability to moderate their experience of the Super Cyclone: a belief that they have a capacity to serve themselves and others through the mind; a tendency to find purpose

and meaning in life's difficulties through their theology; and the practice of meditation that offers BKs a sense of transcendency that can lift them out of the tragedy of the moment. Just as one stockpiles utensils and food, and rehearses behaviour appropriate to safety and physical resilience in disaster, BKs stockpile the practice of meditation and positive thinking, coupled with thoughtful good action, as a method to develop inner endurance.

4.22 Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation(BKRM)

A BK is considered to be someone who has accepted the Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga philosophy and lives by its principles. BK members identify themselves as students, and the path of Raja Yoga as a study. This orientation allows BKs to maintain an evaluative and non-devotional attitude to their spiritual pursuits, although the Dadis discourage 'too much thinking'. Informally BKs refer to each other as Brahmins or Raja Yogis although the latter term was more common twenty years ago. Male BKs are *kumārs* (lit: unmarried son), brothers or brahma kumars, and female BKs are *kumārīs* (lit: unmarried daughter), sisters, or brahma kumaris. In Hindi the term *kanyā kumāri* or just *kumāri* can mean virgin and unmarried interchangeably. In countries outside of India the two are not synonymous. However this is not addressed explicitly, and unmarried foreign BKs are still referred to by these terms, regardless of prior experience.

BKs adopt a lifestyle code they define as *maryādapurushottam*, a term used by adherents of both Hindu and Sikh faiths, and one with complex meaning. The term refers to the code of life, the boundaries, or adherence to principles that one follows to become the highest and most divine amongst humans. The rules of behaviour dictate all forms of physical conduct and social expression, so that BKs are taught to live a virtuous mon- like existence while remaining present in the world (Walsh, Ramsay, and Smith 2007).

The confusion that follows disaster can threaten identity and rapidly undo people's sense of who they are and where they belong. The destruction of the Twin Towers of the World Trade Centre in New York on 11 September 2001 was one event that precipitated self examination once the immediacy of the disaster had passed. In this chapter, I explore how BKs, based in centres in New York, apply spiritual knowledge to understand suffering. Drawing on primary Brahma Kumaris texts and ethnographic data from field research conducted in 2007, illustrate how the

spiritual knowledge and practices of BKs uniquely shape their perspective on catastrophic events.

Disasters are usually experienced as abrupt singular events. However, anthropologists and other social scientists have unveiled many of the hidden systems of disaster (Hoffman 2005; Oliver Smith 1999c; Quarantelli 1989) as well as their psychological processes (Wallace 1956). Disaster does not happen without cause, but rather, as a progressive phenomenon involving social structures and political, environmental and economic decisions that are embedded in communities over time. Disasters undermine people's sense of stability and certainty, and the rightness and perceived predictability of life. Manifesting through abrupt changes in the physical environment and the social world, people are stripped of their access to material goods and to familiar personal ties, and the usual ebb and flow of everyday life is dramatically disrupted. Some populations are uniquely vulnerable to disaster because of geographic, economic or historical factors, but no-one, including members of affluent middle class populations, is exempt. The geography of Manhattan Island, with its limited escape routes and high population density, is an example of this, as one research participant reflected: "There was nowhere to go, you couldn't get off the island."

The presented thesis intends to explore the key motivations of the Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris and hence it is of great significance to study and analyse the key concept of meditation and its significances. In the following section, the basic of meditation and its significances etc have been discussed..

4.22.1 Meditation

Meditation is one of the greatest arts in life. Yoga is honoured as an ancient heritage and culture of India. It is regarded as one of most extraordinary powers, gifted with wisdom, through which one gets freedom from evil. In the Gita's verse below, Karma Yoga is described as the art of balancing of mind, being even-minded while facing both bad and good results in one's life. A journey into the world of meditations is required to achieve the purpose of establishing the role of meditation and values for a better world. The researcher has used the word meditation in connection with yoga and will further attempt to develop with a universal concept of meditation in this study. There is a deep and practical meaning of "Meditation" that can be understood from various philosophical and literacy angles. Some of the key definitions are

presented here-

The Integral Yoga of Shri Aurobindo explains:

- What then is Yoga? The etymological sense of the word is union Yoke (Dutch Juk, German jock, Latin jugum, Sanskrit Yug). It means the linking or union of the human consciousness with something higher, something transcendent, and something eternal and divine. Yoga is movement of the human consciousness to contact the Infinite by self transcendence; it is a direct leap or a headlong plunge into the Eternal.
- Anthony Strano in Brahma Kumaris book Eastern Thought for Western mind replicates the insight of word Meditation. Meditation repairs the inner wounds of the spirit and restores the health of the soul, the Latin word reflects:
- The word 'meditation' comes from the latin word 'meditari' which is a probable cognate of the word 'mederi' meaning 'to heal'. Journeying inside, discovering the inner self and our true power is the beginning of the healing process, in which we are able to put back all the broken pieces with a lot of love.

Meditation is the process of getting to know yourself completely, both who you are inside and how you react to what is outside. Above all, meditation is enjoying yourself in the literal sense of the word. Through meditation, we discover a very different 'me' from perhaps the stressed or troubled person, who may seem superficially to be 'me'. You realize that your true nature, the real you, is actually very positive.

By contemplating deeply on the various meanings and definitions of "meditation" given from different perspectives by the many great spiritual leaders or philosopher and religious founders, we can find it beautiful synthesis of thoughts about Yoga. The words may differ but the essence and meaning is more or less similar. Yoga is the greatest spiritual power that helps to maintain equilibrium in the midst of great challenges and obstacles. All these spiritual leaders and thinkers pointed out specifically that "Yoga" means the linking or union of the soul with the divine.

The religions and spiritual history of the human world is a testimony to our faith and efforts to know God. The great scriptures of the world, based on prophetic utterances, are definitely filled with great philosophy and knowledge. However despite all this knowledge we have accumulated over the ages, we continue to degrade ourselves morally and spiritually. Meditation is the process whereby we gain control over the

mind and guide it in a more virtuous direction. Meditation may be thought of as a technique by which we diminish the force of old thought habits and develop new ones. We thereby protect ourselves from engaging in actions of mind, word, or deed that lead to our suffering. Such meditation is to be used extensively in our spiritual practice.

Bhakti yoga means complete devotion and total surrender to God. It is the faithful devotion of heart and mind.

Patanjali Yoga also explains essential parts of Raja yoga needed to attain effective results. The Brahma Kumaris also cover a few of these aspects and if one keeps focused on these, “Raj Yoga” should not be difficult to practice:

Raja Yoga, as expounded by Patanjali, is also known as the Yoga of eight limbs, for it has eight essential parts, depicted as follows:

- (1) *Abstention from evils (yam)*
- (2) *Various Observances (Niyamas)*
- (3) *Physical Postures*
- (4) *Breath Control*
- (5) *Withdrawal*
- (6) *Concentration*
- (7) *Contemplation and*
- (8) *Absorption or Samadhi.*

Patanjali says that these eight will enable the soul to stabilize in the self and will, ultimately, lead the soul to Absolution. Talking about postures, Patanjali has not asked to practice any particular posture which people practice today but has said that one may sit in any posture in which one feels relaxed and comfortable. Similarly, about breath control, he has said that it should come easy.

As compared to this, the Raja Yoga taught by Shiva, the Lord of Yogis, lays stress on the six, leaving the two – Asana and Pranayama and such other things for He says that when the soul withdraws from the body and concentrates on God and gets stabilized in the Samadhi, one’s posture will, automatically, become stable and the breathing will be as it should be.

Sri Aurobindo, a great yogi and eminent scholar in India, presented a very bold and courageous assertion of “The synthesis of Yoga”. In *The Hour of God*, he has remarkably presented “The entire purpose of Yoga” in “Purna Yoga”. By Yoga we

can rise out of falsehood into truth, out of weakness into force, out of pain and grief into bliss, out of bondage into freedom, out of death into immortality, out of darkness into light, out of confusion into purity, out of imperfection into perfection, out of self-division into unity and out of Maya into God. All other utilization of Yoga is for special and fragmentary advantages not always worth pursuing. Only that which aims at possessing the fullness of God is Purna Yoga; the sadhaka of the Divine perfection is the Purna Yogin.

Using the above invaluable components of Yoga, as presented in the Gita, by Sri Aurobindo and others, on the subject of Yoga in the past, solid sound ground has been created to understand the present contribution of Brahma Kumaris yoga practices for a better world. This chapter is aimed at describing the significant role of the Brahma Kumaris literature and meditation practices as the basis for creating a value-based better society. It has been mentioned that through Yoga, human beings can rise out of falsehood, weakness, pain, grief, bondage, darkness and confusion towards the path of truth, bliss, freedom, immortality, light and purity. It also describes the power of Yoga in that a Karma Yogi is deemed superior to those of austerity (tapasya), and superior to even those of knowledge; the karma yogi is also superior to those of action; therefore be thou a yogi..

4.23 Stages of RAJA Yoga Meditation

Meditation is a progressive discipline. Its four stages are a way to develop our abilities systematically. Do not try to go too far too fast. The idea is to spend time with each stage so that we understand it well before moving on to the next. People must not be worried if it takes you several sessions of meditation to get accustomed to the practice..

4.23.1 Initiation – Self Awareness

Let us start our journey with initiation, preparing our mind for the maximum benefits in yoga. The first step in meditation is inner most journeys. At first we will probably that our mind wanders and that we are unable to remain in concentration. This requires that we create a stillness and peace within by detaching as far as possible from the conditioning of our personality. We need to step back from outer self to listen to inner self. Such attentive awareness enables the mind to create concentrated and pure thoughts. "As Einstein said, I firmly believe, as the ancients believed, that the pure thought can grasp reality".

This is the stage in which we try to remain in soul consciousness by, repeatedly turning the mind within and training it to become detached from external influences. Initial stage is called "turning" the mind from ordinary and waste thoughts to positive thoughts. It is the nature of the mind to produce thoughts continuously. The studies shows interesting facts that human mind has capacity to create more than 14 thousand thoughts in one day. The human mind is sensitive and influenced by sense perceptions and memories of past incidents. As "Rajyoga" is awakening from external material world to thoughtful observing the internal state of mind. As defined in the Murli "Initiation" is the first stage of "Milan" in which the soul gets clean and beautiful before meeting God. Swami Vivekananda has also observe the first step in meditation means observing the internal states "The science of Raja Yoga, in the first place, proposes to give as such a means of observing the internal states. The instrument is the mind itself. The power of attention, when properly guided, and directed towards the internal world, will analyse the mind, and illumine facts for us"

The Brahma Kumaris' "Rajyoga" practice in the initial stage of "preparation of the mind" replacing negative to pure thoughts by introducing "Rajyoga" commentary. These thoughts for meditation in "Rajyoga" commentaries are words that are softly and sweetly spoken by the "Rajyogi" expert teachers to support the new meditators at an initial stage. These practical guided meditation exercises direct the beginner very effectively, as these words lead to help in systematic progress. The Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga meditation played an outstanding role in meditation practice by introducing the "Guided Meditation Commentary" as a novel step in understanding the different stages of meditation. With soft background music at the time of guided meditation, the soul is filled with inner joy. Here is an example of the process:

Sitting comfortable, I take a few deep breaths to allow my body to be energized, and at the same time become cool and calm.... I feel my body settling down.... I become aware of the muscles in my feet, in my legs, my back, my shoulders... Keeping my back upright, to stay alert, I let go of the tension, have been holding, and feel it dissolve.... with my eyes open, gently ahead, alert but no staring, I come to the forehead....my thoughts focus here....I can feel light radiating from a source, a spark of life at the centre of the forehead... this is I, the eternal soul, the origin of awareness in this physical body.... I am a soul, not the body...but this body is a wonderful vehicle, which I hold in trust....in this awareness of the soul, looking inwards, within this spark of

light, I realise that other beings are also souls, being of peace. Iam
..PeaceLove.....Bliss.

Going deep inside, my thoughts slow down and I focus on the point of peace..... as my mind becomes calm and peaceful I am able to connect with the supreme, the Being of Light.....and God's light and love come shining through.

4.23.2 Contemplation

Contemplation means the channeling of thoughts in the direction of God. This is the stage defined in the Murli' as "Vernan", when the self in soul consciousness it can be connected with God and start revealing the qualities of God.

Mind starts to make the connection with the Supreme, and begins to feel a flow of positive energy.... reflecting on the different relationships between the soul and the supreme, and on God's qualities and roles... Contemplation does not require rehearsal of a litany of ideas rather, it's giving my mind a specific task within whatever time I have allotted for meditation. For example I may decide I am going to think about God as the being of truth, and let my mind, explore the truth within God, and the truth God shares. As I do so I'll begin to savor the contentment truth being.

Gently from inward journeys the self' start turning towards God. At first it may be hard to focus on such thoughts that we are peaceful souls, a point of light, eternal. The positive visualization of soul and thinking of original qualities — 'I am at peace with myself, at peace with others, at peace with the world and at peace with God.' God is eternally the unlimited ocean of virtues: God gives without any desire or expectation of return. This means he is totally benevolent. Baba is a sweet and familiar name for 'Father', thus Shiva Baba is the benevolent Father of souls. This contemplation of thoughts in guided commentary below is reflection of true heart conversation with Divine, the soul bows down with gratitude to Almighty, states the higher union, as stated in the Brahma Kumaris' literature:

Wendy Sargent in her book *Creative Raja yogahas* given a touch of Poetry to the Murli words:

In the deep silence in which there is communication with God we can lose ourselves in the Ocean of Peace. We take power, which enables us to maintain a peaceful stage while working in our daily life. The close relationship of Supreme is also stated as the Mother, the Friend and the Beloved in the Murlis. Sri Aurobindo also claims that God

is blissful and surrounds with Ananda. Infinite is all beautiful and All beloved. 'A Bliss surrounds with ecstasy everlasting, an absolute high-seated immortal rapture Possesses, healing love to oneness

4.23.3 Concentration

With sweet centrality of trade. Right when identity separates on properties of God's truth. It may satisfy brought time of center up in framework. Here there is taste of back stillness & calm, as various contemplations obscure away. In this stage soul, can sway into & perceives unadulterated experience that contemplations in past position have made. examinations lead to experience. In Murli this stage is portrayed as "Lagan" which instigates warmly offering our slant to God. Center is possible when we give genuinely our suppositions to God. "Cerebrum is sponsorship off, & working in one heading, towards being of truth that we call God...sit in examination & in glimmer fly into joy of this experience, without mediating strides.

In this mind-blowing relationship, we come closer to God. We change our supposition 'God Almighty up there' & we, lowlife, down here" We feel "God loving" instead of "God fearing". In flight of basic thoughts & more immense experience of God, love delicately stream in, 'redirections have no hold & relationship with Divine stays consistent. With particular last objective to keep this Divine affiliation unending, Murli clears up that we ought to examine most raised fortune of life that is wealth of considerations. From each & every unmistakable point of view, nature of thoughts recognizes colossal part in all seasons of "reflection", diverse center individuals have one sales: Why wouldn't i be able to have lifted stage relationship in reflection? Avyakt Murli 25/3/95 illuminates root issue:

fortune of recognized is gigantically powerful.... whatever stage you wish to get whether it is raised, whether it is of pleasure, or of waste or inadequacy, with one deferral's "I am lifted soul", you will have raised stage & lifted experience minute you have thought, I am fragile soul, "I don't have any impact", then with considered one & second, your happiness vanishes. You will experience signs of disadvantage in your stage. Notwithstanding, reason of both these stages in your bits of information when you sit in insistence, you make your stage on reason of your thoughts. "I am point". By what means may you have ability to have can you make this stage? With your contemplations: "I am regarded movement singular" So how successful considerations are! Notwithstanding, what is result when you misuse your fortune of examinations? You are not set up to make sort out that you require. in like

manner, each one of you understand that waste examinations disable your judgment & your stage.

In Brahma Kumaris content there is summon to focus on different times of Yoga & moreover winds on element issue of standard person that waste encounters make redirection in correspondence with God. Every single Murli clears up how misuse considerations can be controlled. "Waste examinations" are strategy of chitta (mind). Creation of waste bits of learning does not allow "union of cerebrum". It is eye to eye trade with God. It is mind to cerebrum, heart to heart exchange with God. "Raj Yogi" their look, in regular philosophy for "Flawless motivation driving light" & Stan feeling divine light of enjoyment & satisfaction applying, showering on soul. Ken O' Donnel gifts being in general sense lost in this adjacent meeting with God, in verse he goes on:

- *Face to go up against,*
- *meeting place*
- *In inside being's.*
- *Heart to heart,*
- *You fill my part*
- *To most tremendous high*
- *Impressions for perpetually, my affection.*
- *Recorded for all history, my Love.*
- *I couldn't think you'd come to me so in general sense*
- *And treat me to sweetness of your words.*
- *Mind to mind,*
- *You clear line*
- *To your fortune store.*
- *You & I comprehended in thought*
- *Forever more,*
- *Sealed to Truth interminably, my Love.*
- *Living by day's end in Light, my Love.*
- *I couldn't think You'd come to me so basically*
- *And treat me to offer of your words*

4.23.4 Realization & Anubhuti

Confirmation indicates "Anubhuti" moved time of impeccability prompts last time of certification in which we are completely compensated for lost time in Godly happiness. Human soul relates.

This is start of fourth stage, that of confirmation of truth. Every one's ability & capacity to experience this stage is captivating, & it happens in various courses for various people.

Confirmation or Anubhuti is most lifted kind of phenomenal observation. It is condition of being completely mindful of self & God as Supreme Soul. Clarification of experience is hard to express in words. These are scraps of perfect blessing, when experience expansions to super care; God's qualities are our qualities. It is seen:

With brain concentrated on God, flame of Yoga fumes at full burst cleaning soul & dissolving without end amalgam of negative sanskars, past sins are blasted & soul recoups its unique properties of flawlessness, peace, force may, affection & delight.

insistence joins into soul & takes position there for untouched. As we drive, attestation proceeded with & soul experiences true blue changes. It is to incredible degree inconspicuous technique which keeps managing our life. Swami Vivekananda has depicted that through fulfillment of "Samadhi" chose results can be capable "Every one of sets out to perform Samadhi has been contemplated out, appropriately balanced, cleverly managed, & when reliably honed, will clearly lead us to longed for end. By then will all surprises stop, all destructions vanish.

Incomprehensible Yoga power Vyasa in his discussion on Yoga sutra, highlighted on arrangement of Samadhi:

Yoga is Samadhi. Word Samadhi really signifies "setting, gathering." What is "set up together" or "bound together" is conclusion self or subject self or subject near to question of examination. Samadhi is both practice & strategy of unification of care & occurrence condition of "union" with saw object.

This time of immaculate enjoyment, insistence or Samadhi is master just by few amongst thousands who battle for perfection; one perchance knows God if all else fails. As God, himself is announcing last clarification "Vedic presentation, Thou craftsmanship that 'and not of 'That". This information is, in like way, rather fractional. Regardless, when one gets full learning of Supreme Lord, Ishwara, "That" of Vedic affirmation, then one's information is flawless, & such individual is most regarded of Yogis.

"Methodology for information & assertion" (Vijnana – Yoga) states:

Among considerable number of men one perchance battles for flawlessness; even amongst those that battle (one perchance finds opportunity to be perfect), & even amongst those that are faultless, one perchance knows Me honestly.

It is most sure that most huge picture we hold in our mind, single thought on which our whole impression of otherworldly truth is gathered including point of view of our own self, is our experience of God. Much same as our impression of his personality, so is viewpoint we get handle on towards life & qualities that guide our activities. As it is cleared up in Gita among gigantic number of men who battle for flawlessness, one perchance knows him if all else fails. Sakar Murli & Avyakr Murli' besides confers Gods words "Basically couple of striking ones know Me. Out of your young people additionally just few know Me precisely, As I am. So, mix of these four times of "Raj yoga" (1) Initiation (Milan) (2) Contemplation (Vernan) (3) Concentration (Lagan) (4) Realization (Magan) deliberately prompts best postponed result of "Rajayoga".

4.23.5 Transformation

Self-change prompts world change is catchphrase in Brahma Kumaris making & practices. Self-change has critical centrality. Examination derives changing course of our thoughts. It induces that change happens when we have "Way of life" or "System for living" in significant sentiment being. It doesn't recommend that binding ourselves from our duties or nonappearance of engagement in customary existence except for reflection is craft of positive sense & positive living. Brahma Kumaris World intense school has acquired element transformative results lives of individuals. East or West around world, there are such arrangement of living balanced occurrence of individuals, those have changed & changed themselves with force of most critical sentiment being & examination. It is enamoring to investigate that level of advancement can vary from individual to individual. As utilization of qualities & significant sentiment being vacillate starting with one individual then onto accompanying individual, inconceivability of in all actuality change can be one percent or fifty percent in their lives, yet change can't be measured by any physical instruments. Contemplations, suspicions, expressions, words & activities talk themselves of their record of advancement. Recalling last goal to exhibit productive affirmation of reality, she herself met different identities who have gone to Brahma Kumaris World uncommon school at Mount Abu for clarification behind reflection rehearse & critical strengthening. Analyst amidst "Veritable serenity" retreat

program on 10/10/09 bantered with few of across board pros & discovered drawing in changes in their viewpoints & lives concerning indicated research recommendation.

Mrs. Rita from Portugal shares her encounters:

I am here in Mount Abu in "Genuine notions of quietness" retreat from most recent seven days & I had huge riddle to share. From my young age, I all things considered had long for marriage with God. Regardless when I came here to open my brainto clean my cerebrum. Such sweeping number of things I have encountered amidst these seven days in thought. One ismy kinship to God in thought opened & cleaned my psyche; stores of good things appeared to me.... My fantasy persuaded chance to be reality.

Mrs. Great emissaries from Austria bestowed her huge estimations:

In Brahma Kumaris examination I felt conclusion bliss, peace & satisfaction. I have noteworthy contact with sea of love.... Peace.... that experience has touched my complete self. I am feeling changed. In matter of seconds my experience is more imperative & critical I am recuperating assessment gratefulness, experience of affection from Brahma Kumaris family.

Brahma Kumaris writing in kind of books, articles & genuine stories have likewise expected colossal part in upgrade of lives of couple. One of most critical envisioned by Brahma Kumaris exceptional structures "Divine Murli", has been altogether changed contemplations, words & activities of different souls.

4.24 Turning Qualities into Powers

What is result or outcome of Raja yoga practice? This is most run of mill demand by individuals about Brahma Kurmaris thought hone. Brahma Kumaris' composed work through documentation of encounters has demonstrated that how reflection is power of huge qualities which shows ponders when deciphered into positive bits of knowledge, words & activities. All Brahma Kumaris' national & general critical upliftment programs formally get commitment from people & on reason of those feelings; its composed work has induced diverse individuals towards right bearing. Arrangement of changing qualities into forces is one segment delayed consequence of Brahma Kumaris' Raja yoga practice. All through history in every social request & conventions, God is seen as Almighty Authority, awesome wellspring of all qualities. In light of this point it is besides last truth that through reflection or affirmation of

unbounded, wellspring of all qualities & quality qualities can be seen "When we consider & interface, we come to condition of truth in which blend of all traits of soul-peace, love, faultlessness, keenness & bliss fills me with force.

It is Divine instrument of human soul that when we use our experience it gets recorded in sub-understanding. Brahma Kumaris' syntheses have wandered in putting additional determination in introducing dynamic extraordinary technique when qualities are changing into forces. To be able to detail best of thoughts & perform positive, raised, noblest & stately activities, we should be grounded in our critical bona fide & stand-out nature of time everlasting. Our valuable considerations would then offer move to new level of vitality. New powers end up being maybe most key component & perpetual vitality is unleashed, creative ability streams & begins changing into forces.

These qualities or qualities change into forces when we set these qualities to work in our affiliations. These positive qualities help us to defeat pessimism in ourselves & in others. Our activities & affiliations give us chance to use power we have gathered. Properties of God experienced in reflection are in like way unique characteristics of soul, however take up with God is essential for their full imperativeness to be passed on. So, Brahma Kumaris forming stresses standard result or accomplishment of reflection practice is force of executing qualities in activities, in conduct & affiliations. Murli meanders sensible techniques how & from where these qualities can be refined. Avyakt Murli" of 15-3-85 clears up:

To be capable soul hopes to complete all waste.....you are director's god-like, pros of all forces. Whatever drive you wish to summon at whatever time, you can do likewise, through unadulterated examinations. By then that force will be open before you. You are masters, & all forces are your laborersstay in nature with your remarkable genuine supernatural structure & through that unique structure, unprecedented excellencies & forces will rise typically. As is structure, so are ethics & qualities & these along these lines come eagerly.

Here of indicated suggestion, subject of reflection has been investigated by reviewing tremendousness of past & its blend with present viable arrangement of thought by Brahma Kumaris works.

Murli itself has made such generous number of living depictions & qualities of their syntheses have mixed different souls, even after maker left his ethical body. Association has kept up itself & furthermore thrived after originator passed away in

light of way that he didn't make educates yet made pioneers. These edified creatures secured sapling planted by facilitator & changed it into goliath tree & included branches, trademark things & blossoms of unprecedented aroma. Another refinement was that originator vivaciously contributed through his case & served world, never with inclination being master or head, yet dependably as unassuming server who was made arrangements to association of mankind. He was sensational in all regards that he showed others clearly not to compliment him in scholarly manifestations, but rather to show him as he was – humble instrument of God. one of kind associations stepped of organizer by not recognizing people or fundamentally attracted souls, as found in other contemporary works however by praising Supreme God, who is last power, maker, power & total in all regards. Brahma Kumaris essayists went well past in making divine care, unprecedented nearness or reflection is convincing reaction for present uncontrolled emergency. In this portion, definitions, brightening's, & arrangement of thought appeared by changed Brahma Kumaris' manifestations are establishment on substance from Murli. They all have further made, refined & analyzed critical thoughts & accommodating frameworks by including their sensible encounters so others can assemble better comprehension of these calm minded strategies.

Brahma Kumaris "Rajayoga" has utilized word "Sahaj" with to awesome degree particular that "Raj yoga" ought to be performed while doing standard responsibilities. Its standard subject is not renunciation of activities yet rather renunciation of indecencies. So, it winds up being immediate right noteworthiness of Yoga & Yogi. We comprehend that yoga does not mean renunciation of world & activities. In Brahma Kumaris 'Yoga creating it is lit up that Sahaj "infers" helpful procedures for yoga, which can be satisfactorily entered by anybody in world. One of critical parts of this Sahaj Raja yogais that it goes on forces to proficient to perform better & adjusted activities. General Brahma Kumaris focus people are doing Yoga while playing out their duties.

It has acknowledged centrality of antiquated consecrated compositions on subject of Yoga & in addition advances essential substance of Yoga i.e. clear & simple to rehearse in current circumstances. Word Sahaj Raja yoga means I am tranquil soul & have huge finishes of veneration for God. This kind of yoga has inconspicuously converged inside it criticalness of all yoga's demonstrated in Gita.

Brahma Kumaris' Yoga lessons are besides amalgamation of yoga in current condition which bears reference to extraordinary message of Giza. In sense substance of Brahma Kumaris' Yoga is "Be Holy: Be Yogi" which means be discerning & general Yogi, while performing conventional duties & commitments. "Yoga" does not mean renunciation of our fundamental duties & activities as said in Gita essentially, yet rather, to repudiate shortcomings of soul e.g., sentiment self, longing, avarice, affiliation & disappointment, which are stunning foes of human soul. As Sri Aurobindo has fittingly said it is method of moving out from insufficiencies to ethics. besides, Kumaris' examination hone fervently underscores that there is "No other way however system for clear Raja yoga meditation" who can lead human soul from indecencies toward estimations of peace, affection, delight, light, fulfillment & restraint. There are various ways & procedures yet they ought to be aide & to advance. In any case, "Raj yoga" examination is most colossal sublime procedure for Yoga.

Brahma Kumaris' examination hone also reacts to need of hour in sense that it gives monstrosity & significant appreciation to old frameworks for reflection. It is enormous to note this point in light of association with considered renaissance which shows up in title of speculation. Brahma Kumaris making & practices out of "Raj yoga" reflection are restoring & stiring our antiquated soul of intense nearness & qualities. It is new invigorating, that does not dismiss substance of obsolete seeing, yet it is crystallization of bits of knowledge into new perfect & viable systems for change & flawlessness for use by present period. Mirror of human character reflects vision of all that is excellent yet dependably imagines presentation of more unmistakable & more serene potential results. Brahma Kumaris are making vision & positive trustworthiness for better self, life, family, society & world.

Brains of today's chance are exhausted on complex speculations & is searching for open methodology for enhancing world as exhibited by present time, spot, circumstances & difficulties. Brahma Kumaris' "balanced" thought answers to these difficulties in book "Fresh starts".

To make examination more essential entire game-plan of presentations are offered; who we are, spot we are from, where we are going, who God is, thing that His part is path by which to make association with him so that peace, veneration, knowledge & enhancements stream into soul, reestablishing it to its genuine control over matter. Seeing every one of these focuses helps us to counterbalance ourselves in such

condition of mettle that not just does our own life tune on totally new & radiant tint; yet we get ourselves arranged to move different others to respond to get of taking off new universe of self-change.

At beginning, it might be said that is come what loathsome that at whatever point we examine Yoga today, we have each one of stores of being inferring that strategy of physical Yogic positions, which have been eccentrically portrayed in Hatha Yoga or else to that specific conventional framework.

Believed is more experience than something that we complete more process than accomplishment, steadier inside journey than destination. Brahma Kumaris World noteworthy school has been propelling showing up & honing Raja yoga meditation since 1937. Phenomenal bits of data & comprehension contained inside Brahma Kumaris noteworthy learning & Raja yoga meditation courses were solidified by organizer of University some place around 1937 & 1969. He gave his life.”

Originator of Brahma Kumaris gave clarion call to mankind; his last words are fast strategy & message of self-impeccability. He guided that God alone is Supreme Father, Supreme Teacher & in like route Satguru of all souls. No individual can observe chance to be God they can be only examinations to show right way. In Brahma Kumaris Raja yoga practice there is given careful purpose of joining of all yoga's. Raja yoga means "mental union or relationship between individual soul & Supreme Being or God".

"Raja" recommends 'Kind', so 'Raja Yoga' can be recognized in various ways:

- King of Yoga's or Royal Yoga.
- Yoga through which soul observes chance to be sovereign over its mind, sagacity & character subsequently choice, sense or organs of body & being in completed control of any condition.

Raja yoga means relationship of soul with phenomenal soul. That is reason yoga sharpened by Brahma Kumaris is most basic kind of Yoga. Raja Yoga proposes King of all Yogas. Why is it "Raja"? it is by reasonability of in Hindi, word "Raj" signifies 'Kind'. Why is it pioneer of all yoga's? "raja yoga" is best in light of way that in sense it is about having most central achievements & Raja other than prescribes control over resources – mental & physical. "Raja yoga" takes its complete shape when soul associates with Supreme God, without this Union "Yoga" is parceled & imperfect. In looking, unpretentious significance of "Raja yoga" is about knowing self, being soul

Careful making unadulterated mental illumination behind higher relationship with Supreme.

Dazzling favored works of world in light of prophetic expression are totally stacked with amazing soundness & learning. Incidentally, paying little respect to all data we have amassed over ages, we continued undermining ourselves morally & basically. "Since nature of torment is disillusionment of wise force in us to meet weakens of closeness & taking in wake of contracting & weight & its root is irregularity of that responsive & having power, as result of our self-concealment by vanity happening on rudeness of our true-blue self."

Believed is answer for our beginning & end current issues. Critical reflection is exceedingly recommended for all-inclusive community why ought to begin discover amazing quality & nature of their own inside character. If we have to stay mindful of continually creating pace of life, its complexities & issues, we need to make power of cerebrum to awesome degree.

Is reflection basically inducing method to make power of mind? answer is yes – reflection is most old & most remarkable supernatural fortune. From its amazing past, India is at present thought to be extraordinary "Reference point" for rest of world. Since Vedic period until today our extraordinary foremost pioneers & Yogis, who sharpened Yoga in their life, have in like way demonstrated that past religious traditions, points of confinement & traditions power which can change life is "Standard of Yoga". Routine of Yoga has vital relationship with in all cases human qualities. In light of this principal point simply broad human qualities & reflection practices for better world is associated in this part. Today people are looking for right approach to manage hone values for range of their life. Thought or Yoga sharpens have been found & finished into certain specific systems through which human learning can be vexed & changed. Brahma Kumaris making & sharpens concentrate commonly on routine of Yoga reflections & through routine of yoga, utilization of characteristics comes more easily & normally in life.

Oxford Dictionary depicts centrality of "practice" as action of finishing choice that is rather than theories about it; setting approach into practice. In association of this criticalness, Brahma Kumaris making is remarkable blend in sense that it is compelled to speculation just, furthermore "reflection" is regular "practice" & vital bit of ordinary way of life. Sharpen makes human faultless, by doing in that utmost & setting values indisputably, makes values talk louder in life. At whatever point today,

clamoring present day individuals are assuming that it's difficult to practice thought constantly, Brahma Kumaris World immense school has made vitalizing for reflection experience.

Murlis are contraption for most massive thought on data & yoga. In Murlis this truth has been unmistakably elucidated in direct way, "Who God is" & "Who is Supreme"? No individual can be Supreme God. They can be called Devi or Devatas (by God) yet not Supreme God. In Murlis it is cleared up that God comes & elucidates favored bits of data of Vedas & sacred structures. God is Purifier, Almighty Authority. He is other than called World Almighty Authority. He knows beginning, focus, & end of whole world.

Brahma Kumaris' Yoga sharpens don't release some other thought related with thought sharpen yet rather progressed further in change & mixing of different sorts of Yoga for leveling & upliftment of life. Brahma Kumaris' normal of "Yoga" for better world is in like way old "Raja yoga" which is depicted & given centrality in Gita, & by Sri Aurobindo & Swami Vivekananda. Before making jump critical examination of Brahma Kumaris "Raja yoga" practice, examination of outdated considered Raja yoga in regards to motivation behind this part is required. Brahma Kumaris "Raja yoga" sharpen presents conviction that this examination system is told by God himself, who is similarly called "Yogeshwar". God is one however there are diverse names of God. So also, God has this name. There are more foremost number of names for God than tongues of world, & each name highlights one of his specialties. Brahma Kumaris shaping has used word "Parampita Paramatma Shiva" for Supreme God Father as essentialness of Shiva is in like manner exhaustive. "Sanskrit Word "Shiva" diagrams His external attributes & purposes of repression. It construes Benefactor Father, Seed of Creation & Point Source, & suggests that there can be no other producer above Him".

Since Yoga taught by Shiva, Lord of Yogis, depends huge amounts of self, universe, moral laws, Supreme Soul etc. It is generally called Yoga of Knowledge or Gyan Yoga. Further, since it must be invaded by method for wisdom, as it avoids any physical positions, it is likewise called "Insightful Communion or Buddhi Yoga. Yet again, since master of this yoga needs to keep his cerebrum associated with God even while discharging social, fit & unmistakable commitments, it is generally called "Karma Yoga". Routine of this yoga, does not require renunciation of one's family or one's obligations & Karmas; it demands renunciation of just knowledge slants,

association & that which is pitiable. Beginning there of point of view, it is in like path named as Sanyasa Yoga or Yoga of Renunciation. One, who sharpens it, goes about as amere trustee with God overhead; he sees himself as to be irrelevant instrument. He acts with psyche blowing wishes for all. He surrenders himself soundly & totally to God & accords to his requests. This makes him free of all troubles, elucidations behind prepared, vain contemplations & negative perspectives. Thusly, it is also called Yoga of Equanimity or 'Samatwa Yoga' & one who performs it is called 'Sthitha Prajna' – yogi having equality. Besides, yoga relies on upon paramount fondness for any commitment to God; therefore, it may nearly be called Bhakti Yoga at any rate, it should be noted, one doesn't play out any love or Japa. It can be called Bhakti Yoga just in resources that adoration for & respect for God is fundamental piece in this yoga.

This yoga sufficiently prompts Samadhi or condition of processing; accordingly, it is by & large called 'Sahaj Raja Yoga' – word Sahaj surmises: what is clear or that which winds up being touch of one's inclination. Thusly, it ought to be borne as top need that Gyan Yoga, Karma Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, & whatnot, are not distinctive sorts of Yoga yet rather these are different names given to Raja Yoga, taught by Shiva, Lord of yogis, given to it to raise its striking portions. Every one of general population who hone this Raja Yoga do by & large make them learn, soul of obligation or devotion & so on, despite some have more significant measure of these than others have.

Examination of Raja Yoga is not fundamental, in sense that it is truly huge & that it identifies with true blue substances. Brahma Kumaris examination hone in like way tensions "Raj yoga" as science in that is examination of calm, inside reflections, & internal disclosure. Brahma Kumaris producer out of India organized in London. She began all around tackles subject of examination & her understandings of voyage of western character, has driven her to frame different books. She is producer of Practical Meditation, God's Healing Power, Dreams & Reality, Spirituality in Daily Life & Art of Thinking. Consequently, accentuation of thought practice is twofold one:

Examining all truths about Yogas as depicted in Gita, & by Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo, in present setting, gives amazingly immense message that there is phenomenal need of routine of Yoga. Brahma Kumaris have altogether fathomed that at this present sensitive time of undermining qualities & intense nearness; there is

essential necessity for fundamental serious framework for Yoga to dismiss further corruption of attributes & significant sentiment being.

4.25 Advantages of Meditation

In this section of the presented thesis, some of the key benefits of Yoga are mentioned.

4.25.1 Psychological level based benefits of meditation

A normal person's mind is extremely susceptible to the changing environments. A mentally healthy person retains the stability of mind under adverse circumstances. One's mind having been liberated from wasteful habits such as smoking, taking alcoholic drinks or intoxicating drugs, spending time and money on obscene films, etc. and one's concentration and efficiency having increased and relations and capacity of adjustment, tolerance and endurance having improved, one's social, economic and over all development now takes place.

- There is the resulting change in one's belief system, value system, one's purpose, attitude and behaviour.
- Meditation increases the coherence of brain wave patterns in the brain, which suggests it improves creativity and learning and changes the way the brain works. Meditation helps to decrease anxiety, depression, irritability and moodiness.
- Meditation improves memory.
- Meditation increases the subjective feeling of happiness and contentment.
- Meditation increases emotional stability.

4.25.2 Physiological Benefits of Meditation:

Some of the physiological advantages of meditation are given as follows:

- Meditation decreases the metabolic rate and lowers the heart rate, thus indicating a state of deep rest and regeneration.
- Meditation reduces stress which is indicated by lower levels of stress-hormones such as cortisol.
- Meditation reduces high blood pressure.
- Meditation has been found to help asthma patients, making breathing easier for them.
- Meditation seems to slow down the aging process of the brain and thicken the grey matter of the brain, thus increasing the brain.
- Medical scientists would be keen to know the psycho-physiological explanation about the benefits of Raja Yoga in promoting positive state of one's mind. Enkephalin and Endorphins (Endogenous Morphine) are secreted due to yogic life style which helps in detaching oneself from the various kinds of pains. They produced

harmonious Alpha or Theta waves not only while meditating but even when various mental and intellectual works was done.

4.25.3 Spiritual Benefits of Meditation

Meditation has traditionally been seen as a tool for spiritual realization and fulfilment. While the physiological and psychological benefits have so far been concentrated on in the West, modern brain science helps to understand and explore the spiritual aspects of meditation more and more. Another scientific tool is to question people on the subjectively perceived effects which meditation has on them. Such methods have been used in recognized scientific disciplines such as psychology or sociology.

Studies show that people who meditate are likely to report a shift in their outlook and goals in life towards personal growth and spiritual fulfillment rather than more materialistic goals. Brain research shows how meditation can train the higher capacities of the mind, such as perception, awareness and compassion. The progress of brain research opens up ways of getting a clear, scientific understanding and evidence of the spiritual dimension of meditation. While for the sake of clarity, the positive effects of meditation have been categorized into physiology, psychology and spirituality, all these areas are somehow connected. For example, feeling physically healthy will have a positive effect on one's mind, too, as well as the other way round.

4.25.4 Consciousness & Self-Realization

Self-awareness and self-understanding are cultivated in order to realize one's true spiritual identity. In the meditative state, the self is experienced as conscious energy taking the form of a point of light. This spiritual energy, the soul, is experienced as both different and separate from the energy of the material body.

The roles and interplay between mind, intellect and personality are understood through a process of self-observation. The mediator learns to quiet and control the mind, allowing the conscience to be clearly heard. Understanding the relationship between acquired values and innate values and between values and virtues is emphasized, along with the importance of reviewing and renewing one's values at the deepest level of one's life. Conscious awareness of the soul is thus developed, allowing full understanding of the self

4.25.5 Soul

Has your sense of identity been changing lately? Are you experiencing a move, a change of career, or your children leaving the nest? Do you have the vague feeling

that you could be doing something that has greater heart and meaning for you? Are you re-evaluating your life's purpose?

Change loosens the tight hold that my sense of bodily identity generally has on me. Because the familiar labels that have defined how I think of myself are changing, I feel uncertain as to who I really am and unclear as to how to find out. It is fortunate when such uncertainty causes me to search for my true identity with fresh openness, for then I am naturally led towards a state of higher awareness. The spiritual knowledge of the *Brahma Kumaris* encourages each of us to visualize ourselves as a spiritual being, an infinitesimally tiny star, a minute point of invisible luminous non-physical energy, that is, as a soul. Is this really who I am? For so long, I have thought of myself as woman, or man; as a physical being rather than a spiritual being.

Allow yourself to experiment. For a few moments think of yourself as a tiny star of pure living light – the light of the energy of consciousness. Think of yourself as a soul, the 'being' located in the centre of your forehead, behind the 'windows' of your eyes. When you are in this awareness, you are soul conscious. This is your spiritual identity.

4.25.6 Self Realization

Throughout time, philosophers have affirmed that by stepping beyond the limitations of the egocentric self, an individual can experience 'self realization'. With this realization comes a deep understanding of the worth of a human being. When I am soul conscious, my sense of identity is derived from the inherent worth of the soul, rather than from the limited impermanent image of the body. After self-realization comes self remembering. To remember who I am is to develop the ability to maintain soul consciousness as I think, move and interact to mindfully use my mind and body with wisdom, care for them with accuracy and discipline, and communicate respect and love through my attitude, thoughts, vibrations and expressions.

4.26 Soul: Mind, Intellect & Personality

Every soul has three separate faculties which are inherent in all human beings irrespective of place of birth. Just as electrical energy produces warmth, sound or light depending on the device through which it passes, similarly, the energy of consciousness functions through three different but closely connected faculties, referred to respectively by the terms mind, intellect, and personality.

- **The Mind**

With the power of the mind, one imagines, thinks and forms ideas. Thoughts are created in the mind. The thought process is the basis of all emotions, desires and sensations. It is through the minds that, in an instant, thoughts reach anywhere, a memory can be relived and the feeling of happiness or sadness is experienced. The metaphysical mind should not be confused with the heart, the physical organ that maintains blood circulation.

- **The Intellect**

Thoughts are processed and interpreted by the intellect. This is the faculty which understands. The capacity to understand is perhaps the single most crucial ability of the soul. Clear understanding of anything is possible when the intellect becomes broad, deep and farsighted through the regular study of spiritual knowledge and the disciplined practice of meditation. The intellect also reasons, memorizes, discriminates and makes decisions. The non-physical intellect should not be confused with the physical brain, which is the physical focus of the nervous system. The brain is the soul's control panel; it provides the facilities for the soul's expression.

- **The Personality**

Any action once performed leaves an impression on the soul. Habits, temperaments and tendencies are all embedded in the soul (as images, feelings, sounds, trains of thought, etc.) as a result of every action performed. The most fundamental feature of every soul, its personality, is determined by such stored impressions. These impressions, formed in the past, are the reservoir which we draw upon, often sub-consciously, as our source of thoughts and actions in the present. Since, the presented research work emphasized on the Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, hence considering significance of a better awareness of Raj Yoga meditation, in this section, a brief of Raj Yoga meditation and its significance etc have been discussed.

4.27 Raja Yoga Meditation

Raj-Yoga Meditation is awareness of the metaphysical self and absorption of one's mind in hopeful and purposeful consciousness of God and his divine attributes. The word 'Yoga' means 'to unite'; Yoga is, therefore, the practice or art of uniting or linking the mind with God by focusing attention on him as an incorporeal being-of-light and thinking of nothing but his divine qualities. This takes one into a state of

absorption in bliss and peace through positive thinking. It recharges one's self or soul with light and might and fills one with creative energy.

Raja yoga Meditation is the way for realization of the real identity of the self and for experiencing it. It helps a person to know the truth about the real nature of mind or the self. Raja yoga enables a person to withdraw from the thoughts of the body and the material world for a while. The philosophy of Rajyog enables the participant to focus the mind on the metaphysical self and link itself lovefully to the supreme soul who is light, bliss, peace, love and might personified in the form of a brilliant and radiant point. Raja yogameditation is refreshing, energizing, relaxing, reassuring and reawakening. Raja yogamakes the soul increasingly aware of its divine origin, divine destiny and divine peaceful real nature. Raja yogahas social benefits. It helps in developing spiritual approach towards others and created an attitude of Universal Brotherhood in the aspirant of Yoga. It is the means for bringing about national integration and international brotherhood.

In the name 'Raja-Yoga' the word 'Raja' means the king, the sovereign or the supreme. This yoga is called Raja-Yoga because it is the supreme or the highest yoga, being true and most effective. Another reason for calling it 'Raja-Yoga' is that it is related mainly to mind and mind is considered as the 'King that rules the sense-organs and the body. Moreover, the term Raja-Yoga also implies that even such a person as a king, who is very busy and has so much to do, can practice it, there is no need to practice breath-control, physical postures, or use a mantra, or an image nor does it require one to stop all thoughts, but stop only, worldly or negative thoughts and concentrate our mind on God.

The word 'Meditation' means 'to think'. As we all know, man's mind is, ordinary, occupied with hundreds of thoughts of the world; in Raj-Yoga meditation, one withdraws one's mind from all the worldly thoughts, including the thoughts of one's own body, and one collects ones, consciousness, at least for some time, and thinks of the shining and peaceful self as a point of divine and conscient light and, then, focuses one's attention on god as supreme soul, who also is a point of conscient light and is the ocean of peace. The inhibition of worldly thoughts and the recollection or recapitulation of thoughts of the luminous self is attained by directing the flow of thoughts towards god i.e. the supreme soul in his supreme adobe or Paramdham which is the world of divine light. In this sense, this meditation is withdrawal or

reversal of one's consciousness, from the body and its world to the soul and its silent world, or from the dark lanes of negative thoughts on the bright path of contemplation on god. Raj-Yoga meditation may therefore, be defined as a disciplined exercise of awareness, utilizing such processes as creatively thinking, intuitively perceiving and silently reflecting and concentrating on the metaphysical truths of self and god which lead to comprehension and realization of the subject. This practice involves the turning of one's mind and the flow of his love in the direction of god, giving him the hot-link to communicate with him.

4.28 Pillars of Raj Yoga

In general there are four pillars of Raj Yoga. A brief discussion of these pillars is given as follows:

Fig. No. 44: Pillars of Rajayoga

4.28.1 Satwic Diet (Shudha Ann)

There's truth in saying that we are what we eat. The satwic means pure vegetarian diet. Today as a result of research studies on food, it is found that vegetarian food is better for health. The food that a person takes has a deep impact on the working of

mind. The Brahma Kumaris' philosophy has taken an innovative step by promoting the concept of a 'Vegetarian Diet' as Compulsory rule for mental and physical hygiene of human being. The Brahma Kumaris meditation centres and its spiritual students all over the World follow the same vegetarian life style for the upliftment of the soul. Hence the saying "*Jaisa ann vaisa mann*" – As is the food so is the mind. It is therefore obligatory on a yogi, to observe discipline in regard to the purity of food. In meditation practice, purity of food helps in several ways. It helps mainly in purity of thoughts and concentration. A Yogi's food is 'satwic' i.e., simple, fresh and does not contain meat, fish, egg, onion, garlic, liquor and tobacco. It went further in promoting the concept that if food is cooked in positive consciousness and if also offered to God before eating resulted in tremendous improvement in health and life style of the people. Gandhiji has elevated the control of the palate and has regarded it as one of the aids to brahmacharya. Of the various aids to brahmacharya, this vow has also been prescribed by him. According to him, a brahmchari should practice this moral Weapon in order to control his palate. This vow means that we should take extremely simple food.

4.28.2 Good Company (Satsanga)

Everything we observe and hear affects our mind and will make a difference to behaviour. There is an old adage, which says, "As is the company so is the colour" (*Jaisa sang Vaisa Rang*). By keeping good company of those who also aspire to purity and self transformation will help the yogi to attain better results. A company of a well - wisher means"

2. A well-wisher who has positive thoughts for others (Shubh Chintak)
3. One with positive thoughts (Shubh Chintan) for the self.
4. Pure feelings for others

A Pure and elevated awareness and form Brahma Kumaris morning and evening Murli and Meditation classes have rendered positive company and education for the common people.

4.28.3 Divine Virtues (Divya Gun)

The practice of Divine Virtues or values is the important pillar of Raja Yoga. One who wants to be virtuous or good has to refrain from bad company, had books and bad thoughts and should attend spiritual discourses. Spirituality nurtures the virtues of the soul. Divine Virtues of humility, love, truth, honesty, faith and courage elevates

the practice of Yoga. The result end of yoga is gift of values. The soul starts flying, leaving behind shell of ego:

Maintain yourself respect by remembering that you are not going to allow ego to reach you, you are going to keep it behind you.... While you just continue to fly....

4.28.4 Brahmacharya or Chastity

The most powerful of all the five major vices enemy is sex lust. It is also mentioned in our holy books to control and conquer this vice. The practical reason for celibacy is that the soul's energy is conserved and channeled in more creative and beneficial ways in serving others. "Lust" is the greatest enemy of a Raj Yogi as it increases attachment to the body and to others. Our history is the testimony of the fact that many spiritual sages and leaders lived the life of celibacy for spiritual upliftment. The Brahma Kumaris persuaded the idea in more dignified manner that it observed the purity of thoughts words and actions. It is also remarked:

"Brahmacharya is the most important of the vows prescribed by Gandhiji.... Gandhiji took the comprehensive meaning of brahmacharya, if properly practised, ultimately leads to the realisation of Brahma.....it consists in the control of all the senses. Anger and impure thought do not provide strength to brahmacharya. Thus, Gandhiji maintained this moral weapon as means of self control."

Murli supported the vision of God for the establishment of a Pure, Peaceful and Prosperous world, following Purity in mansa (mind), vachha (words) and karmana (actions). In order to uplift the human soul from the elongated darkness of the vices, pure vision (d1'isti) and pure attitude (vriti) and pure actions (kriti) is the vital remedy to the degenerating values. When mind is established in the Brahuua, as the word Brahmacharya connotes and therefore, acharya means acharan (behaviour) of human soul will take pleasure in spiritual love towards others with feeling of brotherhood. It becomes more elevated as it is beyond the physical affections. It generates more mental and physical stamina, moral force and spiritual strength. It enhances our willpower, Creates clarity of judgement, efficiency and equipoise.

4.29 Values of Raj Yoga Meditation

The presented research intends to examine various values of Raj Yoga meditation and novelties of value provisioning through BKRM, which significantly motivates people to consider Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris. It is important to understand and realize various types of values and their respective significances to make successful human life. In this section, some of significant and key values of Raj Yoga meditation are discussed.

4.29.1 Creating peace

The ancient Indians for well being, brotherhood and harmony on earth, always called for peace through several shanti mantras. It is chanted together for universal peace. The truth, however is that peace is the name of an inner spiritual experience. It is a state of mind in which there are no thoughts of hate, anger, jealousy, rivalry, etc., but rather the soul is in a state of tranquility. The soul's original nature is peace. Today we find the shadow of world war, terrorism or violence is increasing among the nations of the world. Thus peace has come to be identified with the absence of war or war-like Conditions. In order to discuss the question of universal peace, it has become necessary to discuss the question of war as well. The threat of war creates fear in humankind and challenges universal peace. On one side there is that period of history during which there has been more and more moral degeneration which does not refer to the original nature of human brings-peace, love and divinity and that is why humans want to achieve peace again.

The Brahma Kumaris'and spiritual philosophy is sincerely awakening our peaceful consciousness and is dedicated in the noble task of bridging the gap which has been created by ignoring the deep root of our soul original values. If we look at _it in the light of this truth then the fire of aggressiveness, hate, anger and greed can be eliminated through sprinkling the water of peace. The Brahma Kumaris believe that it can be achieved through "The New Paradigm" for world peace:

In this new paradigm of universal peace, which is in consonance with the ancient wisdom, human will lead a life of purity and divine values. He will have goodwill for all. He will feel that he is a member of the world-wide family of mankind. He will have control over his physical organs and will be soul-conscious....., but, one thing sure enough is that universal peace is not mere dream of idealists; it is not a mere utopia. The path to it is paved with ethical values, with meditation and with Godly wisdom. There is an open invitation to one and all to march along this only path of sanctity....ie, Shanti!

Murli develops the true consciousness of peace by indicating the original nature of soul. A Sakar Murli of dated 16/06/96 reflects the way of experiencing peace:

4.29.2 Love

Benjamin Franklin says that when one falls in love with himself, he will have no rivals. Love is the principle which creates and sustains human relations with dignity and depth. Spiritual love is higher, gives silence to soul, and that silence has the power to unite, guide and energize. Love is the bedrock for the belief in equality of spirit and personhood. When love is combined with faith it creates a strong understanding in human relations. Love is the catalyst for change, development and achievement. Gandhiji also devoted his thoughts on the great value of love, he tried to connect truth and love together.

In its Universal sense love is above the present limited, cheap meaning of physical satisfaction. The basis of real love between human beings is spiritual. To see each individual as a spiritual being, a soul, is to see the spiritual reality of the other. To be conscious of that reality is to have spiritual love. The spiritual love is divine. True love is when the soul has love for the soul beyond the limited consciousness. Love for the soul is eternal; the truth is that soul never dies, it is immortal. Such elevated love is righteous, and it brings joy. Attachment to that which is perishable is unrighteous and it brings sorrow and pain. All religious founders, Christ, Mohammad, Guru Nanak, Buddha and the Sufi saints, each one gave the message of love and brotherhood.

Love bears all positive hopes, patience, right attitude and kindness. This value of love is also the essence of all religions. There is no religion in the world that believes that we should be jealous, arrogant, rude, irritable, resentful and hateful to each other. Love is the great quality that we need most today in the world. Love conquers over all negativities of jealousy, hatred, ego, inhumanity, resentment and war.

Power of love beyond limited attachments can conquer all things. We can learn to give more true love to others when we detach ourselves from limited consciousness. Spiritual love has a power to destroy limited consciousness of animosity, hatred and jealousy. When spiritual love prevails then negative feelings are transformed into positive feelings with the coolness of love. In spiritual love there is harmony, since love removes controlling or co-dependent tendencies and ensures kindness, caring and amicable understanding.

4.29.3 Respect

Self respect and the respect of others are related to each other. Those who have claimed self-respect stay in their stage of self-respect, and in this way claim respect

from others. And such a soul speaks, sees and has a connection with others, with respect. The meaning of respect for the self is to give respect to everyone. God is the one who receives respect of all the souls of the entire world. Every one gives Him so much respect, but He gives respect to all the children: “To say, “you first means to be constantly stable in the state of self-respect and to give respect to others means to say, you first—constantly stable in the state of self—respect and is the bestower who gives respect to others, does not have those two attitudes neither ego nor insult”.

The Murli gives deep insight into self respect that it means being a self sovereign who lives a life of dignity, grace and fulfillment. The desire “to live” desire “to achieve” and desire ‘to be’ are natural to human life. Human beings do not merely want to progress materialistically but also wish to grow mentally and spiritually. Out of many desires the one that is most strongly sought after is the desire to share respect. One wants to live respectfully and gracefully. Self respect means give respect to self and others, having a non-exploitative nature and respecting the laws and rules and also speak about respecting rights and freedom of others.

The Brahma Kumaris believe in the connection of one value with other values. This means that if we practice one value, another value comes in automatically. A similar scenario applies with vices. If you give disrespect to someone, automatically there will be jealousy, hatred, fear and insecurity in our life. When human beings are trapped in desires for pleasure and power, every thread of respect for the self and others need of respect, for the self and others is lost.

4.29.4 Co-operation

One who co-operates receives co-operation. The method to give co-operation is to use the energy of mind to create vibrations of good wishes and pure feelings. Human achievement is like a mountain range with cliffs, slopes and valleys. To aim for excellence in collective achievement is to aspire to climb to the crowning point. However, no climb should ever be undertaken without the safety rope of co-operation. Co-operation ensures Easiness, enthusiasm, equanimity and empowerment. The Co-operation is governed by the principle of mutual respect. Co-operation requires recognizing the unique role of every individual while maintaining a sincere and positive attitude. Pandit Nehru also remarked on the power of co-operation.

We live in a world of conflicts and yet the world goes on, undoubtedly because of the co-operation of nations and individuals. Even today between countries which are

opposed to each other in the political or other fields, there is a vast amount of co-operation. Little is known and little is said about this co-operation that is going on perhaps, it will be a trailer picture of the co-operating in the world today were put toward and we were made to think that the world depends on Co-operation and not conflicts. Swami Vivekananda has pointed out importance of education of goodness for one and all is one of the most significant contribution to development of aesthetics in every human being. Education leads us to elimination of hatred and victory of love. The education of service to society leads one to have in being a selfless server. Therefore it is right for us that we should serve and co-operate with our millions of brothers rather than being selfish.

The method of receiving co-operation is giving co-operation, with the power of good wishes and pure feelings for the others, difficult situations can be solved. By remaining detached and inspired by the inner values and not external circumstances, subtle co-operation in the form of wisdom emerges. Co-operation improves human relations. It is governed by the principle of mutual respect, caring and sharing, courage, consideration and goodwill provide a foundation from which co-operation can be developed. If one has faith and confidence in others and with mutual support, Co-operation can be achieved. Co-operation is everyone's responsibility. Co-operation requires recognizing the unique role of every individual while maintaining a sincere and The Brahma Kumaris been spreading this message in the process of world transformation that the time is now for each person to lend a finger of co-operation. The time has come, when we need each other's cooperation for a greater task for a better world.

4.29.5 Humility

Humility is a very noble quality, it is free from pride or ego. As ego is great obstacle in path of the humility. At first, going into the ocean for the exploration can lead to buried treasures, one searching his Or her inner world can find jewels buried in the depths. The jewel buried deepest -which is the brightest and gives the most light – is humility. It removes fear and insecurity and opens up door to universal truths and values. But humility cannot shine, when there is ego. People often wonder why vices are increasing in society instead of values. As society gives more place to ego, it disturbs the complete union with the Divine in the chapter 'The ego - the desire soul' :

We have seen that the integral surrender of the human being is an essential pre-requisite of his complete union with the Divine and the total transformation of his nature, we have also seen that, paradoxical as it may appear it is the ego that at once initiates and impedes this surrender. In order that our surrender may be sincere and integral, we must now try to understand what this ego is, Its origin purpose, characteristic function, growth and end and how we can proceed to deal with it in the light of a true knowledge.

The Brahma Kumaris' writings define a simple and practical meaning of "Humility"- it is listening to others, accepting others and observing other's qualities. One word spoken in humility has the significance of a thousand words. The consciousness of trusteeship enhances self-esteem and respect in our relations.

Humility is to inculcate natural principles in personal behavior relationships, and other area of development. Without humility, we can neither build societies with values, nor can we 'serve the world benevolently. John Bunyan says that those are humble, are fearless:

- He that is down needs fear no fall
- He that is low no pride,
- He that is humble ever shall
- Have God to be his guide.

Ego makes you criticize and caught up in a web. Ego puts a lock on the intellect, obscuring your own responsibility: it says, " it is your fault, it has nothing to do with me." Humility is the key to this lock. It frees you from self-deception. Humility allows you to hear and obey your conscience. With humility there is the power of realization, which allows transformation to take place.

4.29.6 Purity

Purity is the mother of peace and prosperity. Without purity there will be no peace and prosperity. Over recent years, it seems that there has been a decline in moral standards of our society. Purity is the soul of all virtues. The virtue of purity has a deep and universal definition. Pure ones should be pure not only in their exterior

selves but also in their inner selves. The world is in great darkness due to the decreasing power of purity. Where there is purity, there are peaceful thoughts of the self and others. Prosperity does not only mean physical wealth or worldly fame but means the wealth of pure and peaceful thoughts, which is priceless, countless and unlimited. Pure feelings touch the heart and soul. Where there is arrogance, anger and impurity, there will be no purity. In Gita, lust, anger and greed, are described as three types of gates to hell. The Gita gives us the warning from God that these three vices should be abandoned from life by all means. These vices are gates leading to hell (NARKA). By nearly entering at the gate, the self is ruined. The Gita warns us in different verses, in different discourses that worldly desires such as hypocrisy, arrogance, greed, and anger are completely impure and a distracter to soul. So the chapter sixteenth of Bhagavad Gita defines the rejection of these vices.

There are three types of gates to hell destructive of the self - lust, anger and greed; therefore these three should be shunned. Of the demoniac vices described above, three that are the basis of all the rest should be shunned by all means. This is being stated: There are lust, anger and greed these are three types of gates to hell; hence they are destructive of the self i.e., leading to lower births, Therefore these three should be shunned by all means..

4.29.7 Truth

The Bhagavad Gita has defined the auspiciousness of the word "Sat", truth as it is stated in the two verses. "Sat" is used to denote goodness and existence. Truth means accurate, true, good and real and central with the power of falsehood. Truth is always victorious.

The defeat of truth is short lived and its victory is for all time. "Great is the Truth and mighty above all things". The Brahma Kumaris' "Avyakt Murli" and the Bhagavad Gita denote that truth is good and auspicious. The Murli defines the foundation of truth is purity: The foundation of truth is purity, and the practical proof of truth is divinity on your face and in your activity. Many souls in the world call themselves true or consider themselves to be truthful, but the only real basis of truthfulness is purity. If there is not purity, there cannot be constant truthfulness. Being the embodiment of truth on the basis of purity is constant and easy. Truth is not just speaking the truth and doing that which is true, but the first truth is that through which you receive the power of purity or the power of truth.

The Brahma Kumaris' literature on values describes how to practice honesty in present difficult times. The Brahma Kumaris' Positive Thoughts Books on Virtues, Blessings, pearls of Love from God and Thought for Today inspire readers to have a positive attitude for the day. The university's primary aim has always been to impart a practical ethical education so that individuals may transform their lives by tapping the hidden reservoir of their potential creative energies and channeling those powers in positive directions. Ultimately, this transformation on the individual level would lead to change in society.

Dr. Roger Cole is a best-selling author from Australia. He is a cancer specialist. He was inspired by Brahma Kumaris World University. Dr. Cole is also an author of Brahma Kumaris' book Mission of love and in his book Blessings for a peaceful world he shares.

Once again, I send my thanks to the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual Organization, to its leaders and members for their wisdom and knowledge, and the teachings of Raja Yoga meditation. I believe you have brought me closer God... If you wish to learn the meditation technique that inspired me to write these blessings.

Dr. Cole feels blessings are gifts of wisdom and understanding for our world. They will inspire us and reawaken the beauty of our spirit. Blessings strengthen our mind, heal our soul and awaken our heart to the power of love. Give these blessings to a friend, and visualize a world of loving values, unity and happiness. When we offer these blessings, we create a wish for a Peaceful world and share our wish with others. His blessing book for a peaceful world shares practical thoughts on honesty. He wisely observes:

- You are a soul with an honest heart and the integrity to be the same inside and out.
- Be True to yourself and always give Love.
- With a true and honest heart you are free to experience God's Love and Power.
- You have a true heart and never feel separate from the divine.
- With Love for everyone your honest and open heart gives peace and hope to the world.
- Your honest actions and words defuse conflict and reveal pure spiritual Values to the world.
- You are a wise soul with a powerful intellect and an honest heart You reveal truth to the world and remain humble.

Politicians Like Dr. Rajendra Prasad, Jawaharlal Nehru, Sardar Patel, etc., had raised the nation high in the eyes of other nations by vista of their selflessness, Sacrifices and Character but politicians who are involved in many cases of corruption and crime have brought it down and made it a laughing stock for other nations.

4.29.8 Non-violence

The twentieth century has already seen two world wars and numerous others, devastating nature and humanity. There has also been a long cold war, and the race for superior armaments between the world's two major powers has not yet ended. People all over- the world are worried about the increasing fear of nuclear weapons and war. We all know the tragedy of war is violence. In the history of mankind we have observed the gradual progress of violence in our society. Gandhiji's life was the finest example of non-violence. He realized that violence cannot be met by violence but only by non-violence. According to Gandhiji it was only through the application of non-violence that violence can be minimized. He writes:

The function of non-violence is different from other moral Laws in the sense that its source is divine. The votary does not act with his strength. Strength comes from God. "All through my life", says Gandhiji "I have acted in that faith. Never have I attributed -any independent strength to myself.....Thus this moral power is humanly operated upon, but divinely controlled. It is inconceivable -without the control of God. Hence, a man who believes in non-violence also believes in God as the ultimate source of all moral strength. It is the greatest moral force at the disposal of mankind. It is mightier than even the mightiest Weapons ever devised by the ingenuity of man. There is, as such, no defect in it.

One of the deepest meanings of non-violence is defined in the Murli as that which gives sorrow or pain by thoughts, words or action toward others is also subtle form of violence. Violence doesn't just mean war or use of weapons and sometimes we ignore these subtle forms of violence. This violence can be even more dangerous than the violence created by weapons. The Murli further defines even a more subtle layer of violence in human Mind. As Frances Lawrence in Observer 17 December 1995 has explained "Violence is not a knife in the hand. It grows like a poison tree inside other people who have not learned to value other human beings.

The Brahma Kumaris' education and teachings emphasizes that the first violence is in thoughts and is the poisonous root which gives birth to violence in action. To

eliminate violence, first we must practice positive, peaceful and loveful thoughts for the self and others.

The resultant values emerging from the core values are:

- ✓ **Happiness**
- ✓ **Responsibility**
- ✓ **Freedom**
- ✓ **Simplicity**
- ✓ **Tolerance**
- ✓ **Unity**

4.29.9 Soul Source

The Brahma Kumaris' has given spiritual insight into values. There is happiness when each moment is used in a worthwhile way. Happiness is such nourishment that it can transform a person from weak into a powerful being. It makes difficult things easy and heavy things light. To remain happy and share happiness with others is a great act of charity. No matter what happen, my happiness should not be lost.

Happiness is not a destination,

- *It is every day journey.*
- *Happiness is not a dependency,*
- *It is a decision.*

Give happiness and take happiness, don't give sorrow and take sorrow. Happiness is prosperity which comes from self-sovereignty. Self sovereignty means being master over the mind, intellect, personality traits, and physical senses of the body; being complete with all powers and virtues.

Swami Vivekananda also believed in inner happiness of the soul:

Happiness is not in this heaven or in that heaven; it is in the soul

Richard Schoch in his book Secret of Happiness says that it is human need to aspire for something more and we want to attain it.

Of course from time we shall fail in the attainment, but we shall have learned enough to know that we are stronger than our failure; our life is an ever striving, and we call the striving happiness.

Happiness can be increased by smiling. In busy world people find it difficult even to smile. Happiness does not mean laughter, it means gentle smile which costs nothing:

A Smile costs nothing,

- *But gives much*
- *It enriches those who receive,*
- *Without making poorer those who give,*
- *It takes but a moment,*
- *Yet the memory of it sometimes lasts forever.*

Spirituality says to be happy in the present moment. The present moment is gift from God. Happiness and joy are the innate qualities of the soul. The human soul is always in search of happiness, but it is not found in the outer, it is inner:

- *Happiness is the only Good*
- *The place to be happy is Here*
- *The time to be happy is Now*
- *The way to be happy is to make others Happy*

4.29.10 Responsibility

A responsible person fulfills the assigned duty by staying true to the aim. Duties are carried out with integrity and a sense of purpose. In our life human beings have different responsibilities according to time and place. Being responsible means to have moral responsibility.

Personal responsibility in life comes from many expected and unexpected sources and involved partnership and participation, commitment and co-operation. Social and global responsibility requires all the above as well as justice, humanness and respect for the rights of all human beings. Particular attention is paid to ensure that benefit is for all without discrimination.

Some interpret responsibility as a burden and fail to see it as personally relevant. It becomes convenient to project it as someone else's problem. These people deny their responsibility, yet when it comes to rights, they are the first in line. When the role is played accurately, there is efficiency and effectiveness which result in satisfaction and contentment at having made a significant contribution. Responsibility also means striving to do one's best. We should also engage ourselves in deep reflection of what each one could do to enhance our birthplace. We are responsible for our family, society and country and for our self as well. We are doing what we are capable of doing toward bettering our inner self and can we live up to the best ideas that we can

dream of deep inside us'? Mahatma Gandhi urged:

The difference between what we do and what we are capable of doing would suffice to solve most of the world's problems. The Brahma Kumaris' literature -presents values in a natural manner so that they flourish in our actions until they become a natural part of our thinking, being and doing. It is expressed in the literature that:

The world is a stage and we are all actors. Each plays a unique part and is responsible for one's own actions. Responsibility means doing the right thing no matter how big or small the task may be. Each one of us has a special role to play in making the world a better place.

Responsibility means

- *Responsible for mental, physical and spiritual balance*
- *Responsible for self-improvement*
- *Responsible for results of each action as it has equal and opposite reaction. Admiring each one's role with dignity.*

The Murli clarifies that we are all responsible for each thought and action. Seeing and thinking are the two special methods for either becoming complete or complaining. In order to increase responsibility means that while we see and listen, we must always have divine thoughts.

4.29.11 Freedom

Freedom is a precious gift, which promises an experience of liberation and a feeling of no limits. The concepts of freedom and liberty have fascinated human beings. One of the greatest aspirations in the world today is to be free. People want the freedom to lead a life of purpose, to select freely a lifestyle in which they and their children can grow healthily and can flourish through the work of their hands, heads and hearts. In modern times the term freedom is misunderstood to mean to choose or risk doing whatever we like. The concept is misleading and a misuse of choice: For example, the rights to peace, happiness, and justice – regardless of religion, culture and gender - are innate. To violate the rights of one or more in order to free the self, family or nation is a misuse of freedom.

Misuse of freedom creates conflict and imbalance - in the self, in others and in the nature - and the result of that is evident in the modern world. Full freedom functions only when rights are balanced with responsibilities and choice is balanced with

conscience. There cannot be the experience of freedom, individually or collectively, if attention and effort are focused only on rights and choice.

The very first paragraph of the Preamble of the Declaration of Human Rights focuses one of the inherent dignity of all members of the human family.

It says that “recognition of the inherent dignity” is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world.

The foundation of human values, such as freedom, justice and peace rests on the dignity and worth-of the human being. The first article of the Declaration of human rights prepares the ground for “dignity” and asks all human beings to act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

Are we free to think on our own without undue, unwanted, harmful, external influences and binding internal impulses from deep-rooted habits and addictions within? Are we really able to articulate our purest thoughts unstained, accurately and clearly into words or actions? What about our freedom of choice and decision—making? Great pioneer souls like Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King and Nelson Mandela on their missionary journey in this world had exercised strong will-power in opting for decisions based on their strong convictions aligned with moral laws. Victor Frankl whose words of wisdom address our innermost being, said:

“Everything can be taken from us but one thing - the last of the human freedom to choose one’s attitude in any given set of circumstances, to choose one’s own way. Even when the body might be chained, does not the spirit remain free? Man was born free but found himself in self-created bondages as the spider weaves its own net”.

People have self created ‘bondages’ of lust, anger, attachment, ego, greed and violence. They continue to do battle internally, within their own minds and it is from that “battlefield” that all wars are born. The most invaluable freedom would be the freedom from sinful actions, which all human beings must surely be seeking deep in their hearts. We cannot really conceive true authentic freedom without inner liberation. Freedom is not absence of bondages, restrictions and limitations but it is a state in which the human soul can grow, develop and mature. Adverse situations also carry the seed of invaluable lessons.

Necessity is the mother of invention. We are clever in attributing the reasons why nowadays violence and aggression is rising. We can change only by changing the self.

4.29.12 Simplicity

Simple living and high thinking is an old saying. Simplicity calls on instinct, intuition and insight to create essenceful thoughts and emphatic feelings. Simplicity is the conscience which calls upon people to rethink their values. Simplicity grows from sacred roots. Simplicity is beautiful and like the moon, it radiates coolness. Those embodying simplicity are free from negative and complicated thinking. There is egolessness in simplicity and humility in feelings. We have many examples of simple living and high thinking in our history about great people who lived very simple life and preached the morals of high thinking:

Simplicity is truth....No matter how many disguises may come in front of it, the light of truth cannot remain hidden; it will reach out to the masses in a language so simple yet with a message so profound. The messengers of truth have always embodied ordinary forms, led simple lives, and adopted simple mediums of imparting their messages. They lived and spoke the truth, bringing beauty to the life of others.

Today in the modern world, our complications are increasing due to artificial lifestyle. Simplicity asks us to remove the mask of artificial life, the arrogance of expensive clothing and extravagant living:

Complications seem to be inevitable by-product of modern living. Simplicity gives birth to inspirations. Keeping my own mind calm and clear is the easiest method to sort out messy situations. Maintaining a balance of living simply yet comfortably, and only using what I really need of the earth's resources, I will always have abundance in my life.

In the Avayakt Murli of 03-10-92 there is a definition of the value of simplicity in the practical platform of life. You have become body conscious. These things cause many obstructions to reaching the destination. You have to maintain simplicity....Greatness should be visible in your simplicity.

Simplicity teaches economy and it helps to fill the gap between 'the haves and 'the have-nots'. The founder of Brahma Kumaris was also an example of "simple living". After his spiritual awakening, he dedicated his wealth and possessions in service of: humanity and adopted a very simple lifestyle.

4.29.13 Tolerance

Our failures are not so much in the realm of knowledge, techniques and skills but in that of increasing intolerance to challenges. The aim of tolerance is peaceful co-

existence. While tolerance recognizes individuality and diversity, it removes divisive masks and defuses tension created by ignorance. The seed of tolerance is sown with compassion and care. Where there is lack of love, there is lack of tolerance. In present times due to changing beliefs people consider tolerance as a weak point and that it creates suffering. More attention is being paid to gaining comforts by adopting shortcut methods of intolerance, and the lack of the inner strength of tolerance gives rise to violence and disharmony. In Spiritual Greatness it says of tolerance:

When tolerance begins to operate as a power, it is the people around us who notice. We ourselves are hardly aware of it. An image used for this power is a fruit—laden tree, yielding its fruits to the children who are throwing stones in an attempt to have the fruits. Tolerance as a power works in the same way. We are not affected by the stones being thrown at us. We remain untroubled and effortlessly continue to give of our ‘fruits’ the healthy thoughts and feelings that come from our innate goodness.

Tolerance develops the ability to accommodate the problems of everyday living:

“To tolerate life’s inconveniences is let go, be light, make others light, and move on. Mountains are made into molehills, and molehills are made into mustard seeds”.

Tolerance is not concession, not indifference. Tolerance is the knowledge of the other. It is mutual respect through mutual understanding. Let’s throw out the old myths and take up the results of current research. Man is not violent by nature. Intolerance is not ‘in our genes’. Fear and ignorance are the root causes of intolerance, and its patterns can be imprinted on the human psyche from an early age.

Tolerance gives contentment and inner peace. It is essential to imbibe this virtue in order to become successful and stable. The Avyakt Murli of 8.6.71 explains the benefits of the power of tolerance:

Those who are tolerant, are able to make a difficult task easy with the power.....The virtue of tolerance is a very important dhama. The more you see the power of tolerance within yourself; accordingly, you should consider yourself to be content with yourself and others to be content with you. How will you develop the power of tolerance in yourself? The more you become loving; the greater the power is in that love.

4.29.14 Unity

According to Gandhiji, religion includes in it the idea of unity in the world.

There should be no distinction of caste, creed and color. He did not maintain any

fundamental difference between any great religions. India has a mission for the world and the mission is “World-Unity”.

He had the dream of Vishva Kuturnba or the world as one family. Unity is harmony within and among the individuals in the group. Unity is sustained by concentrating energy and focusing thought by accepting and appreciating the value of mutual understanding. Unity increases from the spirit of equality and respect for universal principles. Looking inward helps harmonize thoughts, words and actions. Such personal integration keeps the individual in harmony:

The orchestra creates a conscience of sounds by combining the distinct rhythmic patterns of each of its instruments. In the same way, the gathering becomes sweetly harmonious when each individual adopts the power to accommodate the capacities and specialties of the others.

United we stand, divided we fall. But today our world is facing diverse problems of disunity. Nations are at war with each other. There is again communal riots and violence in the society on different issues. Ego and inferiority produces disharmony. Sometimes, even in little matters, people quickly get upset, aggressive and isolate themselves into groups. As a result, humanity has not been able to sustain unity against the common enemies of civil war, poverty and violation of human rights. One definition of unity is:

Unity is harmony within and amongst people. It is built with a shared vision for the good of all and a common goal. Unity is appreciating the value of each person for their unique contribution. When there is willingness to accommodate others, unity blossoms.”

We would never be at peace and unity, until and unless we come to appreciate the power of unity in our thoughts, words and actions. So we need harmony in the heart, home, nation and the world.

“Wars are born in the minds of men” and “Peace is also born in the minds of men. In fact, deep reflection would enable a person to come to the conclusion that the root of war or peace, virtue or vice, good or evil is in the human mind. In the history of human development, whenever human mind and actions had violated human laws, steps were taken to control the violation of these laws. The Declaration of Human Rights by the United National General Assembly on 10th December, 1948 is one of the major steps in this direction. If we observe carefully we will notice that “Human

Rights are rooted in Human Values". As Jagdish Chander in his book on Human Rights. Thus, one must first know one's real identity, for, without knowing one's identity, one begins to discriminate on the basis of race, colour, caste, gender, etc; - all based on body. Body - consciousness is the cause of violation of human rights. Soul — consciousness naturally gives a person the tendency to act towards others as his brothers and to be loving, kind, considerate, compassionate and cooperative.

“During the present century, the great teachers of Indian namely, Ramakrishna Paramhansa, Vivekanand, Tagore, Radhakrishnan, Iqbal are considered to be great humanists. They all have preached the gospel of brotherhood, cooperation. Among these Indian contemporary philosophers, Vivekanand, Tagore and Gandhiji have made significant contributions.

The contemporary Indian philosophers', writers' and reformers' writings and thoughts have created the awareness in the minds of people, for the need of values in human life. Similarly yet in a more practical sense in every moment of the present scenario, the Brahma Kumaris' and thoughts raise the question "Why we are not peaceful and happy" and share that only by means of "Practice of values and virtues in our personal and individual life" can we change. This must be our main and only endeavour. Here practical means that thoughts are translated into an action. Thoughts can be translated in action by the simplest step - start thinking about our true nature, about what we are. The more we think of love, purity, peace, wisdom, the more we will become them. Weakness invites negative thinking Instead of thinking though we are not good, start thinking "we are good". Just by starting with this simple step, our mind will make us feel good. Slowly practicing one value will encourage us to follow others. This experience will break the cycle of negative comfortable thinking that tells us there is nothing wrong in violating human values.

The Researcher feels deeply concerned that while in process of writing a deeper analysis of "Universal Human Values", she has had wonderful inspirations and touching of visions from God's to write about the experience of values. Greater than the definition of values is the experience of values. The researcher feels that through the natural experience of writing, thinking and explaining values, they became "Living Values" and started taking positive shapes and faces in front of the eyes of researcher. These experiences have become "Practical Experiences" and practical

experiments to add to the Research of Values where the only thought about virtues and values was that they are the hidden solution to so many of our problems. As we think so we become and as we sow, we shall reap. So by sowing the seeds of peace, love, purity, joy, harmony, compassion and respect in our mind, we can feel the positive fragrance of values in our relations. Values are not alone, practice of one value is gently connecting us with other values and they become easy to practice.

4.30 Benefits of Raj Yoga Meditation

The teachings of Raja Yoga are extremely beneficial for developing positive attitude. In various situations one thinks; “I am just an actor in the world drama. I must try to play the role given to me in the best possible manner. I should not become anxious, depressed or worry about the activities of others because they are also playing their roles in the huge world dram. I remain detached and peaceful because I am just an observer of various scenes of the drama. I even observe my own activities. More so because my original nature is peaceful. I am a peaceful soul. I am a child of the ocean of peace—the Supreme Being.”

Fig. No. 45: Raja yoga Meditation Effects to Human Mind, Soul & Body Medicine

The spiritual knowledge also helps one to see the hidden benefits in every situation however stressful it may seem at its outset. He always thinks about the positive side of the coin. Hans Selye, Canada’s most honoured scientist also laid importance on

attitudes as “Rather than relying on drugs or other techniques, I think there is a better way to handle stress, pleasant or unpleasant. “Raja Yoga taught by BrahmaKumaris world spiritual university contains ample knowledge helping one to develop this attitude. More than thinking about it, talking about it, what is needed is to practice the method to develop the positive habit for the effective management of stress.

Meditation gives us mental relaxation as well as physical relaxation and constant peace and improves the quality of being. We ask one who has not felt pressed, at times, by the turmoil of events or the inanity of physical and natural environment, to seek inner calm and peace and fresh resources of vitality, within him? Meditation is the sure way to experience new zeal, powerful energy and real and lasting peace and to have in it a fountain of bliss.

One also gets his past errors of moral judgment and past acts, vitiated by ignoble tendencies, washed off the soul, for Yoga-Meditation is the detergent of mind. Thus meditation is of great value because it brings a great change in personality-traits and negative habits. This eliminates one’s tendencies of aggressiveness, exploitation, sensual indulgence, attachment, suspicion and hate. One, thereby, becomes a peaceful person, spreading vibrations of peace, having good will, doing positive thoughts. Raja yogameditation is thus the science of peace in one’s personal and social life.

Understanding of the spiritual knowledge helps one to do positive thinking and transform his attitudes towards the stressful situation. Hence meditation and spiritual knowledge help one to maintain stability of mind in the adverse circumstances. He accepts criticism and tries to correct himself. He will not be influenced by anger, Hopelessness, Attachment, Fear etc. He remains away from the unhealthy habits which provide only a temporary pleasure and makes ones mind weak. Thus spirituality based positive thinking helps one to attain the highest level of emotional equilibrium.

In recent years, the various health benefits of meditation have become more and more acknowledged by the scientific community as well as the public. While initially,

research concentrated more on the physiological benefits of meditation, there have recently been an increasing number of studies on the various psychological benefits, too. Apart from the pioneers of meditation research such as Harvard's Dr. Herbert Benson ("The Relaxation Response") and Jon Kabat-Zinn, there are now scientists such as Richard Davidson and Sara Lazar using the tools of modern brain research to explore the effects of meditation on your mind and health. Meditation can have various health benefits. Apart from its physiological benefits, it can also improve your psychological and spiritual well-being. More and more doctors are prescribing meditation in health centres all around the world and it certainly deserves your contemplation and consideration. Research has scientifically proven that practicing meditation in health and fitness programmes is a safe and simple way to balance your physical condition, emotional state and mental wellbeing and its countless *va lues* have been known and practiced for thousands of years. Listed below are just a few of the benefits sports professionals, celebrities and people all over the world are endorsing after practicing meditation in health and fitness programmes. In addition, there are numerous other advantages which are facilitated by Raj Yoga meditation.

4.30.1 Some of predominant benefits retrieved by means of power of Raj Yoga meditation are given as follows:

- ✓ *Enhances energy, strength, vigor and fitness.*
- ✓ *Helps keep blood pressure normal.*
- ✓ *Amazing stress buster.*
- ✓ *Creates a state of deep relaxation and general feeling of wellbeing.*
- ✓ *Increases concentration and strengthens the mind.*
- ✓ *Helps reduce heart disease*
- ✓ *Helps with weight loss.*
- ✓ *Builds self confidence.*
- ✓ *Reduces anxiety attacks as it lowers the levels of blood lactate.*
- ✓ *Increases serotonin which influences moods and behaviour. (Low levels of serotonin are associated with depression, headaches, obesity and insomnia.)*
- ✓ *Helps weight loss*
- ✓ *Helps cure addictions*

- ✓ *It produces contentment*
- ✓ *It reduces negativity and waste*
- ✓ *It frees the mind of bias, prejudice & hatred*
- ✓ *It enhances mental concentration\It improves decision making powers*
- ✓ *It improves efficiency and strengthens the will power*
- ✓ *It promotes innovation and intuition*

In path of spiritual upliftment, some unexpected moments came in the life of researcher when her experience was enriched in the process of sharing of experiences of meditation. The most memorable moments were when she got an outstanding opportunity to conduct meditation sessions for the President of India, Her Excellency, Mrs. Pratibha Devi Singh Patil, during her visit to Mount Abu in June. 2006, when she was the Governor of Rajasthan. At that time, during her visit to Global Hospital & Research Center, she was impressed by the effects of Raja yogaMeditation on the patients. Then she invited the researcher to conduct three days meditation sessions in the Governor House, Mount Abu. After the sessions she shared that she enjoyed the meditation process and experienced peace.

Meditation empowers us to assess a situation dispassionately and instead of acting out of habit, it creates a new solution of response. The Brahma Kumaris powerfully advocate idea of greater insight into the truth of the slogan—when we change the World changes.

Till, in the previous sections, the fundamental discussion of the various aspects of Brahma Kumaris, meditation, Raj Yoga meditation and Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris spiritual centre were discussed. Now, to explore further and in depth, the understanding of the spirituality concept is of great significance. In the following section, a brief of the spirituality and its significance have been discussed. Furthermore, the motivational aspects in human life are also discussed in the following section of the presented manuscript.

4.31 Reincarnation

Consciousness is ‘meta’ physical. As such, it cannot be destroyed by anything physical. Thus, the soul is immortal. It cannot die. The realization of the self as an immortal being brings an understanding of birth, life, death and rebirth as the cyclical stages of an eternal existence.

4.31.1 Reincarnation: Why Believe?

Once I have begun to base my sense of ‘who I am’ on perceiving myself as a soul rather than on perceiving only my temporary costume, the body, I deeply realize that, as a being of spiritual energy giving life to the body, I am immortal. I begin to understand that I change bodily costumes just as a snake sheds its skin, but I – the eternal soul – can never die.

4.31.2 Death & Rebirth

At the moment of physical death, the soul withdraws its energy from the organs of the body and vacates its seat in the middle of the forehead. It takes with it the impressions accumulated in that life and enters into the body of an unborn baby, while that new body is still being formed in its mother’s womb. This normally happens between the fourth and fifth month of pregnancy. A human soul only enters a human body. The type of body the soul enters and the conditions of birth are determined by the past actions of the soul in its previous life or lives, and the cumulative account of give and take that it has built up with other souls. Without proper understanding of this process, the leaving of one body and the taking of another is often an experience of great fear and anguish; but the details of the old life are soon obliterated by new experiences so that the soul is not overwhelmed and confused by past memories.

Fig. No. 46: Physical death, soul withdraws energy from middle of forehead

4.31.3 Reincarnation: What You Take with You

By the time the baby's body and brain are developed, the soul has all but forgotten the past and become accustomed to its new conditions and to the parents of its new body. However, although the soul cannot usually remember details of its past life or lives, it carries with it—in the form of attitudes, tendencies and personality—the cumulative effect of all that it has experienced and learned. All that is genetically brought to the new life is the physical make-up of the body, the racial type, the colour of eyes, shape of nose and so on. And although the environment in which a child is raised – as well as the personalities of those around the child – definitely exert an influence on the child's development, its tendencies and reactions to people and events are not biologically generated but are inherent in the soul from previous existences. Those predominant impressions recorded in the past life soon begin to manifest themselves and are expressed in the new surroundings.

4.31.4 Relationship in Other Lifetimes

Human life is based on inter-relationships between souls, which in turn are based on the different impressions present in each. These impressions determine the course of life, the nature of the soul's activities and its physical placement in a particular environment. Thus there is typically a link or an 'account' between two souls who have formed a relationship in one lifetime; that link will bring them together again in other lifetimes. This explains why many people have the sense of having met or

known a person before, even though they are apparently meeting for the first time. Or they experience meeting someone with the feeling of either attraction or repulsion even though they don't know them well enough in the current life to have developed those feelings. What is taking place is that the soul is recognizing the other soul – even though they have different bodies – from the last time they met.

4.31.5 Reincarnation: Process of Rebirth

Reincarnation is a process of rebirth. With each death come a new birth and the opening of a new chapter in the never ending story of life. With each new birth the soul carries on with its journey through eternity where it left off in terms of its 'accounts' in the previous birth. The soul is not the victim of an angry or vengeful God condemning it to a lifetime of deprivation or suffering for no apparent reason. The soul inherits a past created by its own self. The fact that the precise past causes for the circumstances of the new life are not apparent or visible does not mean that they don't exist. In other words, a soul born in fortunate circumstances is not the recipient of God's grace or blessings; rather it is reaping the reward of its own generous and beneficial actions done in the previous birth(s). Each soul is constantly experiencing the effect of some past action and also planting seeds to be reaped as some future fruit.

The understanding of reincarnation reinforces, in meditation, the experience of my own immortality, my eternal existence as a soul. This is excellent medicine for many types of fear, anxiety and limited thinking.

4.32 Our Home of Silence

Beyond the physical world of planets and galaxies there is a non-physical realm of subtle spiritual energy. Beyond that is a luminous world of pure silence, where souls abide in an incorporeal state-beyond acting or thinking-still, silent, aware, and in total peace. That world 'beyond sound' (nirvana) is the original home of all souls, from whence all souls have come onto the earth.

Fig. No. 47-World Paramdham ‘beyond sound’ (nirvana) of all souls onto earth

4.32.1 Where have I come from?

When I begin to consider myself to be a soul, the question often arises, “Where do souls come from?” In meditation I can explore dimensions of consciousness beyond the physical senses. Experiencing these dimensions increases my awareness of subtle realities of thought and feeling and ultimately takes me to a place of utter peace, purity and silence in which I feel as if I’ve returned to my original ‘home’. Together, the physical, subtle and soul ‘worlds’ comprises the three main levels of human consciousness.

4.32.2 Physical World

The world in which we are now living is known as the physical or corporeal world, because all living beings here have a gross, corporeal or manifest form. The physical earth can be thought of as a vast stage where we ‘play our parts’ in the drama of life, in different bodily ‘costumes’. It can also be thought of as a field, where seeds of action are sown and fruits are reaped as experiences of happiness and sorrow. Here ‘time’, ‘space’, ‘history’ and ‘geography’ are important parameters of existence; here the laws of science apply. It is a world of expression and experience.

4.32.3 Subtle World

Beyond the limits of the vast expanse of our solar system and distant galaxies there are regions of non-material light, unreachable by physical means and inaccessible to the physical senses. These realms can only be experienced through deep meditation

and divine insight. The subtle world is an intermediate dimension of pure, positive luminous energy in which there is the experience of one's subtle body of light and communication with other souls through pure spiritual thoughts and vibrations.

4.32.4 Soul World

Beyond the physical realm of action and the subtle realm of pure thought lies an infinite, timeless dimension of complete stillness, silence and peace. Suffused with golden-red luminosity, this is the realm of God, the Supreme Being, Parent of all souls. It is the original home of all souls, where we once dwelt in a dormant, seminal state of total belongingness and bliss. Experiencing this 'supreme region' (Paramdham) of highest consciousness in meditation renews and recharges the soul, empowering it with the strength to play its part in the physical world with peace, equanimity and enlightened clarity.

4.32.5 Going Home

In Raja Yoga meditation, not only do I journey inward to experience my essential self; I also journey upward into higher consciousness, going beyond the awareness of the physical body and the physical world. With practice I am able to perceive and experience the dimension of pure soul consciousness, beyond sound, activity and thought. In this place or state of awareness I experience complete freedom, peace, rest and comfort, as if I've come home to a place where I truly belong and where I can simply be.

4.33 Relationship with God

As meditation helps consciousness move beyond self-limiting beliefs, the presence of God is experienced in the state of yoga – a mental link with the Source of spiritual power.

We are used to knowing things by seeing them, hearing them, tasting them, touching or smelling them. Most of us have grown up in a 'seeing-is-believing' and 'hands on' culture and we are used to perceiving things in that way. Because we can't see, hear, taste, touch or smell God, the question arises – is God for real?

One can reach out to God with pure thoughts and be connected to Him. The soul experiences the response of pure feelings and spiritual strength. God is truth itself and thus can be recognized with the eye of truth.

Fig. No. 48: GOD – The Spiritual Sun

4.33.1 God: Supreme Soul

Like us, God is also a soul. Unlike us, He is referred to as the Supreme Soul – the only soul who never takes a body (gross or subtle, human or angelic) of His own. He is beyond the effects of actions and is never subject to the dualities of birth and death, pleasure and pain, success and failure. Being beyond the limits of time of this physical world, He retains absolute knowledge of the universe and all its dimensions.

4.33.2 Where is God?

God lives, not everywhere but somewhere. A thought of God almost always takes the eyes upwards, as though one is perhaps expecting a face to miraculously appear from behind the clouds or to beam down from the moon. Thoughts are powerful. They link one soul to another. If they are properly channelled, thoughts can even go where only the soul can travel – beyond the moon and stars to a dimension of golden red light, the original home of all souls. Immersed in the experience of the warmth of this light, the soul feels as though it is truly at home at last, and with God.

4.33.3 God – Spiritual Sun

Like the physical sun, which gives light and life indiscriminately to all beings, God is the Spiritual Sun, giving light to all, whomever and wherever they may be. He serves altruistically, without any selfish motives, reminding each one of their innate qualities

of love, peace and happiness. This is why He has been remembered in some countries and cultures by the name Shiva, The Benevolent One.

4.33.4 God's Wisdom, Love & Power

People may wonder why, if God exists, He doesn't wave a magic wand and fix things, making or at least influencing everyone so that they do exactly what they 'should' do. But God never takes away anyone's freedom of choice. God's wisdom is to recognize and respect each soul's individual identity, freedom and inherent goodness. God shares knowledge – a profound understanding of the dualities and dilemmas of love and hatred, happiness and sorrow, victory and defeat, etc. – but He does not make our choices for us. The soul is free to choose 'to be or not to be', 'to love or not to love'. God's love strengthens the soul's will to free itself from the distresses caused by vices such as selfish desire, anger, fear, ego and attachment. God's power helps the soul to recognize its highest potential and to aim for perfection by practising the art of simple living and high thinking. Such practice by a significant number of souls eventually brings about positive change in the whole of humanity.

When you learn to tune your mind in meditation to the mind of God, then whatever the situation, you always have a source of help and strength to draw upon – an infinite reservoir of power and virtues that is only a thought away

4.34 Law of Karma

Karma is a natural spiritual law or principle which governs all our interactions. It starts with the seed of thought which develops and grows over time through our feelings, attitude, words, actions, and relations. It finally settles into our souls as personality traits, only to emerge again in the form of another thought.

The Law of Karma can be understood as the spiritual equivalent of Newton's Third Law of Motion, which states that for every action [on the physical plane] there is an equal and opposite reaction. In physics, the understanding of the absoluteness of Newton's law shed so much light on a world that had previously been shrouded in mystery, that today it lies at the foundation of many advances in science and technology.

The Law of Karma is equally unequivocal in the spiritual dimension. It states that 'for every action on the spiritual plane there is an equal and opposite reaction'. This means that if happiness is given, happiness will be experienced in return and if sorrow is

given, sorrow will be experienced in equal measure. In other words, whatever emotion I cause another to experience must ultimately become my own experience. Understanding the natural Law of Karma – which governs the relationships between the human soul, God and the material world – is essential for cultivating right awareness and consciously choosing right thoughts and actions. As the practice of meditation leads to an experience of inner strength, practical methods are offered to help shape and direct spiritual power into accurate and effective responses and actions in daily life.

Fig. No. 49-Law of Karma

4.34.1 Consequences of Law of Karma

Understanding the Law of Karma makes me aware that each action (or karma) causes a return, a consequence; equally, events (and their effects) can only occur when there has been a corresponding cause. This means that whatever circumstances I'm in at the moment – whoever or whatever is compelling me or repelling me and whatever I am experiencing – is the consequence of my own prior thoughts, decisions and actions. Understanding the Law of Karma gives deep significance to concepts such as responsibility and justice. Sometimes the Law of Karma is only half understood. Someone may think helplessly, "If whatever is happening to me now is because of my past actions, then there's nothing I can do about it". But if the past created the present, the present also creates the future. Instead of being a slave to one's past,

understanding the Law of Karma inspires us to actively participate in creating our own destiny.

4.34.2 Law of Karma: Absolute Justice

Thought is a seed; action is its fruit. The quality of fruit is determined by the quality of its seed. Good thoughts lead to good actions which benefit others as well as one's self. The Law of Karma begins to work to my advantage when I stop habitual actions that are harmful, take responsibility to positively address the consequences of any such actions performed in the past, and pay attention to performing positive actions from this moment forward. The Law of Karma is a law of absolute justice whose long arm reaches easily from one life to the next, enabling the soul to reap the fruit of whatever seeds it has sown and to create the destiny it wants.

Meditation enables me to understand my karmic circumstances, empowers me to settle my 'karmic accounts' in the best possible ways and shows me how to accumulate 'karmic credit' for the future.

4.35 Eternal World Drama

Time is perceived as moving in cycles and life as a whole is presented as an unlimited drama on the stage of the world. This perspective of time and constantly changing scenes (history and geography) restores the ability to find meaning and significance in local and global events.

4.36 Eternity: Time as Cycle

It is difficult for the mind to comprehend eternity – no beginning, no end. Reasons 'why' are moot and mute when there's no starting place. If we look at a circle, at a wheel, it is impossible to find the beginning or the end. As we look at the natural world around me, we see never – ending cycles everywhere – in the waxing and waning of the moon; in the gradual changing of the seasons; in the measure of time on the face of a clock. Nothing in nature is a straight line. Why should human nature be an exception?

Fig. No. 50: Eternal World Drama

4.37 World Drama Cycle

The World Drama is a story of human souls, their rise and fall, victory and defeat, happiness and suffering, wisdom and ignorance, freedom and bondage. It is the story of the play of good and evil forces, and of the different stages through which human souls pass in five different epochs (acts). It is the story of humanity on its dramatic journey through the cycle of eternity. It is the greatest story ever told... And we all love a good story!

4.38 Five Acts of World Drama

Act 1- The Golden Age

Act One begins with the early morning scene of a golden age. Each individual manifests the divinity of purity, peace, happiness, love, and truth with complete inner harmony. Their loving actions and interactions are the threads of the fabric of society. These are divine beings whose respect for nature is such that they are served with abundance from the earth. Family life is fulfilling because relationships are based on mutual honesty and trust. The behaviour and attitude of all is selfless and sharing. The integrity of the soul is expressed in its natural wisdom and spiritual accomplishment. It is paradise.

Act II-The Silver Age

Act Two continues with an afternoon scene in which a very gradual decline is taking place, unnoticed by the actors, who have significantly increased in number. Even though they are still radiant with love and peace, even though nature is still

resplendent with colour and beauty, the original freshness that characterized the morning has gone. The actors are paying greater attention to external form and function and less to inner realities; the experiences of the senses are leaving impressions on the soul. Integrity begins to give way to influence. Material resources are spread a little more thinly to accommodate the growing demand. Although there is no negativity or sorrow, and all remain masters of the arts of life, the quality of everything is slightly less.

Act III- The Copper Age

The change from Act Two to Act Three as evening begins is a dramatic one. It is marked by a massive shift in consciousness from self-awareness to self-forgetfulness. This forgetfulness of the true spiritual self creates duality within the minds of the actors. The first traces of conflict within and of external strife appear within the play. This fall from the grace of soul-consciousness into the illusion of body-consciousness brings with it the loss of mastery. Human beings become compelled by a search for power and possessions to compensate for a growing inner void. Even while searching for lost truth and enlightenment they are deceived into believing that accumulating material possessions will bring them security and peace of mind.

Act IV- The Iron Age

Act Four finds the stage of the world in total darkness, illusion and despair. There has been an extreme decline in moral, ethical and spiritual values. Human beings are chained to the pillars of immoral practices and habits. Widespread sorrow and unrest have become the norm of human experience. The world is divided into many groups, many of which are pitted against each other in games of power conditioned by self-interest and expediency. The human family is at a breaking point. As the night wears on, the population explodes exponentially until the planet's resources reach their limits.

Act V- The Diamond Age

Act Five consists of only one scene in which the Director of the Drama becomes the primary Actor. He appears quietly in one corner of the stage and begins to unveil the truths inherent in the story of human life: the truth of the immortality of the soul, its true, eternal relationship with God and the true path to upliftment and fulfilment. These words of truth stir, in the actors, deep memories of their long distant past; there is an awakening. Standing at the dawn they can again observe the carousel of life in

its entirety – from divinity to duality, from gold to iron – each soul melding with the eternal rhythm within every moment until it comes full circle. With love for God in their hearts and truth once again permeating their being, the actors dance their way gradually off the stage, united in their vision of the approaching golden morning. The darkness of the night slowly lightens into the dawn of the new day. As the curtain comes down on Act Five, it rises again to mark the beginning of Act One. Humanity has come full circle: the old journey of life has ended; a new world begins.

The Tree of Life

The lesson on the Tree of Life offers insights into evolution and creation, illustrating why the world is so fragmented today, and explaining the value, the roles and the relationships between diverse human interest groups and disciplines such as religion, science, politics and business.

4.38.1 The Human Family Tree

The lifecycle of a tree in nature – its origin, growth in size, decline and rejuvenation – offers a good analogy for the lifecycle of the Human Family Tree. All parts of a tree are interconnected. Something that happens to one part of a tree affects the whole tree. To look at the almost fully – grown tree of humanity’s life on earth today is to observe and understand its journey through time

Fig. No. 51: Tree of Life

4.38.2 Seed of Humanity

The seed of humanity, of the human family, is God, the Supreme Being, the essence from which the whole tree of humanity grows. The trunk of the tree symbolises the era of paradise which emerges from that perfect Seed – that golden era before recorded history when there is unity of belief, culture, language and governance; that period of perfected civilization when there is no difference between the theory and practice of righteous living. People in such a time lack nothing, are totally fulfilled, and share a harmonious way of life. The closeness of the trunk to the seed symbolizes how souls at that time embody God’s qualities, living lives based on the principles of truth. Such souls are memorialized in stories and legends as ‘gods’ and ‘goddesses’, but few any longer understand that such divine beings actually once walked upon our earth.

4.38.3 Tree of Life Grows

As a tree grows, its trunk naturally expands in size. Similarly, the human population expands. More ‘leaves’ (individual human souls) appear on the tree. Just as leaves naturally leave their bud-like state and begin to unfold, so the deities open themselves to greater involvement with the physical world and concern with the physical body – the temple of the soul. Completely unaware that they are losing awareness of their true identity – the soul itself – in the process, they also lose touch with their original nature of purity, peace and truth.

4.38.4 Paradise Lost

This shift in consciousness brings a marked decline in power, purity and the ability to discern right from wrong. Divinity departs. Paradise is lost. Suddenly there is the experience of something other than peace and happiness. Suddenly there are feelings that are strange and uncomfortable. Suddenly there is unpleasantness, unrighteousness, unrest, and untruth. These ‘insects’ gnaw at many of the leaves and human actions become motivated by ever – growing demands for possessions, prosperity, position, and power. No longer the masters of self, souls become slaves to their desires.

As the unity of the trunk loses its integrity, minds begin to search for truth and hearts to long for comfort. The memory of God, the Seed, resurfaces from the depths of the human psyche. This intensifies the search for truth. In response, great prophet souls

one by one make their entrances, Abraham, Buddha, Christ and Mohammed – respectively bringing messages of a return to righteousness, of hope and forgiveness, of mindfulness and of single – mindedness. Each prophet soul establishes the mighty branch of a great religion on the Human Family Tree. The ideals of love, law, enlightenment, and surrender now manifest as major differences in approach.

4.38.5 Chaos & Confusion

Many new leaves emerge on the branches as the human family drastically increases in size. Chaos and confusion ensue as the search for self-realization and truth gives rise to divergent beliefs and ways of thinking. Each main branch diversifies into smaller limbs and twigs. Cults, sects and ‘– isms’ emerge. Meanwhile, within the central trunk of humanity, the worship of nature and of human beings as gurus takes hold. The human family is now divided by colour, race, religion and ideology, its increasing dysfunction mirrored by a corresponding increase in natural calamities, mental and physical disease, poverty and untimely death.

4.38.6 The Tree Reaches its Limits of Growth

In this ever increasing peacelessness more and more people turn toward God; but without knowing who He really is or what He does, doubt in His very existence also arises. The search for truth comes to focus exclusively on physical evidence, giving rise to wondrous advances in science and technology. Quickly faith in the veracity and power of science proliferates while religion and philosophy become materialistic and politicized. Meanwhile among the branches, faith becomes fundamentalism as those who tenaciously cling to traditional beliefs feel compelled to violently defend their views. Religion, language, culture have strayed very far indeed from their roots in divinity.

The tree reaches its limits of growth. Its roots are in a state of decay, its trunk barely visible amidst its jumbled tangle of sagging branches. Each soul hangs on helplessly, like a forlorn leaf on a twig of a wintry tree.

4.38.7 God Seed Regenerates Tree

But before old life dies, new life is given by the Seed, the Creator of the tree. God, the Seed of the Human Family Tree, reveals how that which was can be again. Awakened by the advent of this Seed, and deriving strength and sustenance by forming a renewed relationship with this One, individual human souls become foundational

roots from which a new young sapling can emerge. The regeneration of the Human Family begins.

Meditate deeply, visualizing yourself as a root soul sitting close to God, the Seed of our Human Family. Draw from that Seed the eternal essence of all that can be attained in life. Remain beneath the canopy of the knowledge of our Human Family Tree and all of your pure desires will be fulfilled.

4.39 SUCCESS STORY: -

A journey of thousands step starts with a single step. The single step is as important as the single positive thought. It is said that faster than the speed of light is the speed of mind. History is the witness of the truth of this statement from time immemorial, there are great and small examples in the world of people, who has changed the picture of their life, from falsehood to truth, despair to hope and hatred to love. The researcher in traveling back to the history of Brahma Kumaris from 1937 to the present moment, and she has heard of countless true stories of self transformation at different levels, at different times. As in the journey of transformation, each single step is important. In 1937 a single spark of Divine visions that transformed the whole life of one among the thousands and this was the founder of Brahma Kumaris Brahma Baba. His exemplary transformation was a revolutionary step and this single step was followed by million of steps on path of self-transformation. There are so many stories and songs of the souls, whose silent words, pure vibrations and joyful eyes tell the truth. Their transformation is visible from their lives. It is with difficulty that the researcher is to select a few examples of life stories to present when each one has a unique story to tell, Out of millions of such voices of hopes and change in their life through spirituality a few are presented here that are still inspiring others,, which can show the path of "Spiritual Renaissance" to present humanity.‘

CASE STUDY I

A survey on youth Transformation Through Rajyoga Meditation

A comprehensive survey of Brahma Kumaris Youth group was carried out in the month of January—February, 2006 with multiple objectives. The basic objective was to get a reliable data to identify different levels and areas of transformation among the youth due to Rajyoga practice. This was a nationwide survey involving more than eleven thousand Brahma Kumar Rajyogi youth across the length and breadth of our country.

The population of the present survey is Rajyogi youth from all states of India falling in the age group of 16 to 35 years. All of them are regular students of Rajyoga training followed by Rajyoga practice for different periods of time. It is noteworthy that the subjects under study have practiced Rajyoga, for at least one year after their Rajyoga training.

The subjects were asked whether they had any vice» before the exposure of Rajyoga. They had also to mention whether they had given up the respective vices after the practice of Rajyoga and since when.

The vices considered in the present survey included (I) addictions to drinking liquor, smoking, tobacco consumption and drug abuse; (II) immoral behaviour such as lust, corruption, gambling, viewing obscene films and reading obscene literature; (III) undesirable practices like taking non- vegetarian food, revengeful nature, indiscipline anti raging and (IV) antisocial acts such as destructive activities and violence.

Here is a brief synopsis of a statistical analysis of the survey:-

- The Rajyogi youth were divided into four age groups: 16 to 20(20%), 21 to 25(28%), 26 to 30(26%) & 31 to 35(26%) years. They were also subdivided into four groups according to their marital status: Kumari (Unmarried Female, 36%), Kumar (Unmarried Male, 43%), Manied Female (12%), Married Male (9%).
- Considering the years of practicing Rajgoya, youth were divided into five groups: 1-5 years (50%), 6-10 years (26%),- 11-15 Years (15%), 16-20 Years (5%), 21-25 Years (2%), 25-30 Years (1%). Thus youth practicing Rajyoga for] to 5 years formed half of the sample surveyed.
- The survey revealed the percentage of youth indulged in vices before the practice of Rajyoga where in 42% of youth were non- vegetarian, 29% were having revengeful nature, and the proportion of indulging in lustful activities and undisciplined behaviour was around 21% each. Fifteen percent had violent activities – Indulging in corruption, gambling, raging, drinking, drugs, obscene literature, smoking, tobacco consuming was in the range of about 5 to 12%. Thus 72% of the youth had indulged themselves in different vices before the exposure of Rajyoga.
- The results indicate that while all the 100% of subjects under survey have voluntarily committed themselves for observing lifelong celibacy, only a small

proportion amounting to 1.71% is yet to go for lifelong commitment in this regard.

- Celibacy is a great virtue, which Mahatma Gandhi also propagated, that results in holistic development of a person, and the nation in more ways than one. It has been seen as a simple, easy and natural result to Rajyoga practice.

The findings of the study indicate that 99.55% of the youth surveyed gave up different vices as a result of Rajyoga practice. Thus Rajyoga technique plays a very powerful role in the behavioural transformation of youth.

- Different youth in the study took different time spans to get rid of their vices. The time—frame varied from one year to five years. The most heartening fact is that around 90% of them managed to get rid of their negativities within five years of Rajyoga practice. About 75% of them took only one year to get transformed and about one to two percent of them took as long as 3 to 5 years. A marginal 3 to 4 percent of cases fell into the category of two to three years.
- To compare the proportion of total non-indulgence in vices before and after practicing Rajyoga, the statistical large sample test was carried out. The proportion of non-indulgence in vices was found very large after Rajyoga practice. So we can conclude that Rajyoga Practice is significantly effective in bringing positive transformation among youth.

Effect of Rajyoga – At a Glance

	No of Youth	%
Youth Surveyed	11393	100
Youth Not Indulged in Vices before Rajyoga Practice	3248	28.51
Youth Indulged in Vices before Rajyoga Practice	8145	71.49
Youth Gave up Vices after Practicing Rajyoga	8108	99.55
Total no. of Youth who gave up Vices after Rajyoga Practice	11356	99.68

4.40 MOTIVATION

4.40.1 Meaning of Motivation

Motivation is a theoretical construct used to explain behavior. It represents the reasons for people's actions, desires, and needs. Motivation can also be defined as one's direction to behavior, or what causes a person to want to repeat a behavior and

vice versa. A motive is what prompts the person to act in a certain way, or at least develop an inclination for specific behavior.

Motivation is literally the desire to do things. It's the difference between waking up before dawn to pound the pavement and lazing around the house all day. It's the crucial element in setting and attaining goals—and research shows you can influence your own levels of motivation and self-control..

4.40.2 Motivation Definition

Motivation is something that supports someone to do something. Harmer reported in his book “English Language Teaching” that motivation is some kind of internal drive which pushes someone to do some things in order to achieve something. In other hand, Brown defines motivation based on behaviorist and cognitive definition. Based on behaviorist brown defines motivation as anticipation of reinforcement which is powerful concept for the class room. Based on cognitive definition, Brown classified motivation definition into three categories. First based on drive theory, motivation stems from basic innate drives, so motivation have been exist since we are born. Second based on hierarchy, motivation is something that comes from individual needs. Third, based on self-control theory, motivation is something that appear if there is opportunity to make some one to make own choices about what to pursue and what not to pursue (self control). So, motivation is one of influential factor in learning that drives learners to struggle to reach their goals in learning process and can become a stimulus in learning process. It very influences the success of learning motivation. For example, a learner who is motivated to study English because he want to get a gift from his teacher will try to study hard to get the gift that is as stimulus in the learning process. Therefore, motivation is one of the most influential factor in teaching learning process.

4.40.3 Kinds of Motivation.

Motivation can be categorized in to some categories. Based on how motivation comes from, it can be divided into two categories. They are intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation rises from individual inside but extrinsic motivation come from outside of individual.

Intrinsic motivation is not influenced by external factors but it comes from individual inside factor. The internal factors might include needs, interest, and enjoyment. The needs of students can engage them to achieve learning goal. For example, a learner who learns English because he needs English skill to do communication In his social live has a high motivation in learning English in order to master English to help him

survive in social life. In other hand, interest also has a role in increasing motivation level of student. If a student is interested to study English they will reach the learning goal easily. Then, enjoyment is also important in increasing motivation of student. If the students do not feel enjoy in learning class, the material taught is difficult to be transferred. So, intrinsic motivation is motivation that is created by individual self influenced by personal factors that are needs, interest and enjoyment. The learners can create motivation by their self. For example, Indonesian students who study in English speaking country are motivated to learn English because English is the language that they use in their social life. They have to learn English because they need it to survive.

Intrinsic motivation is more influence than extrinsic motivation because intrinsic motivation rises from learner self not influence by external factor. This makes a learner to be aware that they need to learn it. Brown reported in his book that intrinsically motivated activities are ones for which there is no apparent reward except the activity self. People seem to engage in the activities for their own sake and not because they lead to an extrinsic reward .

Extrinsic motivation is the contrary of intrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation is influenced by external factor of learner. Marsh wrote in his book that motivation refers to external stimulus which follows as result of a certain response. In addition, Harmer explained in his book that extrinsic motivation is caused by any number of outside factors. That might include the hope of financial reward; need to pass an exam, or the possibility of future level (Harmer, 1988:51). So, extrinsic motivation is any stimulus which comes from outside of learner and which drives the learner in learning process. Any factor that comes from learner outside and that support students to study harder in learning process is called extrinsic motivation.

4.40.4 Theories of Motivation

Some of the most important theories of motivation are as follows: 1. Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory 2. Herzberg's Motivation Hygiene Theory 3. McClelland's Need Theory 4. McGregor's Participation Theory 5. Urwick's Theory Z 6. Argyris's Theory 7. Vroom's Expectancy Theory 8. Porter and Lawler's Expectancy Theory.

From the very beginning, when the human organisations were established, various thinkers have tried to find out the answer to what motivates people to work. Different approaches

applied by them have resulted in a number of theories concerning motivation. These are discussed in brief in that order.

4.40.4.1 Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory:

It is probably safe to say that the most well-known theory of motivation is Maslow's need hierarchy theory. Maslow's theory is based on the human needs. Drawing chiefly on his clinical experience, he classified all human needs into a hierarchical manner from the lower to the higher order.

In essence, he believed that once a given level of need is satisfied, it no longer serves to motivate man. Then, the next higher level of need has to be activated in order to motivate the man. Maslow identified five levels in his need hierarchy as shown in figure.52

Fig. No. 52: Maslow's Need Hierarchy

These are now discussed one by one:

a) Physiological Needs:

These needs are basic to human life and, hence, include food, clothing, shelter, air, water and necessities of life. These needs relate to the survival and maintenance of human life. They exert tremendous influence on human behaviour. These needs are to be met first at least partly before higher level needs emerge. Once physiological needs are satisfied, they no longer motivate the man.

b) Safety Needs:

After satisfying the physiological needs, the next needs felt are called safety and security needs. These needs find expression in such desires as economic security and protection from physical dangers. Meeting these needs requires more money and, hence, the individual is prompted to work more. Like physiological needs, these become inactive once they are satisfied.

c) Social Needs:

Man is a social being. He is, therefore, interested in social interaction, companionship, belongingness, etc. It is this socializing and belongingness why individuals prefer to work in groups and especially older people go to work.

d) Esteem Needs:

These needs refer to self-esteem and self-respect. They include such needs which indicate self-confidence, achievement, competence, knowledge and independence. The fulfillment of esteem needs leads to self-confidence, strength and capability of being useful in the organisation. However, inability to fulfill these needs results in feeling like inferiority, weakness and helplessness.

e) Self-Actualization Needs:

This level represents the culmination of all the lower, intermediate, and higher needs of human beings. In other words, the final step under the need hierarchy model is the need for self-actualization. This refers to fulfillment.

The term self-actualization was coined by Kurt Goldstein and means to become actualized in what one is potentially good at. In effect, self-actualization is the person's motivation to transform perception of self into reality.

According to Maslow, the human needs follow a definite sequence of domination. The second need does not arise until the first is reasonably satisfied, and the third need does not emerge until the first two needs have been reasonably satisfied and it goes on. The other side of the need hierarchy is that human needs are unlimited. However, Maslow's need hierarchy-theory is not without its detractors.

The main criticisms of the theory include the following:

1. The needs may or may not follow a definite hierarchical order. So to say, there may be overlapping in need hierarchy. For example, even if safety need is not satisfied, the social need may emerge.

The need priority model may not apply at all times in all places.

Researches show that man's behaviour at any time is mostly guided by multiplicity of behaviour. Hence, Maslow's preposition that one need is satisfied at one time is also of doubtful validity.

In case of some people, the level of motivation may be permanently lower. For example, a person suffering from chronic unemployment may remain satisfied for the rest of his life if only he/she can get enough food.

Notwithstanding, Maslow's need hierarchy theory has received wide recognition, particularly among practicing managers. This can be attributed to the theory's

intuitive logic and easy to understand. One researcher came to the conclusion that theories that are intuitively strong die hard’.

4.40.4.2 Herzberg’s Motivation Hygiene Theory:

The psychologist Frederick Herzberg extended the work of Maslow and proposed a new motivation theory popularly known as Herzberg’s Motivation Hygiene (Two-Factor) Theory. Herzberg conducted a widely reported motivational study on 200 accountants and engineers employed by firms in and around Western Pennsylvania.

He asked these people to describe two important incidents at their jobs:

- (1) When did you feel particularly good about your job, and
- (2) When did you feel exceptionally bad about your job? He used the critical incident method of obtaining data.

The responses when analysed were found quite interesting and fairly consistent. The replies respondents gave when they felt good about their jobs were significantly different from the replies given when they felt bad. Reported good feelings were generally associated with job satisfaction, whereas bad feeling with job dissatisfaction. Herzberg labelled the job satisfiers motivators, and he called job dissatisfies hygiene or maintenance factors. Taken together, the motivators and hygiene factors have become known as Herzberg’s two-factor theory of motivation Herzberg’s motivational and hygiene factors have been shown in the Table Herzberg’s motivational & cleanliness fragments have been appeared in Table6

Hygiene: Job Dissatisfaction	Motivators: Job satisfaction
	Achievement
	Recognition
	Work itself
	Responsibility
	Advancement
	Growth
Company Policy & administration	

Tab. No. 5: Herzberg's motivational & hygiene factors

According to Herzberg, the opposite of satisfaction is not dissatisfaction. The underlying reason, he says, is that removal of dissatisfying characteristics from a job does not necessarily make the job satisfying. He believes in the existence of a dual continuum. The opposite of 'satisfaction' is 'no satisfaction' and the opposite of 'dissatisfaction' is 'no dissatisfaction'.

According to Herzberg, today's motivators are tomorrow's hygiene because the latter stop influencing the behaviour of persons when they get them. Accordingly, one's hygiene may be the motivator of another.

However, Herzberg's model is labeled with the following criticism also:

1. People generally tend to take credit themselves when things go well. They blame failure on the external environment.
2. The theory basically explains job satisfaction, not motivation.
3. Even job satisfaction is not measured on an overall basis. It is not unlikely that a person may dislike part of his/ her job, still thinks the job acceptable.
4. This theory neglects situational variable to motivate an individual.

Because of its ubiquitous nature, salary commonly shows up as a motivator as well as hygiene.

Regardless of criticism, Herzberg's 'two-factor motivation theory' has been widely read and a few managers seem untamined with his recommendations. The main use of his recommendations lies in planning and controlling of employees work.

4.40.4.3 McClelland's Need Theory:

Another well-known need-based theory of motivation, as opposed to hierarchy of needs of satisfaction-dissatisfaction, is the theory developed by McClelland and his associates'. McClelland developed his theory based on Henry Murray's developed

long list of motives and manifest needs used in his early studies of personality. McClelland's need-theory is closely associated with learning theory, because he believed that needs are learned or acquired by the kinds of events people experienced in their environment and culture.

He found that people who acquire a particular need behave differently from those who do not have. His theory focuses on Murray's three needs; achievement, power and affiliation. In the literature, these three needs are abbreviated "n Ach", "n Pow", and "n Aff" respectively'.

They are defined as follows:

a)Need for Achievement:

This is the drive to excel, to achieve in relation to a set of standard, and to strive to succeed. In other words, need for achievement is a behaviour directed toward competition with a standard of excellence. McClelland found that people with a high need for achievement perform better than those with a moderate or low need for achievement, and noted regional / national differences in achievement motivation.

Through his research, McClelland identified the following three characteristics of high-need achievers:

1. High-need achievers have a strong desire to assume personal responsibility for performing a task for finding a solution to a problem.
2. High-need achievers tend to set moderately difficult goals and take calculated risks.
3. High-need achievers have a strong desire for performance feedback.

b) Need for Power:

The need for power is concerned with making an impact on others, the desire to influence others, the urge to change people, and the desire to make a difference in life. People with a high need for power are people who like to be in control of people and events. This results in ultimate satisfaction to man.

People who have a high need for power are characterized by:

1. A desire to influence and direct somebody else.
2. A desire to exercise control over others.
3. A concern for maintaining leader-follower relations.

c)Need for Affiliation:

The need for affiliation is defined as a desire to establish and maintain friendly and warm relations with other people'. The need for affiliation, in many ways, is similar to Maslow's social needs.

The people with high need for affiliation have these characteristics:

1. They have a strong desire for acceptance and approval from others.
2. They tend to conform to the wishes of those people whose friendship and companionship they value.
3. They value the feelings of others.

Figure is quick overview outline of three need hypotheses of inspiration just talked about. plan shows parallel relationship between necessities in each of theories. Maslow infers higher-lower sort out requirements, however Herzberg proposes inspiration & cleanliness parts.

4.40.4.4 McGregor's Participation Theory:

Douglas McGregor formulated two distinct views of human being based on participation of workers. The first basically negative, labeled Theory X, and the other basically positive, labled Theory Y.

Theory X is based on the following assumptions:

1. People are by nature indolent. That is, they like to work as little as possible.
2. People lack ambition, dislike responsibility, and prefer to be directed by others.

3. People are inherently self-centered and indifferent to organisational needs and goals.

4. People are generally gullible and not very sharp and bright.

On the contrary, Theory Y assumes that:

1. People are not by nature passive or resistant to organisational goals.

2. They want to assume responsibility.

3. They want their organisation to succeed.

4. People are capable of directing their own behaviour.

5. They have need for achievement.

What McGregor tried to dramatise through his theory X and Y is to outline the extremes to draw the fencing within which the organisational man is usually seen to behave. The fact remains that no organisational man would actually belong either to theory X or theory Y. In reality, he/she shares the traits of both. What actually happens is that man swings from one set of properties to the other with changes in his mood and motives in changing environment.

4.40.4.5 Urwick's Theory Z:

Much after the propositions of theories X and Y by McGregor, the three theorists Urwick, Ranganekar, and Ouchi-propounded the third theory labeled as Z theory.

The two propositions in Urwick's theory are that:

(i) Each individual should know the organisational goals precisely and the amount of contribution through his efforts towards these goals.

(ii) Each individual should also know that the relation of organisational goals is going to satisfy his/her needs positively.

In Urwick's view, the above two make people ready to behave positively to accomplish both organisational and individual goals.

However, Ouchi's Theory Z has attracted the lot of attention of management practitioners as well as researchers. It must be noted that Z does not stand for anything, is merely the last alphabet in the English Language.

Theory Z is based on the following four postulates:

1. Strong Bond between Organisation and Employees

2. Employee Participation and Involvement

3. No Formal Organisation Structure

4. Human Resource Development

Ouchi's Theory Z represents the adoption of Japanese management practices (group decision making, social cohesion, job security, holistic concern for employees, etc.) by the American companies. In India, Maruti-Suzuki, Hero-Honda, etc., apply the postulates of theory Z.

4.40.4.6 Argyris's Theory:

Argyris has developed his motivation theory based on proposition how management practices affect the individual behaviour and growth. In his view, the seven changes taking place in an individual personality make him/her a mature one. In other words, personality of individual develops

Immaturity	Maturity
√ Passivity	√ Passivity
√ Dependence	√ Independence
√ Capable of behaving in a few ways	√ Capable of behaving in many ways
√ Shallow interest	√ Deep interest
√ Short –term perspective	√ Long –term perspective
√ Subordinate position	√ Super ordinate position
√ Lack of self awareness	√ Self awareness and control

Argyris views that immaturity exists in individuals mainly because of organizational setting and management practices such as task specialization, chain of command, unity of direction, and span of management. In order to make individuals grow mature, he proposes gradual shift from the existing pyramidal organization structure to humanistic system; from existing management system to the more flexible and participative management.

He states that such situation will satisfy not only their physiological and safety needs, but also will motivate them to make ready to make more use of their physiological and safety needs. But also will motivate them to make ready to make more use of their potential in accomplishing organizational goals.

4.40.4.7 Vroom's Expectancy Theory:

One of the most widely accepted explanations of motivation is offered by Victor Vroom in his Expectancy Theory. It is a cognitive process theory of motivation. The theory is founded on the basic notions that people will be motivated to exert a high level of effort when they believe there are relationships between the effort they put forth, the performance they achieve, and the outcomes/ rewards they receive.

The relationships between notions of effort, performance, and reward are depicted in fig 53

Fig. No. 53: Vrooms expectancy model of motivation

Thus, the key constructs in the expectancy theory of motivation are:

- a) Valence:** Valence, according to Vroom, means the value or strength one places on a particular outcome or reward.
- b) Expectancy:** It relates efforts to performance.
- c) Instrumentality:** By instrumentality, Vroom means, the belief that performance is related to rewards.

Thus, Vroom's motivation can also be expressed in the form of an equation as follows: $Motivation = Valence \times Expectancy \times Instrumentality$

Being the model multiplicative in nature, all the three variables must have high positive values to imply motivated performance choice. If any one of the variables approaches to zero level, the possibility of the so motivated performance also touches zero level.

d) However, Vroom's expectancy theory has its critics. The important ones are:

1. Critics like Porter and Lawler labeled it as a theory of cognitive hedonism which proposes that individual cognitively chooses the course of action that leads to the greatest degree of pleasure or the smallest degree of pain.
2. The assumption that people are rational and calculating makes the theory idealistic.
3. The expectancy theory does not describe individual and situational differences.

But the valence or value people place on various rewards varies. For example, one employee prefers salary to benefits, whereas another person prefers to just the reverse. The valence for the same reward varies from situation to situation.

In spite of all these critics, the greatest point in the expectancy theory is that it explains why significant segment of workforce exerts low levels of efforts in carrying out job responsibilities.

4.40.4.8 Porter & Lawler's Expectancy Theory:

In fact, Porter and Lawler's theory is an improvement over Vroom's expectancy theory. They posit that motivation does not equal satisfaction or performance. The model suggested by them encounters some of the simplistic traditional assumptions made about the positive relationship between satisfaction and performance. They proposed a multi-variate model to explain the complex relationship that exists between satisfaction and performance.

What is the main point in Porter and Lawler's model is that effort or motivation does not lead directly to performance. It is intact, mediated by abilities and traits and by role perceptions. Ultimately, performance leads to satisfaction,. The same is depicted in the following Fig 54

Fig. No. 54: Porter & Lawler Motivation model

There are three main elements in this model. Let us briefly discuss these one by one.

a) Effort:

Effort refers to the amount of energy an employee exerts on a given task. How much effort an employee will put in a task is determined by two factors-

- (i) Value of reward and
- (ii) Perception of effort-reward probability.

b) Performance:

One's effort leads to his/her performance. Both may be equal or may not be. However the amount of performance is determined by the amount of labour and the ability and role perception of the employee. Thus, if an employee possesses less ability and/or makes wrong role perception, his/her performance may be low in spite of his putting in great efforts.

c) Satisfaction:

Performance leads to satisfaction. The level of satisfaction depends upon the amount of rewards one achieves. If the amount of actual rewards meet or exceed perceived

equitable rewards, the employee will feel satisfied. On the contrary, if actual rewards fall short of perceived ones, he/she will be dissatisfied.

Rewards may be of two kinds—intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. Examples of intrinsic rewards are such as sense of accomplishment and self-actualization. As regards extrinsic rewards, these may include working conditions and status. A fair degree of research support that, the intrinsic rewards are much more likely to produce attitudes about satisfaction that are related to performance.

There is no denying of the fact that the motivation model proposed by Porter and Lawler is quite complex than other models of motivation. In fact motivation itself is not a simple cause-effect relationship rather it is a complex phenomenon Porter and Lawler have attempted to measure variables such as the values of possible rewards, the perception of effort-rewards probabilities and role perceptions in deriving satisfaction.

They recommended that the managers should carefully reassess their reward system and structure. The effort-performance-reward-satisfaction should be made integral to the entire system of managing men in organization.

4.40.5 Role of motivation in any learning process

Motivation has several effects on students' learning and behavior.

- *Motivation directs behavior toward particular goals.* Motivation determines the specific goals toward which learners strive. Thus, it affects the choices students make—for instance, whether to enroll in physics or studio art, whether to spend an evening completing a challenging homework assignment or playing videogames with friends.
- *Motivation leads to increased effort and energy.* Motivation increases the amount of effort and energy that learners expend in activities directly related to their needs and goals. It determines whether they pursue a task enthusiastically and wholeheartedly or apathetically and lackadaisically.
- *Motivation increases initiation of and persistence in activities.* Learners are more likely to begin a task they actually *want* to do. They are also more likely to continue working at it until they've completed it, even if they are occasionally interrupted or frustrated in the process. In general, then, motivation increases students' time on task, an important factor affecting their learning and achievement .

- *Motivation affects cognitive processes.* Motivation affects what learners pay attention to and how effectively they process it. For instance, motivated learners often make a concerted effort to truly understand classroom material—to learn it meaningfully—and consider how they might use it in their own lives.
- *Motivation determines which consequences are reinforcing and punishing.* The more learners are motivated to achieve academic success, the more they will be proud of an A and upset by a low grade. The more learners want to be accepted and respected by peers, the more they will value membership in the “in” group and be distressed by the ridicule of classmates. To a teenage boy uninterested in athletics, making or not making the school football team is no big deal, but to a teen whose life revolves around football, making or not making the team may be a consequence of monumental importance.
- *Motivation often enhances performance.* Because of the other effects just identified—goal-directed behavior, effort and energy, initiation and persistence, cognitive processing, and the impact of consequences—motivation often leads to improved performance. As you might guess, then, students who are most motivated to learn and excel in classroom activities tend to be our highest achievers. Conversely, students who have little interest in academic achievement are at high risk for dropping out before they graduate from high school.

Motivation has a direct impact on how an individual learns. The affects of motivation is normally far reaching because it increases an individual’s energy level, determines the persistence in reaching a specific goal, affects the types of learning techniques used and an individual’s thinking processes.

According to human development professionals, there are two types of motivation, extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic is determined by the individual’s outside surrounding and specific tasks. Intrinsic motivation can be found within the individual since the task can be viewed as valuable. Therefore, when applying the affect that motivation has on the learning process, it is clear that people learn better based on the perceived value of the task, subject matter, personal goals, financial incentives and wide array of different factors.

Motivation can be increased or decreased based on many different factors. This is one of the reasons why instructors in any educational institution can have a substantial

impact on their students learning, since they are a part of the student's intrinsic motivation environment.

Some instructors are better at employing numerous positive motivation techniques and strategies than others. As a result, the students can obtain a sense of satisfaction from excelling in a class or they may receive low grades because they are demotivated.

For instance, if the instructor can explain to the students how a specific subject matter can relate to real life situations, the students are more likely to have a personal interest in learning what's being presented to them. One of the best examples of real life value situations is the importance of learning math. Math instructors who know how to relay the value of knowing how to count one's personal funds, will have a better chance at gaining the students interest and keeping them engaged at all times.

While some students are motivated by extrinsic factors, others may be motivated purely by intrinsic factors. In these situations, the student may have a goal that they want to reach by a certain time. In order to accomplish their goals, the information that they learn is of great value to them.

For instance, if the student wants to be a physician or work in the medical field, they may be driven by it as an attainable goal. As a result, they may want to invest all of their free time in getting to the next level. If they want to get into the top Ivy League schools, they will also seek to achieve the highest grades. Whatever the individual's motivation factor is, it is clear that motivation and learning will often go hand in hand. Sometimes an individual motivation can be adversely affected. From past failures with certain subject matter to teachers who fostered an intimidating learning environment, adults and children may be demotivated because of numerous situations. Getting motivated again is often hard but it can be done.

Motivation has a great impact on the learning process. Motivation alone can determine if the person will pass or fail. While some people learn more by outside influences, others may achieve more by their personal aspirations. Whatever the situation, everyone involved in any learning process should know how motivation affects learning.

4.40.6 Motivation factors for learning meditation in particular

Everyone hits a slump in life, but there is always hope. If you have found yourself in a rut, suffering from a stalled career, or even finding it hard to get out of bed in the

morning, meditation is the key to get you back on track. Here are 5 reasons meditation can pump up you up:

a) *Meditation can help focus your mind and renew your enthusiasm.* When you meditate, you learn to let go of your negative thoughts, refreshing your mind, so that life feels new again. By disciplining the mind, a natural untapped, latent store of energy surfaces from within, thereby making the impossible, possible.

b) *Meditation naturally reforms negative thinking.* If your lack of motivation comes from depression, cynicism, or from disenchantment with life in general, meditation is a great way to change your thought patterns. Often, ruts come from the repetition of thoughts, words, and deeds. Meditation can put you back on the mountaintop, or at least give you the necessary positive mindset.

c) *Meditation eliminates anxiety, depression, and addiction.* Ninety percent of the thoughts you had yesterday will make up the thoughts you have today. Do you see the implications? After meditation roots out all of the dysfunctional thought patterns, anxiety, depression, addiction, etc, in the most dramatic way, your life will be forever transformed. A transformed life is a motivated life.

d) *Meditation gives you a new identity.* When you meditate, you stop identifying with the same thoughts and feelings you had yesterday, giving yourself space to step out of your routine, viewing the world through a new set of eyes. Change breeds motivation.

e) *Meditation reconnects you to higher levels of emotion.* Another way meditation motivates us is through its natural ability to increase our feelings of happiness, love, inter-connectedness, compassion, and well-being. When these states are created in the mind, we feel better about ourselves, our lives, and others. Feeling good about life is what keeps us moving forward.

4.40.7 Advantages of Meditation

There are so many advantages to meditation. When I first originally thought of this post, I indeed wanted to make it 100 benefits long (think big right!), however, I wasn't sure I could find more than perhaps 20-25 benefits. Well, I made it happen! Meditation is as powerful as I thought it would be. Here is the definitive list of benefits that meditation can provide you.

4.40.7.1 Physiological benefits:

- 1- It lowers oxygen consumption.
- 2- It decreases respiratory rate.
- 3- It increases blood flow and slows the heart rate.
- 4- Increases exercise tolerance.
- 5- Leads to a deeper level of physical relaxation.
- 6- Good for people with high blood pressure.
- 7- Reduces anxiety attacks by lowering the levels of blood lactate.
- 8- Decreases muscle tension
- 9- Helps in chronic diseases like allergies, arthritis etc.
- 10- Reduces Pre-menstrual Syndrome symptoms.
- 11- Helps in post-operative healing.
- 12- Enhances the immune system.
- 13- Reduces activity of viruses and emotional distress
- 14- Enhances energy, strength and vigour.
- 15- Helps with weight loss
- 16- Reduction of free radicals, less tissue damage
- 17- Higher skin resistance
- 18- Drop in cholesterol levels, lowers risk of cardiovascular disease.
- 19- Improved flow of air to the lungs resulting in easier breathing.
- 20- Decreases the aging process.
- 21- Higher levels of DHEAS (Dehydroepiandrosterone)
- 22- prevented, slowed or controlled pain of chronic diseases
- 23- Makes you sweat less
- 24- Cure headaches & migraines
- 25- Greater Orderliness of Brain Functioning
- 26- Reduced Need for Medical Care
- 27- Less energy wasted
- 28- More inclined to sports, activities
- 29- Significant relief from asthma
- 30- improved performance in athletic events
- 31- Normalizes to your ideal weight
- 32- harmonizes our endocrine system
- 33- relaxes our nervous system
- 34- produce lasting beneficial changes in brain electrical activity

35- Cure infertility (the stresses of infertility can interfere with the release of hormones that regulate ovulation).

36- Helps in building sexual energy & desire

4.40.7.2 Psychological benefits:

Builds self-confidence.

- 1 Increases serotonin level, influences mood and behaviour.
- 2 Resolve phobias & fears
- 3 Helps control own thoughts
- 4 Helps with focus & concentration
- 5 Increase creativity
- 6 Increased brain wave coherence.
- 7 Improved learning ability and memory.
- 8 Increased feelings of vitality and rejuvenation.
- 9 Increased emotional stability.
- 10 improved relationships
- 11 Mind ages at slower rate
- 12 Easier to remove bad habits
- 13 Develops intuition
- 14 Increased Productivity
- 15 Improved relations at home & at work
- 16 Able to see the larger picture in a given situation
- 17 Helps ignore petty issues
- 18 Increased ability to solve complex problems
- 19 Purifies your character
- 20 Develop will power
- 21 Greater communication between the two brain hemispheres
- 22 React more quickly and more effectively to a stressful event.
- 23 Increases one's perceptual ability and motor performance
- 24 Higher intelligence growth rate
- 25 Increased job satisfaction
- 26 Increase in the capacity for intimate contact with loved ones
- 27 Decrease in potential mental illness
- 28 Better, more sociable behaviour

- 29 Less aggressiveness
- 30 Helps in quitting smoking, alcohol addiction
- 31 Reduces need and dependency on drugs, pills & pharmaceuticals
- 32 Need less sleep to recover from sleep deprivation
- 33 Require less time to fall asleep, helps cure insomnia
- 34 Increases sense of responsibility
- 35 Reduces road rage
- 36 Decrease in restless thinking
- 37 Decreased tendency to worry
- 38 Increases listening skills and empathy
- 39 Helps make more accurate judgements
- 40 Greater tolerance
- 41 Gives composure to act in considered & constructive ways
- 42 Grows a stable, more balanced personality
- 43 Develops emotional maturity

4.40.7.3 Spiritual benefits:

- 1 Helps keep things in perspective
- 2 Provides peace of mind, happiness
- 3 Helps you discover your purpose
- 4 Increased self-actualization.
- 5 Increased compassion
- 6 Growing wisdom
- 7 Deeper understanding of yourself and others
- 8 Brings body, mind, spirit in harmony
- 9 Deeper Level of spiritual relaxation
- 10 Increased acceptance of oneself
- 11 Helps learn forgiveness
- 12 Changes attitude toward life
- 13 Creates a deeper relationship with your God
- 14 Attain enlightenment
- 15 Greater inner-directedness
- 16 Helps living in the present moment
- 17 Creates a widening, deepening capacity for love

- 18 Discovery of the power and consciousness beyond the ego
- 19 Experience an inner sense of “Assurance or Knowingness”
- 20 Experience a sense of “Oneness”
- 21 Increases the synchronicity in your life

4.40.8 How to Enhance motivation

The most important types of motivation for *educational psychology* is achievement motivation, peoples tendencies to strive for success and choose activities that are goal oriented. The main difference in achievement is the difference in how someone is motivated. Some people are motivated to learn, while others are motivated to perform well and get a good grade. It is important that teachers should try to convince their students that learning rather than grades are the purpose of academic work. This can be done by emphasizing the interest value and practical importance of the material that the students are studying and by de-emphasizing grades and other rewards.

It has also been seen that *teachers'* expectations of their students have an effect on student motivation. Research has generally found that students will live up or down to their teachers' expectations for them, particularly in younger grades when teachers know relatively little about their students' levels of achievement. In order to make sure that students will achieve communicates positive expectations to them. The teacher must communicate the expectation to their students that they feel that their students can learn the material.

There are also ways that a teacher can imply that they have positive expectations for their students. These include:

- * Waiting for the student to respond to a question.
- * Avoid making distinctions of achievement among students. Assessment and results should be a private matter.
- * Treat all students equally. Call on all students regardless of achievement levels, and spend equal amounts of time with them. Guard against biases.

4.40.9 Increasing Motivation

Sometimes the course itself is interesting enough and useful enough for a student to be motivated to do well in it. However, much of what is learned in school is not inherently interesting to most students. For this reason a variety of incentives and

rewards for learning are introduced. These might be praise, grades, recognition or prizes. However, it has been researched whether or not extrinsic rewards end up decreasing intrinsic *motivation*. There are ways to enhance intrinsic motivation in the classroom:

a) Arouse interest: It is important to convince students of the importance and interest level of the material that is about to be presented, to show that the knowledge to be gained will be useful.

b) Maintaining curiosity: A skilful teacher will use a variety of means to further arouse or maintain curiosity in the course of the lesson. The use of demonstrations helps to make students want to understand.

c) Use a variety of interesting presentation modes: The motivation to learn is enhanced by the use of interesting materials, as well as by a variety in the way that material is presented. For example a teacher can use films, guest speakers, demonstrations and so on, in order to maintain interest in a subject. However, all of these different materials need to be carefully planned and should all focus on the course objectives and complement each other.

d) Help students set their own goals: People will work harder for goals that they have set for themselves, than if they were set by others.

e) Express clear expectations: Students need to know exactly what they are supposed to do, how they will be evaluated, and what the consequences of success will be. Failure often stems from confusion about what was asked of them.

f) Provide clear feedback: Feedback can serve as an incentive. It can be an adequate reward in some cases. Feedback must be clear and specific and given close in time to the performance. It should be informative and motivational and help by giving them suggestions for future success.

4.40.10 Brahma Kumaris students Experiences:

Thousands of people across the world shared their actual transformation experiences and few are listed below

4.40.10.1 Ken O' Donnell in his book in his book Pathways to Higher Consciousness about how after practicing many other meditation methods, he ultimately found the Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga to be the most practical approach. He writes :

I first made contact with the teachings of the Brahma Kumaris World spiritual

university in 1975 during a period of intense search. After journeying through many countries and having a firsthand experience of some of the world's major traditions. I was looking for something more than just answers. I was after fresh insights into living with myself and with world around.

I was aware that mystics in Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam and Judaism, have drawn upon meditative techniques to deepen spiritual experience for thousands of years. My greatest experience difficulty was in finding people who were true to what they preached. I clearly wanted to set out towards the top of the mount of higher consciousness but realized I needed help. I couldn't do it on my own.

Knocking the door of the London branch of the Brahma Kumaris, I was greeted by a woman who radiated so much love and light that I was immediately intrigued and inspired to begin the study of the most ancient yet modern form of meditation called Rajyoga. I was advised to experiment with the ideas. I was encouraged to put the ideas I understood and accepted into practice as much as possible. The purely practical approach I had now discovered, appealed to me profoundly. I've been studying and practicing Raja Yoga meditation ever since

4.40.10.2 **Anthony Strano** has been practicing and teaching Raja Yoga meditation with the Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university for nearly 35 years. He shares his experience in his book *Eastern Thought for the Western Mind*, "raja Yoga meditation gently and naturally opens the doors of our perception, producing insights and experiences that bring lasting change in his life. It heals old wounds and restores our capacity to love, to learn and adapt and to envision and build a better future. One of the exceptional points of the Brahma Kumaris literature is that the books written by western and India author's on subjects of spirituality and meditation are also the reflection of their practical

4.40.10.3 **Anthony Strano** in *The Alpha point – A Glimpse of God* describes loving close link with God in silence.

Rajyoga meditation does not involve concentration on any physical object such as a flower or a candle. It is also not the repetition of mantra, but rather it defines the word "Mantra" (man+tra) as flow of thoughts:

A mantra is a sacred phrase, word or sound which is repeated constantly, either

loudly, silently or in thoughts only. It translates literally as man (mind) and tra (to free); so, a mantra is that which frees the mind. Raja Yoga meditation does involve concentration, but no physical object is involved. The object of concentration is the inner self. Instead of repeating one word or phrase, as in a mantra, a flow of thoughts is encouraged, thus using the mind in a natural way.”

Rajyoga deals with the spiritual dimension of our inner life. So that the mind can go beyond the distraction of the physical world and into that realm of infinite light which is the spiritual dimension. There, our focus of mind is on God as a point of Light, and to connect with the qualities of the Supreme. This changes the quality of our consciousness. In this way, meditation practice is a process of shifting from body consciousness to soul consciousness, which is the pure consciousness of inner virtues of peace, love, purity and positivity. So meditation practice strengthens our inner values of soul.

4.40.10.4 Dr. Peter Iveson from London shared his experiences as

“I am experiencing the peace and love and bliss that flow from God”

Little did I imagine, when I walked into the Raja Yoga centre in London on 18th August, 1977, that my life would be totally transformed within the space of a few days, that I would experience for myself the peace and love and power of God, and that I would truly be born again and start a new life in Raja yoga.

Brought up as a Christian, I lapsed into agnosticism in the course of my studies at university, when I encountered the writings of such atheistic philosophers as Bertrand Russell, Julian Huxley, Karl Marx. Studying Bio- Chemistry and Molecular Biology, I felt that human life would eventually be explained in terms of molecules and chemical reactions and that there was no need to assume the existence of a soul.

When I came to the Raja Yoga centre in August, the experience which I had been seeking for so long, all hit me at once. The effect was quite overwhelming. Now I know that my search for knowledge and truth is over. I have found my Father, the Supreme Father, Shiv Baba and I am experiencing the peace and love and bliss which flow from HimI have had more spiritual experiences than I expected to have in my life time. My relationships with others as souls and have renounced the vices of sex lust, anger, greed etc. I can get through my work with much less stress and worry than before. I have renounced the use of alcohol, adopted a simple vegetarian diet,

and freed myself. Now my aim is to study this Raja Yoga, so that I can teach it, and enable others to have the experience of, peace and love and bliss

Fig. No. 55: Why to practice BKRM

4.41 Background

On the basis of the employed qualitative and quantitative research paradigm and respective data collection, in this section of the presented thesis, the responses retrieved from devotees at Brahma Kumaris and Raja yogapractioners statistically and their significances have been discussed. The data has been retrieved through semi-structured interviews conducted with Rajyogis at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. The responses have been processed for sampling so as to process further for statistical process based data analysis. In this research study, 500 respondents have been interviewed.

4.42 Data Reliability

For any empirical analysis based research or study, it becomes significant to verify the answers collected through interviews and provided by the respondents. To verify the questionnaires, the reverse wording questions were also asked while interviewing the respondents. The predominant objectives of this process was to avoid the biasing probability, especially in that case when the respondents doesn't read out all questions and doesn't understand properly, and tends to respond irrespective of his ability and understanding.

Collecting the response data, it was processed for outlier verification and removal. In fact, the outlier detection and removal was done for those cases when the respondent has given same answer for forward as well as reverse question. Such outlier presence can also be possible due to typing or during response collection process. Eliminating the outliers (having insignificant responds or ambiguous responses), a total of 500 responses were considered for analysis.

4.42.1 Reliability Test

Preparing the complete genuine data responses for analysis, the data were processed for internal constituency and reliability. The consistency check included 5-point Likert scale response consistency, responses for each questionnaire, etc. Furthermore, to assess the internal consistency and reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha estimation was done using SPSS software tool. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was retrieved at 0.872 for 5-point Likert scale that signifies the higher level of internal consistency and reliability. It should be noted that the Chronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.70 or higher value signifies good reliability. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was estimated for various factors such as 1)personal thrust, 2)Psychological, Physiological and Spiritual factors, 3)psychological soundness, mental stability, physiological strength and disease resilience, 4)novel life culture, environment, and 5)holy practices at Brahma Kumaris, which too depicted higher reliability with the score of 0.847, 0.873, 0.895, 0.871, and 0.915 respectively. Furthermore, the higher reliability index of the considered scale revealed that the removal of any question might result into reduced coefficient output and hence considered all questionnaires to ensure reliability of the empirical study.

4.43 Profile of Participants

In this research and study, the predominant objective of the study has been emphasised on assessing various motivational factors that motivates devotees or Raj yogis to practices Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris organization. In order to explore significant information from Raj Yoga practitioners (Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga Meditation (BKRM)) at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, a total of 500 respondents have been interviewed where the well defined semi-structured interviews and personal interaction was scheduled with respondents. Among these respondents, the devotees at different level or hierarchy of BK organization were interviewed, including people from public service domain, administration, educational verticals, organizers etc, were interviewed.

In any organization, the purpose of serving at different hierarchical status plays a significant role in assuring personal satisfaction and zeal to serve, and particularly with the organization like BK, such factors and their significance become inevitable. Therefore, considering the key research objective to assess the various motivational factors to learn Raj Yoga meditation and practices at Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters, Mount Abu, in these research respondents from different department or division along with different status have been interviewed on personal basis. The quantitative distribution of respondents is given in Table 7.

As depicted in following Table 7, the respondents from five complexes have been considered. Since, Pandav Bhawan is one of the oldest complex of Brahma Kumaris spiritual center, it accommodates majority of elderly devotees residing since long time. Since, the proposed study intends to explore various motivational factors which motivates youths to follow Raj Yoga meditation at BK, majority of respondents have been interviewed at Shantivan Complex that accommodates majority of youths. Similarly, considering exploration towards physiological analysis, a total of 22 respondents have been interviewed at Global Hospital and Research center. A total of 116 respondents have been interviewed Gyan Sarovar Complex. The diversity of responses from different hierarchal and demographic background affirms optimal research paradigm and ensures best possible information retrieval to enable effective motivational factor identification for different type of people having distinct demographic constructs.

Tab. No. 6: Respondent distribution

Type of respondents	Location	Departments	Number of respondents
Brahma Kumaris Raja yoga Practitioners Between 20-45 years	Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pandav Bhawan Complex	80
		Gyan Sarowar Complex	116
		Shantivan Complex	262
		Global Hospital & research center	22
		Brahma Kumari Peace park	20

Source- Primary Data

4.44 Demographic Findings

In this section, demographic findings of respondents are discussed. overall summary of demographic findings is given in Table 8

Tab. No. 7: Demographic profile of respondents

Variables	Number of participants
Sex	
Male	461 (92.2%)
Female	39 (7.8%)
Age	
20-25	40 (8%)
26—30	82 (16.4%)
31-35	106 (21.2%)
36-40	110 (22%)
41-46	164 (32.8%)

Source- Primary Data

This is the matter of fact that education level and experiences have direct impact on personal (someone's) ability to understand and make proper decision. Therefore, in

this dissertation, to retrieve optimal data and reliability respondents from varied background, education level and thoughts were considered. As depicted in the above table 8, it can be found that 92.2% (461 out of 500) respondents were male and the remaining 7.8% (39 out of 500) were female. This is the matter of fact that age or maturity does have great significant impact on the reliability of responses and its authenticity. Among the respondents 8 % of the respondents (40 out of 500) were in the age range of 20-25, while 16.4% of respondents (82 out of 500) were in the age range of 26-30 years. 106 out of 500 respondents counting 21.2% were in the age range of 31-35 years. A complete of 110 counting 22% respondents were in the age range of 36-40 years and the remaining 164 respondents, counting 32.8% were in the age range of 40-45 years.

This is the matter of fact that Brahma Kumaris is considered to be the place accommodating major yogis following Brahmachari principle of life. The research outcome in the following table 9, affirms the similar results, where the unmarried respondents were counted as 481 out of 500 (96.2%). On the other hand only 19 respondents (3.8%) were married.

Tab. No. 8: Marital status of respondents

Marital Status	
Unmarried	481 (96.2%)
Married	19 (3.8%)

Source- Primary Data

Tab. No. 9: Educational qualification of respondents

Educational Qualification	
No Basis education	4 (0.8%)
Below 10 th standard	60 (12%)
Below Graduation	163 (32.6%)
Graduation	186 (37.2%)
Post Graduate	83 (16.6%)
Others	6 (1.2%)

Source- Primary Data

As depicted in above table10, it can be found that at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters the most of respondents (37.2%) were graduate. Approximate 32.6% of

respondents have education below graduation, while 12% of respondents were below 10th standard of education. Almost 16.6% respondents were post graduate. These all figures indicate that Brahma Kumaris accommodates well educated people along with formal educated or even non-educated people who serve the organization and learn Raj Yoga as per their ability. These evidences states how motivated the people are towards BKRM at Mount Abu, Rajasthan. The presence of post graduate devotees signifies that people prefer learning Raj Yoga at BKRM, because of its novelties, significances and optimal environment.

Tab. No. 10: Religious background impact

Religious Background	
Hinduism	490 (98%)
Sikhism	0 (0%)
Buddhism	1 (0.2%)
Jainism	3 (0.06%)
Christian	3 (0.06%)
Islamism	1 (0.2%)
Other Religion	2 (0.04%)

Source- Primary Data

In practical life and present day scenario's world, it can't be stated that religious background and its associated success doesn't have relationship. On the other hand, Brahma Kumaris even being an international spiritual organization, states that it doesn't consider multiple god in Raj Yoga meditation, rather they follow a way of life where people devote their life towards supernatural power, the almighty god and spent life to keep others happy. As shown above (table 11), among the respondents almost 490 respondents (490 out of 500) were from Hindu background, while Jainism and Christianity was approximate 0.06 % (3 out of 500). From the respondents Buddhism and Islamism counted for 1% each who is practicing Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris international headquarter at Mount Abu, Rajasthan India.

Tab. No. 11: Professional backgrounds of respondents

Professional Background	
Profession	Respondents
BK service	144 (28.8%)

Student	101 (20.2%)
Business	73 (14.6%)
Govt service	24 (4.8%)
Public/Private service	132 (26.4%)
Unemployed	2 (0.4%)
Agriculture	14 (2.8%)
Other	10 (2%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

As pictured above (Table 12), a total of 144 respondents counting 28.8% were devoted for BK services and were proactive participants in various services and supports for BK organization. The predominant services at BK comprise public service, research, medical services, spiritual encouragement and physio-psychological enrichment programs, Yoga practices, etc. Here, interestingly 132 practitioners counting approximate 26.4% belong to the public and private sector. Students being the future foundation of a society have counted 101 (20.2%). Considering unemployed people joining BK Raj Yoga, an interesting fact has been found that merely 2 people (counting 0.2%) were unemployed. The respondents belong to the business community were 72 (14.6%). These all figures represent the inclination of people towards Raj Yoga meditation. This is the matter of fact that the financial background and sufficiency do have significant impact on the individual person to make its decision and follow certain way of life. Therefore it is important to perform or examine the impact of financial ability on the BK Raj Yoga practitioner. The following table (13) presents the financial background of the respondents.

Tab. No. 12: Financial earning of respondents

Financial Earning Background	
Monthly Income(Rs)	Respondents
Below 10000	406 (81.2%)
10-30000	62 (12.4%)
30-50000	23 (4.6%)

50-70000	4 (0.8%)
Above 70000	5 (1%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

The above table represents that approximate 406 people counting 81.2% of the total respondents had the monthly income less than 10000 per month. On contrary, merely 1% people had the financial background with per month income of more than 70000 rupees (INR). 23 respondents (4.6%) had the income of 30-70000 INR per month, while 62 (12.4%) respondents were having financial background of 10-30000 INR per month. These results reveal that in fact most of the people serving BK and practicing Raj Yoga at BK are with low financial background. It gives an inter-related conclusion, that the people having low financial ability are joined to BK and on the other hand, people belonging to various social segments having even higher or better financial background are allied with BK. It states that BK Raj Yoga has provided a new way of life not only to the financially weak people but also to the rich human society.

Tab. No. 13: Monthly salary of benefits of practitioners at BK headquarters

Monthly Salary/ financial benefits at Mount abu	
Response	Respondents
Yes	17 (3.40%)
No	483 (96.60%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

The above table gives an interesting outcome stating that approximate 482 people counting a total of 96.60% are dedicated for social cause and don't receive any financial gain from the BK organization. Only 17 respondents (3.4%) accepted that they get certain benefits from BK in different forms. In fact people at BK HQ are dedicated purely for godly service and not for money / financial benefits but they will be given required accommodation, food. Clothing etc once they became permanent members.

Tab. No. 14: Initial Contact for BK Raja yoga meditation

Initial Contact for BK Raja yoga meditation	
Source	Respondents
family/ friends	252 (50.4%)
BK people	136 (27.2%)
TV/ Media	22 (4.4%)
Banner/ poster	14 (2.8%)
Dream/vision	7 (1.4 %)
Seminar/ Conference	4 (0.8 %)
Exhibitions	57 (11.4%)
Other	8 (1.6%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

Table 15 depicts that majority of respondents have got the reference or they came to know about BK by their friends and family. The other source of awareness was the already associated BK people who motivated others to join BKRM.

Tab. No. 15: Spiritual interests

Spiritual age (Gyan)	
Duration	Respondents
Below 5 yrs.	61 (12.2%)
5-15 yrs.	167 (33.4 %)
15-25 yrs.	157 (31.4%)
25-35 Yrs.	98 (19.6%)
Above 35 yrs.	17 (3.4%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

Spiritual age is estimated once after they learn the godly knowledge and starts practicing RY meditation. Here, the results from table 16 , reveal that, the most of respondents have got the Gyan of BKRM after practicing Raj Yoga for 5-12 years. Interestingly results also stated that 17 respondents have been practicing BKRM since last 35 years.

Tab. No. 16: Permanent membership status at Mount Abu

Permanent Membership status at Mount Abu	
Response	Respondents
Yes	409 (81.80)
No	91 (18.20)
Total	500 (100)

Source- Primary Data

After successful trial period of 2-5 years, devotees at BK HQ will be eligible for permanent membership wherein they are entitled for all benefits. response & its analysis depicted in above table 17 has revealed that total of 91.8% respondents were permanent member at international HQ of BK.

Tab. No. 17: Residential duration at BK HQ Mount Abu

Residential duration at BK HQ: Mount Abu	
Duration	Respondents
Below 2 yrs.	83 (16.6%)
2-10 yrs.	197 (39.4 %)
10-20 yrs.	136 (27.2 %)
20-30 Yrs.	78 (15.6 %)
Above 30 yrs.	6 (1.2%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

From above table 18 results reveals that there are major people or practitioner who have been doing Raj Yoga and are associated with BKRM since last 2-10 years. Only 6 respondents counting 1.2% were the resident since last 30 years.

Tab. No. 18: Substance usages at BK HQ Mount Abu

Substance Usage Background	
Substances	Respondents
Alcohol	22 (4.4%)
Smoking	7 (1.4 %)

Drugs	1 (0.2%)
Pan Masalas	12 (2.4%)
No addiction	458 (91.6%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

The above table 19 represents the substance usages at the BK institution or organization. As studies, approximate 91.6% respondents affirmed that there is no permission and they don't take any kind of substance such as alcohol, smoking, drugs etc. However 22 people counting 4.4% affirmed that they take Alcohol. This can be their respective addiction and during Raj Yoga it would be intended to reduce such substance usage. & respondents out of 500 stated that they smoke occasionally.

Tab. No. 19: Physical health condition at BK international head quarters

Physical health condition	
Health Parameters	Respondents
Low/High BP	14 (2.8 %)
Diabetes	5 (1%)
Asthma	3 (0.6%)
Arthritis	2 (0.4%)
Cancer	1 (0.2%)
Heart	3 (0.6%)
Other	2 (0.4%)
Good Health	470 (94%)
Total	500 (100%)

Source- Primary Data

Results from table 20 affirms that fact that because of good food, exercise and peace of mind, physical health is also good.

Tab. No. 20: Mental health situation at BK international head quarters

Status of Mental health		
Parameters	Respondents	Percentage%
Anger	20	4
Anxiety	1	0.2
Insult	4	0.8
Mood Change	6	1.2
Fear	5	1
Tension	6	1.2
Other	2	0.4
Good Health	456	91.2
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Results from table 21 shows that by Creating good & positive thoughts through mind for self & others keeps one's mind healthy & peaceful.

Tab. No. 21: Source of income at BK international head quarters

Other Sources of Income at BK HQ Mount Abu		
Response	Respondents	Percentage%
Yes	16	3.20
No	484	96.80
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Results from table 22 demonstrates that, this study incorporates both perpetual & non-changeless individuals at BK HQ. Here individuals simply devote for administration to humankind & not for common Income benefits. 96.8 % have no other pay source.

Tab. No. 22: Stress level in respondents at BK international head quarters

Stress levels		
Level	Respondents	Percentage %
Very High	3	0.6
High	1	0.2
Moderate	14	2.8

Low	17	3.4
Very Low	55	11
No stress	410	82
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Results from table 23 demonstrates that,) shows that, 82% people has no stress and 11% has very low stress at BK HQ. High and very high stress people are less than 1% which clearly indicated that, Raja yoga meditation has direct impact on stress reduction and removal.

Tab. No. 23: Daily Raj Yoga reflection hone at BK worldwide head quarters

Daily Raja Yoga Meditation practice		
Duration (Hrs)	Respondents	Percentage%
Less than 2hrs	90	18
2-4 hrs	227	45.4
4-6 hrs	145	29
6-8 hrs	31	6.2
More than 8hrs	7	1.4
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Results from table 24 demonstrates that, 45.4 % people practice raja yoga meditation daily between 2-4 hours, 29% people practice raja yoga meditation between 4-6 hours , 18% people practice raja yoga meditation less than 2 hours , 6.2 % people practice raja yog ameditation between 6-8 hours and 1.4 % people practice raja yog ameditation above 8 hours which clearly indicated that, people devote their time either in morning 4 am Amrit vela meditation, 6.30 am morning smeditation before spiritual class or evening time 5.30 pm to 7.30 pm compulsorily for Raja yoga meditation at BK HQ, Mount abu and they practice raja yoga meditation daily without fail

Tab. No. 24: Dedicated people residing at BK HQ compulsorily practice RY meditation daily

Daily Godly service		
Duration (Hrs)	Respondents	Percentage%
Less than 2hrs	2	0.4
2-6hrs	101	20.2
6-10 hrs	313	62.6
10-14 hrs	67	13.4
More than 14 hrs	17	3.4
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

results from table 25 demonstrates that, 13.4 % people do godly service between 10-14 hours, 62.6 % people do godly service between 6-10 hours, 20.2 % people do godly service between 2-6 hours, 3.4 % people do godly service more than 14 hours and less than 1 % people do godly service less than 2 hours which clearly indicated that apart from practicing RY mediation, they will do godly service compulsorily in their respective departments where in nearly 90 departments were observed at Shantivan complex during my research.

Tab. No. 25: Sleeping pattern of devotees

Sleeping Pattern		
Duration (Hrs)	Respondents	Percentage%
Less than 2 hrs	2	0.4
2-4 hrs	65	13
4-6 hrs	272	54.4
6-8 hrs	158	31.6
More than 8 hrs	3	0.6
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Food & rest are essential for humans because sleep has an impact on physical , mental and spiritual health. Hence taking into consideration of overall health, here at BKHQ; importance is given for sleep/ rest apart from food, study, exercise, training , meditaion , godly service etc

Tab. No. 26: Sleeping quality of Raj Yoga practitioners at BKHQ

Daily Sleep Quality		
Parameters	Respondents	Percentage%
Excellent	111	22.2
Good	346	69.2
Average	24	4.8
Fair	17	3.4
Poor	2	0.4
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Because a balanced life style of early morning meditation, morning spiritual class, selfless godly service, pure Veg food, churning of godly knowledge etc sleep quality which appears good & excellent at BKHQ campus

Tab. No. 27: Way of living: Dressing sense exploration

Dress Colour at BK HQ Mount Abu		
Dress Colour	Respondents	Percentage%
White	500	100
Saffron	0	0
red	0	0
yellow	0	0
other	0	0
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

People at BKHQ wear clean neat white dress with a badge of identification all the time that symbolizes for peace purity and vairagya life style. The outer dress patten reflects the inner personality.

Tab. No. 28: Amrit vela mediation practioners

Daily 4 am Amrit vela Raj Yoga Meditation Practice

Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	484	96.80
No	16	3.20
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Amritvela is the name given for Brahma muhrt of 4am where in taptavis & rishis do tapasya/ renunciation for self & world benefaction. This meditation is unique to Brahma kumaris. Here at Bk HQ, people daily wake up at 3.30am & regularly practice RY meditation at 4am to 4.45am ie for 45 minutes. This Daily / regularly attending Amrit Vela Raj yoga meditation is compulsory at BK HQ. The above table s5.2 (v) shows that, brahma kumaris being the voluntary organization, 96.8% residents at BK HQ campus compulsorily attend the Amrit vela meditaion as this is days foundation time and has direct for influence on the entire day activities.

Tab. No. 29: Attending morning Murali/ spiritual class.

Attending Murali/ spiritual Class Daily Morning at 7am		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	476	95.20
No	24	4.80
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Daily / regularly attending morning spiritual classes is compulsory at BK HQ. This helps to over come laziness, activates brain to imbibe knowledge, keeps day fresh , keeps mind & body healthy.

Tab. No. 30: Knowledge exploration & revision

Revision/ Churning of Godly Knowledge- Daily		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	480	96.00
No	20	4.00
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Stirring is self-correction of Godly learning which enhances memory & fixation. Builds consideration amid contemplation keeps mind dynamic & positive.

Tab. No. 31: Knowledge exploration & revision

Traffic Control -RY Meditation Practice Daily		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	478	95.60
No	22	4.40
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Churning is self revision of the Godly knowledge which helps to improve memory and concentration. Increases attention during meditation keeps mind active and positive

Tab. No. 32: Self Experiences in Daily RY Meditation

Self-Experiences in Daily RY Meditation		
RY Stages	Respondents	Percentage%
Seed	46	9.2
Angel	47	9.4
Churning	12	2.4
Chit chat	29	5.8
All	366	73.2
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Tab. No. 33: Self Experiences in Daily RY Meditation

Serving Others Through Powerful Thought Vibrations		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	488	97.60
No	12	2.40
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Serving others is one of the main subjects of BKs, now day world requires pure thought vibrations for Peace and blissful life. Hence BKs at HQ regularly do service to others through powerful mind / thought vibrations.

Tab. No. 34: Self-analysis & introspection

Chart of Self Analysis & Progress		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	387	77.40
No	113	22.60
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Chart is written generally at the end of the day to check progress and deviations to the aim/ goals. In same way BKs at HQ keep chart of RY meditation, Inculcation of divine values & service

Tab. No. 35: BKRM Training , lectures & Seminar participation

BKRM Training, lectures & Seminars Participation		
Duration	Respondents	Percentage%
Once in Month	120	24
Once in 6 Months	129	25.8
Once in Year	170	34
Once in 5 Years	19	3.8
Don't attend	62	12.4
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Like other institution, here at BK HQ, Training, lectures & Seminars on RY meditation were organized which improve knowledge, skills and abilities.

Tab. No. 36: “Visit to home” by respondents

Visit to their native birth Place		
Frequency	Respondents	Percentage%
Once in 6 Months	42	8.4
Once in 1 Year	177	35.4
Once in 2 Years	237	47.4
Once in 5 Years	27	5.4
Once in 10 Years	3	0.6
Don't visit	14	2.8
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Even though BKs do renunciation, but unlike other Rishis, they are connected to their family and friends and keep harmonious relationships.

Tab. No. 37: “Visit to home” by respondents

Recreation through Cinema		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	46	9.20
No	454	90.80
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

By & large individuals visit silver screens for entertainmen and people visit cinemas for recreation but at BK HQ, source of recreation is raj yoga meditation, learning spiritual knowledge and serving others.

Tab. No. 38: Use of new technology for godly service

Use of new technology i.e. Mobile, Internet, social media etc. for Godly service		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	437	87.40
No	63	12.60
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

BK HQ even though located at a village place like Mount abu but adopts new technology for spreading RY mediation to entire world and for administration of their branches

Tab. No. 39: Food habits of vegetarianism

Food habit of consuming Vegetarian food with onion & garlic		
Response	Respondents	Percentage %
Yes	0	0.00
No	500	100.00
Total	500	100

Source- Primary Data

Devotees/ RY practitioners at BK HQ are strict Vegetarians. They don't take vegetarian diet with onion and Garlic as these substances have negative impact of concentration of mind and meditation practice. They take food prepared in the remembrance of GOD within the complex and consume in the name of God as Parasadam.

In the following table (41) the birth place of respondents are examined. The demographic statistics states that among the respondents, the maximum (59 out of 500, counting 11.8%) devotees at the Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu were from Karnataka. On the other hand, being native state of BK, Mount Abu, only 21 respondents (4.2%) were from Rajasthan. This fact reveals that BK has motivated people from not only its native state of neighbouring state (Punjab 13 (2.6%), Gujrat 29 (5.8%), Uttar Pradesh 42 (8.4%)) etc), but nationwide including remote northern states (Assam 6(1.02%), Manipur 1 (0.02%), Tripura 2 (0.04%)). It should be noted that in this research or study, the respondents have been considered only from India, even though Brahma Kumaris have established its presence across 142 countries, with proud millions of devotees. The geographical distribution of the respondents at BK HQ, Mount Abu is presented in Table 41

Tab. No. 40: Geographical distribution of respondents based on their birth place

Birth Place	
Andhra Pradesh	33 (6.6%)
Telangana	12 (2.4%)
Karnataka	59 (11.8%)

Maharashtra	56 (11.2%)
Delhi	17 (3.4%)
Haryana	27 (5.4%)
Chhattisgarh	20 (4%)
Uttar Pradesh	42 (8.4%)
Tamilnadu	30 (6%)
Punjab	13 (2.6%)
Orissa	36 (7.2%)
Madhya Pradesh	26 (5.2%)
Gujrat	29 (5.8%)
Bihar	20 (4%)
Nepal	5 (1%)
Rajasthan	21 (4.2%)
Jammu & Kashmir	2 (0.04%)
West Bengal	4 (0.08%)
Assam	6 (1.2%)
Goa	1 (0.02%)
Manipur	1 (0.02%)
Himachal Pradesh	13 (2.6%)
Kerala	6 (1.2%)
Tripura	2 (0.04%)
Uttarakhand	7 (1.4%)
Jharkhand	10 (2%)

Source- Primary Data

4.45 Descriptive analysis

In this section some of the key constructs and related motivational factors have been assessed to have influence on devotees or the people consciousness to observe or follow the Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris. In order to examine these key constructs, in this thesis primarily the following constructs have been examined:

Tab. No. 41: Motivational constructs & assessment variables

Motivational Constructs	Assessment variables
Personal constructs	These constructs explore personal preferences, motivations, suppositions attainment etc.
Spiritual affinity & universal acceptance	These constructs intend to assess spiritual affinity & novelties of BKRM that enable people from different religion & geographical location to follow Raj Yoga meditation.
Environment & ambiances	Under these constructs various factors such as environment of BK HQ, Mount Abu & various ambience related factors have been examined.
Mental, Psychological & Physical constructs	In Mental, psychological & physical construct analysis, various associated factors, & significances have been investigated which motivates people to join BKRM.
Practices	In this analysis paradigm, numerous practices being conducted at BK HQ, Mount Abu & other BKRM related practices have been examined for their significance to attract or motivate people to join BKRM.

Now, in the following sections, the analysis of the aforementioned motivational constructs has been done based on the responses retrieved through 5-Point likert scale. Here, to examine the personal constructs representing personal preferences, motivations, suppositions attainment etc, have been examined.

Tab. No. 42: Personal constructs & Achievement as Motivational Factors

Total Respondents- 500 (5-Point Likert Scale), Location- Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India		
Motivational factors	Mean	Std. Dev.
Purity in Mind, Speech & Actions	4.838	0.414
Inculcation of Divine virtues	4.832	0.414

Devine experience at Amrit vela	4.788	0.485
Orientation towards static food/ pure vegetarianism	4.948	0.231
Enhanced positive thinking	4.894	0.339
Increased concentration during meditation	4.886	0.324
Focused towards soul consciousness	4.800	0.456
Practicing Celibacy in all circumstances	4.884	0.367
Orientation towards supreme/ supernatural power is GOD	4.912	0.290
Develops art of living	4.862	0.362
Full Satisfaction & Contentment in life	4.858	0.360
Attainment of godly love & spiritual powers	4.913	0.294
Increased work efficiency	4.878	0.333
Overall personality development & character building	4.874	0.349
Proper time & resource management.	4.834	0.422
Proper management of 6 Ms men, machinery, money, materials, method & marketing	4.742	0.536
Attainment of world benefactor stage	4.812	0.448
Develops quality of leadership	4.782	0.476
Develops ability to inspire & motivate others	4.852	0.355
Develops ability to plan & set Goals	4.83	0.430
Brings spiritual empowerment in life	4.886	0.318
Develops art of Communication & public speech.	4.792	0.474
Develops art of hearing & listening	4.808	0.459
BKRM activates & enhances core values of SOUL/ Individuals	4.92	0.299
Peace	4.966	0.181
Love	4.960	0.196
Happiness	4.962	0.191

Bliss	4.956	0.205
Harmony in relationships	4.944	0.238
Constant stage of Soul consciousness	4.898	0.328
Gods Consciousness	4.928	0.273
Self-esteem & self confidence	4.924	0.279
Self-transformation	4.917	0.282
Self-control (MIS)	4.918	0.281
Accuracy & punctuality	4.897	0.340
Truth & Honesty	4.938	0.272
Vice less & ego less stage	4.879	0.392
Experience angelic & seed stage	4.863	0.382
Strengthen inner values & powers	4.912	0.297
Self-development& personality development	4.914	0.287
Value based life style	4.902	0.323
Enhanced mental stability	4.892	0.352
Positive attitude & positive thinking personality	4.911	0.323
One can regain self-sovereignty	4.918	0.288
One can conquer vices	4.921	0.268
One can completely control & rule sense organs	4.915	0.318
Motivates to serve mankind through mind (thoughts) & intellect.	4.936	0.244
improves Visualization process	4.926	0.276
Divines Intellect	4.932	0.251
Purify Sanskars (Habits)	4.925	0.277
Motivates to inculcate divine virtues & powers	4.934	0.248
Constant peace of mind	4.95	0.218
Removes unworthy habits & desires	4.934	0.248
Mastery over self	4.91	0.300
Brings relaxation & restores inner peace.	4.948	0.222

*Source: Primary Data

In personal construct and motivational factor analysis intend to examine those factors which significantly impacts someone personal way of life and intended achievements. The responses collected from 500 respondents from Brahma Kumaris International headquarters using 5-point likert scale state that Raj Yoga meditation plays significant role in enhancing or enriching the purity of mind speech and actions (M=4.83, SD=0.414). The similar responses have been obtained for the inculcations of divine (M=4.83, SD=0.414) virtues of the regular practices of Raj Yoga meditation. This is the matter of fact that in human society the eating habits have immense diversity but people often prefer fulfilling their eating preferences and interests. In general, it can be found that people don't prefer leaving their interest towards eating habits, but interestingly the responses affirms that Raj Yogis at BK show positive affinity towards Satwik food or pure vegetarian (M=4.94, SD=0.231). In fact, assessing such factor predominantly depends on respective observation and thinking of an individual, but results reveal that the Raj Yogi ensures their life style as a pure and holy spirited even by sacrificing majority of worldly being facilities and numerous alternatives to please personal habits including food habits or living style. Perhaps these are the reason that they do feel an elevated positive thinking (M=4.9, SD=0.34) and concentration at daily activities (M=4.886, SD=0.324).

The responses retrieved have affirmed that the devotees practicing Raj Yoga meditation at BK can be typically found soul consciousness (M=4.800, SD=0.456). Even here the higher value of standard deviation can't be neglected and it can be stated that Raj Yoga can enable numerous benefits, but still there exists environmental and worldly events which can have certain definite impact on consciousness while performing any task or activities. No doubts, the respondents have affirmed that Raj Yoga meditation often motivates devotees to encourage towards supreme power "The Almighty God" (M=4.912, SD=0.290). Such devotion lead them to realize the attainment of godly love and spiritual power (M=4.913, SD=0.294).

Raj Yoga meditation can be the catalyst to enrich the art of living (S=4.862, SD=0.362) and can lead towards the contentment and satisfaction (M=4.588, SD=0.360). The significance of such satisfaction can't be ignored to have the positive impact on the increased work efficiency (M=4.878, SD=0.333). The elevation in personal productivity usually leads towards enriched personality development &

character building (M=4.874, SD=0.349). To achieve higher productivity and personal life achievement, Raj yoga meditation can enable proper time and resource management capability (S=4.834, SD=0.422). The respondents replied an interesting fact that Raj yoga meditation can enable human being to achieve proper management of 6 Ms men, machinery, money, materials, method & marketing (M=4.742), but the standard deviation (SD=0.536) affirms that being multi variables construct, it might have discrete impact and satisfaction.

Through the proposed empirical analysis, it has been found that Raj yoga can be of great significance to achieve leadership skills (M=4.812, SD=0.448) because of focused and enhanced behavior and ability to plan the objective along with respective accomplishment (M=4.830, SD=0.430) and art of communication (M=4.79, SD=0.474). Not surprisingly it enables human to possess ability to motivate others by its holy spirited acts (M=4.852, SD=0.355). These all achievements ensure empowered life (M=4.886, SD=0.318). On the other hand, various activities organized by BKRM towards skill and life style enhancement of its practitioners, enable them to enhance the core values of the individual life (M=4.92, SD=0.300). Furthermore, the attainment of peace (M=4.966, SD=0.181), love (M=4.960, SD=0.196), happiness (M=4.962, SD=0.191), bliss (M=4.956, SD=0.205) and relational harmony (M= 4.94, SD=0.238), and soul and almighty god consciousness ((M=4.898, SD=0.328) and (M=4.928, SD=0.273)) can be achieved by BKRM.

The responses retrieved has exhibited that Raj yoga can be of great significance to enable human life Vice less & ego less ((M=4.879, SD=0.392), and strengthened inner values and power (M=4.912, SD=0.297). In addition, it can be vital to achieve self development ability (M=4.914, SD=0.287) and value based life style (M=4.902, SD=0.323), which can't be accomplished completely without having enhanced mental stability (M=4.892, SD=0.352).

This is the fact that positive thinking and attitude makes human getting success, which can be achieved by Raj Yoga motivations (M=4.911, SD=0.323). To enable seamless life conquering vices (M=4.921, SD=0.318) and retaining the self sovereignty (M=4.918, SD=0.288) can be of great significance, which can no doubt be enabled by Raj Yoga meditation at BKRM. In this worldly being, no doubt to make a human life successful maintaining intellectual life balanced (M=, SD=0.251) and retaining

purified habits called Sanskars (M=4.925, SD=0.277) is of great significance, for which BKRM can be a vital pathway.

Being across worldly beings and surrounded by varied conditions, keeping consistent peace of mind (M=4.950, SD=0.218) and eliminating the unworthy habits makes the life worry free and prestigious (M=4.934, SD=0.248), and these all personal habits can be enhanced by means of continuous Raj Yoga meditation at BKRM.

Tab. No. 43: Spiritual affinity & universal acceptance

Total Respondents- 500 (5-Point Likert Scale), Location- Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India		
Motivational factors	Mean	Std. Dev.
BKRM is spiritual science & not religion & is experimenting with thoughts about GOD/ Supreme power/ supernatural power	4.918	0.308
BKRM is taught to all religious people across world without any discrimination	4.954	0.209
BK people at Mount Abu have abundance selfless love, kind hearted, completely dedicated, happy & source of inspiration	4.892	0.347

*Source: Primary Data

In the present world scenarios, having the novelties and its global acceptability is of great significance. The responses collected from the respondents state that BKRM is a spiritual science and not a religion and hence is experimenting with the thoughts about GOD/ Supreme power/ supernatural power (M=4.918, SD=0.308). In addition, it has been observed that the holy practices and activities by BKRM for all human being irrespective of their respective religion (M=4.954, D=0.209) strengthen the global acceptability of BKRM.

Tab. No. 44: Environment & ambiances

Total Respondents- 500 (5-Point Likert Scale), Location- Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India		
Motivational factors	Mean	Std. Dev.
BK HQ Mount Abu is believed to be GODs	4.962	0.201

incarnation & very sacred place on earth		
BK International HQ Mount Abu has positive learning environment	4.97	0.170
BK Mount Abu complexes have better spiritual training & development facility	4.954	0.209
BK Mount Abu complexes have world class infrastructure to learn Meditation	4.936	0.260
At Mount Abu, learning of Meditation is made easier under effective guidance & blessings of Dadis, experienced Raja Yogis, tapaswis & saints.	4.95	0.218
Mount Abu is very pleasant location located in Arravali hills area.	4.96	0.196
environment at BK Mount Abu is free from air pollution, water pollution & noise pollution	4.896	0.305
BK Mount Abu complexes have Asia's biggest & self-sufficient Solar plants	4.884	0.356
Even though BK International HQ Mount Abu is located in village place but adopted latest technology for learning & development of spirituality	4.898	0.346
All people at BK International HQ Mount Abu compulsorily follow principle of brahmacharya & take pure static vegetarian food daily.	4.934	0.264
People at Mount abu don't consume non-vegetarian food & food prepared by outsiders	4.928	0.288
All people at BK Mount Abu complexes wear very neat & clean white colored dress daily with badge of identification	4.94	0.254
People at mount abu serve with divine love, humility, respect, brother hood & smiling face	4.903	0.327
BK Mount Abu complexes don't have hotel, private lodges, pan masala & cigarette shops	4.918	0.274
Complete dedication towards serving mankind	4.896	0.318

nature of people at Mount abu is Satisfied, Contented & self-disciplined.	4.841	0.430
Whenever BK people meet together anytime, they greet with sacred mantra "OM SHANTHI"	4.97	0.170

*Source: Primary Data

In order to make any organization successful, it becomes inevitable to examine the working or operational environment. The environment and associated friendly practices do have significant impact on people perception to get associated with the organization. Hence, taking into consideration of the global presence of Brahma Kumaris organization and its spiritual practices, in this thesis the environmental or ambience aspect of Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters, Mount Abu has been examined, whether it does have any significant impact on people perception or any motivation to follow or practice Raj Yoga meditation.

The responses retrieved from 500 respondents from Brahma Kumaris International Headquarter, Mount Abu, India state that BK HQ Mount Abu is believed to be the GODs incarnation and very sacred place on earth (M=4.962, SD=0.201). The responses also affirm it that BK International HQ Mount Abu enables positive learning environment for devotees or Raj Yoga practitioners (M=4.97, SD=0.170). BK provides spiritual training and development facility which encourages people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation (S=4.936, SD=0.260). Responses also affirm it that Considering the organizational leadership and administration to ensure friendly and optimal environment, respondents stated that at BK HQ, Mount Abu the learning of Meditation is made easier under the influensive and skilled guidance and blessings of Dadis, experienced Raja Yogis, tapaswis and saints (M=4.95, SD=0.218). Furthermore, the results obtained depicts that being located in the Aravali hills area, Mount Abu enables pollution free ambience (M=4.896, SD=0.305) having self-sufficient solar powered electricity provisioning (M=4.884, SD=0.356). Even being located in rural areas it houses the latest technology for learning and development of spirituality (M=4.898, SD=0.346). Considering living principle and uniformity across the organization, it can be found that all the people at BK International HQ Mount Abu compulsorily follow the principle of brahmacharya & take pure satwic vegetarian food daily (M=4.934, SD=0.264). In fact such uniformity and consistency makes the

ambience sound and well connected or integrated, thus enabling devotees to do their best with organization and intended objectives while considering equivalence across the organization. In addition, it also provides unique recognition. All the people at BK Mount Abu complexes wear very neat & clean white colored dress daily with a badge of identification (M=4.940, SD=0.254).

To make any family successful, the relationship, brotherhood and pleasing environment is important. Being a large scale family, BK considers these inevitable needs and the respondents affirmed that BK provides divine love, humility, respect, brotherhood and smiling face (M=4.903, SD=0.327). The simplicity and purity of this environment can be understood by the fact that BK Mount Abu complexes don't have hotel, private lodges, pan masala and cigarette shops etc (M=4.918, SD=0.274). Respondents also stated that the nature of people at BK is disciplined and contented which motivates and coordinates people to get connected and follows BKRM (M=4.841, SD=0.430). Greeting others by saying "Om Shanti" makes people connected together (M=4.970, SD=0.170)

In order to make any organization successful, it becomes inevitable to examine the working or operational environment. The environment and associated friendly practices do have significant impact on people perception to get associated with the organization. Hence, taking into consideration of the global presence of Brahma Kumaris organization and its spiritual practices, in this thesis the environmental or ambience aspect of Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters, Mount Abu has been examined, whether it does have any significant impact on people perception or any motivation to follow or practice Raj Yoga meditation.

The responses retrieved from 500 respondents from Brahma Kumaris International Headquarter, Mount Abu, India state that BK HQ Mount Abu is believed to be the GODs incarnation and very sacred place on earth (M=4.962, SD=0.201). The responses also affirm it that BK International HQ Mount Abu enables positive learning environment for devotees or Raj Yoga practitioners (M=4.97, SD=0.170). BK provides spiritual training and development facility which encourages people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation (S=4.936, SD=0.260). Responses also affirm it that

Considering the organizational leadership and administration to ensure friendly and optimal environment, respondents stated that at BK HQ, Mount Abu the learning of Meditation is made easier under the influensive and skilled guidance and blessings of Dadis, experienced Raja Yogis, tapaswis and saints (M=4.95, SD=0.218). Furthermore, the results obtained depicts that being located in the Aravali hills area, Mount Abu enables pollution free ambience (M=4.896, SD=0.305) having self-sufficient solar powered electricity provisioning (M=4.884, SD=0.356). Even being located in rural areas it houses the latest technology for learning and development of spirituality (M=4.898, SD=0.346). Considering living principle and uniformity across the organization, it can be found that all the people at BK International HQ Mount Abu compulsorily follow the principle of brahmacharya & take pure satwic vegetarian food daily (M=4.934, SD=0.264). In fact such uniformity and consistency makes the ambience sound and well connected or integrated, thus enabling devotees o do their best with organization and intended objectives while considering equivalence across the organization. In addition, it also provides unique recognition. All the people at BK Mount Abu complexes wear very neat & clean white colored dress daily with a badge of identification (M=4.940, SD=0.254).

To make any family successful, the relationship, brotherhood and pleasing environment is important. Being a large scale family, BK considers these inevitable needs and the respondents affirmed that BK provides divine love, humility, respect, brother hood and smiling face (M=4.903, SD=0.327). The simplicity and purity of this environment can be understood by the fact that BK Mount Abu complexes don't have hotel, private lodges, pan masala and cigarette shops etc (M=4.918, SD=0.274). Responded also stated that the nature of people at at BK is disciplined and contented which motivates and coordinates people to get connected and follows BKRM (M=4.841, SD=0.430). Greeting others by saying “Om Shanti” makes people connected together (M=4.970, SD=0.170).

Keeping in mind end goal to make any association fruitful, it gets to be inescapable to look at working or operational environment. Environment & related neighborly

practices do have huge effect on individual's observation to get connected with association,

Reactions recovered from 500 respondents from Brahma Kumaris International Headquarter, Mount Abu, India express that BK HQ Mount Abu is accepted to be GODs incarnation & extremely consecrated spot on earth (M=4.962, SD=0.201). reactions likewise assert it that BK International HQ Mount Abu empowers positive learning environment for fans or Raj Yoga specialists (M=4.97, SD=0.170). BK gives otherworldly preparing & improvement office which urges individuals to receive Raj Yoga contemplation (S=4.936, SD=0.260). Reactions additionally confirm it that Considering hierarchical initiative & organization to guarantee cordial & ideal environment, respondents expressed that at BK HQ, Mount Abu learning of Meditation is made less demanding under influence & gifted direction & favors of Dadis, experienced Raja Yogis, tapaswis & holy people (M=4.95, SD=0.218). Moreover, comes about got delineates that being situated in Aravali slopes range, Mount Abu empowers contamination free mood (M=4.896, SD=0.305) having independent sunlight based controlled power provisioning (M=4.884, SD=0.356). Notwithstanding being situated in rustic zones it houses most recent innovation for learning & advancement of otherworldly existence (M=4.898, SD=0.346). Considering living guideline & consistency crosswise over association, it can be found that all individuals at BK International HQ Mount Abu obligatorily take after standard of brahmacharya & take unadulterated static veggie lover sustenance day by day (M=4.934, SD=0.264). Actually, such consistency & consistency makes atmosphere sound & all around associated or coordinated, subsequently empowering enthusiast's o do their best with association & proposed destinations while considering identicalness crosswise over association. Likewise, it additionally gives novel acknowledgment. All individuals at BK Mount Abu edifices wear extremely flawless & clean white shaded dress every day with identification of distinguishing proof (M=4.940, SD=0.254).

To make any family effective, relationship, fellowship & satisfying environment is essential. Being expansive scale family, BK considers these inescapable needs & respondents attested that BK gives divine affection, lowliness, regard, fraternity & grinning face (M=4.903, SD=0.327). effortlessness & virtue of this environment can be comprehended by certainty that BK Mount Abu buildings don't have inn, private cabins, skillet masala & cigarette shops & so on (M=4.918, SD=0.274). Reacted

likewise expressed that nature of individuals at BK is trained & satisfied which propels & organizes individuals to get associated & takes after BKRM (M=4.841, SD=0.430). Welcoming others by saying "Om Shanti" makes individuals associated together (M=4.970, SD=0.170)

Tab. No. 45: Practices as motivations

Total Respondents- 500 (5-Point Likert Scale), Location- Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India		
Motivational factors	Mean	Std. Dev.
Raja yoga detaches individuals from worldly attractions & motivates them towards spiritual learning & experience	4.926	0.284
Raja yoga facilitates to explore moral & spiritual values & guide towards art of living	4.924	0.279
Raja Yoga effectively manages stress through self-management technique.	4.891	0.336
Raja yoga facilitates to develop mainly 8 inner soul powers.	4.896	0.324
Attention to Murali & Imbibing Godly Knowledge accurately (Gyan)	4.878	0.373
There are continuous activities such as research, lectures, training, seminars & conferences pertaining to Rajayoga meditation throughout year at BK Mount Abu complexes	4.942	0.233
BK Mount Abu complexes don't have shopping mall & cinema theatre	4.94	0.254
People at Mount abu don't visit cinema theatres & see any kinds of cinema	4.88	0.371
You can't find any persons/ donors name in any places/ buildings/ infrastructure in BK Mount Abu complexes	4.909	0.319
There is no display of price chart for food,	4.944	0.230

accommodation, transportation& other services at BK Mount Abu complexes.		
Pure vegetarian & Satwic food is served 3 times day in full quantities FREE OF COST at specified scientific times at BK Mount Abu complexes.	4.946	0.234
Meditation teaching Service done continuously to all segments of society without any discrimination through 20 wings at BK Mount Abu complexes.	4.941	0.234
Services at Mount abu extended to all people across Globe without any partiality & discrimination throughout year	4.934	0.264
Waking time at BK complexes, mount abu is 3.30 am & it is compulsory to attend Amrit vela (4am to 4.45am) Rajayoga meditation class daily.	4.898	0.351
People at BK complexes, mount abu daily attend to Murali class (7am to 8am) without fail.	4.884	0.361
Pleasant& harmonious relationships exist between members at Mount abu	4.886	0.353
Picnic, recreation, drama, dance & other cultural activities organized regularly	4.829	0.416
Attending sat sang daily & regularly	4.874	0.355
First of all, all people at Mount abu study & practice godly knowledge meditation daily& then preach to others.	4.886	0.370

*Source: Primary Data

Considering good activities and practices at Brahma Kumaris, this research reveals that Raja yoga motivates people towards spiritual learning (M=4.926, SD=0.284). In addition, the respondents affirms that Raja yoga facilitates to explore moral &spiritual values and guide towards art of living (M=4.924, SD=0.279). The respondents also stated that Raja Yoga can significantly manage stress through self management technique (M=4.891, SD=0.336). In addition, Raja yoga facilitates to develop mainly inner soul powers (M=4.896, SD=0.324). Brahma Kumaris spiritual centers also

facilitate practices such as Murali that as a result imbibes Godly Knowledge to the devotees (M=4.878, SD=0.373).

In addition, at BK there used to be various activities such as research, lectures, training, seminars & conferences pertaining to Rajayoga meditation throughout the year, which motivates people from different background and skills level to get connected (M=4.942, SD=0.233). In addition, there are numerous other factors such as individual's non-affinity towards worldly beings such as Mall culture (M=4.88, SD=0.254), cinema theatre (M=4.88, SD=0.371). The true devotion and dedication can e easily visualized throughout BK that there is no any name plate or any symbolic signatures of donors (M=4.909, SD=0.319).

Majority of existing literatures have stated that Raj Yoga meditation can be of great significance to enhance the psychological, mental as well as physical constructs. In the following section some of the predominant factors have been examined for their respective significance at motivation to encourage people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation. .

Tab. No. 46: Mental, Psychological & Physical constructs

Total Respondents- 500 (5-Point Likert Scale), Location- Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India		
Motivational factors	Mean	Std. Dev.
BKRM plays major role in physical health optimization i.e. BP, sugar level, pulse, BMI etc.	4.834	0.472
BKRM is significant in healing of disease like cancer, arthritis, heart diseases etc.	4.766	0.521
BKRM is helpful to maintaining good physique/ physical stamina	4.848	0.425
BKRM is helpful in de addiction from substance usage & affinity	4.89	0.371
BKRM is helpful for mental health optimization i.e. anger, depression, fear, tension, anxiety, guilt, insult, mood swings etc.	4.892	0.374
BKRM eliminates mental illness such as sleeplessness, sleep walking, bad dreaming etc.	4.874	0.398
Raja yoga is effective for mental stability &	4.933	0.264

concentration		
BKRM is easy mental process & have no difficulties of physical asanas/ postures.	4.944	0.230
People at Mount abu don't consume alcohol, tobacco, cigarettes, pan masala, drugs & they don't have any other bad habits.	4.877	0.373

*Source: Primary Data

The respondents affirmed that BKRM can be significant for physical health optimization such as blood pressure control, sugar level control and various other physiological control purposes (M=4.834, SD=0.472). The significance of BKRM to heal disease like cancer, arthritis, heart diseases etc (M=4.766, SD=0.521). Respondents affirms that BKRM is helpful to maintaining good physique/ physical stamina (M=4.848, SD=0.425). Similarly, BKRM is helpful in de addiction from substance usage and affinity (M=4.890, SD=0.371). Considering the significance of BKRM for mental health enrichment i.e. anger, depression, fear, tension, anxiety, guilt, insult, mood swings etc (M=4.892, SD=0.374). In addition, BKRM can be effective eliminates mental illness such as sleeplessness, sleep walking, bad dreaming etc (M=4.874, SD=0.398). This research states that Raja yoga is effective for mental stability and concentration (M=4.933, SD=0.264) and BKRM can be an easy mental process and have no difficulties of physical asanas/ postures (M=4.944, SD=0.230).

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discussion and respective significances, it can be found that there are a number of factor such as personal constructs, spiritual affinity and universal acceptance, environment and ambiances, mental, psychological and physical constructs, and various practices, which significantly influences people to observe Raj yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India.

4.46 Hypotheses Testing

Taking into consideration of the proposed research objectives and respective subject matter analysis, in this dissertation certain well defined research hypotheses have been defined. The proposed research hypotheses represent the predominant motivational factors motivating people to practice Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International Headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. Particularly, in this thesis, various factors such as demographic factors, physiological and psychological factors, affinity towards service people, devotion towards supernatural godly power etc have been considered as the key motivational constructs, which have been examined to have significance towards motivation people to join Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation (BKRM). A number of factors such as spiritual lifestyle, physical/mental and spiritual advantages, BKRM novelties and practice's influences and advantages of BKRM etc have been examined empirically in this thesis. In order to examine these key constructs and motivational factors, in this thesis questionnaires have been prepared. Collecting the responses and processing the retrieved responses from Raj Yogis at BK international headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, the hypothesis proposed in this study have been tested or examined using statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel and SPSS analysis performed in terms of mean, standard deviation and correlation.

The discussion of the performed statistical analysis for various motivational factors motivating people to join Raj Yoga meditation at BK international headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India, is given as follows:

Hypothesis-1

Demography factors play very significant role in motivating people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

In the previous sections of the presented thesis, a number of demographic variables and their respective significances towards motivating people to join Raj Yoga at BK HQ, Mount Abu, Rajasthan (India) were studied and analysed. In order to assess these variables the demographic factors such as educational level, geographical locations, gender, income, experiences etc can be of great significance to assess the facts about the specific constructs which can impact people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation, especially BKRM.

Considering present study, it can be found that the majority of devotees at BKRM are male. It can be easily inferred here that the changing socio-cultural conditions, stress level and physical-mental stresses in profession as well as in socio-personal life has played significant role in motivating people to join Raj Yoga meditation. On the other hand, the statistical outcomes state that majority of the devotees are unmarried, which significantly indicates the personal thrust towards godly knowledge, spiritual power and affinity. No doubt, in certain narrowed perception the majority of unmarried people at BK indicates the optimal spiritual environment where an individual prefer serving society and its well being by godly knowledge, motivation and peace of mind, which are the key ingredients to keep society connected and peaceful.

On the other hand, the educational factors also indicates that approximate 186 out of 500 (37.2%) respondents were graduate and were functional at different hierarchy of BK organization, while maintaining selfless and dedicated practices towards better society. It signifies that the practices such as BKRM has significant impact on people perception towards devotion, affinity towards spiritual powers, godly knowledge, peace of mind and harmony, balanced and stress free life, punctual and value based or enriched (sanskritic) life style, and inner success attainment.

Discussing other factors such as age, it has been observed that 164 respondents counting 32.8% of the overall respondents were in the age range of 40-45 years and similarly, 106 out of 500 106 out of 500 respondents counting 21.2% were in the age range of 31-35 years. On contrary, only 8% of respondents were in the age range of 20-25 years. These figures crisply state that as age increases human intends to get

better way of life, which can make and enable it to be away from worldly beings and self-centric practices. Exploring the need of a self-less, devoted life and peaceful living culture motivates people to incline towards BKRM. In some other way, the increase in stress level, physical troubles and associated mental instability too motivate people to join BKRM.

This is the matter of fact that in present day scenario where numerous internal as well as external battles are being imposed by the name of religion and associated practices and principles. Therefore, no doubt there can be direct relationship between religion and respective preferences towards certain organization, whether it is for novel causes. To explore this fact, this thesis intended to investigate the religion based analysis, and it was observed that being an international spiritual organization with the motive to maintain and promote harmony and peace, there were 490 respondents (490 out of 500) from Hindu religion, while Jainism and Christianity was approximate 0.06 % (3 out of 500). From the respondents Buddhism and Islamism counted for 1% each who was practicing Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris international headquarter at Mount Abu, Rajasthan India. These all factors indicate that the highest count of Hindus at BK practicing holy BKRM, prefers peace and harmony across human civilization. The dedication towards a peaceful and soulful life indicates their motive to motivate people to attain supernatural power and godly knowledge rather fighting for worldly beings and mortal short-term advantages. In addition, there are numerous demographic variables which do have great significance on encouraging people to join BKRM at BK headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. Thus, with these significant demographic variables it can be stated that the proposed or stated hypothesis is justified to have the impact of demographic constructs on motivating people to join BKRM.

Hypothesis-2

Personage thrust towards search for true spiritual means of life motivates people to become Raj yogis with Brahma Kumaris organization.

The following table presents the correlation analysis for hypothesis-2, where various factors such as personal zeal, spiritual factors and enthuse etc have been examined to have significant relation with BKRM practices.

**Tab. No. 47: Correlation Analysis for Spiritual factors & Raj Yoga
Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan**

		Spiritual Factors	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Spiritual Factors	Pearson Correlation	1	0.825
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.825	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source – Primary data

In general, this hypothesis at a confidence level of 95% or at significance level of 0.05. From the Table48 it can be observed that the correlation coefficient between spiritual factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan (India), is 0.825 and the significance of the correlation coefficient is less than the significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis could be rejected under test statistically. Therefore it can be prescribed that a correlation exists between the spiritual factors and the Raj Yoga meditation practices at Brahma Kumaris. The correlation coefficient is positive. So it can be inferred that the various spiritual practices and ambience motivates people to join BKRM at Brahma Kumaris international headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. Further, to examine the key personal factors such as affinity to join Raj yoga practices, devotion towards serving society through mind, willingness to observe godly relationship with supernatural power etc, the correlation coefficient has been estimated.

In this thesis, various factors such as god consciousness, love, peace (inner as well as worldly), bliss, soul consciousness, self transformation, vice less and ego less stage

positive attitude etc have been considered self development, and devotion towards society, sanskar (habit) purification, self control zeal towards getting divine virtues and power etc have been considered as personal factors that motivates people to join Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

Tab. No. 48: Correlation Analysis for personal factors, devotion towards serving society & BKRM.

		Devotion towards serving society	Godly Relationship	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Devotion towards serving society	Correlation Coefficient	1	0.881	0.824
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.047	0.000
	N	500	500	500
Godly Relationship	Correlation Coefficient	0.881	1	0.896
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.025	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Correlation Coefficient	0.824	0.896	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500	500

Source- Primary Data

Taking into consideration of Table 49 and its parametric significance, it can be observed that there is a strong positive statistically significant correlation between devotion towards serving society and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan. Here, the data analysis reveals the correlation coefficient has been obtained as 0.824, which is much higher than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the retrieved correlation coefficient is much higher than the significance level

and hence it indicates rejection of associated null hypothesis, and therefore it can be affirmed that there exists a relation between devotion towards serving society and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris. Interestingly, the correlation coefficient retrieved for godly relationship and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris has been obtained as 0.896, which is significantly higher and sufficient to affirm positive and strong relationship between Raja yogameditation at Brahma Kumaris (BKRM) and godly relationship or personal thrust to devote towards supernatural power.

Furthermore, the correlation between godly relationship and 0.881 and devotion towards serving society has been obtained as 0.881, which is higher enough to affirm positive strong relationship. Here, the factor stated as godly relationship also indicates and relates the experience of god in different relationship and as an omnipotent point of light. Thus, it can be easily observed that the motivation to connect with supernatural godly power motivates people to join and practice Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris, which as a result introduce and motivate people or devotees to serve society. Considering the emergence of Brahma Kumaris and its functional philosophy, it can be easily observed that the devotees do consider god as supernatural source of energy, which can be retrieved by means of meditation like Raj Yoga. .

Chi-Square Analysis

Tab. No. 49: Chi squared Analysis

Chi-Square Tests				Table Systematic measures			
	Value	df	Asymp.Sig (2-sided)			Value	Approx. Sig.
Pearson Chi-Square	238.308		0.000	Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.888	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	116.588	121	0.596	N of Valid cases		500	
Linear-by- Linear Association	38	1	0.000				
N of Valid cases	500						

Source- Primary Data

Here, in this dissertation and data analysis paradigm, a significance level of 0.05 has been considered to accept or reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, in case it is estimated the measured significance of less than 0.05 reflects the rejection of hypothesis and the significance > 0.05 , it suggests for acceptance of hypothesis. In addition, observing above table it can be found that the association strength value is 88.8% that signifies statistically significant strength. The statistically significant association has been observed between personage thrust towards the search for true spiritual means of life and Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

In order to justify or verify this hypothesis, the correlation analysis has been done for different associated variable and constructs. In this dissertation, initially the independent analysis for the relationship between Psychological factors and interest, and Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris has been done. It has been followed by the correlation assessment between Physiological factors. Similarly, the correlation between people spiritual interest and its impact on their affinity towards Raj Yoga

Hypothesis-3

Psychological, Physiological & Spiritual factors are vital motivational factors that put enthuse in Raj yogis or Raj Yoga practitioners.

meditation at Brahma Kumaris have been examined.

Tab. No. 50: Correlation Analysis for Psychological factors & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

		Psychological Factors	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Psychological Factors	Pearson Correlation	1	0.843
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu,	Pearson Correlation	0.843	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Rajasthan			
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Source-Primary data

The correlation analysis for Psychological factors and Raj Yoga meditation at BKRM has depicted the correlation value of 0.843, which is much more than the significant level of 0.05. It indicates strong positive relationship between Psychological factors and Raj Yoga meditation. On the basis of my personal visualization and behavioural analysis, I do find that a significant amount of people are there suffering from certain Psychological disorder who are practicing Raj Yoga Meditation.

The obtained Pearson correlation between the physiological factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris is given in the following Table 52.

Tab. No. 51: Correlation Analysis for physiological factors & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris

		Physiological Factors	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Physiological Factors	Pearson Correlation	1	0.742
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.742	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source-Primary data

Table 52 represents the correlation result obtained between physiological factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris. Here, the correlation coefficient obtained between these two factors have been obtained as 0.742, which is much more than significance level (0.05), and therefore it can be stated that there exist a positive relation between spiritual factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma

Kumaris.

This research also reveals that Raja yoga meditation can help in curing numerous psychological problems such as neurotic illness and many other diseases like hypertension, Insomnia, depression etc. Raj Yoga removes tension, nervousness, fear and other negativities, which disturb a person, hence relaxing the mind completely. This way the negative symptoms that the average middle class neurotics experience are cured with the help Raja yoga. Some of the neurotic diseases, which can be easily cured through Raj Yoga, are anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorders, phobias etc by combing Raj Yoga with conventional psychopharmacology and psychotherapy. Further more positive thoughts can be used during Raj Yoga to overcome stress, fear for holistic health. The dose of medicine can be reduced and the disease can be eradicated to the core, since meditation removes the root cause of psychosomatic diseases.

To examine the relationship between spiritual factors and Raj Yoga meditation, the correlation has been obtained, which is given in Table 53

Tab. No. 52: Correlation Analysis for Spiritual factors & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris

		Spiritual Factors	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Spiritual Factors	Pearson Correlation	1	0.893
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.893	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source-Primary data

Above mentioned table (53) represents the correlation result obtained between spiritual factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris. Here, the correlation coefficient obtained between these two factors have been obtained as 0.893, which is much more than significance level (0.05), and therefore it can be stated that there exist a positive relation between spiritual factors and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris. In the journey of life from past to present, values and spirituality have played an important role in enhancing peace and progress in Indian society and the world as a whole.

Hypothesis-4

Novel life culture, environment & holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World's spiritual center at Mount Abu, Rajasthan motivates people to get associated with it.

This is the matter of fact that the organizations such as Brahma Kumaris, intends to introduce a device way of life thus leading human being towards supernatural power, dedication and holy spiritual inclination towards almighty god. Even though, believing this fact that being in 21st century, where majority of human being intends to live a luxury and prosperous life encompassed with numerous worldly beings and activities, sometime seems difficult. And the predominant reason behind this fact is the human behavioural and livelihood inclination towards worldly beings. On contrary, having a glance and exploring the lifestyle of Raj Yogi, it can be easily found that Raj Yogis used to have not much significant inclination towards worldly beings. In such cases, it becomes very significant to investigate the predominant reason and those factors which attracts and motivates Raj yogis to prefer joining Brahma Kumaris.

In this thesis, two predominant factors the life culture and various holy practices being conducted in Brahma Kumaris have been taken into consideration to examine the related motivational factors. This is the fact that life culture, living style and behavioural factors influences human being significantly and thus motivates people to join BCRM..

Tab. No. 53: Correlation Analysis for Life Culture & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris

	Life culture	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ:
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		Mount Abu, Rajasthan	
Life Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.923
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.923	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source-Primary data

In this dissertation, the significance level has been considered as 0.05 for accepting and rejecting the null hypothesis. Here, it can be found that the correlation coefficient retrieved between the life culture and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris is 0.923 which is higher than 0.05 and therefore its rejects the null hypothesis. Researches state that BK HQ Mount Abu is supposed to be the God's incarnation and very sacred place on the earth, which attracts devotees to be a part of it to accomplish godly knowledge, supreme power connectivity and alignment towards peace and socio-mental achievement.

Further, to examine the inter-relation between the spiritual environments and Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, the correlation analysis has been performed. The results obtained for the correlation are given as follows:

Tab. No. 54: Correlation Analysis for Spiritual Environment & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris

		Spiritual Environment	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Spiritual Environment	Pearson Correlation	1	0.911
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000

	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.911	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source-Primary data

As depicted in the above table 55, it can be found that the correlation coefficient between spiritual environment at Brahma Kuamris International headquarters, Mount Abu and the Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris is found as 0.911, which is significantly much more than the defined significance level of 0.05. Therefore it affirms a very strong and positive relation between spiritual environment and Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu (for Raj Yoga Meditation). This results affirms those belief that the Brahma Kumaris international organization and its spiritual practices have facilitated optimal environment for devotees to practice Raj Yoga meditation.

The obtained results affirm that the novel culture, spiritual practices and environment motivates people to join Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu. In addition, the respondents have stated that BKRM is the holy, mental & spiritual which motivates them to join it. BKRM has provides various facilities including yoga practices, spiritual activities, accommodation etc. these factors significantly motivates people to join BKRM. Exploring inside the infrastructure and ambience of BK HQ, Mount Abu, it can be found that it houses world class infrastructure including solar powered establishments for accommodation, self-sustained accommodation facilities etc. This factor enables such large scale organization to attract people towards it. But empirical analysis it affirms that there are a number of devotees who merely care about physical or subjective infrastructure or facilities, rather they appreciate holy practices and spiritual environment as the main motivation.

In addition to these two factors, in this thesis the holy practices as the motivational factors have been assessed. To examine the holy practices as the motivational factor its correlation has been estimated with respect to preferences to perform Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, the Pearson correlation coefficient has been estimated, with the standard significance level of 0.05. Table 56 represents the correlation analysis for holy practices and Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.

Tab. No. 55: Correlation Analysis for Holy Practices & Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris

		Holy practices	Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan
Holy Practices	Pearson Correlation	1	0.927
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500
Rajayoga Mediation at Brahma Kumaris HQ: Mount Abu, Rajasthan	Pearson Correlation	0.927	1
	Sig (2- tailed)	0.000	0.000
	N	500	500

Source-Primary data

As depicted in the above table 56, it can be found that the correlation coefficient between various holy practices such as Murli (godly knowledge), etc is 0.927, which is much more than the standard significance level of 0.05. This result affirms the strong positive relation between the holy practices and motivation towards performing Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India. Exploring the various practices, it can be found that BKRM is holy and highest technique taught by god himself that motivates people to join Raj Yoga at BK. On the other hand, the flexibility of Raj Yoga practices and its effective execution and following mechanism encourages people to join it. There are many practices such as Murli and Amritwela etc, which signify godly knowledge too motivates people to get inclined towards BKRM. Reviews state that the practices such as waking up early and joining Murli, study and practice the godly knowledge and particularly Raj Yoga meditation, Brahmacharya principle etc significantly ignite spiritual ignition among devotees to join BKRM international headquarters at Mount Abu, Rajasthan. On the other hand, the clothing nature of devotees enables uniform and device tradition and environment which motivate people to follow the Raj Yogi principles.

In addition, there used to be various other activities such as research, health care research and development, lectures, training practices, conferences which motivates people to get associated with BKRM and practice Raj Yoga for supernatural power and god oriented affinity achievements. The personal investigative and explorative research efforts have revealed that the people at Mount Abu are completely dedicated and serving mankind without any discrimination all the 365 days a year. Such dedication affirms a strong bond between people and practices, environment and spiritual affinity at BK head quarter Mount Abu. There are numerous behavioural characteristics such as greeting each other with “Om Shanti” makes the people well connected and holy hearted. The pleasing and harmonious relationship makes people joining BKRM. Thus, observing overall responses and respective significances, it can be affirmed that the novel life culture, environment and holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World’s spiritual centre at Mount Abu, Rajasthan motivates people to get associated with it.

Overall hypothesis results obtained & their justification is given as follows:

Tab. No. 56: Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	Statement	Results
1	Demography factors play very significant role in motivating people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris.	Accepted
2	Personage thrust towards search for true spiritual means of life motivates people to become Raj yogis with Brahma Kumaris organization.	Accepted
3	Psychological, Physiological & Spiritual factors are vital motivational factors that put enthuse in Raj yogis or Raj Yoga practitioners.	Accepted
5	Novel life culture, environment & holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World’s spiritual center at Mount Abu, Rajasthan motivates people to get associated with it.	Accepted

CHAPTER-5

5 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, FUTURE SCOPE, RECOMMENDATION & LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH WORK

5.1 Background

This section of the thesis discusses the significant summary, conclusions, recommendations and limitations derived from the proposed research work. The summary and conclusions derived from the empirical study and analysis for assessing -various motivational factors encouraging people to go for Raj Yoga meditation are discussed in this section. Later, some of the key recommendations have been presented in this chapter.

5.2 SUMMARY

This is the matter of fact that the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University has emerged as a new religious movement that came into existence in 1936 in Hyderabad, Pakistan, the religion consisted of little more than a close-knit gathering of Lekhraj's closest family, friends, and business associates, although it quickly grew by attracting mostly young women as member

The Brahma Kumaris insist that the God whom they channel is the same God whom all other religions worship throughout the world. This kind of universalistic claim is not uncommon among Hindu sects, but the Brahma Kumaris are unusual insofar as they firmly reject polytheism, henotheism, pantheism, and all other understandings of God worldwide, insisting instead on a strong form of monotheism wherein only one God has ever existed.

The Brahma Kumaris are registered with national governments and the global community of international non-governmental organizations as two separate corporate entities. The religious organization is known as The World Renewal Spiritual Trust, and their secular educational and service organization is known as The Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University (also known as The Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa-Vidyalyaya). The religious side is a “trust,” their secular side is a “spiritual university.”

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation teaching spiritual knowledge and practicing the ancient technique of Raja Yoga Meditation, as taught by the Prajapita Brahma

Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya, Mount Abu, for the past 80 years. It conducts motivational paths and opposite on a wide spectrum of themes such as: Stress Free Lifestyle, Leadership Skills, Emotional Intelligence, Art of Right Thinking, Living Values, Exploring Inner Powers, Self Management, Harmony in Relationships and the Practical Technique of Raja Yoga Meditation.

Brahma kumaris defines members (BKs) of the Brahma Kumaris as social ascetics. BKs live a life of rigorous purity, based around their central practice of meditation. The disciplines of these social ascetics are designed to free the mind, through mastery over the body, culminating in self-sovereignty. While some BKs live in ashrams in moderately cloistered communities, most live at home with their families and conduct normal lives according to their environment, culture and circumstances.

The great majority of Brahma Kumaris administrators throughout the organization are women. The Brahma Kumaris look forward to the return of a rapidly approaching Golden Age wherein men and women are entirely equal. Meanwhile, in order to aid its members in their efforts to balance their souls and attain perfect purity before the coming world transformation, the organization elevates women to the highest offices so they may learn to exercise their leadership abilities and so men may learn humility.

Significantly, the word “Kumaris” in the organization’s name, “Brahma Kumaris,” means “Children” in Hindi, and the Brahma Kumaris understand themselves as children of God, making them all siblings to each other. One of the organization’s three primary modes of interaction is familial, and it is in precisely this sense of sisterhood (and brotherhood) that the Brahma Kumaris understand family, with God as the only true parent. Brahma Kumaris earn their level in the hierarchical administration by deepening the purity of their spiritual attainments, specifically the virtue of their moral conduct, their capacity for dignity and respect. Advancement within the organization is familial, spiritual, and administrative. Each of these three modalities for the attainment of power work together to provide checks and balances against the others

The Brahma Kumaris is the world’s first and largest spiritual movement led by women. It is the leading institution in the world catering to the spiritual needs of

women- Eighty years ago the founder of this spiritual university while honoring women stated, **“Women power opens the door of heaven”** and attributed them a dignified position. Hence the name given to this Vishwa Vidyalaya, “Brahma Kumari” is the ultimate status and dignity to women. This was one of the revolutionary steps in the history of Brahma Kumaris and in the whole of the world. Brahma Kumaris contributed in easily accessible and pulsating panorama of practical wisdom enriched in oriental heritage of values, spirituality and yoga in crystallization of the self from the darkness of ignorance, so one may be able to sense their subtle presence and savor the essence of their messages for peace, purification and illumination of the mind. Deeply understanding the need of the hour, the Brahma Kumaris literature and teachings is promoting practical wisdom of character building and enriching values that lie at the core of our inner being.

Some BKs consider their path to be distinct from Hinduism, as do other Indian founded NRMs, including the International Society for Krishna Consciousness (ISKCON) and others

By 1984 the Brahma Kumaris was established in approximately 30 countries. In 1986 the Brahma Kumaris conducted its first international program, the Million Minutes of Peace, for which it received seven UN Peace Messenger awards. For Million Minutes of Peace, people from 88 countries donated minutes of peace through time spent in prayer, meditation and peaceful thought, creating a ‘bank’ of peace. In four weeks, 1,231,975,713 minutes (equivalent to 2,344 years) were collected. In 1988, the Global Cooperation for a Better world was created as a follow –up to million minutes of Peace. People were asked to share their visions of what a better world might look like through dialogue, art, performance and workshops. The Living Values Education Program (Tillman 2007), as well as other values –based initiatives (virola and corpus 2008), began from these pioneering initiatives.

As BK international membership has continued to expand, with 100,000 in 1988 and 850,000 in 2009, the organization has constructed two new campuses: Gyān Sarovar (1995) that accommodates 1700 people and is halfway down the mountain, and Shāntivan (1998), in the plains of Rajasthan at the foot of Mt Abu. Shantivan, These campuses accommodate pilgrims who come in tens of thousands from within India and overseas for regular meetings and spiritual

retreats during the summer season between September and April, the cooler season. There are particular times reserved for Indians and foreigners, arranged to expedite comfortable accommodation for large (15,000) and small (3,000) numbers respectively. The division between 'Indian season' and 'foreign season' is somewhat flexible, with both Indians and foreigners invariably present at each occasion. Visitors from India usually stay for only a few days given their large numbers, whereas the recommended length of stay for foreigners is two weeks, particularly considering the distances some non-Indian BKs cover to get there .

The practice of open-eyed raja yoga enables positive feelings and good wishes to be exchanged through the practice of drishti, a most fundamental form of spiritual dharnā (inculcation of divine virtues) and a sacred ritual for BKs. Drishti is both a natural spiritual gaze, and the act of exchanging positive energetic vibrations through the eyes. BKs understand that a meditative state of mind creates an atmosphere the vibration of which can be transmitted to one another through the eyes. Drishti is considered to be one of the highest forms of expressing spiritual love, power and good feeling between souls. While the eyes are open, attention is focused inward, and so the eyes are passive, used only to transmit vibrations and not to 'see' (Whaling 1995).

The Brahma Kumaris has as its prime purpose of spreading the message of peace, love, unity and harmony all over the world. To accomplish this task, BK organization has widely spread its roots and grown into a gigantic tree. It has established nearly 9200 spiritual/ service centres in 142 countries of the world with more than 10 lakh regular raja yoga practioners/ devotees and crores of followers through media.

Courses offered:

As a leading institution imparting education in spiritual knowledge and human values the Brahma Kumaris offers people of all backgrounds an opportunity to explore the deep mysteries of the soul, God, karma, the cycle of time and the technique of Raja yoga meditation. Courses offered includes, Foundation Course in Raja yoga Meditation, Self- Empowerment Workshops, Stress Management and Right Thinking(SMART), Diploma, P.G. Diploma & M.Sc., in Values & Spirituality, M.B.A. in Self Management & Crises Management, Life

Management Skills, Positive Change in Life (for youth), Positive Approach to Total Health, Values in Family Life (for women), The Art of Happy Living etc

Other Spiritual Courses includes, Positive Thinking, Stress Free Living, Self Managing Leadership(SML) , The Four Faces of Woman , Self Management Quality of Life , The Secrets of Self-Esteem , Project Positive Change , Positive Approach to Total Health (PATH) etc

In 1950, the institution moved to Mount Abu, a quiet place reputed for its ancient heritage and regarded as a sacred destination by many in search of spiritual rejuvenation and empowerment. Nestled high in the Aravali Mountains of Rajasthan, it provided an ideal location for reflection and contemplation. In the folklore of ancient texts, Abu is praised as a holy place and is associated with the names of sages and seers; thus there are many temples and hermitages to be found upon it. The Brahma Kumaris global headquarters are based in Mount Abu, Rajasthan, in India. The headquarters complex consists of mainly five campuses -Madhuban (Pandav Bhawan), Gyan Sarovar , Shantivan , recreational park called Peace Park, and the Global Hospital & Research Centre(GHRC).

Cradled by Mount Abu 's rugged splendor and lush vegetation, and nestled near the still waters of Nakki Lake, lies 'Madhuban', the global headquarters of the Brahma Kumaris.

Madhuban is a place where thousands of BK students from nearly **142 countries** gather to deepen their meditation practice. Madhuban's clear and subtle atmosphere of spirituality inspires profound experiences. A practitioner of Raja Yoga meditation has no need to make radical changes in life-style or permanently leave home and family. However, a few weeks in Madhuban, away from worldly responsibilities, dramatically assists a student's spiritual growth. Lectures and workshops provide essential tools which enable students to explore and emerge the powers of spirituality innate within each human being. Madhuban has a powerful spiritual ambience created by years of meditation by senior Rajyogis, Lakhs of BK students go to Madhuban each year for spiritual refreshment and advanced spiritual learning.

Second complex is Gyan Sarovar is officially known as 'The Academy for a Better World'. The name Gyan Sarovar is reminiscent of 'Mansarovar', about which a legend goes that anyone who dipped into the lake emerged in the form of a fairy or an angel. Gyan Sarovar is an environment which enables individuals to dip into the 'Lake of Knowledge' and emerge highly transformed.

Founded by the Brahma Kumaris in 1996, the Gyan Sarovar Academy for a Better World was inaugurated as part of the celebration of the University's 60th anniversary. The Academy is an international campus - a place where men, women and children can reach their unique human potential and cultivate the values of our common humanity.

Gyan sarovar which is located on Mt. Abu four kilometres from Madhuban, the Brahma Kumaris have created a retreat atmosphere without disturbing the natural topography and the original environment. The design integrates both urban and rural elements into a harmonious and holistic environment which lends itself to being eco-friendly and free from air and noise pollution.

Gyan Sarovar is an ultra-modern campus in a rural setting that presents a soul elevating, eco-friendly atmosphere where learning and experiencing spiritual values become an unforgettable experience.

Western Rajasthan is one of the least privileged areas of India. Much of it is desert, water is in short supply and the illiteracy rate is high. The majority of the population has long been deprived of basic health measures. The Global Hospital and Research Centre is a dream come true for the tribals and local people of Mount Abu. The GHRC was built with an aim to provide holistic health-care in this predominantly rural and poor area, by blending the best of western science and oriental remedies with the techniques of Raja yoga meditation. The unique aspect of GHRC is its beautiful surroundings, clean interiors and the serene, smiling faces of the hospital staff.

Day to day operations in GHRC are supervised by qualified personnel, most of whom are also practitioners of Raja yoga meditation. It has 15 clinics in the Out-Patient Department, 70 in-patient beds, fully equipped operating rooms, radiology and path lab for diagnostic procedures and special clinics for

homeopathy, magneto therapy and nature cure. The hospital provides more than 80% of its services free of charge.

The Brahma Kumaris Peace Park is both lovely and serene, a natural environment where silence and recreation co-exist. The park offers a perfect recreational environment, with level playing fields, picnic areas, swings, and nature walks. Nestled between two famous peaks of the Aravali hills-the well known spiritual pilgrimage destinations of Gum Shikhar and Achal Garb-Peace Park is an oasis of natural beauty only 8 kms from the Madhuban campus. The Peace Park is a tribute to the Brahma Kumaris' commitment to sustaining natural environments. The park is an oasis of natural beauty where silence and recreation co-exist. It is located 8 km from the BK headquarters.

The other main campus is Shantivan- The Forest of Peace (Talhati, Abu Road)-The fast pace of service across the world has seen the BK family growing and attracting spiritual seekers in large numbers. Consequently, by 1997 a huge campus, Shantivan, came up at the foot of Mount Abu, outside Abu Road town. The main features includes- accommodation for 15,000 people; a three-storey dining complex, a conference hall, six seminar halls, two meditation rooms and an art gallery, printing press for publishing BK literature, magazines and publicity material, the mammoth Diamond Hall, which can seat 20,000 people and the largest parabolic solar facility in India for cooking and generating electricity.

Other BK HQ initiatives :

Godly Wood studio-Incorporeal God Shiva, through Brahma Kumaris, has gifted to every Robin hood of Multi media planet, a creation called Godly wood Studio. The main aim is to awaken the masses with high –tech facilities and train them in Godly Knowledge and easy Raja Yoga, to relay the live shows of Brahma Kumaris teachings and meditation courses, to prepare and relay such courses for a tension free and spiritual living and to bring about the manifestation of Godly plan of the new World through transformation and propagation of purity, peace and prosperity

Peace of mind TV Channel – Gods greatest gift to spiritual enlightenment :-

Brahma Kumaris brings Peace of mind Channel for living peaceful life. Peace of Mind, as the name suggests, is a channel that helps viewers experience peace and joy in their life through programmes that not only entertain but also enrich, empower and enlighten them. Yet, this is not another religious channel. Peace of Mind shows viewers how they can lead a more focused, stable, healthy and successful life by using spiritual principles effectively. It shows a better way of life whereby one can achieve success without stress, enjoy harmonious relationships at work and at home, and have the inner strength to deal with all challenges.

The channel provides an eclectic mix of programmes, including guided meditation, songs, talks by experts on self-improvement and the practical application of spirituality in various walks of life, besides cultural programmes and panel discussions where viewers can get solutions to their various problems in life. There are also first-person accounts by well-known people who have used spirituality in their life and found that it works.

The programmes planned for the 24x7 Channel on Cable network will be offered in all major languages (English, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Marathi, Oriya, Tamil, Telugu) to reach Direct-To-Home (DTH) in India and many parts of the world.

Broadcasting 24 hours a day, Peace of Mind is brought to you by the Brahma kumaris, for helping hundreds of thousands of people to transform their lives for the better. The institution nurtures respect for all faith traditions and delineates an enlightened lifestyle. Through numerous social service activities and partnerships, it promotes spiritual understanding, leadership with integrity and elevated actions towards a better world.

This TV channel provides the viewers to Watch all Brahma Kumaris Programmes and Live programmes from Madhuban, international HQ's of Brahma Kumaris and totally dedicated to the cause of re-establishing moral and spiritual values, and bestowing peace of mind to the maximum number of people, who are genuinely searching for inner peace and happiness.

Radio Madhuban- 90.4 FM : SUNTE RAHO MUSKURATE RAHO

Radio madhuban community Society(RMCS) has been formed with the noble aim of serving all the sections of the community. Radio madhuban community Society(RMCS) is a registered body under the societies Registration Act XXI of 1860 with all India registration no: S/401/2013 .

Aims and Objectives of Radio madhuban community Society is to create awareness in Healthy way of life/Hygiene/Cleanliness/Rural Sanitation, to facilitate needy health care at villages., to Literate the populate / Value Education for all, women Empowerment/Child Care/Stopping of Female Feticide, to conduct campaigns for Drugs / Substance abuse etc

“INDIA ONE”- Solar Thermal Power Plant Project

Energy is one of the most important requirements for this world to function properly. Its availability and regular supply are of paramount interest. As we are all aware, energy and fuel prices are rising day by day and the negative effects of global warming are ore and more visible. World Renewal Spiritual Trust (WRST), a registered Charitable Trust/ recognized Solar Research Centre and sister organization of the Brahma Kumaris, is setting up **“India One”** a 1.0 Mw el. Solar thermal power plant in order to demonstrate and multiply this innovative technology for India. “India One” will supply power and hot water for the headquarters of Brahma Kumaris (25 000 people) in Abu Road, Rajasthan, India.“India One” is based on a Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) technology with a unique concept of 770 nos in-house developed 60 SQM flexible paraboloid dishes which offer a static focus with fully automatic dual axis tracking mechanism.

Due to the unique feature of a static focus, there is an advantage of integrating energy storage at the focus. High intensity solar radiation can be injected into a cavity receiver that acts as thermal energy storage; energy can be stored for 16 off-sunny hours, thus enabling 24 hour operation. Project delivers an indigenous technology suitable for India and provides standardized manufacturing process, enabling replication of the technology. For this project, WRST has teamed up with Fraunhofer Institute (ISE), enjoys the support of Wolfgang Scheffler and has secured part funding

from the Indian and German Government. WRST is in close liaison with various solar R&D institutions and manufacturers and has started fabrication and erection by beginning of 2011.

“India One” is partly financed by the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India and Ministry of Environment (BMU) Government of Germany via the GIZ. “The thermal solar power plant (solar only) will be the first of its kind in dish technology in direct steam generation mode, with full thermal storage for 16 hrs continuous operations for base load.”

Brahma kumaris offers many spiritual service activities in India namely foundation course in Raja yoga meditation, Spiritual Service through Multimedia, Om Shanti Help Line- which provides 24-hour free assistance to people who are suffering from depression, sorrow and stress. The helpline is available in many languages and in several cities in India, Print media services ie, Brahma Kumaris publishes several spiritual magazines in English, Hindi and regional languages. Prominent among these are Gyanamrit (Hindi monthly), World Renewal (English monthly) and Purity (English monthly). Cyber media serving through lots of websites dedicated to provide information about the activities and courses of Brahma Kumaris. The official websites are: www.bkwsu.org and www.brahmakumaris.com. Important events In the institution are also web cast through the internet, Brahma Kumaris have been constantly striving to build bridges between people of different faiths and cultures. They strive to promote the core spirituality in all faiths, which is the common thread that leads to mutual understanding and respect. Apart from lots of interfaith programmes at the local level, significant events such as the Inner Voice of Peace dialogue in 2005, Dharmacharya Sammelan in 1993 and Universal Peace Conference in 1987 have been held at Mt. Abu, On the third Sunday of every month, group meditation for world peace is held at the same time in all BK centres in the world. Group meditation programmes are specially organised when calamities and disasters strike so that vibrations of peace can be created to support distressed people, Brahma Kumaris service centres, conduct awareness campaigns in the fields of health, education, de-addiction and environmental conservation. During major festivals and public occasions they join other local groups to bring people together by organizing fairs, cultural events, exhibitions, rallies and public talks in order to help enhance people's quality of life through the application of spiritual, human and

ethical values. There is a growing demand for the skills and services of Brahma Kumaris from public organizations.

There are 19 service wings of Raja yoga Education and Research Foundation (RERF) that reach out to a wide cross-section of the society and offer the benefits of various courses developed by the Brahma Kumaris. The RERF is a sister body of the Brahma Kumaris which was established in 1982 for providing specialized services to different sections of society. Throughout the year each wing holds seminars and conferences at BK campuses and organizes activities to help people integrate values and spiritual wisdom into their lives and share them in their family and workplace. The wings were created to match the understanding and serve the spiritual needs of the people of various backgrounds. It aims to create a wave of positive elevated spiritual awareness that will empower people to counteract the increasing climate of negativity, corruption, hostility and degeneration of human values..

The most popular courses of Bks which have benefited millions in India, are Stress Management, Self Development Leadership, Spiritual Empowerment and Holistic Personality Development and Education In Values and Spirituality

BKs regularly conducting many research activities among which CAD Regression Project and Meditation and Medicine attracts importance., Brahma Kumaris strive for establishing a harmonious relationship between humanity and nature. The institution has been exploring reliable, cost-effective and fossil-fuel-free alternatives to diesel generators and electricity grid extension systems for more than a decade. Among the environmental initiatives, all the BK campuses have integrated eco-friendly technology in their buildings and energy consumption, the BKs have been global pioneers in the installation and use of solar energy within large communities. The BKs are the largest private producers of solar energy in the world.

The Brahma Kumaris affiliation to the United Nations:-

- The DPI in 1980
- To ECOSOC in 1983
- To UNICEF in 1987
- To UNFCCC in 2009
- To UNEP in 2014

Brahma Kumaris contribute to the work of the United Nation

- In promoting the purpose and principles of the United Nations Charter, the trajectory of awareness, attitude, vision, and action is used in the areas of the Millennium Development Goals, Climate Change, Food Crisis, Gender Equality, Global Public Health, Humanitarian Emergencies, Human Rights, Women, Children, Youth, International Decades, Days.
- Attending UN conferences, preparatory committee meetings, commissions: presenting oral and written statements; hosting parallel events; working with NGO committees and caucuses.

Bks succeeded in many International projects and took lot of global initiatives. Some of them are Just-a-Minute -2006, Culture of Peace Manifesto-2000, Sharing our Values for a Better World -1994, Global Co-operation for a Better World 1988, The Million Minutes of Peace appeal, Living Values: An Educational Programme (LVEP), Call of the Time, Self-Managing Leadership (SML), Values in Healthcare, Four Faces of Women, International Youth Forum – IYF, Interfaith Activities, Images and Voices of Hope, Science and Consciousness, Arts and Spirituality etc

Courses on Raja yoga meditation, Stress-Free Living, Positive Thinking, Self Empowerment etc. are held round the year globally at Oxford- England, New York- USA, New South Wales,-Australia, Melbourne- Australia, Italy, Brazil, Argentina and Philippines BK retreat centers:

A mine of wisdom and compassion, Dadi Janki- Chief of Brahma kumaris and other senior dadis are the true motivational force behind the Organization. Dadi Janaki seems to live beyond the time-space barrier as she tirelessly travels from one country to the other, offering insights and inspiration to millions of people. She is one of the ten wisdom keepers of the world nominated by the World Parliament of Religions, and also the President of Janki Foundation for health care. A centenarian, living legend and Chief of Brahma Kumaris, **B.K.Rajayogini Dadi Janki** is like a light-house of wisdom to all, constantly caring, sharing and inspiring, to achieve noble objectives in life.

Spirituality can never be disassociated from way of life. Spirituality is that non-material energy which actually empowers and governs my life and my every

action Just as there are laws that govern matter, so there are also spiritual laws. The law of karma, the spiritual law of cause and effect, informs me of my own responsibility regarding how I behave and the consequence of my actions. The understanding of the soul and the Supreme are also highly relevant and applicable to my life. In the theory and model of reality taught by the Brahma Kumaris, there is wonderful, intricate knowledge that can be studied and experimented practically. To join together or to re-connect' the soul with the Supreme is the purpose of spirituality and includes the understanding of the soul and the Supreme at the deeper level. With that understanding when we perform karma, this leads to values-based actions. So spirituality leads to systematically connecting values in actions:

The word "religion" comes from the Latin religio, which is usually translated as "obligation" or "bond," and Oxford English Dictionary (OED) has it that religion represents the "human recognition of super human controlling power, and especially of a personal God or gods entitled to obedience and worship.

The Brahma Kumaris are practicing 'religion' in the true definition and bringing it into reality by spiritual means by realizing the self through the bond of spiritual reunion with God. We observe that all major religions of the world try to establish the universal values of peace and love.

Mahatma Gandhi has expressed his views-The important religions, Buddhism, Jainism, Christianity, Islam, Hinduism have all in their own way tried to bring about spiritual revolution in and through service of man. All these religions of the World aim at establishing peace and brotherhood. They all emphasize respect for mankind. There are differences among them no doubt, but these differences are superficial ones. The differences are only in details. But there is basic unity in them all. We may call it unity in diversity. All these religions teach us the cultivation of truth, love, fellow-feeling, good-will and mutual respect.

It may be also significant to state that at this same time, scientific and technological developments have conquered space. Yet science has widened the space between the soul and Supreme by limiting spirituality. Have all this scientific progress brought a spiritual revolution in human life? Is there harmony and peace in the world today? The time has come when science is finally catching up with spirituality:

The real peace and harmony can be established on the basis of spiritualism. Spiritual unification, in short, is necessary for peace and tranquility. A question may again arise

here: What is meant by spiritual revolution? The revolutionary spirit, of which Gandhiji was considered to be the symbol, has been expressed in two ways, detachment in action and detachment in service. All work should be done in the spirit of detachment and dedication. The work should be offered as an obligation to the spirit of truth. In short, by spiritual revolution he meant a radical change in man's outlook.”

The Brahma Kumaris’ “Sakar and Avyakt Murlis” give the power of practice along with the definition. Spiritual power is not outer but an inner power of the soul. The power can be enhanced only through the source of spiritual power — the Supreme Soul. The Murli of 13.12.92 presents the essence of "Spiritual Power":

What is the Spiritual Consciousness through which you can easily this elevated life? Think about this too, because according to the atmosphere of the world, this aspect is extremely essential. Therefore, you yourselves must experience this through Spiritual Consciousness (Raja Yoga) and also become instruments to give this experience. Together with your speech, you must also definitely to increase the speech of practical transformation.

The spiritual beauty of the Murli(Flute of GOD) is that Shiv Baba, the Spiritual Father is directly speaking to His Spiritual Children. The use of the words Spiritual Father and Spiritual Children is used in the Murlis and creates an experience of loving conversation of the father to his dear children. This experience is not bookish experience. On the other hand. no other religious founder or spiritual leaders have uttered these words, these divine words of "Supreme Almighty Authority". It is a rare event to observe a divine dialogue, conversation between the Supreme God, when He is speaking and looking at the spiritual power of His spiritual children. This word creates great confidence and faith in the mind of listener that "spiritual power already exists in the soul and each spiritual child has the complete right to reawaken that power from the connection with God, who is the Supreme Source of Spiritual Power.

One of the outstanding features of the Murli is that it never reflects on the negative aspects of the human souls. We all know that defects and weakness are part and parcel of the human souls. God's knows these weaknesses but the words of the Murli always appreciate and strengthen the inner qualities of the soul. The dynamic method of the Divine Murli is that it starts and concludes with spiritual blessing, elevated sound and

spiritual solutions to existing problems. From the above presentation of "spiritual power" from the Murli, there is a definition of the power of spirituality as well as the creation of natural "spiritual consciousness".

The Spiritual Father awakens spiritual strength by spiritual blessings:

- World benefactors
- Fragrance of spirituality
- The embodiment of attainment
- Spiritual Children
- The sparkle of eternal
- Celestial spiritual power
- Elevated Souls
- Great Bestower of love, respect, mercy and co-operation
- Sweet children

Such words of Almighty God speaking to his Divine children have tremendous power to transform the minds of people because he himself is observing the inherent, eternal qualities of the soul not any human being. Today at the time of crisis of values and spirituality, the positive power of such words can heal the wounds of soul. Each and every Murli covers variety of subjects concerning spirituality and values. Every day listening and reading the Murli gives the power of transformation through the direct words of God. The Murli suggests that along with solutions, a spiritual consciousness can be developed. Only through "Rajyoga" can power be developed spiritually. One has to experience this power and become instruments to give this experience to others. It is a life sharing responsibility for the creation of a better world. The Murli is a "Treasure Chest of Blessings". Each day the' Supreme God (Shiv Baba) showers the jewels of love and wisdom, drawn from the Ocean of Knowledge onto the children. It is also a special substance from these pearls from the Ocean also creates a sparkle so bright that they act as powerful blessings.

A national survey of adult Canadians (Bibby 1995) revealed that 52 percent of people acknowledged "spiritual needs". This survey is important in sense that it shows that not only in India but also in other parts of the world, people have started awakening towards the idea of spirit or soul, and understand it as their "spiritual requirement".

One of the very important reasons that the study showed a percentage increase in the awareness of spirituality among the study group is that the world is experiencing

innumerable problems and adverse situations-personal, interpersonal and global. The present crisis is mainly a crisis of values and spirituality which leads to crisis in other areas as well. The Brahma Kumaris literature and teachings focus on solutions to these crises, in the sense that it is aimed firstly at creating the knowledge of self awareness. Knowing the self is the foundation of spirituality:

This understanding of spirituality is one that comes with the opening of third eye of wisdom called "Soul" or "Spirit". It is worthy to note that the connection of values and spirituality as interconnected and interdependent. The root of values is "spirituality" and it is natural outcome when spirituality is translated into actions. Spirituality becomes effective when it is applied in day to day thoughts. It also requires every day, practice, study and also learning from the experience of others:

Spirituality is more a practical science than a mere theoretical dissertation. The various scriptures of the different religions of the world provide us with the theoretical aspect only and cannot give us a demonstrative experience of the reality in the laboratory of the human body.

The Brahma Kumaris' literature and teachings very enthusiastically promotes the idea of Satyug and New Kingdom. It not only explains the prime reasons of "Paradise Lost" but also how Paradise can be regained. Avyakt Murli of 30-1-85 expresses the beauty of Satyug is about how the five elements will serve us there. Mahatma Gandhi also believed that paradise is here on this earth not above in the sky. This is similar to the Brahma Kumaris' spiritual philosophy that suggests when people free themselves from vices and ego, they will be living a life of virtues and this earth will be a paradise of deities. Mahatma Gandhi remarked: "If there is a Paradise on earth, It is here, It is here, It is here". There will be neither paupers nor beggars, nor high nor low, neither millionaire employer nor half starved employee, nor intoxicating drinks or drugs. There will be the same respect for women as vouchsafed to men, and the chastity and purity of men and women will be guarded. Where there will be no untouchability and where there will be equal respect for all faiths."

The Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university is implementing unique methods for

the progress of values through spirituality in the world. How can spirituality and values be developed together? What new dimensions are available? There is no need to separate the efforts used to develop spirituality and values. Spirituality and values are co-related in such a way that when spirituality is developed values automatically emerge; and when values are developed, they increase spirituality.

Central to the Brahma Kumaris practice is the teaching of all their core beliefs in 7 one, or one and a half hour, long lessons traditionally called "The 7 Day Course". Once these 7 lessons are understood, students were then introduced to unpublished scriptures considered to be the direct teachings of God called "Murlis" named after the flute that the Hindu God Krishna is generally illustrated holding. These comprise of the core philosophy of their religion and are known as "Gyan" or "The Knowledge". The use of the word "Knowledge" is specific to these beliefs and absolute faith in this knowledge is seen as central to the liberation of the soul.

Seven basic lessons learnt during the course are:

8. The Soul
9. The Supreme Soul
10. The Law of Karma
11. The Cycle
12. The Tree of Religions
13. The Founder Brahma Baba
14. Brahma Kumaris' Lifestyle and Principles

Education Wing of Raja Yoga Education and Research Foundation of Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya proposed to conduct a formal education programme "Post Graduate Diploma in Value Education and Spirituality" for the graduate degree holders of Indian nationality. World renowned Chiddambaram Annamalai University agreed to launch the programme in Technical Collaboration with Brahma Kumaris Education Wing as a Distance Education Programme. A memorandum of understanding was signed on 7th February, 2009.

Education Wing of RE & RF of Brahma Kumaris in collaboration with different universities has successfully conducted SEVEN convocation programmes till June

2016 and thousands of students have been awarded diploma, degree and master degree in Value Education and spirituality.

The Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya is not only building toward helping to develop the 'integrated personality' of people but it is also promoting emotional integration between various religious communities and ethnic, racial, linguistic and regional groups. Thus the Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya is not a religious institution, preaching any one cult or sect, it is an institution that imparts education on universal spiritual values and brings understanding and unity to all and peace to the planet Earth.

The Researcher wants to clarify that since this university gives education in values and spirituality; it also celebrates some religious festivals and respects the ideas of other religions. Some people get the impression that it is a religious institution. They miss the silent features of this educational institution, which distinguishes it from religious institutions. The Brahma Kumaris World spiritual university is called a spiritual university because it is not religious sect but it is secular. Since it is not a religion, people of all different religious backgrounds, language, caste, colour and nationality come here for spiritual study. Thus, the Brahma Kumaris is not any religious cult or sect. On the other hand it is an institution that imparts education in universal values and brings understanding and unity to all and peace to the planet earth. **It is practical example of unity in diversity:**

Where as most other universities enable a person to attain a Master's Degree in one of the arts or science., the BK Vishwa- Vidyalaya enables him to be the master of his own thoughts, desires, emotions and sense-organs. The BK Vishwa-Vidyalaya does not impart education in all those subjects which are being taught in other Universities, for that would just be the duplication or the overlapping of efforts. **The thrust of knowledge imparted..is first to make man, in 'reality, a man and to enable him to have practical wisdom and to learn lessons for constant peace and happiness and for excellence in life.**

The Brahma Kumaris as called at "spiritual university" because there is daily spiritual study which is the most significant part of the spiritual education. The basic four subjects of this spiritual study are Gyan- Spiritual Knowledge, Yoga- Rajayoga

meditation, Dharna- Inoculation of divine virtues, and Seva- Spiritual service. The balance of these four subjects in everyday life includes a beautiful synthesis of knowledge and practice. These subjects are integrated with each other. Gyan or study of spiritual knowledge is the first founding subject of the spiritual study. This everyday study is based on listening and reading the Divine Godly versions of the Murli. The Murli is the direct direction (Shrimat) of the Ocean of Knowledge Supreme God (Baba) to his beloved children. The 'Murli' covers all the four subjects of spiritual study. The Murli not only gives the knowledge and study of these subjects but also gives direction about how to implement these subjects in daily life. The spiritual knowledge means complete knowledge of Soul which leads to self realization.

In recognition of the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual Organization's services to humanity, the Govt. of India has appointed BK Chief 100-year-old Rajyogini Dadi Janki as the Brand Ambassador of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission) by inviting to the President House for the Clean India Mission program on 10th September 2015

The word 'meditation' comes from the latin word 'meditari' which is a probable cognate of the word 'mederi' meaning 'to heal'. Journeying inside, discovering the inner self and our true power is the beginning of the healing process, in which we are able to put back all the broken pieces with a lot of love. Meditation is the process of getting to know yourself completely, both who you are inside and how you react to what is outside. Through meditation, we discover a very different 'me' from perhaps the stressed or troubled person, who may seem superficially to be 'me'. You realize that your true nature, the real you, is actually very positive. "Meditation is Conscious sleep whereas sleep is unconscious meditation"

By contemplating deeply on the various meanings and definitions of "meditation" given from different perspectives by the many great spiritual leaders or philosopher and religious founders, we can find it beautiful synthesis of thoughts about Yoga. The words may differ but the essence and meaning is more or less similar. Yoga is the greatest spiritual power that helps to maintain equilibrium in the midst of great challenges and obstacles. All these spiritual leaders and thinkers pointed out

specifically that "Yoga" means the linking or union of the soul with the divine.

Raja Yoga Meditation is awareness of the metaphysical self and absorption of one's mind in hopeful and purposeful consciousness of God and his divine attributes. The word 'Yoga' means 'to unite'; Yoga is, therefore, the practice or art of uniting or linking the mind with God by focusing attention on him as an incorporeal being-of-light and thinking of nothing but his divine qualities. This takes one into a state of absorption in bliss and peace through positive thinking. It recharges one's self or soul with light and might and fills one with creative energy. In the name 'Raja-Yoga' the word 'Raja' means the king, the sovereign or the supreme. This yoga is called Raja-Yoga because it is the supreme or the highest yoga, being true and most effective. Another reason for calling it 'Raja-Yoga' is that it is related mainly to mind and mind is considered as the 'King that rules the sense-organs and the body. Moreover, the term Raja-Yoga also implies that even such a person as a king, who is very busy and has so much to do, can practice it, there is no need to practice breath-control, physical postures, or use a mantra, or an image nor does it require one to stop all thoughts, but stop only, worldly or negative thoughts and concentrate our mind on God.

“The word 'Meditation' means 'to think'. As we all know, man's mind is, ordinary, occupied with hundreds of thoughts of the world. In Raja-Yoga meditation, one withdraws one's mind from all the worldly thoughts, including the thoughts of one's own body, and one collects oneself, consciousness, at least for some time, and thinks of the shining and peaceful self as a point of divine and conscient light and then focuses one's attention on god as supreme soul, who also is a point of conscient light and is the ocean of peace.” The inhibition of worldly thoughts and the recollection or recapitulation of thoughts of the luminous self is attained by directing the flow of thoughts towards god i.e. the supreme soul in his supreme abode or Paramdham which is the world of divine light. In this sense, this meditation is withdrawal or reversal of one's consciousness, from the body and its world to the soul and its silent world, or from the dark lanes of negative thoughts on the bright path of contemplation on god. Raja-Yoga meditation may therefore, be defined as a disciplined exercise of awareness, utilizing such processes as creatively thinking, intuitively perceiving and silently reflecting and concentrating on the metaphysical truths of self and god which

lead to comprehension and realization of the subject. This practice involves the turning of one's mind and the flow of his love in the direction of god, giving him the hot-link to communicate with him. Raja yoga Meditation is the way for realization of the real identity of the self and for experiencing it. It helps a person to know the truth about the real nature of mind or the self. Raja Yoga enables a person to withdraw from the thoughts of the body and the material world for a while.

The philosophy of Raja yoga enables the participant to focus the mind on the metaphysical self and link itself love fully to the supreme soul who is light, bliss, peace, love and might personified in the form of a brilliant and radiant point. Raja Yoga meditation is refreshing, energizing, relaxing, reassuring and reawakening. Raja Yoga makes the soul increasingly aware of its divine origin, divine destiny and divine peaceful real nature. Raja Yoga possesses numerous social significances that helps in developing spiritual approach towards others and created an attitude of Universal Brotherhood in the aspirant of Yoga.

Raja yoga meditation can help in curing numerous psychological problems such as neurotic illness and many other diseases like hypertension, Insomnia, depression etc. Raja Yoga removes tension, nervousness, fear and other negativities, which disturb a person, hence relaxing the mind completely. This way the negative symptoms that the average middle class neurotics experience are cured with the help Raja yoga. Some of the neurotic diseases, which can be easily cured through Raja Yoga, are anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorders, phobias etc by combing Raja Yoga with conventional psychopharmacology and psychotherapy. Further more positive thoughts can be used during Raj Yoga to overcome stress, fear for holistic health. The dose of medicine can be reduced and the disease can be eradicated to the core, since meditation removes the root cause of psychosomatic diseases.

Meditation of BKs is a relationship between the soul and the Supreme Soul. The starting point of meditation is always soul consciousness, and the techniques used by novices are the same as those used by BKs of seventy years in gyān. Through the ascetic practices of hypo-arousal techniques (Howell 1997:151) to discipline the mind, BKs first slow their thoughts and maintain mental quietude while concentrating on the self as a soul and remembering the Supreme Soul. The

idea is to slow down the mind enough so that thoughts then produce experiences. During meditation and in daily life, BKs aim to experience the sustenance and happiness of all relationships, such as those of mother, father, friend, companion, child and guide, with Shiv Baba. BKs say they enjoy a meditative state free of all external supports (including mantras, breathing, positions and chanting), drawing all forms of power and sustenance from Shiv Baba.

As meditation helps consciousness move beyond self-limiting beliefs, the presence of God is experienced in the state of yoga – a mental link with the Source of spiritual power. We are used to knowing things by seeing them, hearing them, tasting them, touching or smelling them. Most of us have grown up in a ‘seeing-is-believing’ and ‘hands on’ culture and we are used to perceiving things in that way. Because we can’t see, hear, taste, touch or smell God, the question arises – is God for real? One can reach out to God with pure thoughts and be connected to Him. The soul experiences the response of pure feelings and spiritual strength. God is truth itself and thus can be recognized with the eye of truth.

Like us, God is also a soul. Unlike us, He is referred to as the Supreme Soul – the only soul who never takes a body (gross or subtle, human or angelic) of His own. He is beyond the effects of actions and is never subject to the dualities of birth and death, pleasure and pain, success and failure. Being beyond the limits of time of this physical world, He retains absolute knowledge of the universe and all its dimensions. God lives, not everywhere but somewhere. A thought of God almost always takes the eyes upwards, as though one is perhaps expecting a face to miraculously appear from behind the clouds or to beam down from the moon. Thoughts are powerful. They link one soul to another. If they are properly channeled, thoughts can even go where only the soul can travel – beyond the moon and stars to a dimension of golden red light, the original home of all souls. Immersed in the experience of the warmth of this light, the soul feels as though it is truly at home at last, and with God.

Like the physical sun, which gives light and life indiscriminately to all beings, God is the Spiritual Sun, giving light to all, whomever and wherever they may be. He serves altruistically, without any selfish motives, reminding each one of their innate qualities

of love, peace and happiness. This is why He has been remembered in some countries and cultures by the name Shiva, The Benevolent One.

Beauty is a thing that bewitches man and draws his mind and understanding again towards itself. But beauty of the physical body and other physical things is only temporary and subject to gradual decline and decay. On the contrary, it is the Supreme Soul, the Supreme Father, who is absolutely and truly beautiful. His beauty is spotless; it never suffers change or decline. Remembering Him will make a soul clean and beautiful.

People may wonder why, if God exists, He doesn't wave a magic wand and fix things, making or at least influencing everyone so that they do exactly what they 'should' do. But God never takes away anyone's freedom of choice. God's wisdom is to recognize and respect each soul's individual identity, freedom and inherent goodness. God shares knowledge – a profound understanding of the dualities and dilemmas of love and hatred, happiness and sorrow, victory and defeat, etc. – but He does not make our choices for us. The soul is free to choose 'to be or not to be', 'to love or not to love'. God's love strengthens the soul's will to free itself from the distresses caused by vices such as selfish desire, anger, fear, ego and attachment. God's power helps the soul to recognize its highest potential and to aim for perfection by practicing the art of simple living and high thinking. Such practice by a significant number of souls eventually brings about positive change in the whole of humanity. When you learn to tune your mind in meditation to the mind of God, then whatever the situation, you always have a source of help and strength to draw upon – an infinite reservoir of power and virtues that is only a thought away.

Meditation is the only answer to our all current problems. Practical meditation is highly recommended for those who are beginning to discover the beauty and strength of their own inner self. If we want to keep up with the ever-increasing pace of life, its complexities and problems, we need to develop the power of the mind to a great extent.

Is meditation the only effective method to develop the power of the mind? The answer is yes – meditation is the most ancient and most original spiritual treasure. From its

glorious past, India is now considered to be the spiritual “Light House” for the rest of the world. Since the Vedic period until today our great spiritual leaders and Yogis, who practiced Yoga in their life, have also mentioned that beyond religious rituals, ceremonies and traditions the power which can transform a life is the “Practice of Yoga”. The Practice of Yoga has a deep connection with the universal human values. In light of this important point only universal human values and meditation practices for a better world is connected in this chapter. Today people are looking for the right path to practice values in their life. Meditation or Yoga practices have been discovered and perfected into certain specific methods through which human consciousness can be revolutionized and changed. The Brahma Kumaris literature and practices concentrate mainly on the practice of Yoga meditations and through the practice of yoga, the application of values comes more easily and naturally in life.

The Murlis are the tool for the highest contemplation on knowledge and yoga. In the Murlis this truth has been clearly explained in an easy manner, “Who God is” and “Who is Supreme”? No human being can be the Supreme God. They can be called Devi or Devatas (next to God) but not the Supreme God. In the Murlis it is explained that God comes and explains the secrets of the Vedas and scriptures. God is the Purifier, the Almighty Authority. He is also called the World Almighty Authority. He knows the beginning, the middle, and the end of the whole world.

This yoga easily leads to Samadhi or the state of absorption; so, it is also known as ‘Sahaj Raja Yoga’ – The word Sahaj means: that which is easy or that which becomes a part of one’s nature. Thus, it should be borne in mind that Gyan Yoga, Karma Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, etc, are not different kinds of Yoga but these are the various names given to the Raja Yoga, taught by Shiva, the Lord of yogis, given to it to point out its salient features. All those who practice this Raja Yoga do necessarily have some knowledge, spirit of devotion or dedication etc, though some have more of these than others have.

Since the Yoga taught by Shiva, the Lord of Yogis, is based on knowledge of the self, the cosmos, the moral laws, the Supreme Soul etc., It is also known as Yoga of Knowledge or Gyan Yoga. Further, since it has to be practiced by means of the intellect, as it does not involve any physical postures, it is also called “Intellectual Communion or Buddhi Yoga. Again, since a practitioner of this yoga has to keep his

mind linked to God even while discharging social, professional and other obligations, it is also known as “Karma Yoga”. The practice of this yoga, does not require the renunciation of one’s household or one’s duties and Karmas; it demands renunciation of only evil tendencies, attachment and that which is ignoble. From that point of view, it is also termed as Sanyasa Yoga or the Yoga of Renunciation. One, who practices it, acts as a mere trustee with God overhead; he considers himself as a mere instrument. He acts with good wishes for all. He surrenders himself mentally and absolutely to God and acts according to his injunctions. This makes him free of all worries, fears, vain thoughts and negative moods. Therefore, it is also called the Yoga of Equanimity or ‘Samatwa Yoga’ and one who attains it is called ‘Sthitha Prajna’ – a yogi having equanimity. Furthermore, the yoga is based on deep love for any dedication to God; so, it may also be called Bhakti Yoga though, it should be noted, one does not perform any worship or Japa. It can be called Bhakti Yoga only in the senses that love for and consciousness of God is an essential factor in this yoga.

In general there are four pillars of Raj Yoga .They are

a) Satwic Diet (Shudha Ann)- The satwic means pure vegetarian diet. The Brahma Kumaris’ philosophy has taken an innovative step by promoting the concept of a ‘Vegetarian Diet’ as Compulsory rule for mental and physical hygiene of human being. The Brahma Kumaris meditation centres and its spiritual students all over the World follow the same vegetarian life style for the upliftment of the soul. Hence the saying “*Jaisa ann vaisa mann*” – As is the food so is the mind. It went further in promoting the concept that if food is cooked in positive consciousness and if also offered to God before eating resulted in tremendous improvement in health and life style of the people. **b) Good Company (Satsanga)-** There is an old adage, which says, "As is the company so is the colour" (*Jaisa sang Vaisa Rang*). By keeping good company of those who also aspire to purity and self transformation will help the yogi to attain better results.

c) Divine Virtues (Divya Gun)- Spirituality nurtures the virtues of the soul. Divine Virtues of humility, love, truth, honesty, faith and courage elevates the practice of Yoga. The result end of yoga is gift of values. The soul starts flying, leaving behind

d) Brahmacharya or Chastity

The most powerful of all the five major vices enemy is sex lust. It is also mentioned in

our holy books to control and conquer this vice. The practical reason for celibacy is that the soul's energy is conserved and channeled in more creative and beneficial ways in serving others. "Lust" is the greatest enemy of a Raj Yogi as it increases attachment to the body and to others. Our history is the testimony of the fact that many spiritual sages and leaders lived the life of celibacy for spiritual upliftment. The Brahma Kumaris persuaded the idea in more dignified manner that it observed the purity of thoughts words and actions. It is also remarked: "Brahmacharya is the most important of the vows prescribed by Gandhiji.... Gandhiji took the comprehensive meaning of brahmacharya, if properly practised, ultimately leads to the realisation of Brahma.....it consists in the control of all the senses. Anger and impure thought do not provide strength to brahmacharya. Thus, Gandhiji maintained this moral weapon as means of self control."

Stages of RAJA Yoga Meditation

Meditation is a progressive discipline. Its four stages are a way to develop our abilities systematically.

1) Initiation – Self Awareness-The Brahma Kumaris' "Rajyoga" practice in the initial stage of "preparation of the mind" replacing negative to pure thoughts by introducing "Rajyoga" commentary. These thoughts for meditation in "Rajyoga" commentaries are words that are softly and sweetly spoken by the "Rajyogi" expert teachers to support the new meditators at an initial stage. The Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga meditation played an outstanding role in meditation practice by introducing the "Guided Meditation Commentary" as a novel step in understanding the different stages of meditation. With soft background music at the time of guided meditation, the soul is filled with inner joy. Here is an example of the process:

Sitting comfortable, I take a few deep breaths to allow my body to be energized, and at the same time become cool and calm.... I feel my body settling down.... I become aware of the muscles in my feet, in my legs, my back, my shoulders... Keeping my back upright, to stay alert, I let go of the tension, have been holding, and feel it dissolve..... with my eyes open, gently ahead, alert but no staring, I come to the forehead....my thoughts focus here....I can feel light radiating from a source, a spark of life at the centre of the forehead... this is I, the eternal soul, the origin of awareness in this physical body.... I am a soul, not the body...but this body is a wonderful vehicle, which I hold in trust....in this awareness of the soul, looking inwards, within

this spark of light, I realise that other beings are also souls, being of peace. IamPeaceLove.....Bliss.

Going deep inside, my thoughts slow down and I focus on the point of peace..... as my mind becomes calm and peaceful I am able to connect with the supreme, the Being of Light.....and God's light and love come shining through.

2)Contemplation-Contemplation means the channeling of thoughts in the direction of God. This is the stage defined in the Murli' as "Vernan", when the self in soul consciousness it can be connected with God and start revealing the qualities of God. Gently from inward journeys the self' start turning towards God. At first it may be hard to focus on such thoughts that we are peaceful souls, a point of light, eternal. The positive visualization of soul and thinking of original qualities — 'I am at peace with myself, at peace with others, at peace with the world and at peace with God.' God is eternally the unlimited ocean of virtues: God gives without any desire or expectation of return. This means he is totally benevolent. Baba is a sweet and familiar name for 'Father', thus Shiva Baba is the benevolent Father of souls. This contemplation of thoughts in guided commentary is reflection of true heart conversation with Divine, the soul bows down with gratitude to Almighty, states the higher union, as stated in the Brahma Kumaris' literature.

3) Concentration- The thoughts lead to experience. In the Murli this stage is defined as "Lagan" which means lovingly sharing our feeling with God. Concentration is possible when we share honestly our feelings with God. "The mind is slowing down, and working in one direction, towards the being of truth that we call God...sit in the meditation and instantly fly into the happiness of this experience, without intervening steps. In this luminous relationship, we come closer to God. We transform our feeling of 'God Almighty up there" and we, the sinner, down here" We feel "God loving" instead of "God fearing". In a flight of spiritual thoughts and the deeper experience of God, love gently flow in, 'distractions have no hold and the connection with the Divine remains uninterrupted.

The treasure of thought is very powerful.....whatever stage you wish to adopt whether it is elevated, whether it is of happiness, or of waste or weakness, with the one second's thought "I am an elevated soul", you will have an elevated stage and an elevated experience the moment you have the thought, I am a weak soul, "I do not have any power", then with a thought of just one second, your happiness disappears.

You will experience signs of distress in your stage. However, the basis of both these stages in your thoughts when you sit in remembrance, you create your stage on the basis of your thoughts. "I am a point". How did you create this stage? With your thoughts: "I am an angel" So how powerful thoughts are! But what is the result when you waste your treasure of thoughts? You are not able to create the stage that you want. And all of you know that waste thoughts weaken your intellect and your stage

4) Realization and Anubhuti-Realization means "Anubhuti" an advanced stage of perfection leads to the final stage of realization in which we are fully absorbed in Godly bliss. This is the beginning of the fourth stage, that of realization of truth. Each one's capacity and ability to experience this stage is unique, and it happens in different ways for different individuals. Realisation or Anubhuti is the highest form of spiritual consciousness. It is state of being completely aware of the self and the God as the Supreme Soul. The expression of an experience is difficult to express in words. These are the moments of divine gift, when experience reaches to super consciousness; God's qualities are our qualities.

Murli supported the vision of God for the establishment of a Pure, Peaceful and Prosperous world, following Purity in mansa (mind), vachha (words) and karmana (actions). In order to uplift the human soul from the elongated darkness of the vices, pure vision (dr'isti) and pure attitude (vritti) and pure actions (kriti) is the vital remedy to the degenerating values. When mind is established in the Braluua, as the word Brahmacharya connotes and therefore, acharya means acharan (behaviour) of human soul will take pleasure in spiritual love towards others with feeling of brotherhood. It becomes more elevated as it is beyond the physical affections. It generates more mental and physical stamina, moral force and spiritual strength. It enhances our willpower, Creates clarity of judgment, efficiency and equipoise.

The presented research intends to examine various values of Raj Yoga meditation and novelties of value provisioning through BKRM, which significantly motivates people to consider Raja Yoga at Brahma Kumaris. It is important to understand and realize various types of values and their respective significances to make successful human life. Some of significant and key values of Raj Yoga meditation are discussed are Peace, Love, respect, cooperation , humility, purity, truth and non violence.The

resultant values emerging from the core values are, *Happiness, Responsibility, Freedom, Simplicity, Tolerance and Unity*

Meditation is both the journey and the destination, revealing the secrets of consciousness and the treasures of the soul. It develops the power to be more alert and to be effective in our interaction with each other and with our precious world. But perhaps the greatest gift that comes with meditation is the glow of inner peace that is both gentle and strong.

The practice of Raja Yoga meditation or intellectual communion with God brings into the soul many powers. Of these, eight are very important

Some of the predominant benefits retrieved by means of the power of Raja Yoga meditation are enhances energy, strength, vigor and fitness, helps keep blood pressure normal, amazing stress buster, creates a state of deep relaxation and general feeling of wellbeing, increases concentration and strengthens the mind, reduces heart disease, helps with weight loss, builds self confidence, reduces anxiety attacks as it lowers the levels of blood lactate, helps cure addictions, it produces contentment, it reduces negativity and waste, it frees the mind of bias, prejudice & hatred, it enhances mental concentration, it improves decision making powers, it improves efficiency and strengthens the will power, it promotes innovation and intuition.

Motivation is a theoretical construct used to explain behavior. It represents the reasons for people's actions, desires, and needs. Motivation can also be defined as one's direction to behavior, or what causes a person to want to repeat a behavior and vice versa. A motive is what prompts the person to act in a certain way, or at least develop an inclination for specific behavior. Motivation is literally the desire to do things. It's the difference between waking up before dawn to pound the pavement and lazing around the house all day. It's the crucial element in setting and attaining goals and research shows you can influence your own levels of motivation and self-control.

Motivation can be categorized in to some categories. Based on how motivation comes from, it can be divided into two categories. They are intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation rises from individual inside but extrinsic motivation come from outside of individual.

Motivation has a direct impact on how an individual learns. The affects of motivation is normally far reaching because it increases an individual's energy level, determines the persistence in reaching a specific goal, affects the types of learning techniques used and an individual's thinking processes.

According to human development professionals, there are two types of motivation, extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic is determined by the individual's outside surrounding and specific tasks. Intrinsic motivation can be found within the individual since the task can be viewed as valuable. Therefore, when applying the affect that motivation has on the learning process, it is clear that people learn better based on the perceived value of the task, subject matter, personal goals, financial incentives and wide array of different factors.

Motivation can be increased or decreased based on many different factors. This is one of the reasons why instructors in any educational institution can have a substantial impact on their students learning, since they are a part of the student's intrinsic motivation environment.

Motivation factors for learning meditation in particular includes a)Meditation can help focus your mind and renew your enthusiasm, b) Meditation naturally reforms negative thinking. c)Meditation eliminates anxiety, depression, and addiction. d) Meditation gives you a new identity. e) Meditation reconnects you to higher levels of emotion.

Transformation of the universe from Iron age to Golden age is the top most event in the history of humanity which is going to happened and cannot found in fairy tales. For the forth coming Golden age, Nikola Tesla's science of infinity and Eternal will be the reality and once again there will be the confluence of science and spirituality.

The human soul wants experience. 'The clarion call of the time is experience. Since time immemorial history shows knowledge and practice enforce an enrichment of the experience of life. Today science has various tools to measure physical and external experiments. But science still is unable to measure spiritual experiences. The subject of spirituality and soul is so subtle and vast that it is even difficult to explain in words. As soul is non-physical and the physical body senses are limited in their skill to

express spiritual taste. The beauty of these experiences is that physical eyes cannot see “Divine Light”. It can be seen only through the “Divine Eye” the Soul. Since childhood the researcher herself has experienced ‘Divine Light’, during meditation, which filled her with a deep experience of inner joy and peace. She observed changes in the lives of many people as well as her own deep spiritual experiences which inspired her to present those new dimensions of implementation of spirituality and values.

Where as most other universities enable a person to attain a Master's Degree in one of the arts or science, the BK Vishwa- Vidyalaya enables him to be the master of his own thoughts, desires, emotions and sense-organs. This BK Vishwa-Vidyalaya does not impart education in all those subjects which are being taught in other Universities, for that would just be the duplication or the overlapping of efforts. “The thrust of knowledge imparted.....is first to make man, in ‘reality, a man and to enable him to have practical wisdom and to learn lessons for constant peace and happiness and for excellence in life”.

The science of Raja Yoga is not ordinary, in the sense that it is rather deep and that it relates to true facts. The Brahma Kumaris meditation practice also emphasizes “Rajayoga” as a science in that is the science of silence, inner reflections, and inner discovery.

We are observing a gulf of difference between the past and the present system of education. The Brahma Kumaris has been playing a strong leading role in the restoration of spirituality and human values. Through new dimensions of implementation of universal human values through spirituality, the Brahma Kumaris are filling the missing link of education. According to Swami Vivekananda the education of literature is the manifestation of the perfection of the spirituality already existing in the human being. The challenge lies in the fact that the level and quality of spirituality and values in our society is not improving as required by the need of the hour. It is therefore important to explore and gain access to more effective methods for the development of values and spirituality in our life. The Brahma Kumaris believe that when values are cultivated together with spirituality and practice of meditation is integrated into the process, then implementation becomes successful.

This is the matter of fact that today we are facing the challenging crisis in implementation of values and spirituality into almost every field of society. At

present, youth are greatly influenced by western culture and media and usually ignore ancient ethics and values. Thus the implementation of spirituality and values is not an easy task in the present scenario. These challenges can be cultural, religious, historical, intellectual, personal, professional and educational disorders.

The dark clouds of international terrorism, religious obscurantism and cultural irredentism are turning ominous and have threatened to rupture our social and culture life. It will indeed need a Herculean effort of global statespersons to save Mother Earth from these scourges of civilization. However, in the midst of these challenges people tend to find fault with religious beliefs and cultural systems which are foolhardy and also fraught with inherent danger. The role of religion in human life can never be undetermined as religious beliefs help human beings in overcoming the trials and tribulations of life- There are so many breaking points in life that one is forced to look for solace, spiritual synoptic relief and more often than not, this is provided by religion. The history of religion is not overburdened with crusades and crucifixion; rather it has its fair share of reform, revolt and renaissance. Jesus preaching of universal love, Buddha's emphasis on compassion, Mohammad's conceptualization of a land of peace and the How of devotion and self—realization in Vedas and Upanishads are universal treasures.

There are separation tendencies today at work from all over the world. The family is splitting up, the institutions are breaking up and even nation—states have a tendency to break up into various smaller states based on ethnic, linguistic or other differences. 'I here are divisionistic trends almost everywhere and there are organized groups which indulge in violent and secessionist acts for having a separate homeland. Every religion also has become divided into many sects. The tree of religions has grown to its full mature state, with many branches, sub-branches, twigs and leaves. Not a single religion exists today which has not been split up into sects and sub-sects. These fragmentary tendencies are based on dissension hatred, enmity, intolerance, lack of understanding, lack of adjustment a lack of co-operation.

5.3 CONCLUSION:

This is the matter of fact that almighty god has provided life to each human being to lead a pleasing, harmonious, peaceful life and spend the facilitated life span by encouraging each other to have better and better life. On contrary, in present day scenario, where the day begins with certain global news of terror, grief and crime the universal realization of godly wishes seems getting blurred. To sustain that almighty wishes and motive to create human, there are some holy spirit across the human civilization which intend to streamline human social and behavioural inclination towards a peaceful and soulful life enriched with true godly knowledge and harmonious intension. There are numerous organizations that are making effort and dedicating supernatural power provided by almighty god to achieve these objectives and Brahma Kumaris International spiritual organization is one of them. On the other hand, exploring the past and Vedas, it can be found that there were certain practices that sustained this world unified, pleasing, peaceful and internally as well as externally prosperous, and no doubt Yoga was one of those practices and blessings for the present day human society that encompasses the ray of home towards better human civilization. In this thesis, these key aspects have been explored and respective motivational factors have been examined. More precisely stating, in this thesis the Raj Yoga meditation and its advantages for human society has been explored and respective motivational factors have been assessed. These motivational factors have been assed whether they really have impact on encouraging people to join Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation (BKRM) practices.

Introducing Brahma Kumaris, it can be briefed that being an international spiritual oriented institution, the prime core of Brahma Kumaris is to spread the real godly knowledge and practices to get connected and receive spiritual power from the almighty god. In fact, Brahma Kumaris intends to motivate people to perform holy and selfless practices, Yoga and Asaanas, and various other society oriented divine efforts to enable people realizing supernatural power and peaceful and productive life to attain eventual human goal defined by almighty god. The life at Brahma Kumaris can be characterized by the practice of a style of spirit-possession that has always been more deeply indebted to practices among the royal elite for communing with sovereign temple deities in their territory than with the more spontaneous rural

practices that give voice to the underclass or abject. Moreover, the Brahma Kumaris insist that the God whom they channel is the same God whom all other religions worship throughout the world. This kind of universalistic claim is not uncommon among Hindu sects, but the Brahma Kumaris are unusual insofar as they firmly reject polytheism, henotheism, pantheism, and all other understandings of God worldwide, insisting instead on a strong form of monotheism wherein only one God has ever existed.

The inhibition of worldly thoughts and the recollection or recapitulation of thoughts of the luminous self is attained by directing the flow of thoughts towards god i.e. the supreme soul in his supreme abode or Paramdham which is the world of divine light. In this sense, this meditation is withdrawal or reversal of one's consciousness, from the body and its world to the soul and its silent world, or from the dark lanes of negative thoughts on the bright path of contemplation on god. Raj-Yoga meditation may therefore, be defined as a disciplined exercise of awareness, utilizing such processes as creatively thinking, intuitively perceiving and silently reflecting and concentrating on the metaphysical truths of self and god which lead to comprehension and realization of the subject. This practice involves the turning of one's mind and the flow of his love in the direction of god, giving him the hot-link to communicate with him.

Raj yoga Meditation is the way for realization of the real identity of the self and for experiencing it. It helps a person to know the truth about the real nature of mind or the self. Raj Yoga enables a person to withdraw from the thoughts of the body and the material world for a while. The philosophy of Raj yoga enables the participant to focus the mind on the metaphysical self and link itself lovefully to the supreme soul who is light, bliss, peace, love and might personified in the form of a brilliant and radiant point. Raj Yoga meditation is refreshing, energizing, relaxing, reassuring and reawakening. Raj Yoga makes the soul increasingly aware of its divine origin, divine destiny and divine peaceful real nature. Raj Yoga possesses numerous social significances that helps in developing spiritual approach towards others and created an attitude of Universal Brotherhood in the aspirant of Yoga.

Brahma Kumaris (BK) organization has been leading and providing spiritual training and accommodation across the world since a long time and day by day its universal acceptability has been increasing exponentially. The predominant reason of such expansion and acceptance is the holy practices such as Raj Yoga meditation and numerous peaceful community oriented initiatives. In such circumstances, it becomes inevitable to assess those motivational factors which encourage people to join BK.

In this thesis, with the motivation and intension to explore various motivational factors which encourages people to join Brahma Kumaris International headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan (India), an empirical study and analysis has been done. The proposed research has intended to explore and analysis empirically and analytically the key motivational factors and constructs which do influences people to join BKRM. In this thesis, primarily four hypotheses reflecting demographic constructs to have impact on motivating people to join BKRM, the thrust towards true spiritual means of life as motivation to join BKRM and becoming Rajyogis, the psychological, physiological and spiritual constructs as motivational factors to join BKRM and novel life culture, environment and holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World's spiritual centre at Mount Abu as the motivational factors, have been examined though an empirical study and analytical analysis paradigm.

Considering present study, it can be found that the majority of devotees at BKRM are male. It can be easily inferred here that the changing socio-cultural conditions, stress level and physical-mental stresses in profession as well as in socio-personal life has played significant role in motivating people to join Raj Yoga meditation. On the other hand, the statistical outcomes state that majority of the devotees are unmarried, which significantly indicates the personal thrust towards godly knowledge, spiritual power and affinity. No doubt, in certain narrowed perception the majority of unmarried people at BK indicates the optimal spiritual environment where an individual prefer serving society and its well being by godly knowledge, motivation and peace of mind, which are the key ingredients to keep society connected and peaceful.

This research has revealed that affinity towards spiritual powers, godly knowledge, peace of mind and harmony, balanced and stress free life, punctual and value based or enriched (Sanskritic) life style, and inner success attainment motivates people to go

for Raj Yoga meditation. Considering demographic constructs such as age, crisply state that as age increases human intends to get better way of life, which can make and enable it to be away from worldly beings and self-centric practices. With an effort to explore the need of a self-less, devoted life and peaceful living culture etc motivate people to incline towards BKRM. In some other way, the increase in stress level, physical troubles and associated mental instability too motivate people to join BKRM.

In present day situations, numerous internal as well as external battles are being imposed by the name of religion and associated practices and principles. These facts indicate that there can be direct relationship between religion and respective preferences towards certain organization, whether it is for novel causes. To explore this fact, this thesis has investigated the religion based analysis, and it was observed that being an international spiritual organization with the motive to maintain and promote harmony and peace, it has been found that the highest count of Hindus at BK practicing holy BKRM, prefers peace and harmony across human civilization. The dedication towards a peaceful and soulful life indicates their motive to motivate people to attain supernatural power and godly knowledge rather fighting for worldly beings and mortal short-term advantages. In addition, there are numerous demographic variables such as ambience and spiritual environment, holy practices etc which do have great significance on encouraging people to join BKRM at BK headquarter, Mount Abu, Rajasthan.

The empirical study and analytical outcomes reveal that the spiritual practices, ambience, relationship between Raja yogameditation at Brahma Kumaris (BKRM) and godly relationship or personal thrust to devote towards supernatural power motivate people to join the Raj Yoga meditation at BK HQ, Mount Abu. The research also unearthed that the devotion towards serving society through mind, willingness to observe godly relationship with supernatural power do have impact on encouraging people to follow Raj Yoga at BK. In addition, the factors like soul and god consciousness, love, peace, bliss, self transformation, vice less and ego less stage positive attitude, self control and personality building, and zeal towards getting divine virtues and power etc motivate people to follow Raj Yoga meditation. This research has also revealed that practicing BKRM can imbibe and enrich positive attitudes,

positive thoughts, time managements, self-confidence, communication skills etc, which can be of great significance to enable better life style and eventual attainment.

In existing literatures, researchers have found that Raj Yoga meditation can be significant for alleviating psychological disorders, mental stress and physical illness. With the enthuse to explore these factors, in this thesis, these constructs have been explored and it has been found that BKRM can be of great significance for curing various psychological issues like neurotic illness and numerous diseases such as hypertension, Insomnia, depression etc. Furthermore, it has been found that BKRM helps for dealing with various mental, physiological and psychological problems such as tension, nervousness, fear and other negativities. These all factors motivate people to join Raj Yoga at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India.

Considering the key constructs such as living style, spiritual environment, alignment towards peace and socio-mental attainment, spiritual practices motivate people to practice Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris. This thesis revealed that the novel culture, spiritual practices such as Murli and Amritwela, spiritual environment motivate people to join Raj Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu. In addition, there are numerous activities such as research, health care research and development, lectures, training practices, conferences which motivates people to get associated with BKRM and practice Raj Yoga meditation. The personal investigative and explorative research efforts have revealed that the people at Mount Abu are completely dedicated and serving mankind without any discrimination all the 365 days a year. Such dedication affirms a strong bond between people and practices, environment and spiritual affinity at BK head quarter Mount Abu. Thus, observing overall responses and respective significances, it can be affirmed that the novel life culture, environment and holy practices at Brahma Kumaris World's spiritual centre (International headquarter) at Mount Abu, Rajasthan motivates people to get associated with it.

If the location of all the old civilization across the world like Egyptian, Easter Islands, Mayan etc, joined by a lay line on the earth, then Mount Abu which is in the Arravali Hills in Rajasthan, India comes on the same lay line. The latitude and longitude of Mount Abu are 240N and 720E. With reference to the earth,

Mount abu in India is the centre point of Earth. At this Mount Abu- center point of Earth , “THE ALMIGHTY AUTHORITY- GOD FATHER SHIVA- SUPREME FATHER OF ALL SOULS INCARNATES” at this place and teaching the real spiritual knowledge and ancient Indian Raja yoga meditation for which people are motivating to learn this highest spiritual education and through HIM the present Iron aged world will be transformed into heaven.

On one side humanity is searching for GOD in temples, mosques, churches and Gurudwars at the same time scientists are doing deep research to reveal the secrets of this wonderful universe and on another side, ALMIGHTY GOD- the supreme father, teacher and Satguru, has manifested Himself in the beautiful nature of arravali hills at the International HQ of Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu in Rajasthan India who is the true and key motivational factor and spiritual source for all people .“THE ARTIST OF THE UNIVERSE, PAINTING THE GOLDEN REALITY WHICH WILL BE KNOWN TO THE ENTIRE WORLD IN THE NEAR FUTURE”.

Thus, taking into consideration of the above mentioned factors and their respective significances, it can be found that demography factors play very significant role in motivating people to adopt Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumari and, thrust towards the search for true spiritual means of life motivates people to become Rajyogis with Brahma Kumaris. In addition, psychological, physiological and spiritual factors also encourages people to follow BCRM. Furthermore, the novel life culture, environment and holy practices at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu does have significant impact on motivating people to join Brahma Kumaris International headquarters at Mount Abu, Rajasthan, India to learn Raja Yoga Meditation.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION

There is a need for restoration and reformation of the human values through literature and by other important means of education. Unless there is reorientation in our scientific study, literature and education by giving equal emphasis on spiritual growth and it's by products of human values, there is little hope for humanity to survive progress without values. There is lot of suffering in the world and all people must make united and conerted efforts to change things for the better. No one can compel

other to become a better person but each one can ‘certainly’ make sincere efforts to change the self so that each one individually becomes better. Personal awakening and transformation can be a source of inspiration for others to change. The method for making the world a better place is to bring change in attitudes and to adopt moral, social and spiritual values because much of the agony is due to lack of these. Taking into consideration of the various aspects of Raj Yoga meditation and key features of Brahma Kumaris, it can be found that Brahma Kumari’s Raj Yoga meditation can be of vital significance for people to achieve eventual objectives of human life. Considering recent development and devastative efforts being made across world, the consideration and promotion of Raj Yoga meditation can be helpful to alleviate major negative constructs and vices. Considering effectiveness of the Raj Yoga meditation, it can be recommended to be performed across global societies so as to imbibe positive attitudes, peaceful environment, harmony, self and god consciousness and real godly knowledge retrieval. Furthermore, it can be effective for people belonging from different professional as well as socio-economical background to attain positive energy and spirit to do constructive acts while ensuring peaceful and constructive society. The high pace rise in crime across the world has forced positive thinkers to introduce certain positive practices so as to maintain peaceful and harmonious global society as a village, and in order to attain these objectives motivating youths or society members towards positive though and attitude is of great significance. In order to meet these requirements, Raj Yoga meditation can be of great significance.

This is the matter of fact that Raj Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris has enabled people to accomplish ultimate spiritual power to achieve positive attitudes, mental, physiological and psychological stability and positivity and therefore its practices should be promoted across globe and should be integrated with the various public or private establishments and institutions to motivate people towards BKRM. Strengthening the fabric of religious belief and respective practices and further integrating Raj Yoga with daily life can be a revolution towards making the world peaceful and prosperous in terms of godly blessings, harmonious life, self containment and real godly knowledge achievements.

5.5 FUTURE SCOPE OF RESEARCH

This quantitative/ analytical research focuses on responses retrieved from BKRM practitioners to explore various factors that motivate people to learn Raja Yoga at BKs International world headquarters situated at Mount Abu, Rajasthan area. **research could be further expanded to broader horizon.**

The research performed with sample size of 500 respondents at BK International HQ, Rajasthan, Mount Abu. The sample size & geographical area of research **might be increased to get better research depth analysis.**

This research work considers case study of motivational factors for Raja Yoga meditation of Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university at International HQ, Rajasthan, Mount abu. **Hence, there is future scope to study motivational factors of other meditation practices & techniques.**

5.6 RESEARCH LIMITATION & DELIMITATION

This research work considers case study of motivational factors for **Raja Yoga meditation of Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university at International HQ, Rajasthan, Mount abu** & research **doesn't consider Raja Yoga meditation practices & techniques of other organizations/ Institutions in India** such as “Art of Living” by Shri Ravisankar, “Patanjali Ashram” by Yoga Guru Ramdev, Sahaj Marg Rajayoga meditation by Saint Patanjali etc.

Apart from Raja yoga meditation techniques, lot many other meditation techniques were taught by different institutions across India. This research work is focused only on **Raja Yoga meditation of Brahma Kumaris world spiritual university at International HQ, Rajasthan, Mount abu** & doesn't consider any other types of meditation practices & techniques.

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1) Annamalai University,DDE, Tamilnadu in Technical Collaboration with Brahma Kumaris Education Wing, RE & RF, Mount abu, Rajasthan, **Master Of Business Administration (Self Management & Crisis management) course,**

First Year(2011-12)

- 1.1 Principles Of management
- 1.2 Organizational Behavior
- 1.3 Managing Self
- 1.4 Values to managerial performance
- 1.5 Healthy lifestyle for managers
- 1.6 Synthesis of spirituality &

Second Year (2012-13)

- 2.1 Human resource management
- 2.2 Self managing leadership
- 2.3 Spirituality for managerial excellence

2) Annamalai University,DDE, Tamilnadu in Technical Collaboration with Brahma Kumaris Education Wing, RE & RF, Mount abu, Rajasthan, with support of Janaki Foundation for Global Health Care, UK, **Post Graduate Diploma in Values in Health Care course,**

Year (2014-15)

- Paper 1 :-New Dimension in Health care
- Paper-2 :- Values in Health Care
- Paper 3:-Spirituality in Health care

ANNEXURE-1

RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

RESEARCH TOPIC

**A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS
TO LEARN RAJAYOGA MEDITATION
AT BRAHMA KUMARIS
INTERNATIONAL HEAD QUARTERS
MOUNT ABU, RAJASTHAN**

A RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

SUBMITTED TO

SHRI JAGDISHPRASAD JHABARMAL TIBREWALA UNIVERSITY

**FOR THE DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
IN
MANAGEMENT**

By

**RESEARCH SCHOLAR NAME : NAGESH.N.V.
REGISTRATION NO : 211214079
UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF Dr.A.SACHINDRA BABU**

**SHRI JAGDISHPRASAD JHABARMAL TIBREWALA UNIVERSITY
VIDYANAGARI, JHUNJUNU, RAJASTHAN-333001**

2015

Research Questionnaire

A number of researches have proved that Rajayoga meditation can be of great significance for enhancing mental, psychological, physiological as well as spiritual strength of human being. In recent years, a number of people have attracted towards Rajayoga practices at Brahma Kumaris organization. In this world, where individual often makes efforts to achieve more worldly beings and prosperity, the adoption of Raj Yoga for long run and dedicating towards Brahma Kumaris is an interesting research domain to be explored about.

The study of various motivational factors that put enthuse among people to adopt Raj Yoga, can help both the individual willing to join Raj Yoga at meditation at Brahma Kumaris as well as the organizational management to attract more and more followers of Raj Yoga meditation. Thus, taking into consideration of such significances, here in this research work an empirical analysis has been proposed that intends to analyze various motivational factors that motivate people to join Rajayoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris International headquarters. This research questionnaires intends to explore precise information about the various motivational factors of Rajayoga meditation of Brahma Kumaris at Mount Abu, Rajasthan.

This questionnaire will have 5 sections i.e A, B, C, D and E. This questionnaire is designed to capture demographic details of Raja yogis in sections A, Spiritual Lifestyle Enhancement using BKRM in section B, Psychological, Physical, Mental and Spiritual benefits of Rajayoga Meditation in section C, Positive Influence Factors on Motivation to Learn BKRM at Mount Abu questions in section D and benefits of Raja yoga Meditation in section E.

The aim is also to offer you an opportunity for Self Reflection in a simple manner. It is comprehensive and yet not time consuming.

The Questions in the sections B, C, D and E has 5 options ie Strongly Agree(5), Agree(4), Neutral(3), Disagree(2) and Strongly disagree(1). You are requested to put tick mark β on only one box in each question and requested to answer all the questions. It is requested to submit the data accurately and only once. The Data collected will be used for Statistical Study and purely for Research purpose. Your information details will remain confidential and will not be used for any other purpose other than for the Research.

We appreciate your honesty and accuracy and for devoting your valuable time to fill the questionnaire. Here we declare that all the personal information of respondents in this primary response collection process would be preserved and would not be revealed out for any other purposes.

If you have queries you may please correspond any time to email ID : nag8108@gmail.com

Supervisor

Researcher

- A-9) Kindly mention your monthly Income (Before coming to Mount Abu)- Rupees
कृपया अपने मासिक आय का उल्लेख करें (माउंट आबू में आने से पहले) (रुपय में)
1. Below 10,000/- 2. 10,000 to 30,000/-
3. 30,000 to 50,000/- 4. 50,000 to 70,000/-
5. Above 70,000/-
- A-10) Please mention that you get any Monthly salary/ other financial benefits at Mount Abu
आपको किसी तरह के मासिक वेतन मिलाता है
1. Yes/हाँ 2. No/नहीं
- A-11) Kindly mention that how you came to know about BK Raja yoga Meditation
बीके राजा योग ध्यान के बारे में आप को पता कैसे चला- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Family members/ Friends 2. BK people
परिवार के सदस्यों/ दोस्त बीके लोग
3. TV/ Radio/ Print Media 4. Banner/ poster/ Sign Boards
टीवी/ रेडियो/ प्रिंट मीडिया बैनर/ पोस्टर/ साइनबोर्ड
5. Dream/ Vision 6. Seminar/ conference/ Lectures
सपना/ विजन सेमिनार/ सम्मेलन/ व्याख्यान
7. Exhibitions 8. Other sources
प्रदर्शनियाँ अन्य स्रोत
- A-12) Please mention that, since how long you are learning BK Raja yoga Meditation
(In Gyan)
कितना समय से आप बीके राजा योग ध्यान सीख रहे हैं (ज्ञान में)- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Below 5 years 2. 5-15 years 3. 15-25 years
5 साल से कम 5-15 साल 15-25 साल
4. 25-35 years 5. Above 35 years
25-35 साल 35 वर्ष से ऊपर
- A-13) Kindly mention that You are a permanent member at BK HQ: Mount Abu
बीके मुख्यालय माउंट आबू में एक स्थायी सदस्य हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes/हाँ 2. No/नहीं
- A-14) Kindly mention that, since how long you are residing at BK HQ: Mount Abu
कब से आप बीके मुख्यालय माउंट आबू में रह रहे हैं:- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Below 2 years 2. 2-10 years 3. 10-20 years
2 वर्ष से कम 2-10 वर्ष 10-20 वर्षों
4. 20-30 years 5. Above 30 years
20-30 वर्ष 30 वर्ष से ऊपर

A-15) Please mention Substance usage History

मादक द्रव्यों के उपयोग के इतिहास- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. Alcohol consumption(daily/rarely) ☐ | 2. Smoking (daily/rarely) ☐ |
| शराब की खापत (दैनिक / शायद ही कभी) | धूम्रपान (दैनिक / शायद ही कभी) |
| 3. Drugs (daily/rarely) ☐ | 4. Pan masala (daily/rarely) ☐ |
| ड्रग्स (दैनिक / शायद ही कभी) | पान मसाला (दैनिक / शायद ही कभी) |
| 5. No addiction ☐ | |
| कोई लत नहीं | |

A-16) Kindly mention about your physical health

आपके शारीरिक स्वास्थ्य के बारे में कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. Low/ High Blood pressure ☐ | 2. Diabetes ☐ |
| कम / उच्च रक्तचाप | मधुमेह |
| 3. Asthma ☐ | 4. Arthritis ☐ |
| दमा | गठिया |
| 5. Cancer ☐ | 6. Heart diseases ☐ |
| कैंसर | हृदय रोग |
| 7. other serious illness ☐ | 8. Good physical health ☐ |
| अन्य गंभीर बीमारी | अच्छा शारीरिक स्वास्थ्य |

A-17) Kindly mention about your Mental health

अपने मानसिक स्वास्थ्य के बारे में कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. Anger ☐ | 2. Anxiety & Depression ☐ |
| क्रोध | चिंता और अवसाद |
| 3. Feeling of Insult ☐ | 4. Change of mood frequently ☐ |
| अपमान की भावना | मनःस्थिति में बारंबार परिवर्तन |
| 5. Fear ☐ | 6. Tension ☐ |
| डर | तनाव |
| 7. Other serious illness ☐ | 8. Good Mental health ☐ |
| अन्य गंभीर बीमारी | अच्छी मानसिक स्वास्थ्य |

A-18) Please mention that you have any other source of Monthly income at MountAbu

माउंट आबू में मासिक आय का कोई अन्य स्रोत है कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 1. Yes/हाँ ☐ | 2. No/नहीं ☐ |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|

A-19) Kindly mention about your Stress levels

अपने तनाव के स्तर के बारे में कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

- | | | |
|---------------------------------------|--------------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| 1. Very high ☐ | 2. High ☐ | 3. Moderate ☐ |
| बहुत ऊँचा | उच्च | मध्यम |
| 4. Low ☐ | 5. Very low ☐ | 6. No stress ☐ |
| कम | बहुत कम | कोई तनाव नहीं है |

A-20) Kindly mention how many hours daily you practice Raja yoga Meditation

आप दैनिक राजा योग ध्यान के अभ्यास कितने घंटे करते हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Less than 2 Hrs 2. 2-4 Hours 3. 4-6 hours
2 घंटे से कम 2-4 घंटे 4-6 घंटे
4. 6-8 Hours 5. More than 8 hours
6-8 घंटे 8 घंटे से अधिक

A-21) Kindly mention how many hours daily you do service

कितने घंटे दैनिक आप सेवा करते हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Less than 2 Hrs 2. 2-6 Hours 3. 6-10 hours
2 घंटे से कम 2-6 घंटे 6-10 घंटे
4. 10-14 Hours 5. More than 14 hours
10-14 घंटे 14 घंटे से अधिक

A-22) Kindly mention how many hours you sleep daily

कितने घंटे दैनिक आप नींद करते हैं कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Less than 2 Hrs 2. 2-4 Hours 3. 4-6 hours
2 घंटे से कम 2-4 घंटे 4-6 घंटे
4. 6-8 Hours 5. More than 8 hours
6-8 घंटे 8 घंटे से अधिक

A-23) Kindly mention the quality of sleep

नींद की गुणवत्ता का कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Excellent 2. Good
उत्कृष्ट अच्छा
3. Average 4. Fair 5. Poor
साधारण मध्यम खराब

A-24) Please mention the dress colour you wear in Mount Abu

आप माउंट आबू में पहनने के पेशाक रंग का कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. white 2. Saffron
सफेद केसर
3. Red 4. Yellow 5. Other colour
लाल पीला अन्य रंग

A-25) Please mention that you attend Amritvela(4am -4.45am) Raja yoga Meditation daily

आप प्रतिदिन (4am -4.45am) अमृतवेला राजयोग मेडिटेशन में भाग लेते हैं कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Yes/हाँ 2. No/नहीं

- A-26) Please mention that you attend Murali class(7 am to 8 am) daily in groups in Class halls
आप प्रतिदिन(7 am to 8 am) मुरली क्लास हॉल में समूहों में भाग लेते हैं/कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes / हाँ 2. No/ नहीं
- A-27) Please mention that you practice Traffic control meditation daily
आप प्रतिदिन ट्रैफिक कंट्रोल ध्यान का अभ्यास करते हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes / हाँ 2. No/ नहीं
- A-28) Kindly mention the experiences in Raja yoga Meditation
राजा योग ध्यान में अनुभव का उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Seed stage 2. Angelic stage
बीज अवस्था फरिश्ता अवस्था
3. Churning stage 4. Chit chat stage 5. All the stages
मंथन अवस्था रुह रिहान अवस्था सभी अवस्था
- A-29) Please mention that you Churn the Godly Knowledge daily for self progress
स्वयं की प्रगति के लिए प्रतिदिन पञ्चात्मा ज्ञान मंथन करते हैं कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes / हाँ 2. No/ नहीं
- A-30) Please mention that you daily Serve the world through mind and powerful vibrations
आप प्रतिदिन मन और शक्तिशाली प्रकंपन के माध्यम से दुनिया की सेवा करते हैं कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes / हाँ 2. No/ नहीं
- A-31) Please mention that you keep Chart of Yoga & service daily for self growth.
आप स्वयं के विकास के लिए प्रतिदिन योग और सेवा का चार्ट रकते हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Yes / हाँ 2. No/ नहीं
- A-32) Please mention that you attend training ,lectures, seminars and conferences of BKRM
आप BKRM के प्रशिक्षण, व्याख्यान, सेमिनार और सम्मेलनों में भाग लेते हैं - कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Once in a Month 2. Once in 6 month
महीने में एक बार 6 महीने में एक बार
3. Once in a year 4. Once in 5 years 5. Do not attend
साल में एक बार 5 साल में एक बार शामिल नहीं है
- A-33) Please mention that how frequently you visit your native birth place/ state
किरन्ती बार आप अपनी मूल जन्म स्थान/ राज्य का दौरा करते हैं - कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये
1. Once in a 6 Months 2. Once in a year 3. Once in 2 years
6 महीने में एक बार साल में एक बार 2 साल में एक बार
4. Once in 5 years 5. Once in 10 years 6. Do not visit
5 साल में एक बार 10 साल में एक बार यात्रा नहीं करते

A-34) Kindly mention that you see Cinema

आप सिनेमा देखते हैं - कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Yes / हाँ

2. No / नहीं

A-35) Kindly mention that you use mobile, internet & social media for service

आप मोबाइल, इंटरनेट और सामाजिक मीडिया का उपयोग करते हैं कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Yes / हाँ

2. No / नहीं

A-36) Kindly mention that you take vegetarian food prepared with onion and garlic

आप प्याज और लहसुन के साथ तैयार शाकाहारी भोजन लेते हैं- कृपया उल्लेख कीजिये

1. Yes / हाँ

2. No / नहीं

SECTION B - SPIRITUAL LIFESTYLE ENHANCEMENT USING BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJAYOGA MEDITATION(BKRM)

भाग B-BKRM का उपयोग से आध्यात्मिक जीवन शैली संवर्धन

5	4	3	2	1
Strongly Agree टढ़ापूर्वक सहमत	Agree सहमत	Neutral तटस्थ	Disagree असहमत	Strongly Disagree टढ़ापूर्वक असहमत

	5	4	3	2	1
B-1) Attention to Murali& Imbibing Godly Knowledge accurately (Gyan) मुर्ली और सही ढंग से परमात्मा ज्ञान धारण (ज्ञान) की ओर ध्यान हैं	☐				
B-2) Purity in Mind ,speech& Actions मन, वाणी और क्रिया में पवित्रता	☐				
B-3) Inculcation of Divine virtues दिव्य गुणों के धारण	☐				
B-4) Experiencing Powerful stage at Amritvela अमृतवेला पर शक्तिशाली स्थिति का अनुभव	☐				
B-5) Orientation towards satwic food/ pure vegetarianism सात्विक खाना / शुद्ध शाकाहार की ओर अभिविन्यास	☐				
B-6) Enhanced positive thinking सकारात्मक सोच का बढ़ना	☐				
B-7) Increased concentration during meditation & while at work ध्यान एवं काम पर एकाग्रता की वृद्धि	☐				

- B-8) Focused towards Soul consciousness while doing actions.
 काम पर एवं आत्मा अभिमान की ओर ध्यान केंद्रित
 काम पर एवं आत्मा अभिमान की ओर ध्यान केंद्रित
- B-9) Practising Celibacy in all circumstances.
 सभी परिस्थितियों में ब्रह्मचर्य का अभ्यास
 सभी परिस्थितियों में ब्रह्मचर्य का अभ्यास
- B-10) Attending sat sang daily & regularly.
 दैनिक और नियमित रूप से सत्संग में भाग लेना
 दैनिक और नियमित रूप से सत्संग में भाग लेना
- B-11) Orientation towards supreme/ supematural power ie GOD
 सर्वोच्च / अलौकिक शक्ति यानी भगवान की ओर अभिविन्यास
 सर्वोच्च / अलौकिक शक्ति यानी भगवान की ओर अभिविन्यास
- B-12) Develops the art of living
 जीने की कला में विकसित होना
 जीने की कला में विकसित होना
- B-13) Full Satisfaction & Contentment in life
 जीवन में संतोष और पूर्ण संतुष्टि
 जीवन में संतोष और पूर्ण संतुष्टि
- B-14) Complete dedication towards serving mankind
 मानव सेवा के प्रति पूर्ण समर्पण
 मानव सेवा के प्रति पूर्ण समर्पण
- B-15) Attainment of Godly Love & spiritual powers.
 ईश्वरीय प्रेम और आध्यात्मिक शक्तियों की प्राप्ति
 ईश्वरीय प्रेम और आध्यात्मिक शक्तियों की प्राप्ति
- B-16) Increased work efficiency
 कार्य कुशलता की वृद्धि
 कार्य कुशलता की वृद्धि
- B-17) Overall personality development & character building
 समग्र व्यक्तित्व विकास और चरित्र निर्माण
 समग्र व्यक्तित्व विकास और चरित्र निर्माण
- B-18) Proper time & resource management.
 उचित समय और संसाधन प्रबंधन
 उचित समय और संसाधन प्रबंधन
- B-19) Proper management of 6 Ms ie men, machinery, money, materials, method & marketing
 6 Ms के उचित प्रबंधन यानी व्यक्ति, साधन, धन, सामग्री, विधि और मार्केटिंग
 6 Ms के उचित प्रबंधन यानी व्यक्ति, साधन, धन, सामग्री, विधि और मार्केटिंग
- B-20) Attainment of world benefactor stage
 विश्व फरोपकारी अवस्था की प्राप्ति
 विश्व फरोपकारी अवस्था की प्राप्ति
- B-21) Develops the quality of leadership
 नेतृत्व की गुणवत्ता विकसित
 नेतृत्व की गुणवत्ता विकसित
- B-22) Develops the ability to inspire & motivate others.
 दूसरों को प्रेरित करने की क्षमता विकसित करता है
 दूसरों को प्रेरित करने की क्षमता विकसित करता है
- B-23) Develops the ability to plan & set Goals.
 योजना और लक्ष्य निर्धारित करने की क्षमता विकसित करता है
 योजना और लक्ष्य निर्धारित करने की क्षमता विकसित करता है
- B-24) Brings spiritual empowerment in life
 जीवन में आध्यात्मिक सशक्तिकरण लाता है
 जीवन में आध्यात्मिक सशक्तिकरण लाता है
- B-25) Develops the art of Communication & public speech.
 संवाद एवं सार्वजनिक भाषण की कला विकसित करता है।
 संवाद एवं सार्वजनिक भाषण की कला विकसित करता है।

B-26) Develops the art of hearing & listening
सुनवाई एवं सुनने की कला विकसित

SECTION C - PHYSICAL/ MENTAL/SPIRITUAL BENEFITS OF BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJAYOGA MEDITATION(BKRM)

भाग C- BKRM की शारीरिक / मानसिक / आध्यात्मिक लाभ

5	4	3	2	1
Strongly Agree दृढ़तापूर्वक सहमता	Agree सहमता	Neutral तटस्थ	Disagree असहमता	Strongly Disagree दृढ़तापूर्वक असहमता

 5 4 3 2 1

C-1) BKRM plays a major role in physical health optimization
i.e., BP, sugar level, pulse, BMI etc

BKRM शारीरिक स्वास्थ्य अनुकूलन करने में एक प्रमुख भूमिका निभाता है
यानी बीपी, शुगर के स्तर, नाड़ी, बीएमआई आदि

C-2) BKRM is significant in healing of disease like cancer,
arthritis, heart diseases etc

BKRM, कैंसर जैसी बीमारी और गठिया, हृदय रोग आदि के उपचार में
महत्वपूर्ण है

C-3) BKRM is helpful to maintaining good physique/
physical stamina

BKRM अच्छी काया को बनाए रखने / शारीरिक सहनशक्ति के लिए उपयोगी है

C-4) BKRM is helpful in de addiction from substance usage
and affinity

BKRM पदार्थ का उपयोग की लड़ा मुक्ति और आकर्षण में मददगार है

C-5) BKRM is helpful for mental health optimization i.e., anger,
depression, fear, tension, anxiety, guilt, insult, mood swings etc

BKRM मानसिक स्वास्थ्य के अनुकूलन के लिए उपयोगी है अर्थात् क्रोध,
अपसाद, भय, तनाव, चिंता, ग्लानि, अपमान, मिजाज आदि

C-6) BKRM eliminates mental illness such as sleeplessness,
sleep walking, bad dreaming etc

BKRM अनिद्रा, नींद या सपने में चलना-फिरना, बुरा सपना
देखना जैसे मानसिक बीमारी समाप्त करती है |

- C-7) Raja yoga is effective for mental stability and concentration
 राजयोग मानसिक स्थिरता और एकाग्रता के लिए प्रभावी है |
- C-8) BKRM activates & enhances the core values of the SOUL/ Individuals
 BKRM आत्मा/व्यक्तियों के बुनियादी मूल्यों को बढ़ाता है और सक्रिय करता है |
- C-9) Raja yoga detaches individuals from worldly attractions & motivates them towards spiritual learning & experience
 राजयोग सांसारिक आकर्षण से व्यक्तियों को निकाल आध्यात्मिक शिक्षा और अनुभव करने के लिए प्रेरित करता है |
- C-10) Raja yoga facilitates to explore moral & spiritual values and guide towards art of living
 राजयोग नैतिक और आध्यात्मिक मूल्यों का पता लगाना सहज करके, जीने की कला के प्रति मार्गदर्शन करता है |
- C-11) Raja Yoga effectively manages stress through self management technique.
 राजयोग प्रभावी ढंग से आत्म प्रबंधन तकनीक के माध्यम से तनाव प्रबंधन करता है |
- C-12) Raja yoga facilitates to develop mainly 8 inner soul powers.
 राजयोग मुख्य रूप से आत्मा के भीतर की 8 शक्तियों की विकसित करना आसान करता है |

SECTION D - FACTORS HAVING POSITIVE INFLUENCE ON MOTIVATION TO LEARN BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJAYOGA MEDITATION(BKRM) AT BRAHMA KUMARIS INTERNATIONAL H.Q :MOUNT ABU

भाग D- भाग D- बीके अंतर्राष्ट्रीय मुख्यालय माउंट आबू के राजयोग जानने के लिए प्रेरणा पर सकारात्मक प्रभाव होने के कारक

5	4	3	2	1
Strongly Agree दृढ़तापूर्वक सहमत	Agree सहमत	Neutral तटस्थ	Disagree असहमत	Strongly Disagree दृढ़तापूर्वक असहमत

- 5 4 3 2 1
- D-1) BKRM is holy & highest technique taught by GOD himself
 BKRM खुद भगवान द्वारा सिखाया पवित्र और उत्तम तकनीक है |
- D-2) BKRM is an easy method which can be carried out by anybody, anywhere and at any time.
 BKRM जो एक आसान तरीका है कहीं भी और किसी भी समय किसी के द्वारा किया जा सकता है |

- D-3) BKRM is an easy mental process and have no difficulties of physical asanas / postures.
 BKRM एक आसान मानसिक प्रक्रिया है शारीरिक आसन/ मुद्रा की कोई समस्या नहीं है।
- D-4) BKRM is a spiritual science and not a religion & is experimenting with the thoughts about GOD/ Supreme power/ supernatural power
 BKRM एक धर्म नहीं आध्यात्मिक विज्ञान है भगवान/ सर्वोच्च शक्ति / अलौकिक शक्ति के बारे में विचारों के साथ प्रयोग कर रहा है।
- D-5) Regular& punctual study of Murali i.e., Godly Knowledge नियमित रूप से और समय पर मुरली अर्थात ईश्वरीय ज्ञान का अध्ययन।
- D-6) True & holistic knowledge taught free of cost daily सत्य और समग्र ज्ञान प्रतिदिन मुक्त सिखाया जाता है।
- D-7) BKRM is taught to all religious people across the world without any discrimination
 BKRM बिना किसी भेदभाव के दुनिया भर में सभी धर्म के लोगों को सिखाया जाता है।
- D-8) BK HQ Mount Abu is believed to be the GODs incarnation & very sacred place on earth
 वीके मुख्यालय माउंट आबू भगवान के अवतारण स्थान और पृथ्वी पर बहुत पवित्र स्थान माना जाता है।
- D-9) BK International HQ Mount Abu has positive learning environment
 वीके अंतर्राष्ट्रीय मुख्यालय माउंट आबू में सकारात्मक सीखने के माहौल है।
- D-10) BK Mount Abu complexes have better spiritual training and development facility
 वीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में बेहतर आध्यात्मिक प्रशिक्षण और विकास की सुविधा है।
- D-11) BK Mount Abu complexes have world class infrastructure to learn Meditation
 वीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में मेडिटेशन सीखने के लिए विश्व स्तरीय बुनियादी ढांचा है।
- D-12) At Mount Abu, learning of Meditation is made easier under the able guidance & blessings of Dadis, experienced Raja Yogis, tapaswis & saints.
 माउंट आबू में, ध्यान सीखने के कुशल मार्गदर्शन के अंतर्गत आसान कर दिया है और दादियोंअनुभवी राजा योगियों, तपस्वी और संतों के आशीर्वाद है।
- D-13) Mount abu is very pleasant location located in the Arravali hills area.
 माउंट आबू बहुत ही सुखद स्थान Arravali हिल्स इलाके में स्थित है।

- D-14) The environment at Mount abu is free from air pollution, water pollution and noise Pollution
 माउंट आबू के पर्यावरण में वायु प्रदूषण, जल प्रदूषण और शोर से मुक्त है।
- D-15) BK Mount Abu complexes have Asia's biggest and self sufficient Solar plants
 बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में एशिया की सबसे बड़ी और आत्मनिर्भर सौर संयंत्र हैं।
- D-16) Even though BK International HQ Mount Abu is located in a village place but adopted the latest technology for learning and development of spirituality
 भले ही, बीके अंतर्राष्ट्रीय मुख्यालय माउंट आबू के एक गांव में स्थित है, लेकिन शिक्षा व आध्यात्मिकता के विकास के लिए नवीनतम प्रौद्योगिकी अपनाई गई है।
- D-17) Serving the mankind through Mind is made easy at Mount abu.
 मन के माध्यम से मानवता की सेवा माउंट आबू में आसान बना दिया है।
- D-18) The nature of people at Mount abu is Satisfied, Contented & self disciplined.
 माउंट आबू में लोगों की प्रकृति तृप्त, आत्म संतुष्ट और स्वयं अनुशासित है।
- D-19) All the people at BK Mount Abu, study & practice godly knowledge meditation daily & then preach to others.
 बीके माउंट आबू में सभी लोग, प्रतिदिन ईश्वरीय ज्ञान, ध्यान का अध्ययन और अभ्यास खुद कर के और फिर दूसरों को कराते हैं।
- D-20) All the people at BK International HQ Mount Abu compulsorily follow the principle of brahmacharya & take pure satwic vegetarian food daily.
 बीके अंतर्राष्ट्रीय मुख्यालय माउंट आबू में सभी लोग प्रतिदिन ब्रह्मचर्य और शुद्ध satwic शाकाहारी भोजन का सिद्धांत का पालन अनिवार्य रूप से करते हैं।
- D-21) People at Mount abu don't consume non vegetarian food & food prepared by outsiders
 माउंट आबू में लोग बाहरी लोगों द्वारा तैयार किए भोजन और गैर शाकाहारी खाद्य का उपभोग नहीं करते हैं।
- D-22) All the people at BK Mount Abu complexes wear very neat & clean white coloured dress daily with a badge of identification
 बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में पर सभी लोग प्रतिदिन बहुत साफ और स्वच्छ सफेद रंग की पोशाक पहनते हैं, पहचान की एक के बैज के साथ।
- D-23) There is continuous activities such as research, lectures, training, seminars & conferences pertaining to Rajayoga meditation throughout the year at BK Mount Abu complexes.
 बीके माउंट आबू के परिसरों में राजयोग ध्यान से संबंधित निरंतर गतिविधियाँ रहती हैं जैसे अनुसंधान, व्याख्यान, प्रशिक्षण, सेमिनार और सम्मेलनों।

- D-24) People at Mount abu are completely dedicated & serving the mankind without any discrimination all the 365 days a year & no holidays at Mount abu
माउंट आबू में लोग पूरी तरह समर्पित और मानवता की सेवा कर रहे हैं बिना कोई भेदभाव, वर्ष के सभी 365 दिन और माउंट आबू में कोई छुट्टियां नहीं हैं
- D-25) People at mount abu serve with divine love, humility, respect, brother hood & smiling face.
माउंट आबू में लोग दिव्य प्रेम, विनम्रता, सम्मान, भाईचारा और मुस्कुराते हुए चेहरा के साथ सेवा करते हैं
- D-26) The BK people at Mount have abundance selfless love, kind hearted, completely dedicated, happy and a source of inspiration
माउंट में बीके लोगों में बहुतायत निःस्वार्थ प्रेम है, दयालु, पूरी तरह से समर्पित, खुश और प्रेरणा का स्रोत है
- D-27) People at Mount abu don't consume alcohol, tobacco, cigarettes, pan masaala, drugs & They don't have any other bad habits.
माउंट आबू में लोग शराब, तम्बाकू, सिगरेट, पान मसाला, ड्रग्स का उपभोग नहीं करते और वे किसी भी अन्य बुरी आदत नहीं है
- D-28) BK Mount Abu complexes don't have hotel, private lodges, pan masala & cigarette shops
बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में होटल, प्राइवेट लॉज, पान मसाला और सिगरेट की दुकानें नहीं हैं
- D-29) BK Mount Abu complexes don't have a shopping mall & a cinema theater.
बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में शॉपिंग मॉल और सिनेमा थिएटर नहीं है।
- D-30) People at BKMount Abu don't visit cinema theaters and see any kinds of cinema.
बीके माउंट आबू में लोग सिनेमा घरों पर नहीं जाते हैं और किसी भी प्रकार के सिनेमा नहीं देखते हैं
- D-31) You cant find any persons/ donors name in any places / buildings/ infrastructure in the BK Mount Abu complexes
बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में आप किसी भी स्थानों / इमारतों / बुनियादी ढांचे में किसी भी व्यक्ति / दाताओं नाम (देख)मिल नहीं सकते।
- D-32) There is no display of price chart for food , accommodation, transportation& other services at BK Mount Abu complexes.
बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों पर भोजन, आवास, परिवहन और अन्य सेवा के लिए कोई मूल्य चार्ट(बोर्ड) का प्रदर्शन नहीं है।

- D-33) Pure vegetarian & satwic food is served 3 times a day in full quantities free of cost at Specified scientific times at BK Mount Abu complexes .
- बीके माउंट आबू परिसरों में दिन में शुद्ध शाकाहारी व सात्विक भोजन मुक्त लागत से निर्दिष्ट वैज्ञानिक समय पर 3 बार परोसा जाता है ।
- D-34) Meditation teaching Service done continuously to all segments of society without any discrimination through 20 wings at BK Mount Abu complexes .
- समाज के सभी वर्गों के लिए कोई भी बिना भेदभाव के 20 वर्गों के माध्यम से ध्यान शिक्षण सेवा लगातार किया जा रहा है ।
- D-35) Services at Mount abu extended to all people across the Globe without any partiality & discrimination throughout the year.
- माउंट आबू में सेवाएं बिना पक्षपात और भेदभाव के दुनिया भर के सभी लोगों के लिए साल भर बढ़ाया जाता है ।
- D-36) Waking time at BK complexes, mount abu is 3.30am and it is compulsory to attend Amritvela (4am to 4.45am) Rajayoga meditation class daily.
- माउंट आबू बीके परिसरों पर जागने समय सुबह के 3:30 है, और अमृतवेला (04:00-04:45) प्रतिदिन राजयोग ध्यान वलास में भाग लेना अनिवार्य है
- D-37) People at BK complexes, mount abu daily attend to the Murali class (7am to 8am) without fail.
- माउंट आबू बीके परिसरों पर लोग, प्रतिदिन मुखरी वलास (7am to 8am) में भाग जरूर लेते हैं बिना चूके ।
- D-38) Pleasant & harmonious relationships exists between the members at Mount abu
- सुखद एवं सौहार्दपूर्ण रिश्तों माउंट आबू में सदस्यों के बीच मौजूद हैं।
- D-39) Picnic, recreation, drama, dance & other cultural activities organized regularly
- पिकनिक, मनोरंजन, नाटक, नृत्य और अन्य सांस्कृतिक गतिविधियों को नियमित रूप से आयोजन किया जाता है।
- D-40) Whenever the BK people meet together anytime, they greet with the sacred mantra "OM SHANTHI"
- जब भी बीके लोग किसी भी समय एक दूसरे के साथ मिलते हैं, वे पवित्र मंत्र के साथ नमस्कार "ओम शान्ति" करते हैं।

SECTION E - BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA MEDITATION(BKRM) BENEFITS

भाग E- ब्रह्मा कुमारिस राजयोग मेडिटेशन के लाभ

5	4	3	2	1
Strongly Agree दृढ़तापूर्वक सहमता	Agree सहमता	Neutral तटस्थ	Disagree असहमता	Strongly Disagree दृढ़तापूर्वक असहमता

	5	4	3	2	1
E-1) Peace शांति	☐				
E-2) Love प्रेम	☐				
E-3) Happiness सुख	☐				
E-4) Bliss आनंद	☐				
E-5) Harmony in relationships रिश्तों में सद्भाव	☐				
E-6) Constant stage of Soul consciousness आत्मा चेतना की निरंतर स्थिति	☐				
E-7) Gods Consciousness परमात्मा चेतना	☐				
E-8) Self esteem & self confidence आत्म सम्मान और आत्मविश्वास	☐				
E-9) Self transformation स्व परिवर्तन	☐				
E-10) Self control (MIS) स्व नियंत्रण (एमआईएस)	☐				
E-11) Accuracy & punctuality सटीकता और समय की पाबंदी	☐				
E-12) Truth & Honesty सत्य और ईमानदारी	☐				

- E-13) Vice less & ego less stage
विकार और अहंकार रहित स्थिति
- E-14) Experience the angelic & seed stage
फरिश्ता एवं बीज स्थिति की अनुभव
- E-15) Strengthen the inner values & powers
आंतरिक मूल्यों और शक्तियों को मजबूत होना
- E-16) Self development & personality development
आत्म विकास और व्यक्तित्व विकास
- E-17) Value based life style
मूल्य आधारित जीवन शैली
- E-18) Enhanced mental stability
बढ़ा हुआ मानसिक स्थिरता
- E-19) De addiction from substance usage & affinity
मादक द्रव्यों के उपयोग और आकर्षण से नशा मुक्ति
- E-20) Positive attitude & positive thinking personality
सकारात्मक दृष्टिकोण और सकारात्मक सोच व्यक्तित्व
- E-21) An access to the source of treasure of values and virtues
मूल्यों और गुणों का सजाना के स्रोत के लिए एक पहुँच
- E-22) Experiencing GOD in different relationships
विभिन्न रिश्तों में परमात्मा का अनुभव
- E-23) Experiencing GOD as an Omnipotent point of Light
प्रकाश की एक सर्वशक्तिमान बिंदु के रूप में परमात्मा का अनुभव
- E-24) An experience of Self realization,
God s realization & world time realization.
आत्मानुभूति का एक अनुभव, परमात्मा अनुभूति और विश्व समय अनुभूति
- E-25) One can regain the self sovereignty
स्वयं सभ्यत्व सत्ता हासिल कर सकते हैं
- E-26) One can conquer 5 vices
5 विकारों जीत सकते हैं
- E-27) One can completely control & rule the sense organs
पूरी तरह से नियंत्रण और इंद्रियों पर राज कर सकते हैं
- E-28) Motivates to serve mankind through mind
(thoughts) & intellect.
मन के माध्यम (विचार) और बुद्धि से मानवता की सेवा करने के लिए प्रेरित करती हैं
- E-29) Improves Visualization process
दृश्य प्रक्रिया को बेहतर बनाता है

- E-30) Divines the Intellect
बुद्धि दिव्य बनाता है
- E-31) Purify the sanskars(habits)
संस्कार (आदत) शुद्ध बनाता है
- E-32) Motivates to inculcate divine virtues and powers
दिव्य गुण और शक्तियों को धारण करने के लिए प्रेरित करती हैं
- E-33) Strengthens the power of purity of the souls
आत्मा की पवित्रता की शक्ति को मजबूत बनाती हैं
- E-34) Purifies the body , 5 elements & environment.
शरीर, 5 तत्वों एवं पर्यावरण को शुद्ध बनाती हैं
- E-35) Constant peace of mind
मन की निरंतर शांति
- E-36) Removes unworthy habits and desires
अयोग्य आदतों और इच्छाओं को निकालता है
- E-37) Mastery over the self
स्वयं पर महारत
- E-38) Brings relaxation and restores inner peace.
आराम लाता है और मन की शांति को पुनर्स्थापित

BRAHMA KUMARIS INTERNATIONAL
HEAD QUARTERS COMPLEXES : MOUNT ABU , RAJASTHAN

GYAN SAROVAR COMPLEX

PANDAV BHAWAN COMPLEX

SHANTHIVAN COMPLEX

ANNEXURE-2

DETAILS OF SEMINARS & CONFERENCES ATTENDED

Details of Seminars / Conferences Attended

A) NATIONAL CONFERENCES

1) University & college Educators conference cum Meditation Retreat on “**Divine Wisdom For Golden Era**” organized & hosted by Education Wing(RE & RF) & Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya ,World Head quarters: Mount Abu-307501, Rajasthan from **29th May to 2nd June 2015** at **Brahma Kumaris, Gyan Sarovar, Academy for Better World, Mount Abu, Rajasthan.**

2) Social leaders conference & Meditation Retreat on “ **Value Based Society , Spirituality & Raja yoga**” organized & hosted by Social Service Wing of Rajayoga Education & Research Foundation(RE & RF),Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu from **19th to 23rd June 2015** at **Academy for Better World, Gyan Sarovar, Mount Abu, Rajasthan.**

B) INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

1) Spirituality In Researchers (SIR) conference & Meditation Retreat on “ **Inner Strength & Stability In Ever Changing World**” organized & hosted by SpARC Wing of Rajayoga Education & Research Foundation(RE & RF),Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu from **11th to 15th September 2015** at **Global auditorium, Manmohini Complex, Shantivan, Abu Road, Rajasthan.**

2) Multi-Disciplinary conference-cum-Cultural festival on “ **Rajayoga For Healthy & Happy Society**” organized & hosted by Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya, World Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Rajasthan from **2nd to 5th October 2015** at **Shantivan Campus, Abu Road, Rajasthan, India**

3) International conference on “ **Research Management**” organised by Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University from **30th October to 1st November 2015** at **Shri JJTU Campus, Vidyanagari, Chudela Jhunjhunu , Rajasthan.**

4) International conference on “ **Talent Attrition & Retention –Issues & Challenges**” organized by Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University on **3rd November 2015** at **Shri JJTU Campus, Vidyanagari, Chudela Jhunjhunu , Rajasthan.**

ANNEXURE-3

RESEARCH PAPERS PUBLISHED

1)Article-1*

“BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA MEDITATION (BKRM) – STUDY ON INCUMBENT & PREDOMINANT MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS IN SPIRITUAL ENLIGHTENING PRACTICES”

2)Article-2*

“A STUDY OF SPIRITUAL, PHYSIOLOGICAL & PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS MOTIVATING TO LEARN RAJA YOGA MEDITATION OF BRAHMA KUMARIS”

*Articles 1 &2 published in CENTUM journal ISSN 2231-1475